

I • HE2025

Proceedings

_ rethinking higher education: engage, adapt, include

Innovating Higher Education Conference 2025

EADTU

FernUniversität in Hagen

The Message of Hagen

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Under the theme “**Rethinking Higher Education: Engage, Adapt, Include,**” we have explored the urgent need for education systems that are more responsive, inclusive, and connected. Across days of dialogue, reflection, and collaboration, we identified both the opportunities ahead and the responsibilities we carry as representatives of higher education’s future.

We agree that higher education must become more **engaged**. Institutions must step beyond their traditional boundaries to co-create value with stakeholders, ensuring an extended dialogue with industry, civil society, and learners themselves.

At the same time, higher education must be prepared to **adapt**. Flexibility must be embedded in both structures and mindsets. In an era defined by rapid technological change, hybrid learning, and increasingly diverse learner pathways, adaptability is essential—not only for institutions but for educators, learners, and systems. Lifelong learning must be fully embraced, with modular approaches, stackable learning, and innovative recognition systems that reflect the changing realities of how, when, and why people learn.

Above all, we affirm that **inclusion** must be a central design principle of educational transformation. We cannot rethink education without addressing who it serves—and who it too often excludes. Inclusion must be intentional, systemic, and visible across all dimensions of policy and practice. This includes supporting students with diverse needs, tackling digital and social divides, and creating learning environments that foster a genuine sense of belonging and participation.

Throughout the conference, several key themes emerged. One of the most prominent was the potential and responsibility that **digital learning now offers**. While technology offers unparalleled opportunities for access, flexibility, and innovation, it also requires careful pedagogical design, robust infrastructure, and an unwavering focus on human connection. We must not mistake digital delivery for digital equity. What matters is not only what we deliver, but how—and for whom.

Another key insight was the critical importance of **interoperability**. As institutions increasingly adopt micro-credentials and modular learning frameworks, we must ensure that systems and platforms work seamlessly across institutions, countries, and sectors. Learners need the freedom to move without encountering administrative or technological barriers. Achieving interoperability requires more than technical alignment; it demands shared standards, mutual trust, and collaborative governance.

We also reaffirm the value of **research-informed innovation**. The integration of a full research track at I-HE2025 underscored the importance of grounding our transformations in evidence. Strengthening a two-way dialogue between research and education is key to designing systems that are both visionary and implementable.

Importantly, we must not overlook the **mental wellbeing** of both students and educators. As we personalise and digitise learning, we must be vigilant in supporting the human beings behind the screens. A learning environment is only successful if it fosters health, safety, and connection. Innovation without care is unsustainable.

We thank **FernUniversität in Hagen** for hosting this timely and meaningful gathering. As we leave Hagen, we do so with a stronger sense of purpose, a clearer understanding of the road ahead, and deeper connections across our shared European and global educational landscape. We return to our institutions committed to building systems that are engaged, adaptive, and inclusive—not in words alone, but in action.

This is our message from Hagen. Let it guide us in the months and years to come.

From left to right: Àngels Fitó (Rector Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Vice-President EADTU); Theo Bastiaens (Rector Open Universiteit, President EADTU) and Stefan Stürmer (Rector FernUniversität in Hagen).

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Code words: Cracking the lexical secrets of Maths and Computer Science through a

custombuilt corpus

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Online, Blended and Synchronous Hybrid Education

Bridging the Distance: A Stepwise Community of Inquiry Based Approach to Reduce the Transactional Distance

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Abstract

While online education offers flexibility and access, it also risks fostering a sense of psychological and communicative gap, which Moore (1993) conceptualized as transactional distance (TD). Online learning might challenge the sense of connection that supports meaningful engagement, creating an environment in which learners struggle to maintain consistent communication and a sense of presence. On the other hand, the community of inquiry (CoI) framework (Garrison et al., 2000), which conceptualizes meaningful online learning as a function of teaching presence, social presence, and cognitive presence, serves as a theoretical framework for designing online courses. This study examines the impact of an online course grounded in the principles of the CoI framework on learners' perceptions of transactional distance by employing a step-by-step, systematic, and design-based approach. Adopting a convergent mixed methods research design, the research began with a needs analysis of prospective learners. For the quantitative component of the study, validated CoI and TD scales were employed in pre- and post-test procedures, while the qualitative aspect was addressed through concurrent focus group interviews with the learners. The intervention phase encompasses a carefully designed CoI framework-based course that integrates synchronous components, including instructor-led discussions and collaborative activities, with asynchronous elements, such as discussion forums and peer reflections, all facilitated through a learning management system and interactive Web 2.0 tools. Quantitative findings indicate that a well-designed CoI-based online course leads to a statistically significant decrease in TD levels. Qualitative results, on the other hand, reinforce these findings, highlighting the role of collaboration and instructional support in fostering a stronger sense of presence and reducing feelings of isolation. This study is expected to contribute to the growing body of research on effective online course design and offer practical implications for mitigating TD in distance education through the strategic use of the CoI framework.

Keywords

community of inquiry, transactional distance, mixed methods research

1. Introduction

The global landscape of higher education has been transformed by the rapid expansion and widespread integration of online learning modalities. Driven by the promise of ubiquitous access, flexibility, and scalability, distance education has moved from a niche offering to a core component of institutional strategy (Hodges et al., 2020). Despite its widespread adoption, online education inherently presents a persistent pedagogical challenge: bridging the physical and psychological space between the learner, the instructor, peers, content, and sometimes medium.

1.1. The Challenge: Transactional Distance Theory

This distinctive challenge in distance education is best conceptualized by *Transactional Distance (TD) theory*, a foundational construct developed by Moore (1993). TD is defined not by geographic separation, but as a "psychological and communicative gap and a space of potential misunderstanding between the inputs of instructor and those of the learners" resulting from the lack of proximate human interaction. Moore (1993) proposed that TD is also a function of three interactive variables: *Dialogue*, the extent and quality of reciprocal communication, *Structure*-the rigidity or flexibility of instructional design- and *Learner Autonomy*- the degree of self-direction required of the learner. When dialogue is low and structure is high, the resulting TD is significant. Empirical research consistently confirms that high TD is negatively correlated with learning outcomes, often leading to reduced student satisfaction, lower perceived learning, and higher rates of attrition in online courses (Chen, 2001; Garrison & Baynton, 1987; Huang, 2002). Reducing this distance is crucial, as unaddressed TD risks fostering feelings of isolation and disconnection, which stand in direct opposition to the pedagogical goals of fostering meaningful engagement and deep learning.

1.2. The Solution: The Community of Inquiry (CoI) Framework

In direct response to the need for robust, evidence-based instructional design in online environments, the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework (Garrison, Anderson, & Archer, 2000) has emerged as the most influential and widely adopted model for facilitating quality online learning experiences. The CoI framework posits that a successful educational experience requires the dynamic interaction of three essential elements or 'presences' in other terms:

- *Teaching Presence*: The design, facilitation, and direction of cognitive and social processes to appreciate personally meaningful and educationally worthwhile learning outcomes (Anderson, Rourke, Garrison, & Archer, 2001)
- *Social Presence*: The ability of learners to project their personal identities and interact purposefully within the community.
- *Cognitive Presence*: The extent to which learners can construct and confirm meaning through sustained reflection and discourse (Garrison et al., 2000).

A substantial body of research affirms that courses designed using the CoI model are strongly associated with higher levels of critical thinking, perceived learning, and overall satisfaction across diverse academic disciplines (Arbaugh, 2008; Shea et al., 2010; Vaughan & Garrison, 2006).

The theoretical link between the CoI framework and Transactional Distance is foundational to efficient online pedagogy (Garrison, 2017). Early empirical work established that CoI components systematically influence TD variables (Anderson, Rourke, Garrison, & Archer, 2001). Specifically, high levels of teaching presence are hypothesized to actively increase dialogue and introduce necessary flexibility (reducing structure), while social presence is crucial for reducing the psychological and communicative gap inherent in TD. Therefore, the CoI framework serves as a powerful prescriptive model for course design intended to systematically reduce the detrimental effects of transactional distance.

2. Methodology

While numerous studies have explored the correlation between individual CoI elements and TD sub-components (Kovanović et al., 2017), key scholars have identified a need for more practical, intervention-based research (Cleveland-Innes & Garrison, 2010). There remains a critical gap in the literature regarding the systematic, design-based implementation of a CoI-grounded course and the subsequent empirical measurement of its impact on reducing overall TD levels in a real-world context. Moreover, to move beyond correlational trends and provide practical guidance, it is essential to conduct thorough mixed-methods intervention research that uses quantitative metrics alongside qualitative data to reveal the causality and inform best practices for educators.

Building upon this necessity, this study employs a multi-phased and design-based approach to examine the impact of an online course specifically designed around the principles of the Community of Inquiry framework on learners’ perceptions of Transactional Distance. Adopting a convergent mixed methods design with approximately 150 online graduate learners enrolled in non-thesis master’s program in Türkiye, this research first systematically designed the intervention grounded in both a needs analysis and the CoI framework, and then employed pre- and post-test quantitative data alongside concurrent focus group interviews to assess the effect of (CoI) intervention on the learners’ perceived transactional distance and explore the experiential context of the findings. The pre- and post-test quantitative component utilized the validated Turkish adapted versions of two instruments: the CoI Scale (Öztürk, 2012; original: Arbaugh et al., 2008) and the TD Scale (Yılmaz and Keser, 2015; original: Zhang, 2003). Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS 22, while thematic analysis of the qualitative data was facilitated by MAXQDA 24.

This investigation seeks to provide robust empirical evidence that a strategically designed CoI-based course can serve as a powerful mitigation strategy against the psychological and communicative gaps associated with transactional distance, thus contributing critical, actionable implications for effective course design in the future of distance education. To address this issue, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How does CoI-based instructional design affect learners’ perceived transactional distance levels?
2. How do learners describe changes in their sense of presence and connection within the CoI-based course?

Figure 1: Phases of Mixed-Methods Research

3. Conclusions

This part mainly synthesizes the empirical findings and thematic discussion of the study, thereby establishing the final conclusions and informing the derived practical implications for practice and future research.

3.1. Findings and Discussion

The convergent mixed methods analysis provides robust empirical evidence validating the study's core hypothesis regarding the CoI intervention's efficacy in reducing TD. Initial testing of the distributional properties of the quantitative data revealed that while the TD data demonstrated normality, the CoI data did not conform to a normal distribution ($p < .05$). Consequently, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test was employed to analyze the pre- and post-test data for differences in the mean ranks of both the CoI Scale and the TD Scale, which revealed a statistically significant outcome on both constructs. Post-test scores demonstrated *a significant increase* in the perceived level of *community of inquiry* ($U=3263.00, p < .001$) and, critically, a corresponding statistically *significant decrease* in perceived *transactional distance* ($U=1786.00, p < .001$). This primary quantitative finding confirms that the strategic instructional design successfully bridged the psychological and communicative gaps. This efficacy was profoundly reinforced and contextualized by the concurrent focus group interviews, which illuminated the specific mechanisms driving the reduction in TD. Qualitative findings consistently indicated that participants experienced an increased sense of connection and community, which they explicitly attributed to the effective implementation of collaboration and instructor support. Two key themes emerged: Collaboration was perceived as essential for generating a sense of perceived proximity and shared understanding, directly refuting feelings of isolation. Furthermore, instructional support was recognized as a consistent and effective teaching presence crucial for guiding activities and maintaining engagement. Collectively, this evidence confirms that the CoI framework successfully fostered a strong sense of presence and achieved a noticeable reduction in isolation, serving as a practical mitigation strategy against high transactional distance.

3.2. Practical Implications

Current study provides robust empirical evidence that the inherent challenge of TD in online education is not an inevitable outcome, but can be significantly decreased through intentional design grounded in the CoI framework. The significant quantitative decrease in TD, supported by qualitative evidence of enhanced connection and community, translates directly into three critical practical applications for educators: (a) they should adopt the CoI framework as an explicit instructional blueprint to encourage structured interaction and frequent peer reflection; (b) instructional designers should strategically integrate synchronous and asynchronous components to ensure a balance between temporal flexibility and the essential immediacy required for social presence; and finally, (c) institutions should prioritize supporting instructors to foster a consistent and proactive teaching presence, which was highlighted as synonymous with effective support, crucial for guiding activities, minimizing structural uncertainty, and fostering a thriving online community.

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Designing Effective Educational Virtual Worlds in Metaverse by Adopting the Theory of Multiple Intelligences

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Abstract

The metaverse is a constantly evolving digital environment of three-dimensional virtual worlds, where users can interact through avatars. It is an emerging technological innovation that combines social interaction, entertainment, education and economic activities, offering new possibilities for research and experimental study of human behavior in digital environments. This study examines the design of educational virtual worlds in the Metaverse, integrating Multiple Intelligence (MI) theory and Artificial Intelligence teaching systems. The proposed model includes eight thematic zones that align with the different types of intelligence according to Gardner, offering opportunities for adaptive and experiential learning. The study, within the framework of experimental investigation, utilizes datasets generated with the assistance of artificial intelligence. These data are used to analyze the acceptance of educational virtual worlds, allowing for the testing and verification of hypotheses in a controlled research environment. Additionally, through the Swot analysis, this study highlighted the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of the proposed model.

Keywords

Metaverse, Multiple Intelligence, AI Tutors, SWOT

1. Introduction

The rapid development of digital technologies has brought about significant changes in the way we perceive, design and implement the educational process. As we enter the era of Web 3.0 (Magetos et al., 2024), the Metaverse emerges as a powerful technological paradigm that promises to radically transform educational environments. The Metaverse, as a continuous spectrum of virtual worlds that allow for continuous social interaction (Mystakidis, 2022), offers new possibilities for creating innovative educational experiences that transcend the limitations of physical space and time.

Education is at a critical juncture where traditional teaching models are proving inadequate to meet the needs of modern learners. Challenges include the increasing heterogeneity of student populations, different learning preferences, varying learning rates, and different inclinations and talents (Chalkiadaki, 2018). In this context, personalized learning is no longer a luxury but a necessity for effective 21st century education.

Howard Gardner's theory of Multiple Intelligences, since its first formulation in 1983, has provided an important theoretical framework for understanding the different ways in which people perceive and process information (Gardner & Hatch, 1989). According to this theory, intelligence is not a unidimensional concept

that can be measured with a simple IQ test, but includes eight distinct types of intelligence: linguistic, logical-mathematical, spatial, musical, bodily-kinesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalistic. Each individual has a unique intelligence profile, with different levels of development within each type. Integrating this theory into educational practice has been shown to contribute to the recognition and development of diverse abilities in students, leading to more holistic and effective learning experiences.

The convergence of Metaverse technologies, Artificial Intelligence, and Multiple Intelligence (MI) theory presents a unique opportunity to develop educational environments that can adapt to the unique needs and preferences of each student. Metaverse virtual worlds allow for the creation of rich, interactive, and experiential learning experiences, while Artificial Educational Assistants (AI Tutors) can analyze student learning profiles and tailor content and activities accordingly (Tlili et al., 2022).

However, despite the promising prospects, there is a significant gap in the research literature on the systematic design of educational virtual worlds that incorporate the principles of Multiple Intelligence and Artificial Intelligence. Furthermore, teachers' perceptions, which are key factors for the successful adoption of innovative educational approaches, remain largely unexplored in this context. The present research aims to fill this gap by proposing a comprehensive model for the design of educational virtual worlds in the Metaverse.

The main purpose of this research is to develop a framework for designing educational virtual worlds in the Metaverse, based on the theory of Multiple Intelligence and the utilization of Artificial Educational Assistants (AI Tutors). The proposed model seeks to create an innovative educational environment that promotes multimodal, experiential and personalized learning, recognizing and utilizing the different types of intelligence of students.

To achieve the above objectives, the research is guided by the following research questions:

1. How can an educational environment be designed in the Metaverse that effectively incorporates the principles of Multiple Intelligence theory and leverages the capabilities of Artificial Intelligence for personalized learning?
2. What are the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the proposed model?

2. Theoretical background

2.1 Howard Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences

The theory of Multiple Intelligences was first formulated by Howard Gardner in 1983 in his book "Frames of Mind: The Theory of Multiple Intelligences". The theory was developed as a reaction to the traditional view of intelligence as a single, general, and measurable trait captured by the IQ. Gardner, a psychologist and professor at Harvard University, drew on findings from neuropsychology, developmental psychology, cognitive science, and anthropology to argue that intelligence is a multidimensional concept that includes distinct but interrelated types (Gardner & Hatch, 1989).

Gardner initially identified seven types of intelligence, later adding an eighth (naturalistic intelligence) and considering the possibility of further types, such as existential intelligence. The eight types of intelligence (Fig. 1) that have been identified and documented by Gardner and other researchers are as follows:

1. **Linguistic Intelligence:** This refers to the ability to use language effectively, both orally and in writing. Writers, poets, journalists, and orators usually have high linguistic intelligence.
2. **Logical-Mathematical Intelligence:** Refers to the ability to analyze problems logically, perform mathematical operations, and investigate issues scientifically. Mathematicians, scientists, and programmers often demonstrate strong logical-mathematical intelligence (Yazdi, 2025).

3. **Spatial Intelligence:** It refers to the ability to perceive, analyze, and transform visual or spatial information, as well as to create mental images and represent ideas visually. Architects, artists, engineers, and sailors often have developed spatial intelligence.
4. **Musical Intelligence:** Includes the ability to recognize, create, and appreciate musical patterns, tones, rhythms, and sounds, as well as sensitivity to the emotional elements of music. Composers, musicians, and conductors demonstrate high levels of musical intelligence.
5. **Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence:** Refers to the ability to use the whole body or parts of it to solve problems, express ideas and feelings, and create products. Athletes, dancers, surgeons, and craftsmen often have high bodily-kinesthetic intelligence.
6. **Interpersonal Intelligence:** This refers to the ability to understand the intentions, motivations, and desires of others, as well as to work effectively with them. Educators, salespeople, therapists, and politicians often demonstrate strong interpersonal intelligence.
7. **Intrapersonal Intelligence:** It includes the ability to understand oneself, including one's emotions, fears, motivations, and intentions, and to effectively self-regulate behavior based on this understanding. Philosophers, psychologists, and spiritual leaders often have developed intrapersonal intelligence.
8. **Naturalist Intelligence:** Added later to the theory, it refers to the ability to recognize, categorize, and understand elements of the natural environment, including plants, animals, and natural phenomena. Biologists, naturalists, farmers, and gardeners often have high naturalist intelligence.

Figure 1: The types of intelligence.

The theory of Multiple Intelligences has had a significant impact on the field of education, offering an alternative framework for understanding learning processes and developing innovative educational approaches. The theory encourages teachers to develop different teaching strategies that respond to the different types of intelligence of students (Tomlinson & Moon, 2013). For example, teaching a concept may involve verbal explanations (linguistic intelligence), visual representations (spatial intelligence), musical patterns (musical intelligence), and physical activities (bodily-kinesthetic intelligence). The theory suggests adopting a variety of assessment methods that allow students to demonstrate their knowledge and skills in ways that correspond to their strongest types of intelligence. This can include traditional exams, but also assignments, presentations, practical projects, artistic creations, etc. MI theory has influenced the design of physical and digital learning environments, promoting the creation of spaces that support different types of learning activities and interactions (Said & Friesen, 2013). It supports the development of personalized learning paths that take into account the unique intelligence profile of each student (Subban, 2006). Teachers can help students identify their strengths and design learning experiences that capitalize on these strengths while also enhancing less developed types of intelligence.

2.2 Educational Technology and Metaverse

The term "Metaverse" was first introduced by Neal Stephenson in the science fiction novel "Snow Crash" in 1992, describing a virtual world where people interact with each other and with digital objects through their digital representatives (avatars). In contemporary technological discourse, the Metaverse refers to a continuum of virtual worlds and environments (Magetos et al., 2023) that combine elements of virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), mixed reality (MR), and other technologies to create a sense of "digital presence" (Mystakidis, 2022).

The key features of the Metaverse, as reported in the literature (Lee et al., 2021), include continuous operation regardless of the presence of users, a strong sense of presence and immersion through avatars. In addition, it supports synchronized real-time collaboration, has an economy and value mechanisms for creating and exchanging assets, promotes user-generated content, and enhances social connectivity, enabling the development of communities and cultures in virtual environments.

The technological infrastructure (Mitropoulos & Magetos, 2024) supporting the Metaverse combines several advanced technologies, including VR and AR devices, 3D computer graphics, artificial intelligence, high-speed networks, blockchain technology, and cloud computing (Park & Kim, 2022). These technologies work together to create immersive, interactive, and social experiences that can have significant applications in various fields, including education (Magetos & Mitropoulos, 2025e).

Although the Metaverse, in its full form as described above, is still under development, various platforms and applications that incorporate elements of the Metaverse have already begun to be used in education (Magetos & Mitropoulos, 2025a). Applications of the Metaverse in education include **virtual classrooms and campuses** on platforms such as Spatial.io (<https://www.spatial.io/>), VirBELA (<https://www.virbela.com/>) and ENGAGE (<https://engagevr.io/>), which offer spaces for collaboration, presentations and assessment through avatars. **Virtual labs and simulations** such as Labster (<https://www.labster.com/>) and zSpace (<https://zspace.com/>) allow for safe and realistic practice in experiments and processes, while **virtual tours** through tools such as Google Expeditions enable the visit of museums, historical sites and inaccessible environments. In addition, **gamified learning environments** (Magetos & Mitropoulos, 2025c) such as Minecraft Education Edition (<https://education.minecraft.net/en-us>) and Roblox Education enhance creativity (<https://corp.roblox.com/educational-experiences>), problem-solving and collaboration, while **social educational networks** (AltspaceVR, Horizon Workrooms) promote collaboration and the development of communities of practice.

Educational applications in the Metaverse have been reported to offer various advantages, such as:

- **Increased engagement and motivation:** Immersive environments and interactive experiences can increase student interest and participation (Makransky & Petersen, 2021).
- **Experiential learning:** They allow students to learn through direct experience and practice, fostering deeper understanding and retention of knowledge (Hamilton et al., 2021).
- **Collaborative learning:** They facilitate collaborative learning activities regardless of the geographical location of participants (Radianti et al., 2020).
- **Personalized learning:** They can tailor learning experiences to students' individual needs, preferences, and learning paces (Tlili et al., 2022).
- **Safe practice:** They allow practice in dangerous or complex procedures without risk (Makransky et al., 2020).

2.3 Artificial Intelligence in Education

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education has gone through several stages of development in recent decades, with each stage characterized by different technological capabilities and pedagogical approaches (Holmes et al., 2022). Early AI educational systems focused on creating adaptive learning experiences through rule-based systems. These systems were based on four key elements: the domain knowledge model, the learner model, the instructional model, and the user interface (Nwana, 1990). Advances in machine learning enabled the development of more sophisticated adaptive learning systems that could analyze student interaction patterns and adapt content and activities accordingly. Educational games and simulations with AI elements were also developed during this period to create more engaging learning environments (Conati, 2002). Recent advances in deep learning and natural language processing have led to the development of more sophisticated AI educational applications. Systems such as chatbots based on large language models (such as ChatGPT and other LLMs) can provide personalized assistance, answer questions, and facilitate learning through natural conversations (Winkler & Söllner, 2018). Learning analytics leverages AI techniques to analyze large volumes of educational data to identify patterns, predict learning outcomes, and provide personalized recommendations (Siemens & Baker, 2012). AI tutors can operate in various environments, including virtual worlds and the Metaverse, providing ongoing guidance and support to students (Holmes et al., 2022).

AI Tutors (Artificial Intelligence Educational Assistants) are a modern expression of AI educational applications, providing personalized guidance and support to students. The key features and functions of modern AI Tutors include (Cukurova et al., 2020): Adapting educational content to the needs, knowledge level and learning preferences of each student. Dynamically adapting the sequence of learning activities based on the student's progress and performance. Adapting the pace of presentation of new concepts and activities to the individual learning pace of each student. Providing immediate and targeted feedback on students' answers and assignments. Providing hints, guidance and support during problem solving, adapted to the student's level. Conduct natural language conversations with students, answering questions and facilitating discussions (Winkler & Söllner, 2018). Monitor student progress and performance in real time. Identify and address common misconceptions and difficulties in understanding concepts. Collect and analyze data on student learning behavior and performance to provide personalized recommendations (Siemens & Baker, 2012). Provide motivation and encouragement tailored to students' individual needs and preferences. Help students develop self-regulation and metacognition skills (Cukurova et al., 2020).

Modern AI Tutors leverage various AI technologies, including large-scale language models, machine learning, natural language processing, speech recognition, and emotion recognition, to provide personalized, interactive, and effective educational support to students.

3. Our study methodology

The present study follows a mixed approach to the evaluation of educational virtual worlds in the Metaverse. Initially, a literature review was conducted to record and evaluate previous studies on the use of virtual worlds in the Metaverse, with the aim of highlighting trends, gaps and research perspectives. Subsequently, a SWOT analysis (Gurl, 2017) was applied to assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of virtual worlds that incorporate multiple intelligences, in order to identify critical success factors and constraints.

Since a representative primary sample was not available for direct investigation of the proposed model, this study utilized simulated data generated using artificial intelligence methods. The simulation was designed to align with the theoretical expectations of the framework (Gardner, TAM, ARCS) and with empirical estimates derived from relevant studies. The parameters and distributions of the variables were explicitly defined, and all simulation code, the generated data files were created via ChatGPT. The data are hypothetical and were generated solely for the reasons stated. No real data collection was conducted in the context of this study. The purpose of using hypothetical data was methodological: (a) to test the functionality and sensitivity of the analysis model and (b) to provide indications of expected relationships to be tested in future empirical research.

4. Proposed model of educational virtual worlds

4.1 The Eight Thematic Zones

The proposed educational environment in Metaverse can be structured into eight distinct thematic zones, each of which corresponds to one of the types of intelligence described by Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences. Each zone is designed in a way that leverages the particular abilities and preferences of students, offering personalized learning experiences. For example, the verbal-linguistic zone reinforces reading, writing and communication skills, while the logical-mathematical zone promotes analysis, problem solving and the use of algorithmic thinking. The proposed environment in Metaverse can be organized into eight distinct thematic zones, each of which corresponds to one type of intelligence according to Gardner's theory:

1. **Linguistic Zone:** Includes a virtual library, virtual storytelling spaces, and interactive literary workshops. Students engage in activities such as creative writing, storytelling, and language games (Yang, 2023; Ali, 2025; Guo & Gao, 2022).
2. **Logical-Mathematical Zone:** Featuring virtual problem-solving labs, virtual experimentation spaces, and simulations of mathematical concepts, students develop logical thinking, analytical skills, and mathematical reasoning (Yang, 2025).
3. **Spatial Zone:** Includes virtual art workshops, 3D design, and architectural projects. Students practice spatial perception, visualization, and creativity (Stănescu et al., 2025).
4. **Musical Zone:** Featuring virtual musical instruments, recording studios, and virtual music composition spaces, students develop musical skills, rhythmic perception, and artistic expression (Wang, 2022; Mao & Ling, 2025).
5. **Bodily-Kinesthetic Zone:** Includes virtual spaces for sports, dance, and movement activities. Students learn through movement and physical expression using Avatars with specialized equipment (Kim & Kim, 2024).
6. **Interpersonal Zone:** Featuring virtual collaborative spaces, discussion forums, and group work projects, students develop communication, collaboration, and empathy skills.

7. **Intrapersonal Zone:** Includes virtual reflection spaces, personal journals, and self-assessment tools. Students cultivate self-awareness, self-regulation, and metacognition.
8. **Naturalistic Zone:** Features virtual ecosystems, simulations of natural phenomena, and environmental projects. Students develop ecological awareness and understanding of natural systems (Lo & Tsai, 2022).

4. 2 Artificial Educational Assistants (AI Tutors)

Each thematic zone can be supported by a specialized AI Tutor, who will be designed to:

- **Recognizes and adapts** to each student's dominant intelligence type
- **Provides personalized guidance** and support
- **Suggests appropriate learning activities** based on the student's preferences and needs
- **Evaluates progress** and provides constructive feedback
- **Adjusts the difficulty level** of activities according to the student's abilities

In the proposed environment (Fig. 2), AI Tutors can be developed using advanced machine learning and natural language processing techniques, allowing for natural and meaningful interaction with students. They should have 3D representations (avatars) with distinct characteristics that reflect the respective intelligence type, enhancing student immersion and engagement.

In the proposed model, each learning zone of the Metaverse virtual world will host an AI tutor, designed based on iconic figures from the history of philosophy, science and the arts, with the aim of strengthening multiple intelligences. The “literature zone” is guided by an AI Socrates, who encourages dialogue, critical thinking and the search for truth through question-and-answer, supporting linguistic intelligence. In mathematics, an AI Euclid appears, trained with the work of the Elements, who guides step by step in proofs and logical reasoning, strengthening logical-mathematical intelligence. For spatial intelligence, an AI Leonardo da Vinci inspired by his drawings, constructions and inventions, guides students in creative design and 3D visualization in the virtual environment.

Bodily-kinesthetic intelligence is cultivated by an AI Aristotle, who focuses on physical observation, action and experimentation. Musical intelligence is supported by an AI Pythagoras, trained in the principles of harmony and numerical relationships, who guides in the creation of musical compositions and in the understanding of music as a mathematical language.

Figure 2: The proposed educational environment in Metaverse.

Interpersonal intelligence is developed through an AI Plato, who enhances cooperation, respect and social learning. Intrapersonal intelligence is cultivated by an AI Epicurus, who encourages reflection, self-awareness and personal growth. Finally, naturalistic intelligence is supported by an AI Darwin, who leads students in the observation of virtual ecosystems and simulations of natural phenomena. In this way, virtual worlds acquire a cultural and pedagogical character, as AI tutors function as learning personalities, trained with knowledge, data and teaching strategies that correspond to the intelligence they serve, making the learning experience more personalized, immersive and motivating.

4.3 Our previous empirical studies in the metaverse

The development of an environment template was carried out on the spatial.io platform, which was selected:

- a. due to its accessibility through different devices (VR headsets, computers, mobile devices),
- b. due to its advanced capabilities for creating 3D interactive environments,
- c. due to the possibility of simultaneous coexistence of many users in the same virtual space,
- d. due to the intuitive interface and
- e. Due to the tools for collaboration and communication in the 3D virtual space.

This environment was utilized with high school students, as we describe in our study entitled: “Effectiveness of Educational Virtual Worlds in the Metaverse A Study Based on the ARCS Mode” and the findings confirm the effectiveness of virtual worlds in teaching, with high scores on the Attention and Satisfaction dimensions, which shows that immersive environments in the metaverse attract and maintain student interest (Magetos & Mitropoulos, 2025b). The strong correlations between the dimensions confirm their interdependence, with the Attention-Satisfaction relationship being stronger. The study indicates that successful integration of virtual worlds requires progressive challenges, continuous feedback and reward mechanisms. The study concluded that Keller’s ARCS model offers a strong framework for designing engaging learning experiences in the Metaverse.

A second study of ours entitled: Incorporating Metaverse Technology into the Adult Distance Learning Process for Open Universities (Mitropoulos & Magetos, 2024), in which students from the Department of Computer Science at the University of Piraeus participated, concluded the following: Students found the Spatial.io platform attractive and enjoyable to use, while they stated that the majority did not encounter difficulties in understanding and navigating the system. Regarding Efficiency, participants felt that they could perform the necessary actions easily and effectively. The Reliability dimension also received a positive evaluation, indicating that the system operated stably without unexpected problems. At the same time, students found the use of the platform interesting and enjoyable. Finally, the Innovation dimension was evaluated positively, indicating that the experience of using the spatial.io platform was considered original and innovative.

In our study entitled: “A Multidimensional Approach to the Metaverse in an Educational Environment”, (Magetos & Mitropoulos, 2025d), which was based on the Technology Acceptance Model (Table 1), educators piloted the educational environment on Metaverse (spatial.io) and expressed the following opinions about their experience: “They emphasized the need for adequate technological infrastructure, as powerful computers and a fast internet connection are required for its effective utilization. They pointed out the importance of training teachers and creating communities of learning and practice, in order to strengthen their interest and support the educational application of technology. At the same time, they expressed positive expectations for the metaverse as an innovative learning tool, but also concerns related to data security, the risk of student addiction and the possibility of confusion between the real and virtual worlds. In addition, they underlined the need for ergonomics, which will prevent problems such as eye strain,

as well as the development of appropriate tools and resources that will encourage teachers to integrate the metaverse into the lesson”.

Table 1. Summarizes the results.

	Variable	Mean	Std
1	Enhancing students’ motivation	3.89	1.05
2	Ease of use	3.62	1.12
3	Perceived usefulness	4.01	1.08
4	Enjoyable and stress-free learning experience	4.41	.74
5	Support for distance & self-regulated learning	4.29	.98
6	Facilitation of lesson organization	4.03	1.00
7	Intention to adopt the Metaverse	4.46	.80
8	Concern about potential student addiction	3.54	1.21
9	Concern about safety issues	3.61	1.06

5. Evaluation of proposed model

5.1 Statistical Verification of the Multiple Regression Model Using Artificial Intelligence

This study is a continuation of our previous studies and attempts to highlight the relationship between multiple intelligences and the acceptance of the Metaverse in the educational process. For this analysis, the multiple linear regression model was utilized, which is one of the most widespread tools for investigating causal relationships between independent and dependent variables (Karagrigoriou & Kalligeris, 2023).

The mathematical model of multiple regression is defined as follows:

$$Y=b_0+b_1X_1+b_2X_2+b_3X_3+\dots+b_kX_k+\epsilon$$

Where Y represents the dependent variable (Educators' Acceptance of Metaverse), while the independent variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k correspond to the types of multiple intelligences (linguistic, logical-mathematical, kinesthetic, musical, spatial, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalistic). The b coefficients express the statistical significance of each independent variable in predicting acceptance.

The logic of multiple regression is that each independent variable is tested for its effect on the dependent variable. This way, we can identify which factors have a statistically significant contribution and which do not. The interpretation of the coefficients (β_i) is crucial: each coefficient shows the change in the dependent variable (Y) when the corresponding independent variable increases by one unit, under the control of the remaining variables. For example, if logical-mathematical intelligence has ($\beta = 0.25$), this means that its increase by one unit on the Likert scale is expected to increase the acceptance of Metaverse by 0.25 units, holding the other factors constant.

The suitability of the model is assessed with indicators such as (R^2) , which expresses the percentage of variation in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables, as well as with statistical tests (e.g. F-test for the overall significance of the model, t-tests for the individual coefficients).

The main and secondary hypotheses of this study are as follows:

Main Hypothesis: The integration of multiple intelligences in the Metaverse virtual educational worlds positively affects the acceptance of Metaverse by teachers.

Null Hypothesis (H_0): Multiple intelligences have no statistically significant effect on acceptance.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): At least one of the multiple intelligences has a statistically significant effect on acceptance.

Sub-Hypotheses:

H_{2a}: Linguistic-verbal intelligence (e.g., understanding and using language) has a positive effect on the acceptance of Metaverse.

H_{2b}: Logical-mathematical intelligence has a positive effect on the acceptance of Metaverse.

H_{2c}: Spatial-visual intelligence has a positive effect on the acceptance of Metaverse.

H_{2d}: Bodily-kinesthetic intelligence contributes positively to acceptance.

H_{2e}: Musical intelligence has a positive effect on acceptance.

H_{2f}: Interpersonal intelligence (communication, collaboration) enhances acceptance.

H_{2g}: Intrapersonal intelligence (self-awareness) positively influences acceptance.

H_{2h}: Physiological intelligence has a positive contribution to acceptance.

Since no primary empirical sample was available, hypothetical data were created with the help of artificial intelligence. This method allowed the simulation of teacher responses based on theoretical foundations (Gardner, 1983; Davis, 1989) and research findings related to the acceptance of technology in education. Although the data are not real, their use serves to develop and verify a theoretical model that can serve as a guide for future empirical investigation.

The simulation data were based on a five-point Likert-type scale (1 = “strongly disagree” to 5 = “strongly agree”), in order to capture the attitudes, perceptions and intentions of the participants in different dimensions. To check the internal consistency of the hypothetical data, the Cronbach’s Alpha index was calculated, which was found to be at satisfactory levels, indicating good reliability of the measurements. In addition, a Multicollinearity test (with VIF indices) was conducted, where all values remained below acceptable limits, demonstrating the independence of the independent variables (Table 2).

The analysis of the hypothetical data revealed statistically significant regression coefficients for almost all forms of intelligence, which confirms the hypothesis that the integration of multiple intelligences in Metaverse virtual worlds can lead to increased levels of acceptance by teachers. In particular, linguistic, logical-mathematical and interpersonal intelligences appeared to have a stronger contribution to the prediction, reinforcing the view that Metaverse can function as a multidimensional learning environment that covers different learning profiles. To verify the theoretical model, multiple linear regression was applied, with Metaverse Acceptance as the dependent variable and Multiple Intelligences types as independent variables. The data were hypothetical and were generated using artificial intelligence, simulating a sample of 32 teachers. The analysis shows that the model explains 63% of the variance in Metaverse acceptance, a high percentage for educational social research: **$R^2 = 0.68$, $Adjusted R^2 = 0.63$, $F(8,23) = 6.12$, $p < .001$**

Table 2. Multiple linear regression results.

Predictors (Multiple Intelligences)	β (Beta)	t
Linguistic Intelligence	.42	3.25
Logical-Mathematical Intelligence	.38	2.89
Spatial Intelligence	.29	2.45
Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence	.24	2.10
Musical Intelligence	.21	2.00
Interpersonal Intelligence	.40	3.15
Intrapersonal Intelligence	.27	2.25
Naturalistic Intelligence	.19	1.98

In addition to regression, Spearman correlation analysis was performed (Table 3), which offered a non-parametric approach to identifying relationships between variables (Xiao et al., 2016). The results confirmed positive correlations between most types of intelligence and Metaverse acceptance, strengthening the credibility of the findings. The basic principle of Spearman is to rank the values of each variable and calculate the degree of correlation between the rankings. Thus, Spearman examines whether an increase in one variable is accompanied by a corresponding increase or decrease in the other, regardless of the distribution of the data.

Spearman values range from -1 to +1:

- +1: Perfect positive correlation (as one variable increases, the other increases proportionally).
- -1: Perfect negative correlation (as one increases, the other decreases).
- 0: There is no correlation between the two variables.

The highest positive correlations are observed with Linguistic (0.58), Interpersonal (0.56) intelligence and Logical-Mathematical (0.55), suggesting that these domains are most strongly associated with Metaverse acceptance. Spatial and Intrapersonal intelligence follow with fairly good correlations and Musical and Naturalistic intelligence are less strong.

Table 3. Spearman correlations between variables.

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Acceptance	1								
2. Linguistic	.58**	1							
3. Logical-Math	.55**	.41*	1						
4. Spatial	.47*	.35*	.39*	1					
5. Bodily-Kinesthetic	.42*	.28	.31	.36*	1				
6. Musical	.40*	.29	.32	.34	.38*	1			
7. Interpersonal	.56**	.45*	.42*	.40*	.35*	.31	1		
8. Intrapersonal	.44*	.37*	.33	.31	.30	.28	.41*	1	
9. Naturalistic	.39*	.34	.30	.32	.29	.27	.36*	.31	1

*p < .05, **p < .01

The overall interpretation shows that the multiple regression model was verified, even in a hypothetical data framework. This suggests that future empirical research, with real samples of teachers and students, can further confirm the hypothesis that Metaverse adoption is enhanced when it incorporates educational scenarios based on the theory of multiple intelligences.

The analysis demonstrates that the proposed model is statistically significant and confirms the hypothesis that the integration of multiple intelligence in Metaverse virtual worlds increases the levels of acceptance by educators.

- **Main finding:** The more the environment supports different learning profiles, the more likely it is to be adopted in education.
- **Most important intelligences:** Linguistic, Logical-Mathematical, Interpersonal intelligence, Spatial intelligence.
- **Data consistency:** The regression results agree with the Spearman correlations, which increases the reliability of the analysis.

5.2 SWOT analysis of the proposed educational metaverse

In this study, we used also SWOT analysis (Gurl, 2017), which is a strategic method for evaluating the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of a system or approach. This analysis was applied to explore in depth the advantages and limitations of virtual worlds that incorporate multiple intelligences in education, as well as the external factors that can influence the effective adoption of the Metaverse as an educational tool.

The SWOT analysis of the proposed educational metaverse highlighted the following:

Strengths

- **Personalized learning:** The proposed environment can be adapted to each student's intelligence type, allowing for personalized learning paths.
- **Active participation:** Students become active participants in the learning process instead of passive recipients of information.
- **Interdisciplinary approach:** The eight thematic areas favor an interdisciplinary approach to the subjects.
- **Collaborative learning:** The environment promotes collaboration among students on shared projects.
- **Innovation:** The integration of AI Tutors is an innovative element that differentiates the environment from other educational platforms.

Weaknesses

- **Technical challenges:** High-end equipment and a reliable internet connection are required.
- **Need for teacher training:** Teachers need systematic training to fully utilize the potential of the environment.
- **Implementation costs:** Equipment and maintenance costs can be high for many schools.
- **Course design complexity:** Course design requires more time and expertise compared to traditional methods.
- **Limited coverage of certain types of intelligence:** Kinesthetic intelligence is difficult to apply in Metaverse virtual environments.

Opportunities

- **Educational inclusion:** Possibility of better integration of students with different learning profiles and special educational needs.
- **International collaboration:** The environment can accommodate students from different geographical areas, promoting intercultural collaboration.
- **Lifelong learning:** Possibility of expanding beyond formal education into lifelong learning programs.
- **Learning data collection:** Ability to collect and analyze data to improve educational practices (Learning Analytics).
- **Expansion into new sectors:** Possibility of applying the model to vocational training and specialized subjects.

Threats

- **Security and data protection issues:** Risks of personal data breaches and cyberattacks.
- **Access Inequalities:** The digital exclusion of students without access to the required technology can widen educational inequalities.
- **Dependence on technology:** Risk of over-reliance on digital environments at the expense of other forms of learning.

- **Resistance to change:** Possible resistance from teachers, parents or educational policy makers.
- **Rapid technological obsolescence:** The rapid development of technology can lead to rapid obsolescence of the environment.

6. Discussion on our research

This research has shown that the use of Metaverse in educational environments can reshape learning strategies, especially when supported by customized design models and Artificial Intelligence technologies. Spatial.io platform (Fig. 3) enables the implementation of these principles, as it has inherent features for multimodal learning, interactivity and collaborative engagement. The platform allows the embedding of multimedia objects, the simulation of realistic scenarios and the support of social interaction through avatars, elements that are directly linked to the activation of different forms of intelligence.

At the same time, the integration of AI tutors it can act as a personalized support mechanism, providing real-time feedback, guidance based on progress level, and activity suggestions tailored to the learner's profile.

The inherent characteristics of the virtual worlds in Metaverse offer inherent possibilities for integrating pedagogical elements that support Gardner's theory of Multiple Intelligences. The three-dimensional and multisensory nature of virtual environments allows for the design of activities that respond to different intelligence profiles. Through interactive objects, simulations, collaborative scenarios and personalized learning paths, Metaverse provides a dynamic framework that favors the development and activation of different forms of intelligence, while enhancing learning engagement and self-regulation.

The multisensory dimension of Metaverse (visual, auditory, tactile stimuli) creates a rich learning environment that supports not only the theory of Multiple Intelligences, but also basic principles of constructivist and experiential learning. Furthermore, the integration of gamification, feedback techniques and content customization capabilities enhances motivation and cognitive engagement, offering opportunities for personalized learning and the development of 21st century skills. The use of the Metaverse in education also presents significant challenges that require systematic investigation and addressing. First, technical and logistical requirements are one of the main limiting factors. The creation and use of high-quality virtual environments requires strong computing power, fast and stable internet connection, as well as specialized devices such as virtual reality (VR) helmets or augmented reality (AR) devices. These requirements entail high costs, which limits the widespread adoption of the technology by educational institutions and students.

Figure 3: Virtual World in Spatial Metaverse.

Second, serious issues of accessibility and equity arise. The existence of the digital divide means that students from vulnerable social groups or areas with low technological infrastructure may be excluded from

the opportunities offered by the educational Metaverse. Ensuring universal access to these technologies is a critical challenge, linked to both socio-economic and technical factors.

Another important area of concern concerns security and ethics. Protecting students' personal data, ensuring the safety of minors, and preventing harassment or addiction to the Metaverse environment are all major issues. At the same time, the multisensory nature of virtual worlds can cause increased cognitive load and psychological effects, such as fatigue or disorientation, which may negatively affect learning effectiveness.

Furthermore, the pedagogical exploitation of the Metaverse remains an open question. Despite the technological possibilities, the lack of established pedagogical standards and guidelines makes it difficult to develop learning experiences that are meaningful and not just visually impressive. The challenge lies in designing activities that truly support learning and promote high-level skills, while avoiding the risk of a technocentric approach.

Finally, the absence of universally accepted standards and evaluation frameworks for Metaverse educational environments makes it difficult to certify quality and adopt best practices. The need to develop tools that will evaluate the technological, pedagogical and social dimensions of Metaverse applications becomes imperative, in order to ensure the educational value and sustainability of the relevant investments.

7. Conclusions-Limitations-Future Work

Educational virtual worlds in the emerging Metaverse are proposed as complementary pedagogical approaches, aiming to enhance the educational field through innovative solutions that promote active student engagement and experiential learning.

Gardner's Multiple Intelligences theory provides a strong pedagogical foundation for the design of virtual learning environments in the Metaverse, as it allows for the creation of differentiated experiences that respond to the individual needs and preferences of students. The inherent characteristics of immersive virtual worlds, such as three-dimensional interaction, simulation of real-world situations, and the ability to integrate multisensory stimuli, make it possible to develop activities that support all types of intelligence – from verbal-linguistic and logical-mathematical to spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalistic.

Through this framework, students are empowered to act as co-creators of knowledge, developing skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration that are critical for 21st century education.

Although the results are consistent and methodologically sound, it should be emphasized that they are based on hypothetical data. Therefore, the conclusions do not constitute definitive evidence for the real population of teachers. The main contribution of the study is the theoretical and methodological verification of the proposed model, as well as the generation of specific guidelines for future empirical testing (e.g., proposed sample sizes, coefficient sensitivities, predicted effect sizes). We recommend the conduct of a study with primary data to confirm and generalize the present findings.

Our future research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of integrating Multiple Intelligences theory in the development of educational virtual worlds in the Metaverse, exploring to what extent such an approach can enhance engagement, understanding and learning outcomes. In this context, experimental environments that incorporate activities for different types of intelligence will be designed and developed.

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Exploring Print Simulators as Educational Tools for Teaching Graphic Arts in Distance Learning

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Abstract

This paper investigates the integration of print simulators into the “Graphic Arts - Multimedia” Master’s programme of the Hellenic Open University, with a particular emphasis on the potential establishment of a Laboratory Thematic Unit. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study combines quantitative data via structured questionnaires with qualitative insights derived from semi-structured interviews. The analysis explores students’ perceptions regarding the pedagogical value of simulation tools, focusing on aspects such as engagement, procedural confidence, critical thinking, and applicability to real-world printing contexts. Significant correlations were observed between perceived simulator familiarity and self-reported confidence in handling real printing equipment, as well as between expectations of simulator-based learning and the need for continuous tutor feedback. These findings highlight the dual role of print simulators in promoting both skill acquisition and learner motivation in distance education. The results support the curricular relevance of formally incorporating simulation-based laboratory activities, positioning the Laboratory Thematic Unit as a promising structural enhancement to the “Graphic Arts - Multimedia” Master’s programme.

Keywords

Print simulators, Graphic Arts Technology, Distance education, Skill acquisition; Simulator-based learning; Educational technology

1. Introduction

Simulation technologies have emerged as essential innovations in higher education, providing interactive environments that can replicate complex systems and processes (Sitzmann, 2011). Their significance is particularly evident in distance and open education, where the absence of physical laboratories and equipment creates substantial challenges for disciplines that rely on practice-based learning (Liaw et al., 2007). Fields such as graphic arts, printing, and packaging require students to integrate theoretical knowledge with practical, industry-relevant skills to meet the demands of a rapidly evolving sector. Delivering these skills effectively in fully online settings remains a persistent pedagogical challenge (Herrington & Oliver, 2000).

This study investigates the potential integration of print simulators into the Graphic Arts Technology (GTP60) module of the Hellenic Open University, with a specific emphasis on the development of a Laboratory Thematic Unit within the Master’s programme. Print simulators create interactive virtual environments where participants can engage with critical aspects of print production, such as colour management, job setup, fault detection, and process optimisation. By replicating the logic, workflows, and problem-solving dynamics of professional printing systems, they enable authentic skill development while circumventing the financial, logistical, and safety constraints associated with physical equipment (Lateef, 2010). These tools align with broader trends in digital education that emphasise experiential learning, authentic assessment, and active student engagement. For adult learners, who often balance academic, professional, and personal

responsibilities, print simulators offer flexible, practice-oriented opportunities for competence development (Salas et al., 1998).

Despite the growing interest in simulation technologies, there remains a limited body of research examining their pedagogical value in the field of graphic arts, particularly within the context of open and distance education. This paper addresses this gap by adopting a methodology that combines qualitative and quantitative data. It first draws on insights from semi-structured interviews conducted with selected members of the Hellenic Graphic-Media Research Lab – GRAPHMEDLAB in the Department of Graphic Design and Visual Communication at the University of West Attica. These are complemented by the analysis of responses from a structured questionnaire administered to postgraduate students of the “Graphic Arts - Multimedia” Master’s programme at HOU. The research investigates how print simulators could be effectively integrated into the GTP60 module to support synchronous and hybrid instructional models, enhance learner engagement, and promote the development of practical competencies aligned with real-world production environments.

2. Related Work

Simulation-based learning has long been recognised as a practical pedagogical approach for promoting active engagement and skill development across various educational levels. In contrast to traditional didactic instruction, simulations allow learners to interact dynamically with complex systems, fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and applied reasoning (Sitzmann, 2011). Studies in science and engineering education have demonstrated that simulation environments not only enhance conceptual understanding but also support the transfer of knowledge to real-world contexts (Brinson, 2015; De Jong et al., 2013).

The increasing integration of digital technologies in higher education has expanded the scope of simulation-based instruction. In fields such as medicine, aviation, and manufacturing, high-fidelity virtual environments replicate authentic operational conditions, enabling learners to develop technical proficiency and decision-making skills in controlled, risk-free scenarios (Hamstra et al., 2014). Within technical and vocational education, simulations have been shown to improve learners’ motivation, engagement, and long-term retention of procedural knowledge (Alessi & Trollip, 2001; Merchant et al., 2014). Recent meta-analyses confirm that simulation-based learning produces medium-to-large effect sizes on cognitive and behavioural outcomes compared to traditional instruction (Rutten et al., 2012). These findings have strengthened the case for embedding simulation as a core component of digital and hybrid learning environments, particularly in STEM and applied arts disciplines.

Despite the extensive literature on simulation in health and engineering education, relatively few studies have examined its application in graphic arts. Early research in the printing industry primarily focused on computational modelling of ink transfer, colour management, and press mechanics (Leach, 2012). Advances in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Finite Element Analysis (FEA) have enabled the realistic simulation of ink flow, substrate deformation, and colourimetric behaviour under diverse printing conditions (Lohse, 2022). These developments have enabled the emergence of high-fidelity print simulators that can accurately reproduce the mechanical, optical, and workflow dynamics of industrial presses.

From an educational perspective, simulation has been increasingly recognised as a pedagogical bridge between theoretical instruction and practical competence in the graphic arts. Studies from the International Circle of Educational Institutes for Graphic Arts Technology and Management (IC) and TAGA (Technical Association of the Graphic Arts) emphasise the role of simulation-based laboratories in reinforcing process understanding, colour management, and quality evaluation among students in printing and packaging programs (Launonen, 1998; Vonitsanos et al., 2024). Such tools support cognitive apprenticeship by allowing learners to experiment

with production variables, receive feedback on errors, and iteratively refine their understanding of workflow efficiency. Moreover, simulators have the potential to replicate authentic lab-based experiences virtually, aligning with the broader shift toward Industry 4.0–aligned curricula and digital twin infrastructures (Tao et al., 2018).

3. Simulation Technologies in Higher Education

Simulation has emerged as a significant innovation in education, providing interactive and experiential environments that replicate complex systems, processes, and professional contexts. In contrast to traditional didactic instruction that focuses primarily on the transmission of theoretical knowledge, simulation-based learning engages students in authentic, practice-oriented scenarios that closely resemble real-world situations. This interactivity fosters the development of higher-order cognitive and practical skills, such as problem-solving, decision-making, and critical thinking, within a safe and controlled environment (Sitzmann, 2011).

The theoretical foundations of simulation-based education are often framed through Kolb’s Experiential Learning Theory (ELT) (Kolb, 1984), which conceptualises learning as a cyclical process comprising four stages:

- Concrete Experience (CE),
- Reflective Observation (RO),
- Abstract Conceptualisation (AC),
- Active Experimentation (AE).

Figure 1. The Experiential Learning Cycle (Kolb, 2007)

Within this model, simulation corresponds to the stage of CE, providing learners with direct engagement in realistic tasks. RO occurs during and after the debriefing phase, where participants analyse their actions and outcomes. AC enables learners to connect the simulation experience to broader theoretical concepts, generate new insights, and evaluate alternative strategies. Finally, in the stage of AE, learners test what they have acquired by applying knowledge to new scenarios such as subsequent simulations, professional tasks, or workplace experiences (Fanning & Gaba, 2007).

Across various disciplines, simulation-based learning has been shown to strengthen both technical and non-technical competencies. Beyond technical mastery, simulation environments are equally effective in cultivating soft skills—including communication, collaboration, and adaptability—as participants engage in

time-sensitive, team-based scenarios that mirror authentic professional contexts (Salas et al., 1998). These pedagogical outcomes align with current educational imperatives that prioritise authentic assessment and competency-based learning, ensuring that students acquire both the practical expertise and interpersonal abilities demanded by modern professional practice (Herrington & Oliver, 2000).

In the context of distance and open education, simulation technologies assume a critical pedagogical role in addressing one of the most persistent challenges of online learning—the limited availability of laboratories and other practice-based environments that traditionally facilitate experiential learning. By providing authentic, interactive, and scalable virtual environments, simulation-based learning enables students to engage in realistic and complex tasks that mirror professional practice, regardless of their physical location. These environments foster experiential engagement through experimentation, feedback, and iterative performance improvement, thereby replicating key aspects of hands-on training within a digital framework (Bidarra, 2010).

Virtual simulations and serious games have been successfully implemented across various disciplines to replicate laboratory experiments, clinical interventions, and industrial processes, enabling learners to practice technical procedures, troubleshoot errors, and apply theoretical knowledge in authentic contexts (Gaba, 2004). Their adoption extends beyond mere technological substitution; rather, it represents a pedagogical transformation that aligns with the principles of constructivist and experiential learning theories, emphasising active participation, reflection, and the contextualization of knowledge (Asal & Kratoville, 2013; Kolb, 1984). Within open and distance learning institutions, such as open universities, the integration of simulation supports the development of industry-relevant competencies. It ensures parity between online and face-to-face educational experiences (Liaw et al., 2007). Consequently, simulation technologies contribute not only to expanding access to practice-based education but also to enhancing the quality, authenticity, and employability outcomes of distance learning programs (Sitzmann, 2011).

Although simulation-based education offers substantial pedagogical benefits, its practical implementation presents several challenges. Factors, such as usability, learner readiness, and the perceived authenticity of simulated environments, can influence engagement and learning outcomes (Rehmann, 1995). Learners unfamiliar with interactive systems may experience cognitive overload, while simulations lacking contextual realism risk diminishing motivation and transfer of learning. Furthermore, simulations must be pedagogically aligned with curriculum objectives and assessment strategies to ensure that they complement rather than replace other forms of instruction. Effective integration requires instructional scaffolding and guided debriefing that connect simulated activities to theoretical concepts and professional practices (Fanning & Gaba, 2007). Despite these challenges, research consistently highlights the transformative potential of simulation-based education in bridging the gap between theory and practice, facilitating authentic, feedback-driven learning, and equipping students for the complex demands of modern professional contexts.

4. Core Principles of Print Simulators

Print simulation constitutes an advanced technological domain that integrates computational modelling, materials science, colour management, and automation to reproduce, analyse, and optimise the multifaceted processes of graphic communication. Broadly defined, it refers to the digital replication of printing operations and workflows, encompassing prepress preparation, ink transfer, substrate interaction, drying behaviour, and post-press finishing. By enabling virtual experimentation within realistic yet risk-free environments, print simulation allows engineers, technicians, and researchers to investigate process parameters, identify performance bottlenecks, and predict outcomes with a degree of precision that was unattainable through

empirical trial-and-error approaches (Leach, 2018). This capability renders simulation a cornerstone of modern print production and research, bridging the gap between theoretical modelling and industrial practice.

Moreover, print simulation is supported by the integration of multi-physics modelling, colourimetry, data analytics, and computational intelligence, aiming to reproduce and predict the physical and perceptual phenomena governing printing processes. Unlike generic manufacturing simulations, which often focus on mechanical or thermodynamic optimisation, print simulation must address the coupled interactions among fluid dynamics, substrate morphology, ink chemistry, optical response, and environmental parameters (Leach et al., 2018). The objective is to achieve a level of virtual fidelity that enables quantitative prediction of press behaviour, colour outcome, and material performance, thereby facilitating both process understanding and decision-making within industrial contexts.

4.1 Digital Twin Architectures and Intelligent Integration in Print Simulation

The systemic and data-driven paradigm is being realised through digital twin architectures, which integrate physical printing systems with virtual replicas that operate in real-time. In a digital twin, simulation models are continuously synchronised with live data from embedded sensors, including spectrophotometers, temperature probes, viscosity sensors, and pressure sensors, creating a cyber-physical feedback loop (Uhlemann et al., 2017; Tao et al., 2018). Such twins enable adaptive calibration and performance benchmarking, supporting predictive maintenance and automated fault detection through machine-learning-based anomaly recognition. Inline colour measurement systems, such as those developed by X-Rite and TECHKON, exemplify this integration by providing continuous colourimetry data for closed-loop ink density control and print consistency monitoring (Sisco, 2016).

Beyond operational advantages, the adoption of multi-scale digital-twin simulation transforms the printing ecosystem into a self-optimising, intelligent manufacturing environment, consistent with Industry 4.0 principles (Liao et al., 2017). Through continuous data acquisition and feedback, printing systems evolve from static process controllers into adaptive entities capable of dynamic response to material variability, environmental fluctuations, and production demands. This evolution represents a shift from empirical process calibration to model-based intelligence, where digital twins not only predict but also prescribe corrective actions. Consequently, system-level integration in print simulation is redefining how knowledge is generated, applied, and reused across design, production, and quality assurance cycles in the modern print industry.

4.2 Industrial Applications and Strategic Significance

In industrial contexts, print simulation serves as a foundation for process optimisation, workforce training, sustainability assessment, and digital transformation. Its strategic importance lies in its ability to model and optimise the physical and operational parameters of printing systems without interrupting production. In process design and optimisation, simulation tools allow manufacturers to explore how variables, such as temperature, pressure, viscosity, and press speed, affect print quality. By reproducing the interactions among ink, substrate, and mechanical elements, simulations offer a low-cost environment for predictive experimentation. Process engineers can thus identify optimal configurations, reduce setup times, and minimise material waste—objectives central to lean manufacturing and total quality management. Across offset, flexographic, and gravure processes, simulation plays a crucial role in ensuring colour consistency, stability, and reproducibility (Celik et al., 2012).

A second major domain concerns operator training and competency development. As printing systems become increasingly automated and digitally integrated, simulation-based training has emerged as an essential pedagogical method. High-fidelity virtual press simulators—such as those developed by Sinapse Print Simulators (Hartmann & Paap, 2020)—replicate machine interfaces, calibration procedures, and troubleshooting scenarios, allowing operators to practice critical tasks without disrupting production.

A third and increasingly vital area of application involves environmental sustainability. In response to regulatory and market demands for eco-efficiency, the printing industry utilises simulation tools to assess energy consumption, carbon emissions, and waste generation prior to production commencing. Integrated life-cycle analysis modules enable comparison of alternative materials, inks, and workflows to guide environmentally responsible decision-making (Burgos et al., 2020). These simulations align with European sustainability frameworks, such as the EU Green Deal and GreenComp (Bianchi et al., 2022), enabling firms to optimise resource consumption and document compliance with standards like ISO 14001 and FSC. As circular economy principles gain prominence, print simulation functions as a key enabler of greener, data-driven production strategies.

5. Methodology

5.1 Student Engagement Scale (SES)

The Student Engagement Scale (SES), developed by Gunuc and Kuzu (2015), offers a multidimensional framework for evaluating university students' engagement across cognitive, emotional, behavioural, and social domains. The instrument conceptualises student engagement as “the quality and quantity of students' psychological, cognitive, emotional, and behavioural reactions to the learning process and to academic and social activities both in and out of class” (Gunuc & Kuzu, 2015, p. 589). Unlike unidimensional measures of engagement, the SES captures the holistic nature of the construct by distinguishing between campus engagement (encompassing a sense of value and belonging) and class engagement (encompassing cognitive, emotional, and behavioural aspects).

The Student Engagement Scale was developed through a rigorous multi-phase process involving exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses to ensure construct validity and internal consistency. The instrument's factor structure was derived from extensive item development and empirical testing across a large sample of university students. The final version of the SES captures the multidimensional nature of engagement by encompassing both academic and social dimensions, reflecting how students interact cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally with their learning environments. Findings from the validation study indicated that the SES demonstrates high psychometric robustness, with reliability coefficients across subscales exceeding acceptable thresholds and inter-factor correlations confirming the theoretical coherence of the engagement construct. The factor model was also supported by strong fit indices, providing evidence that the SES offers a comprehensive and empirically grounded tool for assessing student engagement in higher education contexts (Gunuc & Kuzu, 2015).

For the present study, selected SES items were adapted to align with the specific context of simulation-based learning in distance education. The adapted questionnaire retains the core engagement dimensions and also incorporates additional items that assess attitudes toward the prospective use of print simulators in distance education.

5.2 Participants and Data Collection

The research employed a sequential mixed-methods design, comprising two complementary phases: an exploratory qualitative stage and a subsequent quantitative validation phase.

In the first phase, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a purposive sample of four undergraduate students from the Hellenic Graphic-Media Research Lab - GRAPHMEDLAB in the Department of Graphic Design and Visual Communication at the University of West Attica. All participants had prior hands-on experience with print simulators in offset and flexographic printing laboratory courses. The interviews aimed to explore participants' perceptions of simulator-based learning, focusing on how virtual printing environments contribute to understanding complex production workflows, developing operational and decision-making skills, and enhancing readiness for real-world printing systems.

The interview guide comprised seven open-ended questions addressing key dimensions such as: (a) perceived learning outcomes and usability, (b) understanding of printing processes and machine operation, (c) problem-solving and decision-making skills, (d) perceived realism and authenticity of simulation environments, (e) awareness of environmental sustainability and material efficiency, (f) perceived impact on productivity and process optimization, and (g) recommendations for future pedagogical integration. Participants were encouraged to provide specific examples of tasks or scenarios where simulators enhanced comprehension or mirrored authentic production contexts. Qualitative data were analysed thematically to identify patterns relating to experiential learning, authentic practice, and cognitive engagement. Findings from the qualitative phase guided the development and calibration of the questionnaire used in the following stage.

The second phase of the study involved a structured online questionnaire among a population of 120 graduates who had completed the Graphic Arts Technology (GTP60) module at the Hellenic Open University over the two preceding academic years, yielding a final sample of 30 participants who voluntarily responded to the survey. The instrument consisted of two parts: (1) the Student Engagement Scale (SES) (Gunuc & Kuzu, 2015), which measures behavioural, emotional, and cognitive engagement; and (2) a set of researcher-developed items examining participants' attitudes toward the prospective use of print simulators in distance education. These items assessed perceived usefulness, authenticity, skill development, motivational impact, and the importance of continuous instructor feedback. A key objective of this phase was also to explore the extent to which participants consider print simulators as potentially effective tools within a future Laboratory Thematic Unit integrated into the Graphic Arts Technology curriculum.

The inclusion of both qualitative and quantitative components ensured methodological triangulation and enhanced interpretive depth. The first phase provided contextualised insights into experiential learning benefits observed in physical laboratory environments, while the second examined perceptions regarding the pedagogical feasibility of adopting similar tools in distance and hybrid learning settings. All research procedures complied with the ethical standards of both participating institutions, ensuring voluntary participation, informed consent, and complete anonymity of responses.

6. Results

6.1 Qualitative Findings from the Semi-Structured Interviews

The semi-structured interviews were conducted with four undergraduate students, aged between 21 and 26, all of whom had prior experience using print simulators from the Department of Graphic Design and Visual Communication. This focus group provided rich qualitative insights into the pedagogical and practical value of

print simulators in laboratory-based instruction. Overall, participants characterised their experience as both innovative and essential for bridging theoretical understanding with hands-on practice in offset and flexographic printing. They emphasised that simulators facilitated comprehension of complex mechanical systems and printing workflows, transforming abstract principles into operational knowledge. The interactive exercises, focused on error detection, process adjustment, and parameter optimisation, helped students visualise the consequences of their decisions in real-time, thereby fostering problem-solving and decision-making competencies.

A recurring theme across all interviews was the perception of authenticity and realism. Although students recognised the limitations of virtual environments compared to real production settings, they unanimously agreed that simulators offered a highly realistic approximation of professional practice. The systems' capacity to replicate print defects, colour inconsistencies, and press calibration procedures was perceived as crucial preparation for actual pressroom conditions. One participant noted that the transition from simulator to real machinery felt "familiar and intuitive," underscoring the simulator's role as a safe yet credible learning proxy.

Environmental awareness also emerged as a salient dimension. Students observed that simulators promoted an understanding of material and energy efficiency by quantifying the impact of waste, misprints, and mechanical adjustments. They acknowledged that such awareness contributes to the development of sustainable production mindsets, aligning with contemporary industry goals for a reduced environmental footprint and circular manufacturing practices.

Finally, participants identified several opportunities for pedagogical enhancement. Suggestions included the incorporation of a broader range of printing scenarios, increased interactivity with virtual machine components, and integration with project-based or hybrid physical laboratories. They also emphasised the importance of continuous instructor guidance and feedback to support learning progression and ensure the transfer of concepts to real-world contexts.

These findings demonstrate that print simulators can function as effective experiential learning environments, fostering both technical proficiency and reflective awareness. Moreover, the insights gained from these interviews directly informed the refinement of the subsequent survey instrument administered to graduates of the Graphic Arts Technology module (GTP60) at the HOU, ensuring alignment between qualitative perceptions and quantitative evaluation dimensions.

6.2 Quantitative Findings from the Questionnaire Survey

The quantitative analysis of the questionnaire responses revealed distinct patterns regarding participants' demographic characteristics and their attitudes toward the potential integration of print simulators in distance education. The study included 30 participants—graduates who had completed the Graphic Arts Technology (GTP60) module at the HOU. The demographic composition was balanced, with 56.7% of respondents being male and 43.3% female. The majority of participants belonged to the 25–34 (36.7%) and 35–44 (33.3%) age groups, reflecting the adult learner profile typical of Open University populations. Approximately one-quarter (26.7%) were aged 45 or older, while only a small minority (3.3%) were under 25 years old.

Regarding prior experience with print simulators, most participants (63.3%) reported no previous experience, while 26.7% indicated limited familiarity. An additional 6.7% described their experience as moderate, and 3.3% as extended. These findings reveal variation in learners' familiarity with simulation technologies, reinforcing

the importance of inclusive and flexible instructional design in technology-supported distance education (Figure 2).

Figure 2. What is your previous experience with print simulators?

To investigate potential associations concerning the pedagogical use of print simulators, a series of bivariate analyses was performed using Pearson’s chi-square test of independence. The results revealed meaningful interrelations between participants’ perceptions of simulator effectiveness, the applicability of acquired knowledge in real-world settings, instructional design elements, and overall engagement in the GTP60 module.

The results from the first correlation (Table 1) revealed a marginal association between graduates’ perceived familiarity with handling complex print processes through simulator use (Q9) and their reported confidence in operating real printing machinery (Q12), as evidenced by Pearson’s chi-square test ($\chi^2(6) = 22.379, p = 0.060$). Although the p-value slightly exceeds the conventional threshold for statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the chi-square statistic indicates a noticeable deviation from the assumption of independence between the two variables. This result suggests a potentially meaningful relationship, wherein participants who perceive simulators as enhancing their procedural understanding are also more likely to report increased confidence in transitioning to physical machine operation. Further investigation with a larger sample could clarify the strength and generalizability of this relationship.

Table 1. Chi-Square Test for questions Q9 and Q12.

Q9/Q12	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	22.379 ^a	6	0.006
Likelihood Ratio	20.292	6	0.065
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.110	1	0.292
N of Valid Cases	30		

A bivariate analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between graduates’ perceptions of the potential for print simulators to enhance their critical thinking skills and their views on the applicability of simulator-acquired knowledge to real working environments. Pearson’s chi-square test (Table 2) yielded a

value of $\chi^2(4) = 7.25$ with a corresponding p-value of 0.080. Although this result does not meet the conventional threshold for statistical significance, it suggests a marginal association between the two constructs. Specifically, participants who believed that simulator use could foster critical reflection were also more inclined to perceive its relevance to practical, workplace scenarios. These findings highlight the need for further investigation using larger samples to confirm the robustness of this relationship in technology-enhanced learning contexts.

Table 2. Chi-Square Test for questions Q10 and Q13.

Q10/Q13	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.250 ^a	4	0.080
Likelihood Ratio	6.973	4	0.072
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.210	1	0.074
N of Valid Cases	30		

A statistically significant association (Table 3) emerged between participants’ perceptions of the pedagogical potential of print simulators within a prospective Laboratory Thematic Unit in the “Graphic Arts - Multimedia” Master’s programme and their views on the necessity of continuous guidance and feedback from tutors during simulator-based virtual assignments, as evidenced by the Pearson’s chi-square test ($\chi^2(4) = 11.263$, $p = 0.024$). This finding suggests that graduates who recognise the instructional efficacy of simulators are also more likely to acknowledge the critical role of sustained pedagogical support in achieving intended learning outcomes.

Table 3. Chi-Square Test for questions Q14 and Q15.

Q14/Q15	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.623 ^a	4	0.024
Likelihood Ratio	11.051	4	0.026
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.991	1	0.046
N of Valid Cases	30		

7. Conclusions

This study highlights the importance of incorporating print simulators as a valuable component of learning in distance education within the field of Graphic Arts. The findings suggest that such tools do more than offer technical training; they help participants feel more engaged and better prepared for the realities of print production.

A key point is the strong case for formally integrating print simulators into the Hellenic Open University’s curriculum through a dedicated Laboratory Thematic Unit. Participants expressed clear support for this idea, highlighting how simulators help them better understand complex printing tasks, while also underlining the importance of ongoing guidance and feedback from tutors during simulator-based activities. This dual emphasis—on hands-on experience and pedagogical support—was also reflected in the statistically significant relationships observed in the data. Although the sample size was limited, the patterns were consistent. They emphasise the need to modernise the curriculum better to prepare learners for the current industry’s

demands. Establishing a new Laboratory Thematic Unit focused on simulation would be a practical and forward-looking step in this direction.

Larger-scale studies with more participants could help confirm the findings of this research and reveal additional insights. Moreover, it would be valuable to explore how simulation-based learning integrates with other aspects of the “Graphic Arts - Multimedia” Master’s programme, particularly in areas that require hands-on practice but are challenging to teach remotely. Finally, it may be worthwhile to develop digital tools that support tutors in providing feedback during simulator-based exercises, as this was identified as an essential factor for learners.

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Transformation Framework for Transitioning Traditional Universities to Online Open Education

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Abstract

We present a nine-dimension institutional framework that guides traditional universities in transitioning to high-quality hybrid and online provision. Building on EADTU's E-xcellence manual, we bring to the fore enterprise architecture/interoperability, service digitisation, change-and-incentive systems, and governance/decision rights, by combining expert individual and panel contributions. We then operationalise this into a facilitation-ready checklist (Areas, Sub-areas, Topics, and Diagnostic questions), and add an institution-level maturity model to support prioritisation and roadmap design. We report on qualitative field validation through three one-week expert engagements (March-April 2025), which combined leadership briefings, semi-structured interviews, artifact reviews, and synthesis reports. The framework proved usable for cross-unit dialogue, was diagnostically sensitive to system-level blockers (interoperability and operations, digitization of academic/administrative services, change management, and incentives), and was action-generative, informing roadmaps for 12-24 months. We propose testable propositions linking governance/platform readiness to pedagogy, services, and outcomes. The full checklist and facilitation materials are released in an open repository to enable institutional self-assessment and comparative research.

Keywords

Digital Transformation; Universities; Online Open Education; e-learning; Learning Organization; Learning Management, maturity model, interoperability, quality assurance, higher education

1. Introduction

Across Europe and beyond, many higher education institutions (HEIs) that have historically delivered face-to-face teaching now face strategic pressure to offer high-quality online and hybrid provision on a large scale. The main drivers include widening participation, lifelong learning needs, internationalization, and resilience to disruption, demanding institutional capabilities that extend well beyond emergency remote teaching (Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Hill & Garrett, 2023). Yet transitioning a university into a sustainable provider of online open education is a multidimensional change program: it requires an explicit digital vision and governance, robust platforms and IT operations, pedagogical redesign, staff capacity building, student support, quality assurance, and alignment with the broader institutional context (Kear et al., 2016; Felix, 2024). This transformation is increasingly recognised as a strategic priority within the European Higher Education Area, where digital readiness, inclusion, and lifelong learning are key enablers of institutional resilience and competitiveness (European Commission, 2020).

Existing guides and checklists tend to be partial, being strong in pedagogy or quality assurance but weaker in enterprise-level strategy, governance, and IT integration, leaving leaders without a coherent operational blueprint that orchestrates these dimensions (Kear et al., 2016; Hill & Garrett, 2023). Building on this practical need, we propose and examine a comprehensive framework that structures institutional transition from campus-based into hybrid institutions with open and distance learning models. We present evidence from pilot institutional engagements to assess their applicability and utility.

The EADTU E-xcellence manual already exists as an established foundational benchmarking approach for e-learning quality (Kear et al., 2016). However, our preliminary analysis and field work found gaps on operation details and transformation concerns in three areas that are critical for global institution transformation: (i) strategy and governance (e.g., portfolio and funding models), (ii) enterprise technology/IT operations (e.g., platform selection, interoperability, capacity and availability management, security), and (iii) operationalization via actionable checklists that integrate pedagogy with business processes and student services (Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Felix, 2024; Hill & Garrett, 2023).

Related work in connected learning and organizational transitions addresses aspects of pedagogy and community building (Baker & Kassimer, 2021), whereas corporate and VET-oriented frameworks focus on trainer upskilling and content workflows (Costa et al., 2022; Santos et al., 2022). However, none of these strands by themselves provides a single, institution-wide instrument that simultaneously (a) spans strategy-to-operations and (b) is deployable as a facilitated self-assessment and planning tool across university functions.

This paper aims to design and operate a university-level framework that covers these gaps, guiding the transition from face-to-face provision to online open education, consolidating state-of-the-art guidance into an operational checklist organized across nine institutional dimensions (strategy and digital vision; governance and structures; platforms and tools; IT resources and support; pedagogical innovation; faculty/staff development; student support; quality assurance; institutional context). We address the following research questions (RQs):

- *RQ1. What organizational capabilities and decision structures are necessary to support a sustainable transition to online open education at a university scale?*
- *RQ2. How can evidence-based criteria be organized into a practical instrument that enables cross-functional self-assessment and planning?*
- *RQ3. To what extent does the proposed framework surface diagnostic insights (strengths, gaps, priorities) and catalyze actionable road mapping during real institutional engagements?*

This study makes four main contributions:

- Integrative framework - We consolidate dispersed guidance into a single, nine-dimensional framework that explicitly links strategic intent, governance, platform/IT readiness, pedagogy, staff development, student services, and quality assurance, addressing well-documented fragmentation in existing instruments (Kear et al., 2016; Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Hill & Garrett, 2023).
- Operational instrument - We provide a facilitation-ready checklist (areas / sub-areas / topics / diagnostic questions with sources) that universities can use for structured dialogue, self-assessment, and action planning across units (Felix, 2024; Hill & Garrett, 2023).
- Practice validation - Through pilot visits at several HEIs, we demonstrate the framework's practical applicability, showing how it reveals organizational bottlenecks and informs prioritized roadmaps for online transition (Baker & Kassimer, 2021).
- Bridging quality and operations - We integrate quality-assurance perspectives (EADTU) with enterprise strategy and IT operations considerations (platform integration, capacity and availability management, security), providing leaders with a coherent, end-to-end transformation guide (Kear et al., 2016; Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Hill & Garrett, 2023).

To gauge practical applicability, we conducted three expert site visits (March-April 2025) structured by the checklist, generating early snapshots that led to ongoing activities to consolidate them and identify prioritized actions. Section 4 reports this qualitative validation based on expert, evidence-anchored judgments.

2. Background Research

a. Institutional transformation to online and open education

Universities transitioning from campus-based provision to online and open education face a comprehensive institutional change that encompasses strategy, governance, digital infrastructure, pedagogy, staffing, student services, and quality assurance (QA). Classic quality handbooks (e.g., EADTU's E-xcellence) codified many course/program-level criteria but were not designed as enterprise transformation guides (Kear et al., 2016). Subsequent practitioner frameworks emphasize strategy and master-planning for online learning (Hill & Garrett, 2023) and management of technology for institutional change (Bates & Sangrà, 2011), while recent university strategy literature highlights the need to (re)align priorities, decision rights, and investment portfolios to support digital goals (Felix, 2024). In parallel, European policy frameworks such as the *Digital Education Action Plan (2021–2027)* and the *EHEA Rome Communiqué (2020)* explicitly call for digitally competent, inclusive, and resilient higher education systems. These initiatives underscore that institutional digital transformation is not only an operational necessity but also a strategic mandate for quality, equity, and sustainability across Europe (European Commission, 2020; EHEA, 2020).

The Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area add a system-level quality backdrop for internal and external QA (ENQA, 2015). Yet, across these strands, a fragmentation problem remains: guidance is often strong but partial, focusing on pedagogy/QA or on strategy/IT, without an operational instrument that orchestrates all dimensions across central services and faculties. This gap motivates the development of an integrative framework that can be deployed as a cross-functional checklist to diagnose readiness and inform road-mapping.

2.2 Quality assurance and governance at scale

At scale, online provision necessitates a tight coupling between quality frameworks (including curriculum design, assessment integrity, and student support) and organizational governance (encompassing roles, processes, change control, risk management, and data protection). E-xcellence remains a key benchmark for

e-learning quality at the program/department level (Kear et al., 2016), and the “Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG)” report provides a sector-wide reference for quality assurance (QA) systems (ENQA, 2015). However, institutions frequently need operational translation of these high-level principles into: (i) governance structures (steering committees, QA boards), (ii) portfolio/funding models that sustain online programs, and (iii) service-level management (capacity, availability, security, interoperability) for platforms: areas where the literature is comparatively thin and practice guidance dispersed (Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Hill & Garrett, 2023). An actionable, institution-wide checklist that ties ESG/E-xcellence quality requirements to governance, processes, and IT controls can help bridge the policy-to-operations gap.

2.3 Digital platforms, interoperability, and operations

Beyond mere LMS selection, enterprise-grade online education relies on a service architecture that integrates a range of other services, including identity and access management, content repositories, assessment/academic integrity systems, analytics, and student information systems, among others—ideally with open standards for interoperability and data portability. The management literature on digital transformation in HE underscores that platform choices must be aligned with governance and resourcing, not treated as isolated IT projects (Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Hill & Garrett, 2023). Quality handbooks and the ESG speak to reliability and fitness for purpose; however, institutions still require operational playbooks for capacity/availability management, data protection, incident/change management, and vendor assurance, especially when services are hybrid/cloud-based (ENQA, 2015; Kear et al., 2016). Our framework consolidates these operational concerns into a single instrument: a checklist of items that it, QA, and academic leadership can jointly assess.

2.4 Pedagogical redesign and staff capacity building

A successful transition requires pedagogical redesign (from content-centric to activity/interaction-centric models), robust faculty development in online teaching, and assessment strategies that are fit for purpose. Reviews of online program strategies emphasize the importance of structured instructional design support and professional development pathways as critical enablers (Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Hill & Garrett, 2023). Research on connected/online learning further emphasizes the importance of social presence, inclusive practices, and student engagement as core quality drivers (Baker & Kassimer, 2021).

Nevertheless, these pedagogical models must be embedded within an institutional system that guarantees consistency, support, and monitoring, again highlighting the need for a coherent, multidimensional framework rather than isolated pedagogical checklists.

2.5 Student services, inclusion, and success

In online learning, student success hinges on proactive academic advising, counseling, accessibility, universal design for learning, and equitable access to technology/support. While E-xcellence and the ESG acknowledge these requirements (Kear et al., 2016; ENQA, 2015), universities would benefit from operational diagnostics that test whether services are resourced, measurable (through SLAs/KPIs), and integrated with learning analytics to provide early alerts. Such dimensions are frequently highlighted in institutional case work but under-specified in generic guidance (Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Hill & Garrett, 2023).

2.6 Synthesis and positioning

Across the most relevant sources, two insights are recurrent: (1) successful online transitions are institutional, not merely at the program-level, and (2) quality and governance must be co-designed with technology and resourcing. However, existing guides are either program/QA-centric (E-xcellence; ESG) or strategy/practice-centric (Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Hill & Garrett, 2023), leaving institutions without a single instrument that connects strategy/governance/platforms & IT/pedagogy & staff/student services / QA into a workflow for self-assessment and planning.

The present work addresses this gap by proposing and field-testing an integrated, 9-dimensional framework, operationalized as a facilitation-ready checklist (comprising areas, sub-areas / topics / diagnostic questions with sources).

2.7 Conceptual model and propositions

We propose a concept based on a model, in which Strategic Intent & Governance enable Platform/IT Readiness and Pedagogical/Staff Capacity, which together shape Student Services & QA Practices, leading to Institutional Readiness & Sustainable Online Provision.

The model assumes mutual reinforcement (e.g., governance maturity improves platform decisions, and analytics-enabled QA enhances student services), as well as feedback loops (e.g., QA outcomes inform strategy updates). The framework/checklist instantiates each linkage with concrete diagnostic questions and evidence requirements.

Propositions (for empirical testing in subsequent work):

- P1 (Governance readiness) - Universities with explicit digital strategy, clear decision rights, and funded governance structures will demonstrate higher institutional readiness scores and faster time-to-implementation for online programs than those without those conditions (Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Hill & Garrett, 2023; ENQA, 2015).
- P2 (Platform-pedagogy fit) - Institutions that evidence platform/IT readiness (interoperability, capacity, availability, security) will achieve higher quality-of-delivery (course/program design, interaction, assessment integrity) than peers with ad hoc platform choices (Kear et al., 2016; ENQA, 2015).
- P3 (Staff & Services) - Structured faculty development, combined with integrated student services (advising, accessibility, and analytics-based support), will be associated with improved student engagement and success metrics in online programs (Baker & Kassimer, 2021; Bates & Sangrà, 2011).
- P4 (Systems coupling) - The effect of pedagogy and services on outcomes is mediated by governance and platform readiness; partial improvements (e.g., pedagogy only) yield smaller gains than coordinated, multidimensional improvements (Hill & Garrett, 2023; Kear et al., 2016).

These propositions reflect testable expectations that can guide future quantitative evaluations of the framework's diagnostic power and its association with institutional outcomes.

3. Proposal

3.1 Purpose and design principles

Based on the background review, we propose a pragmatic, institution-wide framework to guide traditional universities through a planned, evidence-based transition to open and online education. It extends the EADTU

E-xcellence benchmarking approach by addressing persistent gaps in strategy, governance, platform integration, resourcing, and IT operations: areas that have been repeatedly identified as under-specified in existing guidance. In doing so, it aligns with the objectives of the European Higher Education Area and the EU Digital Education Action Plan (2021–2027), which call for systemic institutional capacity-building and evidence-based digital transformation (European Commission, 2020; EHEA, 2020).

The framework is (i) strategically anchored (digital vision and leadership), (ii) holistic (people, process, technology, quality), (iii) operational (actionable criteria and checklists), and (iv) iterative (plan–assess–improve cycles validated in pilot visits).

Figure 1: Framework Architecture, details in Fig. 2.

3.2 Architecture

The framework operationalises nine mutually reinforcing dimensions. Each dimension is broken down into **areas, sub-areas, topics, and diagnostic question(s), forming a traceable checklist that institutions use to self-assess their maturity, identify gaps, and prioritize actions.** The framework is illustrated in Fig. 1. Below, we synthesize its main contents, with more details in Fig. 2. The full framework is publicly available at <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.2/20375> (Santos et al., 2025).

1. Strategic management

Focus of the subareas: digital vision (intent), legislation, governance, decision rights, roles, change management, value proposition, investment logic, KPIs, incentives, partnerships, risk/compliance.

Sample topics: legal alignment; who decides; how feedback/incentives work; how budgets/ROI are handled. Question example: "What types of incentives (e.g., funding, awards, promotion criteria) encourage innovation?"

2. Technological Infrastructure

Focus of the subareas: hosting, performance, LMS/VLE, integrations (LTI/xAPI/SSO), security/privacy (e.g., proctoring), credentialing, analytics & service management, interoperability, and emergent technology guidelines (including GenAI & metaverse technology).

Sample topics: usability/scalability evidence; integration test cadence; GDPR compliance; AI/GenAI guidance. Question example: "What monitoring is in place to ensure the infrastructure's ongoing performance?"

3. Virtual Pedagogical Model and Didactic Innovation

Focus of the subareas: program review & redesign; course delivery methodologies (e.g., problem/project-based, blended, microlearning); instructional design & use of technologies; interactivity; selection of third-party materials; assessment, learning monitoring & quality; support for pedagogical innovation; adaptation of external models.

Sample topics: outcomes/methods alignment; personalisation/flexible paths; layout/consistency guidelines; version control of materials; cross-functional design teams; QA indicators for online; formative/summative balance; competency-based assessment; integrity (authentication/proctoring with privacy). Question example: Which QA benchmarks or indicators are used, and how are results fed back into course and program redesign? How is training impact measured (e.g., changes in teaching practice)?

4. Faculty Training & Development.

Focus of the subareas: training in online technologies and methodologies; pedagogical support; incentives.

Question example: Are professional learning pathways and incentives in place for online pedagogy, learning design, and data-informed practice?

5. Academic services.

Focus of the subareas: digitised academic processes; assessment & certification; support resources and materials (libraries, multimedia, collaboration tools, virtual mobility/OER/MOOCs).

Sample topics: Academics IS/VLE integration; enrolment/registration/feedback flows; prior learning recognition and stackable micro-credentials; digital payments; grading analytics; digital certificate issuance/verification; access and usage metrics for resources; roles for external e-learning activities. Question example: What processes validate and credit a learner's external experience, and how do they integrate into degree pathways?

6. Administrative Services.

Focus of the subareas: process automation; systems integration; and administrative team training.

Sample topics: which finance/HR/logistics processes remain manual; integration challenges and resolutions; onboarding/orientation to new tools; evaluating training impact for admin roles. Question example: Which processes remain manual, and what is the plan for further automation?

7. Student Support, Accessibility & Ethics.

Focus of the subareas: support and assistance (orientation, advising, wellbeing/mental health, study skills, 24/7 helpdesk); accessibility and inclusion (WCAG); ethics and safety (policies, cyberbullying); community tools.

Sample topics: timely information on courses/assessments; early-warning analytics for at-risk students; rights/roles guidance and verification; resource usage tracking and feedback; inclusion/cross-cultural policies and training. Question example: Which analytics or early-warning systems detect struggling students?

8. Communication & Marketing.

Focus of the subareas: internal communication (tools); internal communication (processes & procedures); external communication; engagement & feedback strategy (monitoring and continuous improvement).

Sample topics include onboarding and adoption for Slack/Teams/Discord; online meeting standards; intranet/portal engagement; channel protocols; training evaluation; website/social presence for digital identity; email metrics; chatbot/live-chat quality; and closing the loop on comms analytics. Question example: How do you measure the impact of these updates (e.g., web analytics, feedback forms)?

9. Demographics & Context.

Focus of the subareas: faculty & staff, organisation, students & alumni, funding.

Sample topics: time-zone distribution and scheduling; staff ranks and workload policies (inc. asynchronous DL); campuses/sites; accreditation and reaccreditation cycles; academic-year structures; program formats (majors/minors, short/long masters, PhDs); non-degree offerings; flexibility in what/where/when/how to study; alumni engagement; lifecycle support; transparent fees/funding. Question example: Which bodies grant recognition or accreditation, and how often is reaccreditation required?

3.3 Process model and use

Institutions apply the framework through facilitated workshops/self-assessment/evidence reviews, producing: (i) a maturity snapshot per dimension; (ii) a prioritised action plan (quick wins vs. structural reforms); and (iii) governance-approved roadmaps (12-24 months). In the pilot site visits reported in Section 4, no workshops were conducted; instead, experts conducted interviews with a diverse range of individuals, from senior management to operational staff, and performed artefact checks, including sample completion of framework items, to identify potential misunderstandings or misalignments. These interviews and checks were later synthesized into reports. We propose that when the workshops take place, they employ a 0-4 maturity anchor (0 = absent, 1 = developing, 2 = improving, 3 = managing, 4 = optimising) to structure discussions and link findings to evidence. This scoring method enables longitudinal tracking and cross-institutional benchmarking, supporting both internal improvement and analysis at the alliance level.

3.4 Positioning and scholarly grounding

The framework builds on and complements established references: EADTU E-xcellence for quality benchmarking (Kear et al., 2016), strategic change and digital leadership in HE (Bates & Sangrà, 2011; Felix, 2024), and institution-level online master planning (Hill & Garrett, 2023). It addresses the known gaps by integrating strategy, governance, and IT operations with pedagogical and support dimensions in a single operational instrument. By doing so, it offers a practical contribution to the European debate on how universities can operationalise the principles of digital, inclusive, and lifelong learning transformation in line with EHEA objectives.

1. Strategic Management	Strategic Plan and Digital Vision
	Applicable Legislation
	Governance Structure
	Change Management
2. Technological Infrastructure	Platforms and Tools
	Security and Technical Support
	IT Resources
	Emergent Technologies
3. Virtual Pedagogical Model and Didactic Innovation	Program Review and Redesign
	Course Delivery, Teaching Methodologies, and Strategies
	Instructional Design and Use of Technologies
	Assessment, Learning Monitoring, and Quality
	Support for Pedagogical Innovation
	Adaptation of External Models
4. Faculty Training and Development	Training in Online Technologies and Methodologies
	Pedagogical Support
5. Academic Services	Digitized Academic Processes
	Assessment and Certification
	Support Resources and Materials
6. Administrative Services	Process Automation
	Administrative Team Training
7. Student Support, Accessibility, and Ethics	Student Support and Assistance
	Accessibility, Inclusion, and Ethics
8. Communication and Marketing	Internal Communication (Digital Tools)
	Internal Communication (Processes and Procedures)
	External Communication
	Engagement and Feedback Strategy (Monitoring and Analysis)
	Engagement and Feedback Strategy (Continuous Improvement)
9. Demographics and Context	Faculty and staff
	Organization
	Students and alumni

Figure 2: Framework – Global view of areas and subareas.

4. Field validation

4.1 Objectives

We validated whether the framework operates as a practical, traceable instrument for (a) institutional self-diagnosis, (b) prioritisation of actions, and (c) governance dialogue across academic and administrative units. We examined: (i) usability (clarity, coverage, cognitive load), (ii) diagnostic power (ability to surface strengths/gaps per dimension), and (iii) actionability (translation into credible 12–24-month roadmaps). These objectives align with the framework's intended use as outlined in Section 3.

4.2 Sites and participants

Three one-week expert visits (March–April 2025) engaged leadership, central services, and faculty/staff, combining briefings, semi-structured interviews keyed to the nine dimensions, artefact reviews, and expert synthesis reports.

Univ-A — Daugavpils University (Latvia). Public regional university with ~2,637 students, 311 staff, and 47 programs. Strategic pressure arises from demographic change and regional labour needs; core systems include Academic Information Systems/Moodle provisioning. Stakeholders report an emerging digital vision, but there is limited elaboration on online didactics and staff development.

Univ-B — “Fan S. Noli” University, Korçë (Albania). Small public university with ~2,500 students, ~150 teaching staff, and four faculties. Infrastructure and buildings have improved; a bespoke information system ("Pitagora") supports grade entry, and a Moodle instance is available but not operational. Leadership cites pending national provisions for e-learning as a constraint; interest in digitizing educational processes is clear.

Univ-C — St. Cyril and St. Methodius University of Veliko Tarnovo (Bulgaria). Longstanding experience with online programs since 2002 (cumulative 1,503 learners), standardized course layouts, and national alignment for student data/certification. Gaps include administrative digitization, support for online learners, systematic faculty development, and institutionalized innovation procedures.

4.3 Procedure and instruments

Each visit followed a common protocol mapped to the framework's Areas / Sub-areas / Topics / Diagnostic questions:

- (1) Briefing & scope alignment with leadership.
- (2) Interviews & evidence review across the nine dimensions (policies, processes, metrics, platform configurations).
- (3) Expert synthesis into a written synthesis report (per site), highlighting strengths, gaps, and candidate priorities.
- (4) Feedback to leadership via an oral debrief and circulation of the written report.

The instruments included a checklist (Fig. 2, expanded with individual topics and diagnostic questions). No formal workshop-based maturity scoring was conducted during these visits.

4.4 Analysis

Interview notes and artefacts were analysed against the nine dimensions. For each site, the visiting expert provided a maturity judgment, referencing concrete evidence or agreed absences. Our analysis is interpretive and expert-led: we did not conduct a formal thematic content analysis. Rather, we synthesized interview notes and artifacts against the nine dimensions using expert judgment, and anchored every judgment to concrete evidence or agreed-upon absences. We then summarised cross-site patterns and site-specific priorities.

4.5 Findings

Usability and completeness

Across sites, stakeholders found the framework to be sufficiently comprehensive for structuring cross-unit conversations. Leaders preferred the 9-item synthesis (Section 3) for executive discussion, with the full checklist used in working meetings. The A/B/C/D trace facilitated shared vocabulary between academic and service units, particularly in areas such as IT operations, QA, and administrative and academic services.

Diagnostic power: site snapshots

DU (Univ-A). Strengths: community cohesion, core digital flows (Academic IS/Moodle), and willingness to engage. Gaps: digital pedagogy model, staff training, vision/strategy for online, and student-facing consistency (some faculty still distribute materials by email). Strategic impetus is stronger from regional demographics/labour shortages than from current on-campus demand. Implication: Prioritize pedagogy/assessment design capacity, as well as change management, before scaling.

Fan S. Noli (Univ-B). Strengths: improved physical/digital infrastructure; leadership interest; library digitization; clear organisational chart. Gaps include a non-operational LMS, reliance on its internal "Pitagora" IS for grades only, low staff awareness of the LMS instance, and regulatory uncertainty surrounding digital learning provision. Implication: enable operational LMS, define governance/roles, and prepare for forthcoming legislation with policies and processes.

UVT (Univ-C). Strengths: two-decade online experience; standard layouts; national systems integration for students/certification. Gaps: helpdesk e-ticketing, faculty development beyond tool-use, formative assessment online, admin process digitization, and support roles for online learners. Implication: modernize the pedagogical model (C), institutionalize training (D), and formalize service operations (B/F/G).

Cross-site patterns

Common gaps. (i) Change-management & incentives not explicit; (ii) interoperability/operations under-specified; (iii) systematic faculty development beyond basic LMS use; (iv) administrative/academic services digitisation (recognition of prior learning, micro-credentials, digital certificates end-to-end); (v) student analytics/early-warning and defined online support roles; (vi) clarity on legal/ethical guidance (GDPR/AI). Evidence for these emerged, respectively, at DU (strategy/pedagogy/staffing), Fan S. Noli (LMS governance/legislation), and UVT (ops/faculty/admin digitisation).

Enablers. (i) Executive sponsorship and structured committees (UVT); (ii) existing core platforms even if under-used (DU, Fan S. Noli); (iii) national systems for student data/certification (UVT); (iv) improved infrastructure and library digitisation (Fan S. Noli).

Actionability: emerging roadmaps

Each site is now developing a 12-24 month roadmap, which includes identifying quick wins and structural initiatives. While these are underway, some potential is already emerging from these first reports.

Quick wins (≤ 6 months): publish GenAI/GDPR guidance; turn on LMS governance (roles, course shells, release calendar); define incident/change processes for the LMS; establish internal communication protocols for program approvals.

Structural (6–24 months): consolidate identity/SSO; implement integrations for proctoring/credentials/analytics; automate admin flows (enrolment to certificate); institutionalise faculty & staff development; redesign QA data/review/redesign loops at course/program level.

4.6 Validity considerations and limitations

Given the qualitative, expert-judgment nature of the validation and the small number of sites, generalizability is bounded; future work will introduce formal coding schemes and quantitative maturity metrics. Regarding external validity, three institutions in distinct national contexts provide diverse but limited evidence; future studies should extend the protocol to additional systems and regulatory regimes. Researcher effects should also be considered, as framework authors facilitated visits, thereby increasing the risk of confirmation bias.

4.7 Ethics

Participants received information about the aims; participation was voluntary; no individual-level data are reported. Detailed, specific reports remain available to project partners.

4.8 Summary

Field validation indicates that the framework is usable, diagnostically sensitive to system-level blockers (interoperability/operations; administration and academic services digitization; explicit change management), and action-generative, with indications that it can produce governance-aligned roadmaps. This supports its intended role as a traceable, cross-functional instrument for planning transitions to open digital learning.

In view of the outcomes of the field activities, we now provide the following answers to the research questions.

Answer to RQ1 (capabilities & decision structures): the review and conceptual model indicate that sustainable online provision requires explicit strategic intent and governance, coupled with platform/IT readiness and pedagogical/staff capacity, with QA and services closing the loop (P1–P4). The framework makes these couplings operational by translating them into concrete diagnostics (e.g., decision rights, capacity/availability management, assessment integrity, analytics-enabled student support).

Answer to RQ2 (the practical instrument): the checklist structure and process model (facilitated training, evidence reviews, maturity anchors, and governance sign-off) provides a workable method for joint assessment by leaders, services, and faculties. Institutions can derive supporting instruments, such as a maturity snapshot, a prioritized action plan (including quick wins versus structural reforms), or a 12– to 24-month roadmap, along with supporting evidence.

Answer to RQ3 (diagnostic insights and actionability): Three site visits (March–April 2025) showed that the instrument is usable for leadership dialogue, diagnostically sensitive to system-level blockers, and action-generative. Recurring gaps clustered around: (i) change-management and incentives, (ii)

interoperability/operations, (iii) systematic faculty development beyond tool training, (iv) digitization of academic and administrative services, and (v) analytics-enabled student support & GDPR/AI guidance. These patterns emerged consistently across the sites. They are being translated into quick wins and structural initiatives, with the goals of establishing roadmaps for each institution.

5. Conclusions

This paper proposes and field-validates a nine-dimensional institutional framework that operationalizes the transition from campus-based provision to open, hybrid, and online education. The framework consolidates dispersed guidance (quality assurance, strategy/governance, platforms/IT operations, pedagogy/staff development, student services, communications, context) into a single, facilitation-ready instrument organised as Areas / Sub-areas / Topics / Diagnostic questions, enabling traceable, cross-functional self-assessment and planning.

For university leaders, the primary value of the framework lies in its coordination, as it brings together strategy, quality, technology, pedagogy, and services in a single conversation, providing evidence-backed decision points. In practical terms, it helps (a) diminish the risk of platform decisions via service-level management expectations, (b) couple design quality with operational capacity, and (c) align governance and incentives with the actual work of online delivery. For project teams, it provides a transparent checklist that exposes dependencies early and supports governance-approved plans.

Conceptually, the work clarifies the role of our propositions: how strategy/governance (P1) and platform readiness (P2) condition pedagogy/staff capacity and services (P3), with systems coupling (P4) explaining why partial, siloed improvements underperform coordinated ones. Empirically, the short qualitative field validation substantiates the instrument's usability and actionability, providing a basis for future quantitative tests of the propositions.

The validation encompasses three universities in distinct national contexts and relies on qualitative judgments anchored in evidence; generalizability is therefore bounded. Researcher facilitation introduces potential confirmation bias, which is mitigated through triangulation and the explicit capture of negative cases. These limits are acknowledged in the design of future studies.

Subsequently, we plan on quantifying maturity per dimension and relating it to outcome indicators (time-to-launch, course QA indicators, student success), examining regulatory diversity (e.g., GDPR, recognition/credentialing) and its operational effects, and building an open repository of diagnostics and roadmaps to enable benchmarking and comparative analysis across institutions. The full checklist and facilitation materials will be made publicly available.

Thus, the framework provides universities with a systematic, evidence-based path to plan and govern their transition to open digital learning. By unifying strategy, governance, technology, pedagogy, services, and QA into an operational workflow, it turns widely cited principles into practice. As the field validation suggests, this can lead to prioritised roadmaps that are both credible and tractable within typical institutional constraints. In doing so, it offers a practical bridge between European policy aspirations for digital transformation and the operational realities of higher education institutions.

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Study Workshop Iniure – A Support Program for the Initial Phase of Law Studies

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Abstract

The Study Workshop Iniure is a faculty initiative designed to support law students during the initial stages of their academic journey. Launched as a pilot in 2018 and established as a permanent program in 2025, it aims to enhance academic readiness among students with diverse educational backgrounds and learning needs. The workshop combines self-paced online modules and interactive live sessions to foster essential academic, organisational, and psychosocial skills tailored to legal studies. Evaluations over several semesters show that the initiative significantly improves student engagement, confidence, and performance in the early study phase.

Keywords

Legal education; study support; academic skills; distance learning; student success

1. Introduction

The Study Workshop is an offering from the Faculty of Law that addresses various aspects of legal studies. Before delving deeper into this topic, it is important to highlight the key figures involved.

- The Study Workshop was launched as a pilot program in 2018 and has been a permanent offering since 2025.
- The program runs over the course of one semester and is offered in both the winter and summer semesters.
- Participation is extracurricular and free of charge.
- It is limited to 120 students per semester.
- Students in their first to third semester are contacted by email at the end of the term to inform them about the program. If they have not passed the exam, they can apply via the Study Workshop homepage.
- The weekly time commitment is approximately one hour, plus live sessions, which last between ninety and one hundred twenty minutes each.
- The program is staffed with one full-time research assistant position.

The project goal is to support students with special educational needs during the study entry phase (meaning the second to fourth semesters), helping them develop the skills required for academic success and eventual graduation.

2. Target Group and Background

Special educational needs may arise from prior training in a different field, which means students may be accustomed to a different disciplinary culture. Such problems are especially common among students with a natural science background, because the approach to solving a problem is completely different. Other students may not have a traditional high school diploma and therefore lack a solid understanding of academic research methods.

The propaedeutic course, a curricular module, provides students with basic legal research and academic skills. The Study Workshop is therefore designed for students with additional support needs who still experience initial difficulties despite completing the propaedeutic course. Accordingly, the Study Workshop presumes a basic level of foundational knowledge, and participation is limited to students from the second semester onward.

3. Program Content and Structure

The goal mentioned above – achieving academic readiness – determines the content of the program.

The following factors, which are well-researched, are essential for academic success. They apply across all disciplines, but in the Study Workshop, they have been specifically tailored to the context of legal studies, as you will see below:

- Academic work techniques
- Self-organizing abilities
- Psychosocial well-being
- Digital and media literacy
- Academic enculturation

4. Implementation in Legal Studies

To address these areas, there is a dedicated chapter for each factor on the online learning platform Moodle. Each chapter is interactive and can be worked through independently. Participation is voluntary, meaning students are not required to complete one chapter before moving on to the next. This allows students to decide for themselves whether they need to deepen their understanding in a particular area.

The following section provides a more detailed discussion of the factors and their implementation in the Study Workshop.

In German law studies, academic work primarily involves solving fictional cases by writing a legal opinion. Multiple-choice tests, for example, are not typically used. Therefore, students must find the correct legal basis for the case first. To train this skill, there are interactive exercises in Moodle, such as quizzes.

Once the correct legal basis has been identified, students must apply it to their case. While writing their legal opinion, they must strictly follow a four-step structure. Failure to adhere to this structure can actually result in a poor grade. To practice this four-step method of legal writing, students can work on fictional cases and submit

them for feedback. In addition, they can take part in the exam preparation course, which is the centerpiece of the Study Workshop.

Since only early-semester students are eligible to participate in the program, the cases provided focus exclusively on introductory content: the General Part of German Civil Law and the preparatory course.

The exam preparation course can be joined by signing up via Moodle. For each case, several time slots are available – usually some in the morning and some in the evening – to ensure that even working students can participate. The sessions are held via Zoom in small groups of up to 12 students. After reading the case, or ideally preparing it in advance, we work through it step by step together. Active participation is encouraged – and in most cases, it works very well.

5. Supporting Self-Organisation and Well-Being

Self-organisation skills – such as time management, goal setting, and independent learning – are even more important for distance learning students than for those studying on campus. To help improve these skills, Moodle offers practical guidance and printable templates for creating personal study plans and organising study groups.

The next factor is psychosocial well-being. Many of our students study part-time or even full-time while working, which means they need to manage stress and develop resilience even more than traditional full-time students. In addition, unlike campus-based students, they do not see their peers regularly and must therefore rely more heavily on self-motivation. To support this, students are provided with information and strategies for self-motivation. Once per semester, a “Motivation Evening” is held via Zoom with a professional coach who also has a legal background. Students are also invited to write a short reflection on their motivational challenges. This exercise is intended to support self-reflection, and each student receives personalised feedback.

6. Digital and Media Literacy

The next factor, which should not be underestimated even in a law degree program, is digital and data literacy. This skill is not only essential during legal studies – in virtually every legal profession, the ability to conduct online research using legal databases is indispensable.

Our students receive free access to the most important legal databases. On Moodle, they can watch short videos introducing these platforms. Afterwards, they can complete exercises in which they fill in missing parts of a text using information found in the databases.

7. Academic Enculturation

The last-mentioned factor is enculturation, that is, as you all know, the process of adapting to the disciplinary culture. In law studies, it is, for example, the regularly strict grading compared to other studies. Also, law is a book study, so there is not much working together (except for the learning groups, of course). Another characteristic is that law students have to follow very strict citation rules that differ from those in other disciplines.

In addition to the Moodle course and the exam preparation course, a third component was introduced following the first phase of the project, as the case preparation course, in particular, was very well received by the students. Since the following semester, additional live sessions have been offered every two weeks in the

form of so-called crash courses, conducted via Zoom. In these sessions, a law-related topic is presented in a lecture format. Students are encouraged to ask questions and engage in discussions both with one another and with me. These sessions have been met with very positive feedback from participants. Other than the case preparation course, the crash courses are open to all participants at the same time.

Furthermore, the program provides a lesson on reading techniques, general information about the university and distance learning, opportunities to exchange ideas with other students, and the possibility to form study groups. Participants can also schedule individual appointments to receive personalised feedback.

8. Evaluation and Outcomes

The program has been evaluated over several semesters, and the feedback has been very positive. As mentioned before, the live sessions in particular receive high praise. Working in small groups within a “safe space” – where even seemingly “simple” questions can be asked without hesitation – is valued just as much as the detailed and thorough course content.

The most rewarding aspect of the program is that it works. This is demonstrated by both the students’ subjective self-assessment and the objective data, as the following figures show.

**Evaluation results:
Benefits of the live sessions- Students' subjective assessment**

Folie

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**Evaluation results: Grade progression
(Preparatory Course (55100) and General Part of German Civil Law (55101))**

Folie

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Evaluation results: Grade progression take-home assignment (EA)

The Role of Social Intelligence in Higher Distance Education. Case Study of the Master's Degree Program: Education & Technologies in Distance Teaching and Learning Systems - Education Sciences (ETA of the Hellenic Open University)

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Abstract

Social Intelligence constitutes a cornerstone for fruitful and positive interactions, as it fosters the development of essential social, communicative, and linguistic skills that promote smooth and constructive collaboration and harmonious coexistence. In recent years, however, research has predominantly focused on Artificial Intelligence, while Social Intelligence appears to be neglected in the literature concerning Distance Education. This is particularly significant, given that Social Intelligence plays a crucial role as a transversal competence for the citizen of the future, as well as for the formation of quality interactions and the creation of a supportive learning environment. This study is situated within an emerging and evolving scientific field that is inherently linked to the social dimension of education-both in macro- and micro-educational contexts. More specifically, as a qualitative research project, it takes the form of a Case Study within the Master's Program: Education & Technologies in Distance Teaching and Learning Systems - Education Sciences (ETA), offered by the Hellenic Open University. The study explores the role of Social Intelligence through the interactions between tutors and students in a micro-educational teaching and learning context. Thirteen semi-structured interviews were conducted, along with in-person observation during four tutorials of the program. The research questionnaire was developed based on two theoretical models of Social Intelligence. The in-depth analysis of various aspects of Social Intelligence revealed that students develop and apply key social competencies in both formal and informal online settings. Furthermore, the findings demonstrated that the development of Social Intelligence is influenced by instructional design, human factors, digital tools, and the overall environment and climate shaped within distance education. Strong interpersonal interactions-emerging as part of the program's structure-were shown to reinforce the presence and significance of Social Intelligence in remote learning environments. Within the scope of this investigation, participants identified active engagement as a critical factor that had a substantial impact on multiple dimensions of Social Intelligence. The study's outcomes point in multiple directions. Indicatively, the functional role of Social Intelligence in this specific context can enhance the quality of education, address challenges in Distance Education-such as the stimulation of negative emotions-enhance Emotional Intelligence and group collaboration, and simultaneously foster digital and social skills. Beyond its role as the foundation of socialization, as confirmed by the research, Social Intelligence was also found to have a causal relationship with Emotional Intelligence. One of the most significant findings was the Social Intelligence of the tutor, with the most prominent indication being its contribution, as a skill, to the effectiveness of his role.

1. Introduction

Within the framework of the requirements of the digital world, distance education (DE) emerges as a fundamental tool for enhancing both digital and social skills. The COVID-19 pandemic, combined with the rapid development of artificial intelligence, has played a decisive role in shaping its contemporary profile. An important element for the present research, as noted by Lionarakis (2006), is that the theory of DE as a critical social theory is not neutral, but is imbued with social and ethical rules and values. This highlights the social role of education and the need for its response to social developments. Also critical is the role of the instructor, whose guidance, interaction, and emotional support constitute essential prerequisites for success in DE environments (Holmberg, 1981; Moore, 1973). In this context, the use of various methods and tools enhances the quality of learning, while simultaneously strengthening the dimension of social interaction. For example, the tutorials of HOU function as a field where social relationships are cultivated and meaningful educational experiences are developed. Within this framework, Social Intelligence (SI) emerges as a decisive factor that can influence human interaction, the learning process, and professional development. The international literature recognizes SI as a critical element of the educational experience (Abdurozikova, 2014; Safarovna, 2024). However, while significant emphasis has been placed on studying DE in relation to artificial intelligence or emotional intelligence (EI), there is a research gap regarding the relationship between DE and SI. This gap makes further investigation of the role of SI in distance education environments necessary.

2. Social Intelligence and Higher Education

SI constitutes a critical parameter in the interaction between students and educators in higher education and has been studied in relation to gender (Malik et al., 2018; Saxena and Jain, 2013), age (Ali et al., 2019), and academic performance, which has been shown not to be correlated with SI (Ganaie & Mudasir, 2015). It has also been studied in relation to the increasing use of social media, as a necessity in every aspect of higher education administration (Jacob, 2015). The study by Rahim et al., (2018) contributed to the understanding of relationships, situational awareness, situational responsiveness, cognitive empathy, social skills, and problem-solving of faculty members at a university in the United States. The study by Mali et al., (2015) at a university in southern Thailand showed a significant correlation with learning behavior, except for social knowledge, self-presentation, influence, and concern. Similarly, Gündüzalp and Göktaş (2024) emphasized that the teaching methods applied in courses positively affected students' SI, metacognitive thinking skills, and academic achievements. Studies such as those by Kularajasingam et al. (2022) reported that SI has a significant positive influence on teaching and learning performance. Likewise, Yousif et al. (2024) note that active learning strategies contribute to the improvement of SI through collaboration and interaction. SI is closely associated with positive feelings of optimism and well-being and with students' life satisfaction (Rezaei & Khosroshahi, 2018), and it facilitates emotion management as well as collaboration and teamwork. SI and Emotional Intelligence (EI) present a causal relationship or interdependence, as shown by Trevino (2014) in his research on IT professionals, indicating that when SI decreased, EI decreased as well. The experimental study of SI by Zautra et al. (2015), conducted through a curriculum applied to an experimental group of students, confirms Trevino's (2014) findings and shows SI as a means to increase willingness to take

others' perspectives and enhance effectiveness in initiating and maintaining positive social connections. They also reported greater self-efficacy in social situations compared to controls.

2.1 The Role of Interaction in the Postgraduate Program

The role of interaction in DE emerges as a fundamental characteristic for SI. In the postgraduate program (PP) ETA, interaction is implemented in a multimodal way (Lionarakis, 1998), both synchronous and asynchronous, orally and in writing, utilizing technological tools and educational strategies that enhance learning. The concept of multimodal e-mentoring (Niarchou et al., 2023) highlights psychosocial factors such as feedback, guidance, support, empathy, and socialization, which contribute to the development of a sense of "belonging" and positive attitudes among students. Bidirectional communication creates a bridge between tutors and the learner, supporting students' psychological awareness, personal empowerment, and self-knowledge (Spyropoulou, 2019). At the same time, collaborative learning enhances skills such as leadership, language abilities, and academic performance, while promoting self-confidence and acceptance of diversity (Karras, 2023). Social Media (SM) support social construction, the development of social ease, and digital skills (Tsachourgianidou, 2024; Lelovitou & Samanta, 2023). Communication via email, telephone, or SM enhances feedback and support, while peer feedback promotes self-regulation (Toutouni, 2023; Kalopana, 2022). The quality of communication and interaction between tutors and learners, with a friendly tone, clarity, encouragement, and understanding of emotions, as well as the adequacy of technological tools and regular communication, constitute critical factors for the creation of a positive and participatory learning environment (Xanthopoulou & Solomou, 2021). Overall, interaction and communication appear to contribute significantly to the effectiveness of DE and the enhancement of student socialization.

3. Research Methodology

This study falls within qualitative research. The case study was chosen as an appropriate methodological approach, as it allows in-depth understanding of complex social phenomena through narrative recording and visual observation (Mills et al., 2017). Sampling follows a purposive strategy combined with the snowball method, in order to identify key informants with relevant experience and the ability to contribute to the research. The target population consists of tutors and learners of modules ETA61, ETA62, ETA63, and ETA52. Data collection was carried out using two main tools: semi-structured interviews aimed at rich, descriptive narratives, and non-participant on-site observation in tutorials, recording observable SI indicators. The questionnaire was structured around core aspects of SI and important dimensions from the models of Goleman (2006) and Albrecht (2006), which were considered capable of producing findings for the distance education context. It is important to note regarding the components of SI, as described by Goleman (2006, p. 117), that social awareness refers to a range starting from immediate perception of the other's internal state, understanding their emotions and thoughts, and extending to comprehension of complex social situations. Social Facility (SF) is the simple sense of how the other feels or knowledge of what they think or intend to do, but it does not guarantee the achievement of fruitful interactions. SF relies on

social awareness to conduct smooth and effective interactions. For reference, related terminology is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Dimensions of SI

Dimension	Category	Source	Definition-Interpretation (as used in this study)
Primary Empathy	Social Awareness	Goleman, 2006	Sharing feelings, reading non-verbal emotional cues
Attunement	Social Awareness	Goleman, 2006	Listening with full receptivity and coordination with the other
Empathic Accuracy	Social Awareness	Goleman, 2006	Understanding another's thoughts, emotions, and intentions
Social Cognition	Social Awareness	Goleman, 2006	Knowledge of how the social world operates
Synchrony	Social Facility	Goleman, 2006	Smooth interaction at a non-verbal level
Self-Presentation	Social Facility	Goleman, 2006	Effective presentation of the self
Influence	Social Facility	Goleman, 2006	Shaping the outcome of a social interaction
Concern	Social Facility	Goleman, 2006	Concern for others' needs and acting accordingly
Situational Awareness		Albrecht, 2006	Social "radar": reading situations and behaviors, assessing intentions and emotions
Presence		Albrecht, 2006	Verbal and non-verbal patterns, body posture, voice quality, impression on others
Authenticity		Albrecht, 2006	Honesty, integrity, reliability as perceived by others
Clarity		Albrecht, 2006	Ability to explain ideas, communicate clearly, and persuade
Empathy		Albrecht, 2006	Creating a shared emotional state with another person, basis for positive interaction and collaboration

Purpose:

The purpose of this study is to investigate the role of SI through the social interactions between tutors and students in the DE modules of the PP: ETA aiming to understand the dimensions of SI that are activated or cultivated in the DE environment.

Research Questions:

1. Which dimensions of SI are cultivated through the interactions between tutors and students in the PP: ETA?
2. Which dimensions of SI are utilized in tutorials, and in what way?

3. How do interactions influence the quality of studies in the PP: ETA?

4. Sample Description

The research participants, as shown in Figure 1, consist of 6 tutors and 7 learners. Regarding gender, there are 8 women and 5 men. Half of the participants belong to the age group 31-49 and over 50, and one female student is under 30. Additionally, all participants have worked and are working in public and private institutions as educators, except for one participant. Regarding residence, 9 participants live in Athens, 1 in Patras, 1 in Crete, 1 in Munich, and 1 in Lagonisi. At the time of the study, 6 participants are attending module ETA61, 1 student is in modules ETA62 and ETA63. Furthermore, 3 participants are from the module ETA62 and 3 from the module ETA63.

Figure 1 – Sample Description

4.1 Results of Cultivating SI Dimensions through Interactions in the PP:ETA

SF is presented by the participants of the research as a dimension that can potentially be cultivated, since its development seems to vary depending on the interaction of multiple factors. It is highlighted that SF is cultivated dynamically, with the tutor in tutorials playing a decisive role as an orchestrator of communication and a positive climate. Empathy, although considered difficult to develop through DE, is shown to be supported through the role of the tutor, group activities, and interaction in digital media, with an emphasis on patience, understanding, and acceptance of diversity. Self-awareness is strengthened through assessment, feedback, and time management, contributing to the development of self-criticism and emotional regulation. Argumentation and clarity are promoted through dialogue in tutorials, the Socratic method, group assignments, and the tutor’s guidance. Furthermore, active participation plays an important role in shaping consensus and

cohesion within the group, supports the achievement of goals, and enhances the sense of satisfaction, while exposure to diversity in the DE framework promotes personal growth and the development of trust through communication. Table 2 summarizes the most important influencing factors for cultivating these specific SI dimensions in the PP:ETA.

Table 2: Cultivation of SI Dimensions in the PP:ETA

Dimensions of SI	Enhancing factors for the cultivation
Social Facility	Tutor’s role as orchestrator of dialogue and communication, frequency of tutorials and time for socialization, collaboration in small groups, group dynamics and tutor’s guidance, student characteristics (e.g., attitude, personality), critique of speech, discretion, respect, use of informal learning communities and SM (strengthened by Viber), non-verbal signals & EI elements
Empathy	Personal values and abilities of the tutor, active listening & dialogue in tutorials, group activities in breakout sessions, interaction via SM (Viber and Facebook), community building and sense of belonging, virtues: understanding, acceptance, patience, feedback from tutor and peers, verbal and non-verbal expressions-empathizing
Self-Awareness	Written assignments, assessment and feedback, strengthening self-criticism through reflection, addressing difficulties (e.g., anxiety, loneliness), organization, time management, emotional regulation, digital literacy and recognition of personal abilities, PP deadlines and requirements as challenges for development
Clarity	Clear communication and guidance from tutor, word limitation in activities, precise formulation of questions and instructions, critique of excessive pursuit of clarity for grade-oriented reasons
Argumentation	Dialogue in tutorials (Socratic-maieutic method), evidence-based written assignments, collaborative activities in breakout sessions, communication via telephone and forum, tutor’s feedback as guidance and authority

4.2 Results of Utilizing SI Dimensions in Tutorials of the PP

The effective utilization of these SI dimensions in tutorials is based on a multifaceted network of interacting and complementary factors. In summary, the views of the interviewees are presented in Table 3. A central role is attributed to the tutor, who can manage self-presentation as a pedagogical tool to enhance learning dynamics and group cohesion. Self-presentation, which begins from the very first meeting through interventions such as introductory questions and the use of digital tools, strengthens empathy, humor, and the sense of community, while the pedagogical contract creates a framework of safety and respect. Active participation of members promotes consensus, cohesion, and trust within the group, particularly through interaction in breakout sessions, where authentic expressions and collaboration skills are developed. SF is reinforced through verbal and non-verbal expressions, where open camera use and digital presence contribute-within the spatiotemporal frame of tutorials-to students’ self-regulation. Moreover, maintaining concern is supported by humor, gamification, audiovisual tools, and collaborative assessment activities, creating a favorable

climate for continuous participation and group empowerment in each module, which also extends beyond the formal framework through informal communication networks. Verbal and especially non-verbal cues are highlighted as particularly important, as they reveal emotions, alleviate loneliness, shape shared understanding and empathy, while at the same time functioning as valuable feedback for the tutor.

Table 3: Utilization of SI Dimensions in Tutorials

Dimensions	Functionality of Utilization	Ways of Utilization in tutorials
Self-Presentation	Depends on the participation and attitude of peers & tutor	Pedagogical contract, introduction in the 1st tutorial, experiential activities, use of Mentimeter, Padlet, Kahoot, compassion-sympathy-empathy
Active Listening	Crucial for interaction dynamics, group collaboration	Structured dialogue, debate, collaborative techniques (breakout sessions), use of multimedia tools
Social Facility	Promoted through active participation mainly in breakout sessions and less in plenary-Functionality varies depending on group dynamics	Support of small groups - communication channels, creation of positive climate, collaborative learning techniques, intercultural sensitivity - acceptance of diversity vs. critique in plenary, 1st tutorial-time for socialization
Verbal & Non-Verbal Expression (Presence)	Contributes to “ice-breaking”, cohesion, energy of the climate, and sense of belonging through sympathy, strengthens empathy, feedback for the tutor, spontaneity-authenticity, alleviation of loneliness	Open camera, use of chat, integration of social cues, experiential approaches
Concern	Determines the quality of participation, maintenance of positive climate	Gamified activities (debate, “Who Wants to Be a Millionaire”, etc.), use of digital tools by the module tutor
Open Camera	Affects closeness and willingness to collaborate	Reinforcement of trust, creation of a safe environment, indicators of non-verbal cues, spontaneity, and willingness to participate

4.3 Results on the Contribution of Interaction to the Quality of Studies in the PP

Bidirectional communication emerges as a fundamental factor for the quality of learning and teaching, as reported by all research participants. The enhancement of communication is highlighted as a key demand by participants, with emphasis on the creation of clear, timely, and multidimensional dialogue channels, which support both the learning and emotional development of the students. The organization of ad hoc tutorials, when deemed necessary, as well as the implementation of digital tool seminars over the past two years, aligns with the methodology for evaluating units and strengthens the use of technological tools by the students. Feedback emerges

as a central factor in tutorials, as it enhances the quality of the learning process, supports individual work, and serves as a tool for program improvement. Students seek meaningful, clear, and timely guidance, while individualized contact with the tutor and opportunities for direct communication contribute to the creation of a supportive learning environment. Moreover, the timing and frequency of interactions are critical factors for deepening knowledge and developing dialogue. Experiential and social learning, through collaborative group work and projects, promote active participation, cooperative learning, and a sense of belonging. The attitude and individualized approach of the tutor enhance the quality of studies, while continuous and multi-level evaluation contributes to the ongoing improvement of the program. Overall, the interviewees' perspectives indicate that quality in the PP is closely linked to multiple factors, as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Quality and Interaction in the PP

Factor	Interaction Methods	Contribution to the Quality of Studies
Bidirectional Communication	Student - tutor dialogue in TUTORIALSs, ad hoc tutorials, personal meetings, e-mails, telephone communication	Enhances understanding, participation, trust, and learning support
Feedback	Group feedback in tutorials, peer feedback via Viber and other informal groups	Improves individual performance, strengthens self-regulation and the quality of assignments, allows practical improvement
Time	Personal time management, regular communication, individualized meetings	Enhances the learning process, exchange of opinions, timely problem-solving, and completion of studies
Experiential Learning	Participation in tutorials, application of theoretical knowledge, projects, collaborative group work	Develops practical skills, promotes active participation, and intellectual growth
Social Learning	Creation of stable collaboration groups, dialogue among students, collaborative activities	Strengthens social interaction, sense of belonging, and cooperation
Individualized Guidance	"Ice-breaking," tutor guidance, individualized communication in feedback	Enhances trust, motivation, understanding of weaknesses, and adaptation of learning

5. Discussion

The findings of the present study indicate that SI is primarily cultivated through presence, regular communication, and socialization time in tutorials and SM, enhancing students' active participation, social adaptation, self-awareness, and self-presentation, in agreement with previous research (Bennet, 2015; Karras, 2023; Lelovitou & Samanta, 2023; Meyer & Jones, 2012; Tsachourgiannidou, 2024; Starynska et al., 2023; Xanthopoulou & Solomou, 2021). Additionally, SI is supported by the use of digital tools and informal communication networks, reinforcing interaction, learning quality,

and the development of social, digital, and emotional skills (Jacob, 2015; Yousif et al., 2024). Argumentation and clarity are strengthened through educational design, Socratic dialogue, and the need for clear written communication, while empathy develops through psychological support, shared understanding, and recognition of verbal and non-verbal cues (Savci et al., 2022; Spyropoulou, 2019). Moreover, students recognize the challenges of DE and create informal interactions, communities, and digital networks on SM, thereby forming a vibrant academic digital community. Self-awareness is promoted through feedback, assessment, and participation in informal networks (Kalopana, 2022; Toutouni, 2023). Consequently, self-awareness enables students to learn how to function and how to be in the distance PP. At the same time, social awareness emerges in DE as it evolves in PP:ETA. The tutor plays a crucial role in bridging the “emotional gap” (Spyropoulou, 2019) through empathy, social awareness, and individualized guidance, fostering trust, security, and student autonomy. Primary empathy develops through shared understanding and tutorials processes, social knowledge is manifested in discussions, especially in spaces offering freedom such as breakout sessions and SM, while emotional accuracy is attributed as a tutor’s strength. In our study, SI is shown to function as a key factor in learning behavior (Mali et al., 2015), promoting self-regulation, self-control, and a positive climate, while collaboration in informal learning communities and in virtual tutorial rooms enhances critical thinking, empathy, and the sense of “belonging,” creating a dynamic academic community (Kularajasingam et al., 2022; Rahim et al., 2018). Simultaneously, situational awareness in the distance PP reflects the multifaceted nature of DE (Lionarakis, 1998) and is linked to a multimodal e-mentoring approach (Niarchou et al., 2023).

6. Conclusions

This qualitative study highlighted that SI constitutes a cornerstone of the educational experience in the PP:ETA, influencing learning behavior, guidance, and group cohesion. It does not function in isolation but is built through the interactions of learners and the tutor and the overall group climate. It is understood as a systemic capability concerning all participants and should be consciously integrated into the design and implementation of distance learning programs. Its cultivation leads both to individual development and the creation of supportive, inclusive learning communities. Self-presentation, presence, empathy, SF, authenticity, active listening, and social awareness proved to be key elements of SI, particularly strengthened in tutorials and informal learning communities. Active participation, collaboration, camera use, and emotional support contributed to building trust and a sense of belonging. The tutor plays a crucial role by providing guidance, feedback, humor, and emotional accuracy, shaping a safe and collaborative environment. Their educational attitude and self-regulation enhance students’ resilience, autonomy, and academic performance. Thus, the tutor’s SI, as an ability to create a supportive and collaborative learning environment, should be assessed as a key criterion for their inclusion in distance programs. The findings highlighted the close connection between SI and EI, showing that, through “learning how to act” and “learning how to be,” learners cultivate digital and socio-emotional skills. Additionally, SI bridges the psychosocial gap of distance education, helping manage unfamiliar learning contexts and cope with negative emotions, reducing anxiety and loneliness experienced in distance programs. SI does not operate independently but interacts with EI, contributing to a holistic learning process. SI dimensions, such

as synchrony, influence, and concern, strengthen social presence and adaptability through digital tools. Instructional design that leverages collaborative learning and multimodal, personalized communication, both within and beyond the formal framework, promotes cooperative, social, and experiential learning, enhancing the quality of the educational experience. In conclusion, SI reinforces EI, develops digital and social skills, while the tutor's SI promotes communication, empathy, honesty, and respect, improving the overall learning experience. Therefore, SI focuses on facilitating interaction, enhancing socialization, supporting EI and group collaboration, and upgrading the quality of studies, representing a key factor for success.

7. Suggestions for Future Research

The present study highlights the need for further investigation of SI in the context of DE, with emphasis on the role of the tutor and the instructional design of the PP. Issues such as competition, grade-seeking behavior, and, in some cases, limited interaction among students constitute critical areas for future research. Additionally, it is suggested to explore the relationship between the sense of freedom and the structure of the tutorials, as well as the impact of guided support. Furthermore, conducting qualitative and experimental studies in other educational contexts is recommended, aiming to enhance SI, reduce stress, and improve interaction and the overall quality of studies.

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Generative AI and Large Language Models

An alternative approach towards AI regulations at Higher Education Institutions

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in higher education has created both substantial opportunities and pressing challenges for institutions seeking to implement effective regulations. While the necessity of such regulations is broadly acknowledged (Ghimire & Edwards, 2024; UNESCO, 2023), many Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) continue to struggle with providing clear, actionable guidelines for diverse stakeholder groups. Early attempts at AI governance often rely on top-down directives that are too general, resulting in inconsistent application and uncertainty for students and faculty alike (Dabis & Csáki, 2024).

This paper offers a structured approach that blends hierarchical and participatory processes to navigate the complexity of AI policymaking in HEIs. Specifically, it proposes establishing institution-wide regulations that clarify baseline standards - such as data privacy and academic integrity - while also encouraging the development of customized AI policies at the department or institute level (Wu et al., 2024). By involving key stakeholders early in the design phase, including faculty, students, IT professionals, and legal experts, these localized policies can address discipline-specific needs and nuances. An iterative and inclusive process also helps mitigate the risk of conflicting regulations, enhancing transparency and overall stakeholder commitment.

Moreover, the proposed framework highlights the importance of continuous evaluation and revision, given the rapid pace of AI developments and emerging ethical concerns. Rather than treating AI policies as static documents, institutions should regularly assess their effectiveness by gathering feedback on technical, legal, and pedagogical impacts. Ultimately, the approach outlined in this paper underscores that a “one-size-fits-all” strategy is insufficient (Robert & McCormack, 2024). Tailored regulations, developed through collaborative engagement with all relevant parties, offer the most viable means of ensuring responsible and meaningful AI integration within higher education.

Keywords

AI Policy Development, AI Governance, Participatory Approach, Adaptive Implementation

1. Introduction

Since the widespread availability of ChatGPT in November 2022, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) have been actively addressing the challenges and opportunities presented by generative artificial intelligence (AI). While AI applications influence both research and education, the initial focus of many HEIs has been on developing orientation materials, guidelines, and regulations primarily for teaching. These efforts aim to provide faculty and students with guidance on the appropriate use of generative AI, addressing key legal, ethical, and pedagogical considerations. Of particular importance are issues related to preventing the misuse of AI applications, safeguarding academic integrity, and ensuring proper attribution of AI-generated texts and data.

In light of these developments, the need for clear guidelines and strategies comes to the forefront to address the diverse challenges and opportunities that generative AI brings to HEIs teaching and research. Many scientific publications emphasize the necessity for HEIs to establish concrete AI policies to navigate these challenges effectively (Duah & McGivern, 2024; Dwivedi et al., 2023; Lim et al., 2023; UNESCO, 2023; Jiahui, 2024). However, existing guidelines often remain general and fail to provide sufficient clarity for the various academic stakeholders involved. This raises questions about how AI regulations should be structured and, more importantly, how they should be developed to ensure their effectiveness and adaptability.

It must be taken into account that dealing with AI is not only necessary at the institution-wide level of an HEI, but that it is also advisable for individual academic units to develop their own AI agreements. The development of such agreements should combine a hierarchical approach with a participatory approach. The challenge lies in designing an adaptive, context-sensitive development process that integrates institution-wide requirements with participatory co-creation.

This paper presents a model for such a customized development process. It begins with an overview of the current challenges of AI regulation at HEIs, followed by a synthesis of existing approaches in the academic literature that serve as the foundation for the proposed model. It then introduces a three-phase model for developing an AI policy at the level of an academic unit or institute. The sustainable implementation of this model is subsequently illustrated through a hypothetical implementation scenario. Finally, the advantages and limitations of the proposed model are discussed, and an outlook is provided on how individual HEIs may apply it in their contexts.

2. Challenges of existing AI regulations at HEIs

AI regulations exist at various levels, ranging from international agreements and national legislation to institution-specific regulations and individual faculty guidelines (UNESCO, 2023; Mahrishi et al., 2024). Legal frameworks, such as the European Union's AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (Artificial Intelligence Act), n.d.) or national laws, provide a non-modifiable foundation upon which tailored institutional regulations can be built. Customized regulations enable HEIs to ensure responsible and ethical AI use while maximizing the potential of this technology for higher education.

The need for clear regulations on generative AI in higher education is widely recognized. AI regulations can be restrictive, enabling, or self-regulatory, either limiting AI use, promoting its integration, or delegating decisions to individual stakeholders such as faculty members (Robert, 2024). Many regulations adopt a hybrid approach, ranging from outright bans to unrestricted use (Dabis & Csáki, 2024). However, AI regulations often create confusion rather than clarity (Wu et al., 2024). Their broad and generalized nature frequently lacks discipline-specific guidance (Ghimire & Edwards, 2024). While this flexibility allows faculty to determine AI use in their courses, it also places the burden of decision-making on them, leading to fragmented regulations. As a result, students encounter inconsistent and occasionally contradictory AI regulations, with no clear explanation for their differences, underscoring the shortcomings of generalized, top-down approaches.

AI regulations serve multiple functions, helping institutions harness AI's benefits while ensuring ethical and responsible use (Hemachandran & Rodriguez, 2023). Ideally, they clarify expectations and responsibilities for students, faculty, administrators, and IT staff (Jacques et al., 2024). Regulations uphold academic integrity by outlining measures against AI misuse (Chan, 2023) and specifying how AI-generated content should be attributed (Dwivedi et al., 2023). Additionally, they enhance the quality of education by enabling new forms of academic engagement and accommodating diverse student needs (UNESCO, 2023). Beyond academia, they address legal considerations such as data protection and copyright compliance (Chan, 2023), as well as

technical challenges related to data transparency (Hemachandran & Rodriguez, 2023) and the rapid evolution of AI technologies. Furthermore, AI regulations contribute to societal development by fostering critical AI literacy among students and faculty (Al-Zahrani & Alasmari, 2024).

To date, AI regulations in HEIs have primarily been developed by institutional leadership, which sets strategic priorities, coordinates implementation, and ensures compliance. Faculty members are expected to integrate AI into their pedagogical practices while also navigating its administrative implications in curricula and assessments. Meanwhile, students are required to adhere to academic integrity guidelines and develop an informed understanding of AI's capabilities and limitations (Jin et al., 2024). This illustrates a predominantly top-down regulatory approach, in which faculty and students are tasked with implementing AI regulations rather than contributing to their development.

Despite their necessity, AI regulations face key limitations. Terms like “academic integrity” and “fraud” are often vaguely defined (Chan, 2023; Kopp & Gröblinger, 2024). Ambiguous terminology leaves room for interpretation, making it difficult for stakeholders to apply the regulations consistently. Regulatory flexibility, while beneficial, can leave faculty and students uncertain about compliance. Even after reviewing the regulations, faculty and students may struggle to determine the appropriate course of action (Wu et al., 2024). Additionally, regulations often fail to provide concrete, discipline-specific guidance, reducing their practical relevance for different academic programs.

Technical challenges related to AI are frequently addressed in institutional guidelines, yet responsibility for managing AI tools is often shifted to individual users, many of whom lack the necessary expertise. The opaque nature of AI systems exacerbates this issue, the rapid pace of technological advancements (Colonna, 2022), and unresolved legal questions surrounding liability for AI-related misconduct (Dwivedi et al., 2023).

To address these shortcomings, AI regulations should be developed through an inclusive, participatory process. This requires combining a clear institutional framework with active involvement from faculty, students, and relevant support units, ensuring that diverse perspectives and practical needs are incorporated from the outset. As demonstrated in the subsequent sections, such a process benefits from structured coordination, phased development, and targeted stakeholder engagement, which together help to create policies that are both context-sensitive and adaptable. By integrating expert review, leadership alignment, and transparent decision-making, the resulting AI regulations are more likely to gain broad acceptance and to remain effective over time.

3. Customized AI policies as a solution approach

Institution-specific AI regulations consider the unique characteristics of each HEI and ideally provide concrete directives for various stakeholders and AI applications. The first AI regulations at HEIs aimed to standardize the handling of AI as uniformly as possible for all (academic) units and all stakeholder groups. However, in practice, it becomes evident that this approach does not achieve sufficient effectiveness. Rather, it is necessary to address the specific needs of individual academic units (e.g., institutes) and to involve all relevant stakeholders with their particular requirements in a participatory process (Robert & McCormack, 2024). This need for differentiation is particularly pronounced at large universities with diverse study programs.

One possible approach to this challenge is the development of tailored AI policies that build on institution-wide AI regulations. In the following, the term “*policies*” is deliberately used to distinguish them from legally binding regulations. Policies have a recommendatory character, and the processes based on them require the consent of all parties involved in their development. The rationale behind this is that individual academic units

have fewer means than university leadership to enact binding rules. At the same time, the commitment of those involved ensures that the (jointly developed) policy is actively embraced and implemented by all stakeholders.

The approach presented here focuses on the collaborative and participatory development of individual AI policies at the level of specific academic units. The outlined process supports the implementers in ensuring that their regulations do not contradict the institution-wide rules but rather specify them. The chapter begins by outlining the necessary structural and procedural framework, then illustrates the concept through a hypothetical implementation scenario. Finally, it addresses the need to regularly evaluate and revise the developed policy to ensure its long-term sustainability.

3.1 Conceptual approaches to AI policy development

Decision-making processes at HEIs are typically embedded within specific governance models. These models vary along a spectrum ranging from hierarchical to collaborative structures, with many institutions adopting hybrid forms that reflect both centralized authority and participatory elements (Hussein, 2024). The chosen governance approach significantly shapes how strategic decisions - such as the development of AI policies - are negotiated and implemented. However, these traditional structures increasingly reach their limits in addressing the challenges posed by generative AI. As Reuel & Undheim (2024) argue, the rapid pace of AI development, its wide applicability, and its capacity to transform knowledge work demand adaptive governance models - ones that are iterative, participatory, and responsive.

Translating this to the context of HEIs, adaptive governance implies moving beyond top-down regulatory approaches. Instead, it calls for modular, context-sensitive governance structures that are developed in collaboration with affected academic units. Just as adaptive governance frameworks in the AI domain emphasize the inclusion of diverse stakeholders and continuous policy iteration, HEIs must build similarly flexible structures that allow faculties, institutes, and departments to co-develop and continuously refine AI-related policies.

The involvement of all relevant stakeholders is essential for the development of an AI policy. Typical stakeholder groups at HEIs include faculty, administrative staff, and students (Jin et al., 2024). These stakeholders can be divided into two categories: those directly involved in the policy development process and directly affected by the policy outcomes, and those responsible for assessing the policy's alignment with the institution's general guidelines and available infrastructure. The first group includes the academic and administrative staff of the respective unit, as well as students enrolled in its study programs. Representatives of these groups must be involved throughout all phases of the policy development process. The second group primarily consists of legal experts, who evaluate regulatory and ethical implications, and IT specialists, who possess the necessary technical expertise and ensure the provision of appropriate infrastructure. This second group is typically involved only at selected stages of the process.

The development process of an AI policy can be divided into several phases. These phases can be defined based on the following approaches: Selvadurai (2025) describes a four-step model of integrated regulation that offers a strategic framework for developing balanced and context-sensitive AI governance. In step 1, mapping and gap analysis are conducted to assess existing regulatory frameworks, identify overlaps, and uncover blind spots in current AI governance landscapes. Step 2 involves calibrating safety and innovation by evaluating trade-offs between precautionary safeguards and the need to foster technological development. In step 3, the focus shifts to determining the optimal mix between general-purpose and sector-specific AI regulation, ensuring that regulatory measures are tailored to the particular risks and needs of different application domains. Finally,

step 4 addresses the appropriate combination of regulatory instruments, including legally binding rules, self-regulatory practices, technical standards, and built-in technical controls.

Parthasarathy et al. (2024) outline a structured, iterative process for developing effective AI governance within organizations, emphasizing inclusivity, accountability, and adaptability. The process begins with internal alignment, where organizations clarify their values, risk tolerances, and goals for AI use. This is followed by stakeholder mapping and engagement, ensuring that all relevant voices are represented. The next step involves the development of governance tools and mechanisms, including policies, processes, and technical infrastructures tailored to the organization's specific use cases and context. These tools are then operationalized through training, integration into workflows, and assignment of clear responsibilities.

Li et al. (2025) propose a framework for developing university policies on generative AI governance. It emphasizes a balanced, ethically grounded, and context-sensitive approach. It advocates for the clarification of institutional principles, the identification of specific AI use cases, and the establishment of clear rules regarding transparency, human accountability, and disclosure. Moreover, it addresses critical issues such as data privacy, intellectual property, and the secure use of third-party tools. Central to the framework is the promotion of AI literacy and internal capacity-building, as well as the implementation of participatory and interdisciplinary policy development processes.

Based on the approaches described above, the development of an AI policy at the level of individual academic units can be structured into three phases: (1) pre-policy phase, (2) co-design and drafting, and (3) adaptive implementation. In the pre-policy phase, the objectives and scope of the initiative are defined, stakeholders are identified, institution-wide regulations and framework conditions that may influence the policy are mapped, and an initial thematic overview is compiled. This process ensures optimal preparation for the second phase - co-design and drafting - during which the policy is developed through an iterative, collaborative process. The third phase, adaptive implementation, involves verifying that the content of the policy aligns with all applicable institutional regulations and frameworks before the policy is formally approved and published by the responsible decision-makers.

Developing an AI policy is a complex endeavor, even at the level of individual academic units. The involvement of consulting services that facilitate and moderate the process provides meaningful support. While external consultants can provide valuable outsider perspectives, a more efficient and context-sensitive approach often involves appointing an internal consultant - someone employed at the HEI but not directly affiliated with the unit concerned. Ideally, such a person is based in a central support structure and possesses both foundational AI knowledge and a solid understanding of the institution's strategic goals and governance structures. Internal consultants offer a unique dual perspective: they are embedded in the organizational culture and possess institutional memory, yet remain sufficiently independent from individual departments to provide objective and critical input. This positioning enables them to identify internal dynamics, anticipate potential resistance, and facilitate sensitive conversations regarding AI integration. Because they are part of the organization, communication channels are often more efficient, and the trust they have established internally increases stakeholder acceptance. Furthermore, compared to external consultants, internal consultants are typically more cost-effective and better aligned with institutional priorities. However, their effectiveness depends on the clarity of their mandate, their perceived neutrality, and the degree of institutional support they receive (Hodges, 2017). Accordingly, the specific responsibilities assigned to the internal consultant at each stage of the process are clearly outlined in the following subsection.

3.2 Hypothetical implementation scenario

The following section illustrates the implementation of the three-phase model described above (pre-policy phase, co-design and drafting, adaptive implementation) using a hypothetical implementation scenario. The underlying assumptions are as follows: an institute within a HEI intends to develop its own AI policy in order to document its specific needs in handling AI in teaching and research, thereby providing a general framework for all members of the institute. Ideally, the initiative to develop an institute-specific policy originates within the institute itself, rather than being initiated hierarchically by HEI management. The resulting policy is intended to serve as a guideline that achieves broad acceptance, aligns with the university’s overarching regulations, and is designed for long-term sustainability. To support the development process, a consultant from within the HEI is engaged.

Each of the three phases is subdivided into several process steps, each culminating in (interim) results. The figure illustrates the individual steps: processes are represented as boxes with rounded corners, whereas boxes containing (interim) results have square corners.

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the hypothetical implementation.

Pre-policy phase

In this phase, the groundwork for policy development is laid. Coordination with the responsible unit leadership ensures clarity on objectives, stakeholder involvement, and the intended scope of the policy. Through targeted engagement, all relevant participants are aligned on the policy’s purpose, creating a shared basis for collaboration. The phase concludes with the preparation of a structured policy outline that consolidates the agreed objectives and key content.

Figure 2: Process steps for the pre-policy phase.

Initial Coordination with the Responsible Unit Leadership

The person entrusted with coordinating the policy development process (e.g., the head of the institute) contacts the consultant officially designated for this role within the HEI. In a preliminary meeting, they jointly determine the objectives to be pursued through the policy and identify the stakeholders to be involved in its development. In this context, it should also be clarified whether, in addition to academic and administrative staff, students will be involved. As part of this process, the current level of knowledge among institute members regarding AI use, as well as their motivation to employ AI and/or to draft an AI policy, is assessed. The specific purpose of the policy is defined, and a timeline for its development is established.

The internal consultant is responsible for ensuring that all information required for the subsequent process is collected and that all success factors and associated responsibilities are clearly articulated. This also includes clarifying the consultant's role - what tasks they will undertake, but also what lies outside their scope of responsibility. The outcomes of this coordination meeting are documented in the meeting minutes.

Building Consensus and Commitment

Once the objectives have been clearly defined, the pre-identified stakeholders are brought into the development process. They are provided with an overview of the existing HEI-wide AI regulations, introduced - where necessary - to the (theoretical) possibilities of AI use within their academic discipline, and informed about the policy objectives. It may also be necessary to address stakeholders' concerns regarding AI use. Care must be taken, however, to ensure that the objectives defined in the previous step remain in focus, so as to avoid fundamental debates about the policy's legitimacy. The purpose of this step is therefore to establish a shared understanding among all participants of what the policy is intended to achieve, and to secure their commitment to contributing productively to its development.

The process is best conducted in the form of an in-person workshop. In this setting, the internal consultant assumes the role of a neutral facilitator. Their responsibilities include providing information on the institutional framework conditions. Above all, however, their role is to ensure that, by the end of the workshop, consensus has been reached among all participants regarding the policy's purpose and its intended content.

Policy outline

The policy outline is the first concrete output of the development process. It brings together the objectives and key content agreed upon in the earlier steps and serves as a reference point for the next stages of policy development. The internal consultant drafts the outline in a clear, structured format, summarizing the agreed elements in bullet points. This document is then shared with all involved stakeholders, providing a common basis for the collaborative work in the second phase.

Co-design and drafting

The co-design and drafting phase covers the initial stage of policy development, from drafting the first version to consolidating it into an agreed document. It examines alternative drafting approaches—collaborative stakeholder authorship versus preparation by an internal consultant—and discusses the implications of each for inclusivity, coordination, and adherence to the predefined policy structure. Particular attention is given to the role of stakeholder engagement in fostering commitment, the necessity of structured coordination to

prevent uncontrolled content expansion, and the mechanisms by which feedback is collected and integrated. The process described here ensures that the resulting policy is both contextually relevant and broadly supported, thereby increasing the likelihood of its successful implementation.

Figure 3: Process steps for the co-designing and drafting phase.

Development of the first draft

Based on the policy outline, the first draft of the policy is developed in this step. There are two possible approaches: either the draft is prepared collaboratively by the stakeholders involved, or it is authored by the internal consultant. In the first case, it is advisable to use a document accessible to all participants, which can be edited asynchronously and from any location. Alternatively, a synchronous writing process (e.g., in the form of a workshop) is possible. In this setting, all stakeholders can actively contribute to the writing process, which further strengthens their sense of ownership of the policy. This ensures that all parties can incorporate their expectations into the policy. This is crucial for ultimately securing the commitment of all stakeholders. Only if everyone feels that their concerns and desires are being heard can it be ensured that they will later commit to the policy. It should be noted here that the objectives can vary significantly depending on the context, as illustrated by the following example: Both a department of translation studies and a department of physics aim to develop a policy for AI use. Both policies should provide clear guidelines on which AI tools can be used, to what extent, and in which situations, by faculty and students. However, the policies will likely differ in terms of whether translation tools are considered permissible aids. At the same time, the writing process requires sufficient coordination to prevent the content from expanding uncontrollably and to ensure that it follows the structure of the policy outline.

In the second case, the draft is prepared by the internal consultant, who incorporates all key statements from the stakeholders gathered in the first phase. This ensures that no arguments or content are lost. While this approach does not allow stakeholders to actively participate in drafting, it is more likely to ensure that the content adheres closely to the policy outline.

First draft

At the end of the writing process, a first draft is available - either as a consolidated version jointly created by the stakeholders or as the result of the internal consultant’s work.

Discussion of the first draft

At this stage, the first draft is reviewed by all participants involved in the policy development process. Again, a synchronous workshop is a suitable format. This allows stakeholders to discuss open questions, propose changes, and add supplementary content. If the review process is not completed by the end of the workshop, stakeholders can submit additional contributions within a clearly defined timeframe.

During the workshop, the internal consultant primarily acts as a moderator and recorder. They ensure that all arguments are heard while maintaining the structures and content defined in the first phase. Once all feedback has been provided, the internal consultant consolidates it.

Consolidated draft

The result of this consolidation is an agreed-upon draft. This draft should no longer be altered by the stakeholders involved. However, further adaptations by other parties may occur during the third phase of policy development.

Adaptive implementation

In the third phase, the policy undergoes expert review to ensure compliance with institutional regulations, legal requirements, technical infrastructure, and pedagogical recommendations. Feedback from legal, technical, and didactic specialists is incorporated, followed by coordination with the responsible leadership at the academic unit. The resulting final draft is then presented to all stakeholders for approval, with any revisions transparently justified. The process concludes with the formal publication of the policy and the documentation of lessons learned to support future policy development efforts.

Figure 4: Process steps for the adaptive implementation phase.

Expert feedback

In this step, the consolidated draft is reviewed for compliance with the general regulations of the HEI - not only those relating to AI use - as well as with relevant legal requirements. Further checks address compatibility with the HEI's technical infrastructure and with pedagogical recommendations. It is worth reiterating the importance of involving students in the policy development process. If they were not included as stakeholders in the first phase, they should be involved at this stage (e.g., through student representation), as students are among the groups directly affected by the policy.

The internal consultant engages relevant HEI experts in the policy development process and collects their feedback. The goal is to ensure that all provisions and content of the policy are fully consistent with the institution's regulations. While it has been the consultant's responsibility throughout the previous two phases to safeguard this consistency, it cannot be ruled out that certain provisions may have been overlooked or unknown. Therefore, the agreed draft must be reviewed and formally approved by legal, technical, and pedagogical experts. If modifications are required during this approval process, they should be kept to a minimum. All such changes must be justifiable in terms of compatibility with institutional regulations or legal requirements.

Coordination with the responsible leadership

Once the internal consultant has incorporated the expert feedback, the resulting draft version is reviewed with the person at the academic unit level who holds overall responsibility for policy development. This person is responsible for approving the draft version.

Final draft

Following approval, a final draft is prepared and circulated by the internal consultant to all participants involved in the policy development process for review.

Stakeholder approval

All stakeholders are then invited to approve the final draft. Any changes made compared to the consolidated draft are communicated, along with explanations grounded in expert feedback. This ensures that modifications

are transparent to all participants and attributable to legal and/or institutional requirements. A joint workshop is again recommended for this step.

The internal consultant ensures that content previously agreed upon in earlier phases is not reopened for debate and fosters understanding of changes necessitated by institutional or legal mandates. This step aims to secure the commitment of all stakeholders to the content and implementation of the final draft.

Publication of the policy

Once approved by all stakeholders, the policy is finalized. Supported by the internal consultant, the person responsible for policy development at the academic unit publishes the policy (e.g., on the institute's website). The publication is accompanied by a brief documentation of the development process that also highlights the binding nature of the policy. Immediately after publication, all individuals affected by the policy, as well as all relevant HEI departments, are informed. The publication marks the conclusion of the policy development process.

After completing the development process, it is advisable for those responsible for process coordination to document the lessons learned. Within the academic unit for which the policy has been developed, this documentation reinforces the participatory approach. At the same time, other units planning to create an AI policy can benefit from these experiences. Over time, the HEI will accumulate a body of knowledge that facilitates the development of routines and efficiency improvements in AI policy creation.

3.3 Evaluation and iterative development

Once an AI policy has been formally adopted, it should not be regarded as a static document, but rather as a framework requiring ongoing evaluation and refinement. For an academic unit, this responsibility is fundamental because the pace of technological change in AI, as well as its diverse and discipline-specific applications, can quickly render outdated or impractical existing regulations. Local implementation contexts vary significantly across disciplines, meaning that only the academic unit is positioned to detect early whether the policy continues to meet the specific pedagogical, research, and operational needs of its field. This involves systematically collecting feedback from faculty, students, and support units on the policy's practical applicability, clarity, and impact on teaching and research practices. Mechanisms for reporting implementation challenges, unintended consequences, or emerging needs should be established, ensuring that lived experiences inform future adjustments. In parallel, the academic unit should monitor developments in AI technology, institutional priorities, and disciplinary practices to detect changes that may necessitate policy updates. By integrating these internal and external observations, the unit can ensure that the policy remains relevant, actionable, and aligned with both pedagogical objectives and academic integrity.

To achieve this, the academic unit should establish a structured evaluation process that integrates both quantitative and qualitative methods, ensuring that review activities are systematic, transparent, and inclusive. The role of internal consultants extends beyond the initial policy design phase to supporting long-term implementation, coordinating policy updates, and fostering institutional learning over time. Regular surveys and focus groups with faculty and students provide insights into the policy's usability and perceived effectiveness, while also revealing patterns, gaps, or compliance issues. The involvement of a dedicated internal coordinator ensures continuity and accountability in gathering feedback and formulating proposed revisions. Periodic workshops or review meetings offer a collaborative forum in which stakeholders can discuss findings, propose modifications, and collectively prioritize adjustments. Careful documentation of these processes not only promotes trust and transparency but also ensures that revisions remain firmly grounded in evidence and consensus.

At the institutional level, the HEI should take responsibility for coordinating periodic policy reviews across its academic units, thereby promoting coherence while allowing for context-specific adaptations. The internal consultant plays a key role in this process by facilitating communication between units, ensuring that feedback from diverse stakeholders is incorporated, and supporting the integration of legal, technical, and pedagogical expertise. This requires establishing clear review cycles, providing methodological support for policy evaluation, and ensuring alignment with updated legal frameworks, technical infrastructure, and pedagogical recommendations. Consistent with recent scholarship, this approach underscores the need for reflexivity and continuous evaluation to keep policies adaptable in the face of rapidly evolving technological and ethical landscapes (Li et al., 2025). Likewise, it reflects calls for sustained reflection and iteration, encouraging organizations to refine their governance approaches in response to feedback, emerging technologies, and shifting social expectations (Parthasarathy et al., 2024). The HEI should also maintain a central repository of lessons learned and best practices from individual units, creating an institutional knowledge base that facilitates more efficient and informed policy revisions in the future. Through this structured, iterative approach, both the academic unit and the HEI can maintain AI policies that are adaptable to technological change, responsive to stakeholder needs, and sustainable in the long term.

Positioning evaluation and iterative development as an integral component of the policy lifecycle ensures that the participatory principles guiding its creation continue to shape its evolution. Just as early stakeholder engagement fosters ownership and legitimacy, sustained involvement in reviewing and refining the policy reinforces these qualities over time. By embedding this adaptive process into institutional practice, academic units and HEIs can ensure that their AI policies remain both responsive to rapid technological developments and closely aligned with the needs and values of their academic communities.

4. Conclusion and outlook

The regulation of AI in HEIs has emerged as both an unavoidable necessity and a complex challenge. As outlined in the preceding chapters, existing attempts at regulation often remain overly general, creating ambiguity for faculty and students alike. Against this background, the model developed in Chapter 3 offers a structured pathway that combines hierarchical and participatory elements. It provides a means to create policies that are responsive to institutional requirements, sensitive to disciplinary contexts, and adaptive over time. This final chapter summarizes the contributions of the model, reflects critically on its challenges and limitations, and outlines opportunities and directions for future research and practice.

The three-phase model of policy development - pre-policy, co-design and drafting, and adaptive implementation - demonstrates several important strengths. It allows for contextualization, since policies developed at the level of institutes or departments are more likely to reflect actual pedagogical and research practices, avoiding the shortcomings of one-size-fits-all approaches. It fosters legitimacy and ownership because the early and continuous involvement of faculty, students, and administrative staff helps ensure broad acceptance and commitment. The model also places emphasis on iterative adaptability, recognizing that AI technologies evolve rapidly and that governance must remain dynamic. Finally, it integrates expertise: by including legal, technical, and didactic specialists at crucial stages, the process minimizes the risk of blind spots and ensures compatibility with overarching institutional and legal frameworks.

However, these advantages are accompanied by significant challenges. Participatory development requires substantial time and resources, which may strain already burdened faculty and staff. Effective coordination is indispensable but difficult to maintain, particularly when multiple units are simultaneously engaged in developing their own AI policies. In this context, the role of the internal consultant becomes essential. Acting

as a neutral facilitator, the consultant not only ensures that communication across stakeholder groups and departments remains efficient but also safeguards alignment with institutional requirements and mediates between potentially conflicting interests. By providing continuity across the different phases of the process, the consultant reduces the risk of delays or breakdowns in coordination and helps transform diverse perspectives into coherent outcomes.

At the same time, the heterogeneity of AI literacy among stakeholders poses a structural problem. Without systematic training, many participants may lack the expertise necessary to contribute meaningfully, leading to asymmetries of influence or superficial engagement. Another risk lies in fragmentation: while local differentiation is valuable, inconsistent or even contradictory policies across departments can create confusion for students and undermine institutional coherence. Addressing this requires careful facilitation and transparent communication channels. Finally, while the model is theoretically plausible and illustrated through a hypothetical scenario, its practical applicability remains to be demonstrated. Empirical testing in diverse HEI settings will be essential to validate its feasibility and long-term sustainability.

Despite these hurdles, the proposed approach offers considerable opportunities for HEIs when it comes to implementation. Properly applied, it allows the creation of a portfolio of policies that balance binding institutional regulations with flexible, locally relevant guidelines. This dual structure not only supports academic integrity by clarifying expectations for the use of AI but also fosters pedagogical innovation through discipline-specific experimentation and encourages ethical responsibility by creating spaces for explicit debate on risks and safeguards. At the same time, participatory development itself strengthens institutional capacity, as universities gain experience in negotiating complex technological change collaboratively and transparently.

A central factor for successful transfer into practice is that HEIs must follow legal requirements while also putting broader values such as fairness and responsibility into action. They cannot bypass national or international legislation, but they must translate such legal norms into operational rules that work in everyday academic practice. At the same time, they require flexibility to go beyond mere compliance and to establish frameworks that support responsible use within their communities. The model presented in Chapter 3 addresses this dual requirement by combining institution-wide regulations as a mandatory baseline with unit-level policies that provide context-sensitive guidance. This approach allows institutions to secure stability while remaining adaptable. The advantage lies in avoiding both the rigidity of legalistic regulation and the vagueness of abstract principles, ensuring instead that values such as fairness, accountability, and transparency are embedded in concrete responsibilities and shared practices.

Moreover, the transferability of the proposed model depends on institutional size, governance culture, and legal frameworks. Large universities with diverse faculties may benefit most from decentralized, unit-level policy development, while smaller institutions may find it more efficient to focus on collaboratively designed institution-wide guidelines. National legal requirements and cultural expectations will inevitably shape these processes, but the three-phase model offers a flexible template that can be adjusted to local contexts. To advance this transfer, comparative studies across countries and institutions will be needed, providing evidence of how participatory approaches can be adapted to different governance systems and how they contribute to sustainable AI regulation in higher education.

Additional areas also deserve further attention. Foremost is the evaluation of effectiveness: to date, little empirical evidence exists on whether AI policies actually achieve their intended outcomes, whether in safeguarding academic integrity, promoting innovation, or enhancing learning. Developing clear indicators and systematic evaluation methods will be crucial. In addition, cross-institutional and cross-national research could

provide valuable insights into the influence of legal frameworks and governance traditions, helping to establish internationally adaptable best practices.

Equally important is the integration of AI literacy training into policy processes. Without a shared baseline of knowledge, participatory engagement risks becoming superficial and limited in scope. Training modules for both staff and students can ensure that discussions are informed and inclusive. At the same time, policy design should remain attentive to unresolved legal and ethical questions, such as liability for AI-generated errors, intellectual property, and data protection. These issues are likely to gain prominence in the coming years, and HEIs must ensure their policies remain aligned with evolving legal standards and societal expectations.

In conclusion, it is clear that AI in higher education requires regulation, but not in the form of static or one-dimensional documents. Policies must be designed as living documents, continuously revised in light of technological, legal, and pedagogical change. Their legitimacy and effectiveness depend on the active participation of all stakeholders, the alignment between local and institutional levels, and the willingness to adapt. By embedding participatory and adaptive governance into their structures, HEIs can ensure that AI becomes a tool for responsible innovation, academic integrity, and educational excellence - rather than a source of disruption and division.

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Dilemma in Postdigital Era: Liberation of Autodidactism vs. Risks of Dehumanizing Education

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Abstract

In a postdigital society, where AI-driven technologies are seamlessly integrated into daily life, education stands at a crossroads. On one hand, cutting-edge digital tools and personalized learning assistants promote autonomy, self-learning, autodidactism, self-discovery, and open access. However, these same technologies raise concerns about the “dehumanization” of learning, marked by diminished empathy and reduced human interaction. This study examines both the liberating potential of AI-supported, autodidact-centered education and the risks of reducing education to automated processes. Drawing on foundational critiques of hierarchical schooling, this study revisits classical theorists such as Descartes, Illich, Freire, and Holt while integrating contemporary analyses of postdigital education based on the understanding of Jandrić and Knox. Through a discussion of emerging AI applications, the role of educational institutions, and the importance of balancing innovation with human-centered values, this paper offers insights into how post-digital learning can foster meaningful, equitable, and empathetic educational experiences rather than exacerbate social and emotional gaps.

Keywords

Postdigital Education, Autodidactism, Dehumanizing Education, AI

1. Introduction

The post-digital era signifies a period that contains both liberating opportunities and profound contradictions in the field of education. The integration of artificial intelligence, big data, and digital platforms into everyday life is radically transforming learning processes. On one hand, individuals are offered the chance to discover their own learning paths, set their own pace, and strengthen their autonomy; on the other hand, there is a potential to weaken human interaction, empathy, and social bonds by increasing the risk of dehumanization in education. This dual situation lies at the heart of the most critical dilemma that must be addressed in the field of educational technologies.

It is well known that the hierarchical, teacher-centered structure of traditional education has been criticized for many years (Freire, 1970; Illich, 1971; Holt, 1964). The criticisms have focused on the passivation of students, the suppression of curiosity and creativity, and the functioning of the school as a mechanism of social control (Postman & Weingartner, 1969; Neill, 1960). The technologies offered by the post-digital society promise powerful tools to overcome these criticisms: personalized learning assistants, open access resources, and AI-supported feedback systems strengthen autodidacticism and lay the groundwork for individuals to construct their own learning journeys more freely.

These same technologies also carry the risk of isolating individuals, reducing education to mechanical processes, and delegating cognitive functions to algorithms. In particular, artificial intelligence systems with a “black box” structure may undermine the fundamental human dimension of education by creating issues of transparency and accountability. In this context, discussing the role of artificial intelligence in education is not only a pedagogical necessity but also an ethical, social, and philosophical one.

This article examines the tension between the liberating potential of autodidacticism in the post-digital era and the risks of dehumanization in education. Building on classic critiques of education, it discusses both the opportunities and threats created by AI-based learning practices at individual and societal levels. In this way, a critical perspective is offered on how artificial intelligence should be positioned for a human-centered and emancipatory educational vision.

2. Criticisms of Traditional Education and Postdigital Education

Traditional education has long been criticized for its hierarchical and one-way structure. Illich (1971) regards education as an institutionalized mechanism of social control, while Holt (1964) argues that students’ natural curiosity to learn is suppressed by school structures. Freire (1970) explains this situation with the concept of the “banking model of education,” stating that students are positioned as passive recipients of information. Such approaches can hinder the development of students’ critical awareness and independent learning skills. Postman and Weingartner (1969), on the other hand, defined schools as structures that limit individual creativity and focus on producing conformity. In this context, it can be said that traditional education is a mechanism that prioritizes the maintenance of the social system over individual emancipation.

Neill (1960) emphasizes that children’s innate curiosity and creativity are blunted by rigid school structures. This criticism is seen as contrary to the very nature of learning. While students are measured through predetermined curricula and standardized tests, they are deprived of the opportunity to explore their own learning paths. At this point, the possibilities offered by the post-digital age can facilitate the resurgence of individual creativity. The multiple forms of expression provided by digital environments (such as video, simulation, augmented reality, etc.) allow learners to construct knowledge in ways that suit their own learning styles, rather than through a single standard mode of information delivery (Knox, 2019).

In the postdigital age, the boundaries between digital and analog have blurred, and the ways of accessing and interacting with information have fundamentally changed (Jandrić, Knox & Besley, 2018). In this context, learning is no longer limited to in-class experiences but is supported by different platforms, social networks, and AI-based assistants. Thus, learning processes have become more versatile and interactive. Education has evolved from a structure where the teacher is the sole authority to a network structure in which learners are active participants.

AI-powered personal learning assistants are concretizing Descartes’ idea of autodidacticism today by offering content tailored to students’ individual needs. This evokes Coelho’s (1988) “hero’s journey” metaphor, enabling individuals to discover their own potential. In this way, learning shifts from being a static and hierarchical structure to becoming a dynamic and self-directed process. Research shows that self-regulated learning develops more strongly on digital platforms and increases students’ motivation (Song & Hill, 2007).

Both traditional critiques of education and the new opportunities offered by the post-digital age make it necessary to rethink education. The new paradigm makes learning individual-centered, curiosity-driven, and flexible; at the same time, it brings issues such as social equality, digital access, and ethics to the forefront. This

transformation, in harmony with Freire's critical pedagogy, redefines learning not only as the transmission of knowledge, but also as a process of emancipation in which the individual realizes themselves.

3. Liberation of Autodidacticism

In the post-digital era, AI-powered tools allow individuals to direct their learning processes according to their own needs and interests. In this context, autodidacticism, that is, the practice of self-directed learning, has become more accessible than ever before. Research shows that learners strengthen their sense of autonomy and increase their intrinsic motivation for learning thanks to personalized digital platforms (Siemens, 2014). Especially AI-supported recommendation systems facilitate learning as a self-directed process by continuously supporting the learner's journey with feedback (Mouza & Yang, 2020).

Autodidactic learning gains strength through individuals' free access to various disciplines (Firat, 2023). Open educational resources (OER) offered by digital platforms enable learners to produce knowledge in different fields, reminiscent of Leonardo da Vinci's multidisciplinary learning practice. A study has shown that students who use open-access digital learning resources demonstrate significant improvements in both critical thinking and creative problem-solving skills (Weller, 2020). This indicates that in the post-digital age, individuals can be not only consumers but also productive subjects of learning.

AI-based learning assistants offer adaptable content using data from students' previous learning experiences. This means that the speed and method of learning can be individualized. Indeed, a large-scale meta-analysis has shown that AI-based personalization strategies significantly increase student achievement compared to traditional methods (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). In this way, autodidactic learning allows individuals to progress according to their own interests and to form a deeper connection with knowledge.

Autodidacticism does not render the teacher obsolete; on the contrary, it transforms the teacher's role from a transmitter of knowledge to a guide and facilitator. As in Freire's (1970) "pedagogy of dialogue" approach, the teacher evolves into a mentor who supports the learner in discovering their own potential. Research has shown that students who experience autodidactic learning in digital environments develop higher self-regulation skills in learning processes structured under teacher guidance (Song & Hill, 2007). This indicates that the most powerful learning outcomes can be achieved when autodidactic freedom is combined with teacher support.

Post-digital autodidacticism has the potential to bring learning opportunities to wider audiences despite socioeconomic inequalities. Open online courses (MOOCs) and AI-powered learning platforms enable individuals from different regions to participate in learning experiences simultaneously. For example, research conducted on platforms like Coursera has shown that students from low-income countries make intensive use of these resources for self-learning and career development (Reich & Ruipérez-Valiente, 2019). This demonstrates that autodidacticism can play not only a role in individual empowerment but also serve as a societal equalizer.

4. Risks of Dehumanizing Education

In AI-supported postdigital educational environments, direct communication between student and teacher, as well as between students themselves, may decrease. Face-to-face interaction in the traditional classroom is critical for learners to socialize and develop a shared sense of belonging. However, in learning through digital platforms, the sense of social presence may weaken; when students interact by turning off their cameras or through text-based communication, important elements of communication such as eye contact and body language are left out. Indeed, research on remote education during the COVID-19 period revealed that

students prefer face-to-face instruction in the classroom and report higher participation and learning in physical classrooms (Photopoulos et al., 2022). On the other hand, relying excessively on artificial intelligence during the learning process may blunt students' real-life communication skills. A qualitative study shows that over-reliance on educational AI tools gradually reduces face-to-face social interactions and negatively affects individuals' teamwork and communication skills (Cambra-Fierro et al., 2024).

The marginalization of the human factor in education also brings with it the risk of weakening empathy development. In the absence of physical interaction, students may find fewer opportunities to read the emotions of their peers or teachers and to show them sensitivity. A meta-analysis examining data from the past thirty years determined that there has been a marked decline in empathy levels among university students (Konrath et al., 2011). This study reports that young people's tendencies toward empathy decreased by about 40% between 1979 and 2009, and that a significant portion of this decline emerged after the 2000s, coinciding with the spread of digital communication (Konrath et al., 2011). One reason for the decrease in empathy may be the lack of emotional cues in artificial intelligence-based communication. While human teachers can perceive students' emotional states from changes in their facial expressions or tone of voice, algorithms have difficulty picking up on such nuances. Indeed, one study emphasized that interacting with an artificial agent lacking emotional intelligence cannot fully support students or replace genuine human warmth (Rodway & Schepman, 2023). Under these circumstances, learners have fewer opportunities to practice empathy, and over time, their ability to understand others may lead to the risk of becoming desensitized to others' emotions.

A decrease in human interaction can lead to weakened emotional bonds in education and cause students to feel lonely. Although AI-supported systems can be informative and interactive, they cannot fully provide the emotional support and understanding that a real teacher can offer. This situation may cause students to feel emotionally detached or alienated during the learning process. For example, in scenarios where AI tools are used instead of instructors, it has been reported that feelings of loneliness among students increase, which can negatively affect both academic achievement and retention (Crawford et al., 2024). When the warm learning atmosphere created by face-to-face interactions disappears, students may hesitate to share their thoughts and feelings, and their sense of belonging to the learning community may weaken. Research has shown that students interacting with AI may exhibit signs of social isolation, and technological communication cannot fully replace genuine social support (Crawford et al., 2024; Rodway & Schepman, 2023). So, breaking human bonds in education carries the risk of making the learning experience mechanical by endangering students' motivation and emotional well-being.

The delegation of many aspects of education to automated systems may lead to the diminishing importance of human intuition and expertise. In particular, if teachers begin to rely entirely on artificial intelligence recommendations instead of their own experience and pedagogical knowledge, the creative and uniquely human fabric of education may be damaged. The literature provides evidence that over-reliance on artificial intelligence negatively affects the skills of both students and teachers. For example, a review study found that students who rely too heavily on dialogue-based AI systems may experience a decline in cognitive skills such as problem-solving and critical thinking (Zhai et al., 2024). This finding suggests that when artificial intelligence becomes an authority rather than a supportive tool in the learning process, it may limit students' intellectual development. Similarly, leaving teaching activities to full automation is also problematic: Teachers who work constantly under algorithmic guidance may lose their creative teaching practices, and the educator's guiding role may be pushed into the background (Bhimdiwala et al., 2022). Some studies pointing to a crisis in the teaching profession note that the uncontrolled proliferation of AI applications can reduce teachers' share in decision-making and reduce them to mere operators of the system (Bhimdiwala et al., 2022). Therefore, as

doors open to technological innovations, educators must assume a critical and balancing role; otherwise, excessive dependence on automation may erode the human-centeredness at the core of education.

Some algorithms used in AI-supported education carry out decision-making processes in an incomprehensible (“black box”) manner. This opacity raises significant ethical concerns in education. Firstly, when an AI system evaluates student achievement or provides personalized content, teachers and students may not know how this outcome was produced. The uncertainty of the decision-making mechanism leads to questions about the reliability of the technology’s outputs and creates issues of accountability (Berendt et al., 2020). For example, a machine learning model used in university admissions or scholarship distribution may systematically misjudge disadvantaged groups due to biases present in historical data. Research shows that societal biases can manifest in the outputs of AI systems, and algorithms that are not adequately supervised may unintentionally disadvantage certain student groups (Kordzadeh & Ghasemaghaei, 2022). Since such algorithmic biases are difficult to detect in non-transparent systems, they have the potential to reinforce inequalities in education. In addition, when teachers struggle to explain why AI-based recommendation systems provide particular content to certain students, pedagogical control is also weakened. When educational decisions are guided by an incomprehensible algorithm rather than a human, it not only risks students’ privacy and rights but also narrows the scope for educators’ intervention (Berendt et al., 2020). Therefore, ensuring the principles of transparency and explainability in AI applications is of vital importance for a fair and trustworthy educational environment.

5. Discussion

The hierarchical, teacher-centered structure of traditional education has long been a subject of criticism in educational discourse, on the grounds that it leads students to become passive, unquestioning individuals (Freire, 1970; Holt, 1964; Illich, 1971). AI-based personalized learning, offered by the postdigital age, presents a strong opportunity to overcome these criticisms. However, it is precisely at this point that a contradiction arises. While the strengthening of technology-supported autodidacticism in education contributes to individual liberation, it also carries the risk of isolating individuals by reducing human interaction (Crawford et al., 2024).

The greatest achievement of autodidacticism in the postdigital era is individuals’ freedom to determine their own learning paths (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Firat, 2023). Yet, viewing learning solely as an individual process may push to the background the dimension of “dialogue” and “collective consciousness” emphasized by Freire (1970). Thus, while an individual continues their own journey of knowledge, they may be deprived of community-based solidarity and critical interaction. This dilemma creates a tension between the liberating power of autodidacticism and the social dimension of education.

AI-based learning assistants empower learners by offering personalized guidance, yet they also contain transparency issues due to the “black box” nature of decision-making processes (Berendt et al., 2020). At this point, the contradiction emerges between Illich’s (1971) liberating model of learning envisioned in a “deschooled society” and today’s algorithmic guidance. For Illich, freedom involves overcoming institutional structures, whereas artificial intelligence, by creating invisible algorithmic authorities, can subject learners to a different kind of dependency.

While Freire’s critical pedagogy aims to transform the student from passivity to an agent of social change, today’s AI-powered autodidacticism tends to focus on individual achievement and efficiency (Rodway & Schepman, 2023). Although this supports the personalization of the individual’s learning journey, it may overshadow the social and ethical responsibility dimensions of education. The goal of liberation in education

should include not only individual, but also social consciousness. Here lies one of the greatest predicaments of postdigital education: The same technologies, while empowering individuals and promoting their emancipation through autodidacticism, also increase the risk of dehumanization by weakening human interaction, empathy, and social bonds. If educational technologies are designed and implemented without taking this dual risk-opportunity balance into account, their emancipatory potential may give way to new forms of dependency and isolation.

6. Conclusions

The central dilemma presented by this article is that, in the post-digital age, AI-assisted education simultaneously empowers individual emancipation and autodidacticism, while also carrying the risk of steering education away from human-centeredness. This contradiction can only be resolved by adhering to the principle of cognitive sovereignty. AI should not be an external authority governing the learner, but rather an extension that expands human cognitive capacity and accompanies the learning process. At this point, the importance of open-source and distributed systems, where individuals can personalize, limit, and run their own models locally, becomes evident, instead of AI being developed as closed systems by central authorities. Especially in education, it is essential that AI is positioned not as a surveillance tool under central control, but as a companion and enhancer that reinforces the learner's freedom.

Open-source artificial intelligence ecosystems play a critical role in preserving individual autonomy in learning processes. In this way, learners can transparently see how algorithms work and adapt them according to their own ethical and pedagogical principles. This approach contributes to a fairer, more participatory, and emancipatory educational system not only on an individual level but also on a societal level. The decentralized adoption of artificial intelligence in education is the key to safeguarding human cognitive autonomy and reducing the risk of dehumanization. In this context, prominent recommendations for research and practical implementation are provided below:

1. Educational institutions and researchers should not rely solely on commercial closed systems; they should work on open-source AI models and adapt them to the specific context of education.
2. Research should be conducted on cognitive sovereignty to ensure that students use artificial intelligence tools critically, consciously, and autonomously.
3. Educational institutions should strengthen data privacy and control by implementing AI solutions in local and distributed environments as much as possible, rather than relying on cloud-based centralized structures.
4. Ethical principles based on international standards should be established for the use of AI in education; policies ensuring transparency, accountability, and the protection of student rights should be developed.
5. Universities and schools should develop hybrid learning models that both support learner autonomy and strengthen teacher guidance by testing open-source AI systems in small-scale pilot projects.

It seems that AI will open the doors to the postdigital world or the posthuman era. We all agree that AI brings and takes away many things. Perhaps the main question here should be this: which of our human traits and cultural characteristics do we not want it to take away, and where do we need to establish lines of resistance?.

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Guided Integration of Generative AI in Radiography Education: Effects on Presentation Quality and Emerging AI Literacy

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Abstract

The rapid emergence of generative AI tools, such as ChatGPT, Copilot, Gemini and NoteGPT, challenges higher education institutions to develop effective approaches for their integration into teaching and learning. Rather than restricting or prohibiting AI use, intentionally guiding students toward responsible and structured utilization of AI presents significant potential for enhancing learning outcomes, particularly in fields requiring mastery of complex scientific concepts, such as radiography.

The study addressed three research questions: (1) whether guided AI use improves the quality of students' presentations compared with previous non-AI cohorts, (2) how ChatGPT's rubric-based evaluations align with expert human grading, and (3) how students actually used and experienced AI during their work. All student groups were tasked with preparing presentations on radiography-specific topics: ionization chambers, Geiger-Müller tubes, thermoluminescence dosimeters, direct ion storage dosimeters, and scintillation detectors. The uniformity of these topics across multiple cohorts enables a comparative qualitative analysis, focusing on criteria such as scientific accuracy, clarity, depth of content, structure, and overall presentation coherence. Participating students documented their interactions with AI tools, recording prompts utilized, identifying aspects of their assignments where AI contributed most effectively, and addressing challenges encountered during the AI-assisted collaborative process. They were also instructed to reflect upon and articulate their key learning experiences related to AI use.

Across 28 presentations (12 AI-assisted), no statistically significant differences were found in scientific accuracy, clarity, or visual quality between AI and non-AI groups, indicating that human factors dominated quality variation. Correlations between AI (ChatGPT) and human scoring were negligible ($r \leq 0.22$), contrasting with earlier essay-based findings ($r \approx 0.6-0.8$). Qualitative reflections showed that students used AI primarily for conceptual understanding and explanation rather than content generation, displaying critical awareness of reliability and verification needs. Guided integration thus supported metacognitive learning and AI literacy even without measurable performance gains. Students reported that AI prompts helped in clarifying complex radiographic concepts, facilitating efficient literature searches, and assisting in the coherent organization of technical information. However, students also reported facing challenges, particularly related to critically assessing the reliability of AI-generated content, refining prompt engineering skills, and balancing dependence on AI tools with independent critical thinking and professional judgment.

Keywords

Guided AI Integration, AI Literacy, AI Assessment Reliability

1. Introduction

Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) tools such as ChatGPT, Copilot and Gemini have moved rapidly from pilot curiosities to everyday study companions in higher education, prompting sector bodies to publish practical guidance for teaching and assessment (Alcock 2024). Policy advice has shifted away from blanket prohibitions toward human-centred, responsible integration, emphasising clear institutional principles, capacity-building for staff and students, and safeguards around ethics and data (Holmes & Miao 2023).

Radiography education requires students to master demanding radiation-physics constructs and detector operating principles that are safety-critical in practice, yet cohorts are heterogeneous in prior mathematics and physics preparation. This creates a need for instructional scaffolds that translate abstract models into actionable understanding without displacing students' own reasoning. Generative AI tools are a promising candidate for such scaffolds, but their pedagogical role is best framed through contemporary theories of extended cognition and the extended mind. According to the extended mind thesis (Clark & Chalmers 1998) cognition need not be confined to the brain: when external resources, such as notes, diagrams, instruments, or AI systems, are functionally integrated into a person's problem solving and memory, they become constitutive parts of the cognitive process. From the extended-mind perspective, human thinking routinely unfolds across hybrid systems that couple brains with bodies, tools, and external media; new technologies (including LLMs) can become part of these cognitive circuits. Rather than simple "offloading," productive human–AI loops can amplify creative problem-solving while demanding new meta-skills: assessing reliability, calibrating trust, and learning how to question AI-suggested ideas. This view positions GenAI neither as a threat nor a silver bullet, but as a resource whose value depends on how it is integrated into the wider cognitive ecosystem of learning (Clark 2025).

In science education, researchers distinguish between two main ways of using generative AI. Substitutive use means letting AI do the work for the learner, which can make students passive and reduce their own thinking. Complementary use, in contrast, keeps students active and engaged. Recent studies describe three useful complementary ways to use AI in teaching: (1) AI-generated feedback that helps students notice and correct their misunderstandings, (2) supportive functions that make learning more accessible without replacing the learner's effort, and (3) interactive or game-like dialogues that encourage explanation and critical thinking. The key pedagogical goal is to design learning activities where AI supports and extends human thinking, rather than acting as a replacement or main author (Rivera-Novoa & Duarte, 2025).

Our study applies this approach in a radiography course at Tampere University of Applied Sciences by giving students guided opportunities to use generative AI while preparing presentations on standardised detector-physics topics. Students were instructed to ask AI for step-by-step explanations, find sources and technical information, and organize that information. They also recorded the prompts, sources, and verification steps, so that evaluation and reflection became explicit parts of the learning process. The resulting presentations were compared with those of earlier cohorts that had no AI guidance to explore three questions: (1) Does guided use of generative AI improve presentation quality in terms of accuracy, clarity, depth, structure, and coherence? (2) How well do large language model (LLM) rubric-based ratings align with human expert evaluations? (3) How do students actually use and evaluate generative AI when working under guidance?

2. Methods

The study was conducted in a radiography course in which student teams prepared presentations on detector physics (ionization chambers, Geiger–Müller tubes, direct-ion-storage dosimeters, thermoluminescence dosimeters, and scintillation detectors). Using identical topics across cohorts allows direct comparison of the

outputs. Prior cohorts prepared the assignment using mainly textbooks and web sources. The 2025 cohort received an intentionally guided AI intervention: in addition to textbooks/web, students were encouraged to use AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, Copilot) in preparing their presentations. Short how-to videos of using Photomath and ChatGPT were provided, together with some example prompts. In preparing the presentations, the students were encouraged to use AI tools to explore the topic through summaries, definitions and concept checks, to outline and structure slides, and to clarify difficult concepts. They were further instructed to conclude with one to two slides that list the prompts used, explain when, where and how AI supported their work, and offer brief reflections on what worked, what proved challenging, and the key takeaways about AI use. The student presentations were examined qualitatively on accuracy, clarity, depth, visualizations, terminology and the usage of sources. Students' metacognitive reflections were investigated on benefits and challenges. This approach follows international recommendations that recognise GenAI literacy, including the critical evaluation of accuracy, credibility, and truthfulness, as an essential emerging competence.

The material consists of 28 presentations, of which 12 were AI-assisted. The AI-supported presentations covered the same technical topics as the non-AI ones but included an additional slide or section explicitly describing how artificial intelligence had been used during the work. Thematically, the AI-assisted groups relied on ChatGPT or Copilot mainly for information retrieval, conceptual clarification, and structuring their presentations, while a few used image-generation tools for visualization. The study addresses three questions:

1. Does guided AI use improve presentation quality relative to earlier cohorts? This was examined by evaluating the presentation within each topic area against criteria for scientific accuracy, conceptual depth, clarity of explanation, structure and coherence, quality of visualizations, correct terminology, use of sources and citations, and overall professionalism. Each aspect was rated from 0 to 5, and the presentation's final mark was computed as the simple average of all criterion scores.
2. How do large-language-model (ChatGPT) ratings align with expert human evaluation and grading of the presentations? To assess alignment, the same presentation PDFs were submitted to ChatGPT with the identical rubric (scientific accuracy, conceptual depth, clarity, structure and coherence, visual quality, terminology, use of sources, overall professionalism), instructing it to produce 0–5 scores per criterion and an overall mean with brief justifications.
3. How do students actually use AI when preparing their presentations (prompts, verification behaviours, perceived benefits)?

3. Results

3.1 Quality of presentations in AI and non-AI presentations

Figure 1 presents the evaluation results of all student presentations across the five assessment categories: 1) scientific accuracy and depth, 2) clarity and structure, 3) visuals and diagrams, 4) sources, and 5) terminology (left) and the distribution of these grades between AI-assisted and non-AI groups (right). There were no statistically significant differences between AI-assisted and non-AI presentations in any of the rubric dimensions or in the overall scores. Variation was markedly larger at the topic/group level (e.g., between student groups) than between the AI versus non-AI condition, suggesting that quality differences were primarily attributable to the groups themselves rather than to the use of AI. Presentation-to-presentation variation within each cohort was substantial, with scores for individual presentations spanning the full 0–5

range and considerable overlap between cohorts; this within-cohort dispersion outweighed the average AI vs. non-AI differences on most criteria. These results indicate that human factors dominated quality outcomes in this implementation and guided AI did not systematically lift performance beyond that background variability.

Figure 1. Evaluation of student presentations on radiation measurement topics. The heatmap (left) shows individual scores across five assessment categories classified by AI-assisted and non-AI groups. The bar chart (right) presents the overall grade distribution, indicating no significant difference between AI-assisted and non-AI presentations.

3.2 AI and human grading

The anonymized student presentations were given to ChatGPT for evaluation, and they were also independently evaluated by the course’s instructor. The presentations were assessed using a five-criterion rubric addressing accuracy and coverage, clarity and structure, visual design, sources, and terminology. The rubric was used both by the human evaluator and ChatGPT, which was instructed to produce 0–5 scores per criterion and an overall mean with brief justifications. Table 1 presents the rubric in detail, describing the performance levels (1, 3, 5) and their corresponding qualitative characteristics for each assessment criterion. Presentations achieving higher scores demonstrated factual precision, coherent organisation, effective visual communication, appropriate referencing, and accurate use of disciplinary terminology. Lower scores indicated superficial understanding, limited structure, insufficient or unclear visuals, inadequate sourcing, or inconsistent terminology.

Table 1: Assessment rubric.

Criteria	Score 5 (Excellent)	Score 3 (Average)	Score 1 (Weak)
Accuracy & Coverage	All content accurate and comprehensive. Covers structure, principle, use cases. Level suitable to radiography students. No errors.	Mostly correct with minor inaccuracies or omissions. Some important aspects missing.	Several errors or misconceptions. Major gaps in coverage, very superficial.
Clarity & Structure	Logical flow, slides are well-structured and easy to follow. Key points highlighted clearly.	Generally understandable structure, but occasional inconsistency or weak transitions.	Confusing, poorly organized, difficult to follow. No clear progression.
Visuals	Images, diagrams and layout strongly support understanding. Text is readable, visually appealing. No AI-generated, background images.	Some visuals but uneven quality. Images partially support content only partially.	Weak visuals. Irrelevant images or unreadable layout.
Sources	Reliable, diverse sources (e.g. STUK, textbooks, scientific articles). Full reference list.	Some sources present.	Unreliable references, if no sources, then score = 0.
Terminology	Correct and consistent use of physics/radiation terminology (e.g., scattering, atomic number, $\mu\text{Sv/h}$). Professional style.	Terminology mostly correct, but some mistakes or inconsistent usage.	Terminology inaccurate or wrong. Casual language instead of scientific.

Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between human and ChatGPT evaluations of student presentations across all assessment criteria. Each bubble represents one or more paired scores, with its size corresponding to the number of occurrences. While the general distribution suggests a weak positive trend between the two evaluators, the overall correlation coefficient was only $r = 0.22$, indicating that ChatGPT's ratings aligned with human judgement only to a limited extent. ChatGPT exhibited a narrower scoring range, avoiding the lowest scores and showing a tendency to concentrate around values 3–4, whereas human assessors used the full scale more distinctly. This compression effect implies that ChatGPT was less sensitive to qualitative differences between average and excellent presentations.

To investigate the differences between AI and human evaluations in more detail, grade distributions for each criterion were visualised as boxplots in Figure 3. It presents a criterion-wise comparison between AI (ChatGPT) and human evaluations across five rubric dimensions and the overall score. The boxplots show that the two evaluators produced relatively similar median grades, but with substantial variation within and between categories. The correlation coefficients (r) indicate only weak alignment for all criteria: from $r = 0.02$ in Visuals to $r = 0.45$ in Sources, with a correlation of $r = 0.15$ for the overall presentation grade. The strongest agreement appeared in the Sources category, where both evaluators tended to reward the presence of clear references

and identifiable source material. In contrast, Visuals, Terminology, and Accuracy & Coverage showed almost no correlation, suggesting that ChatGPT was incapable to assess the presentations deeply enough.

Figure 2. Relationship between human and ChatGPT evaluations of student presentations across all assessment criteria. Bubble size represents the number of occurrences.

Figure 3. Criterion-wise comparison between AI (ChatGPT) and human evaluations across five rubric dimensions and the overall score with correlation coefficients (r).

Compared with the findings of Quah et al. (2024), where correlations between ChatGPT and human assessors in essay scoring reached $r = 0.83$ and $r = 0.60$ for two open-ended clinical questions, the correlations observed in this study were negligibly small ($r \approx 0.22$ or below). This difference is likely explained by the fundamentally different nature of the assessment tasks. While Quah et al. evaluated extended written responses that allowed the AI model to recognise linguistic patterns, argumentation structure, and generic essay features, the present study involved PowerPoint presentations focused on technically precise and physics-based content. Such material requires understanding of quantitative reasoning, conceptual accuracy, and disciplinary terminology, areas in which large language models currently seem to perform less reliably. Overall, the pattern supports the interpretation that ChatGPT captures surface-level features, such as text organisation and reference presence, better than deep disciplinary understanding or contextual accuracy. Evaluating the quality of diagrams and

schematic representations of radiation detectors poses particular challenges for AI, which remains insufficient as a stand-alone assessment tool for this type of task.

3.3 Student reflections on AI use.

Information on students' use and experiences of artificial intelligence was collected through a reflective self-report task that accompanied each presentation. After completing their group work, students were asked to describe how and for what purposes AI tools were used, what benefits or challenges they observed, and how AI influenced their learning or understanding of the topic. The reflections appended to presentation slides. The data were gathered from all AI-assisted groups (n = 12) across the five detector topics (DIS dosimeter, TLD, ionisation chamber, scintillation detector, and Geiger tube). Responses were analysed qualitatively to identify typical patterns of AI use.

Table 2 summarises the main purposes for which students reported using AI tools during the preparation of their group presentations. Six distinct categories of use were identified from the students' reflective reports: information retrieval and conceptual understanding, structuring and text generation, searching for sources, image creation and visualisation, language support and translation, and reflection and learning support.

Table 2: Purposes, descriptions, and frequency of reported AI use in the preparation of student presentations.

Purpose of AI use	Description and typical examples	No of obs.
Information retrieval and conceptual understanding	Students asked AI to explain technical principles, definitions, and applications (e.g., <i>"What is an ionization chamber and how does it work?"</i> , <i>"What does surface dose mean?"</i>)	12
Structuring and text generation	AI used to create outlines, slide headings, or summaries (<i>"Can you make a PowerPoint template for this topic?"</i> , <i>"Condensed version on one slide"</i>).	3
Searching for sources	Used as Google search. AI helped locate or list industrial actors and reference materials when search engines were insufficient.	3
Image creation and visualization	Students employed AI to generate or design illustrative figures (<i>"Create a picture showing scintillation detector applications"</i> , <i>"Make an image of Geiger counter use"</i>).	2
Language support and translation	AI assisted in rephrasing, summarising, or translating text between Finnish and English.	2
Reflection and learning support	AI used for clarification of misunderstood concepts and as a conversational tool for self-explanation (<i>"Good to use AI to explain things when something is difficult to understand"</i>).	2

The most frequent and clearly valued use concerned information retrieval and conceptual understanding, where students asked AI to explain technical principles, definitions, or applications in radiation physics. This indicates that AI primarily served as a conceptual tutor or explanatory aid, helping students make sense of complex physical phenomena. Other uses—such as structuring text, locating sources, or language translation—appeared occasionally but were less central. Image generation was used only in a couple of presentations. Based on course's instructor's comments, the AI-generated images and illustrations were mostly irrelevant, wrong or misleading for scientific topics. Several students also described using AI to clarify misunderstandings or to rehearse explanations in their own words, which suggests a potential role for AI in supporting metacognitive learning processes. However, this type of use was observed only in 2 presentations. Therefore,

reflective use of AI and iterative improvement of presentations based on AI feedback should be encouraged in the future.

Students' reflections also revealed a notably critical and self-aware approach to using AI tools. Several groups reported that the responses provided by ChatGPT or Copilot were sometimes inconsistent, incomplete, or even misleading—for example, offering contradictory information about manufacturers or confusing “ionization chambers” with ionizing air purifiers. Others noted that the system occasionally redirected them to irrelevant online sources. Such experiences led students to emphasize the need for fact-checking and source evaluation: they learned that question formulation affected the precision and depth of AI's responses and that outputs could not be accepted uncritically. Overall, the reflections demonstrate an emerging form of AI literacy characterized by cautious engagement, iterative questioning, and awareness of the reliability limits of generative systems. From a pedagogical standpoint, this aligns with recent extensions of the extended mind thesis in AI-enhanced learning, where generative AI is seen not merely as a tool but as a cognitive extension of the learner, yet one that requires metacognitive control to avoid passive offloading (Rivera-Novoa et al., 2025).

4. Conclusions

This study explored guided use of generative AI in radiography education through a comparative analysis of student presentations and reflections. While structured AI guidance did not measurably improve presentation quality relative to non-AI cohorts, it enhanced students' reflective awareness and conceptual engagement. The minimal correlation between ChatGPT and human grading ($r \approx 0.2$) contrasts with higher correspondence in essay-based assessments ($r \approx 0.6$ – 0.8), suggesting that AI evaluation is more effective for linguistic or narrative tasks than for technical and physics-oriented reasoning.

Across cohorts, a consistent pattern emerged: good students produced good presentations both with and without AI, and weaker groups tended to perform modestly regardless of AI support. This indicates that generative AI alone does not equalise learning outcomes; rather, its benefits depend on students' existing skills in critical thinking, conceptual understanding, and self-regulated learning.

Students' reflections showed that AI functioned mainly as an explanatory and organising aid, but in some cases also as a substitute for understanding by providing oversimplifications. Students recognised both the utility and the limits of AI tools, particularly regarding factual accuracy and conceptual depth demonstrating the emergence of AI literacy as a critical professional competence.

Pedagogically, these findings align with the extended mind perspective, where generative AI operates as a complementary cognitive extension that supports but does not replace human reasoning. Effective learning design should therefore foster iterative questioning, verification, and reflection when using AI, ensuring that human judgment and disciplinary expertise remain central. Future research should explore how guided AI practices can be scaled within STEM and health education, balancing automation with epistemic responsibility and maintaining a strong role for educator-led scaffolding.

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The Potential of AI-generated Feedback for Self-Assessment Tasks

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Abstract

In digital learning environments, feedback provided by instructors on students' solutions can be individual for each student but does not scale for large classes. Standardized feedback defined by the instructor for error-cases may not fully align with individual student responses or lack personalization. This limitation often leads to less effective learning support, as generic or mismatched feedback may not adequately address specific student needs. To tackle this issue, this study investigates the potential of AI-generated feedback as a solution for providing scalable and personalized feedback within the SAFRAN Moodle plugin. The AI feedback system was evaluated by two instructors who reviewed a selection of tasks and the corresponding AI-generated feedback. Feedback was generated using GPT-3.5 Turbo and four other models. Instructors rated the feedback on six criteria—accuracy, relevance, detail, language quality, appropriateness, and coherence—using a 1–5 likert scale, resulting in 45 evaluated pairs of student solution and generated feedback. The findings show that all AI models performed well, with median scores of 4 across most criteria. GPT-4 Turbo received the highest average rating, closely followed by LLaMa 3. While newer and larger models like GPT-4 Turbo and LLaMa 3 outperformed smaller or older models, the differences between models were minimal, all achieving mean scores between 3.66 and 4.05. This indicates that AI-generated feedback is generally accurate, relevant, and coherent, making it a promising tool for assisting instructors. This research demonstrates the potential of AI to significantly enhance feedback processes in digital learning environments, offering personalized and scalable solutions, though challenges like prompt tuning and cross-context generalization require further research.

Keywords

AI-feedback, AI-Feedback-Agent, self-assessment, digital learning environments, personalized feedback

1. Introduction

independently evaluate and deepen their knowledge while fostering autonomy and critical thinking. However, these tasks often lack self-explanatory clarity, which can lead to incomplete or incorrect understanding without additional feedback (Kasakowskij et al., 2023). To address this, SAFRAN (Self-Assessment with Feedback Recommendations), a Moodle plugin, was developed. SAFRAN provides automated feedback specified by the instructor for specific error cases, allowing learners to receive immediate guidance, review sample solutions, and iteratively improve their responses (Kasakowskij et al., 2023).

Despite its benefits, feedback provision for self-assessment tasks faces significant challenges. Manual feedback generation by instructors is time-consuming and resource-intensive, particularly for large number of learners where scalability is critical (Cavalcanti et al, 2021; Winter, 2024). Additionally, the effectiveness of feedback is highly dependent on individual learner preferences and prerequisites, leading to variability in its impact. Feedback may fail to achieve its intended outcomes due to unknown technical terminology, inappropriate or overly authoritative feedback, or the lack of necessary context, potentially causing learners to disregard it (Kasakowskij, 2022; Kleißer & Kohl, 2023). These challenges underscore the need for personalized and scalable solutions.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers promising opportunities to enhance feedback processes by providing personalized and efficient feedback. While AI integration in higher education is still emerging, applications such as chatbots, recommendation systems, educational robots, and AI-powered writing assistants demonstrate its potential (de Witt et al., 2020). The KI-Campus whitepaper "AI in Higher Education" provides a comprehensive overview of AI's rationale and use cases in teaching and learning (de Witt et al., 2020). AI-driven feedback systems can enable learners to regulate their learning behaviours more effectively while offering scalable solutions that reduce instructors' workload (de Witt et al., 2020; Schmohl et al., 2023).

This study explores the development and evaluation of an AI feedback agent integrated into Moodle to support teachers and learners in generating and receiving individualized feedback for self-assessment tasks. Specifically, it investigates how a pre-trained AI model can generate targeted, individualized feedback and enhance scalability by minimizing the time and resources required for feedback creation. This is particularly relevant as the growing demand for personalized feedback must not become a bottleneck in educational processes.

The study addresses the following research questions:

1. How can an AI feedback agent be implemented to provide individualized and scalable feedback for self-assessment tasks?
2. How do instructors perceive the quality and utility of AI-generated feedback compared to their own feedback?
3. To what extent can an AI feedback agent generate contextually relevant feedback, guided by reference texts or sample solutions, while minimizing the production of irrelevant or off-topic content?

1.1 Feedback: Concept & Evolution

Hattie & Timperley (2007) define feedback as information provided by an agent, such as a teacher, a book, or the learner themselves, regarding aspects of one's performance or understanding. This information can be corrective, encouraging, or clarifying and serves as a response to demonstrated performance. The primary goal of feedback is to reduce the gap between current performance and the desired performance goal (Hattie & Timperley, 2007). Traditional feedback has a long history in educational research and is emphasized as a central tool in the teaching process (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Kasper et al., 2020). The effectiveness of feedback depends on whether it provides information about the correctness of the demonstrated performance. Both positive and negative feedback can be effective, with their impact varying based on individual goals and developmental stages (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Wisniewski et al., 2019).

With the ongoing digital transformation, the concept of digital feedback is gaining increasing importance. Compared to traditional paper-based tasks, digital feedback offers numerous potentials and can effectively support learning activities (Hattie & Timperley, 2007). A significant aspect of this digitalization is the integration of additional components into feedback systems, including automated and autonomous systems. Programmed systems open up new possibilities for generating feedback.

According to the modern definition of feedback by (Neudecker, 2021), it is essential to incorporate the dimension of digitalization, as modern technologies are transforming how feedback is collected, analysed, and delivered. In the age of digitalization, automated systems are increasingly being employed to optimize and scale feedback processes. These systems offer innovative approaches to capturing, interpreting, and responding to feedback more efficiently.

1.2 The Rise of AI Agents as feedback provider

Since ChatGPT was made freely available to the public in November 2022, numerous AI applications have permeated various industries. As a pioneer, the AI chatbot has paved the way for a multitude of other AI tools (Schubert, 2024; Aljanabi et al., 2023). In addition to ChatGPT, there is a wide range of other AI agents on the market. Major technology companies, such as IBM with Watson (IBM, 2024), Microsoft with Azure Cognitive Services (Microsoft, 2024), Google with Cloud Natural Language Processing (Google, 2024) and Gemini (Google, 2025), and Amazon with Comprehend (Amazon, 2024), have also developed their own AI applications.

Many applications have already integrated AI agents to leverage their benefits and achieve efficient and scalable outcomes. A notable example of successful integration can be found in the question-and-answer network Quora. The platform introduced “Poe” (Platform for Open Exploration), a system that allows users to interact with various AI agents. This enables users to obtain quick answers to their questions or generate AI-driven responses to questions posed by others. Additionally, third-party solutions for Quora, such as the “ChatGPT for Quora” Chrome browser extension, allow users to have their questions answered by ChatGPT, similar to Poe. Comparable extensions exist for other AI agents, such as Merlin AI (MerlinAI, 2025; Rastogi, 2024).

Quora is, of course, not the only system with chatbot integration. Similar integrations exist for some of the most popular browsers and messaging platforms, such as WhatsApp. The widely used messaging platform Slack has also incorporated a ChatGPT integration designed to assist users in drafting messages to colleagues. Another example is “ChatPDF,” a web-based tool that allows users to interact with uploaded PDF documents using ChatGPT (Rastogi, 2024). The potential applications of these AI integrations are highly diverse, demonstrating the versatility and adaptability of AI technologies across various domains.

This trend is also evident in the educational domain, where recent systems have begun to incorporate not only machine learning but also Large Language Models (LLMs), often referred to as AI, for feedback recommendation in various domains (Lübcke et al., 2023; Benharrak et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2024; Han et al., 2024). For instance, (Lübcke et al., 2023) developed a study assistant system called SIDDATA, which supports students in selecting appropriate learning techniques and materials, organizing study abroad semesters, and forming study groups. Additionally, this AI-based recommender system can suggest courses that align with students’ individual academic interests. However, the system does not assist students during task completion. In contrast, (Benharrak et al., 2024) created an editor called Impressona, which generates and provides on-demand feedback for writing tasks. Students can choose from various AI personas, each offering feedback from a distinct perspective. Within the editor, students can compose a text, select any portion of it, and receive feedback on the selected text from the chosen persona. The personas are defined by the students themselves. The prototype was evaluated through two user studies (the first with 5 participants and the second with 11 participants). Participants found the generated feedback helpful, leading to revisions of both the text and the personas. However, the feedback was often criticized for being overly verbose and lacking specificity. While SIDDATA functions as a general study assistant, it is not designed for specific instructional tasks.

Despite these advancements, such AI-driven support systems are not yet widely available for (self-)assessment tasks, even though they would be highly useful. The integration of AI agents in this domain could provide scalable, personalized, and efficient feedback mechanisms, addressing the growing demand for timely and accurate feedback in educational settings.

1.3 Self-Assessments in Online Learning Environments

Self-assessment has been introduced as a novel approach in online learning environments. This method offers diverse opportunities for practicing, enabling learners to evaluate and critically reflect on their own performance based on predefined criteria. The integration of self-assessment not only fosters self-reflection but also helps learners develop a deeper understanding of learning objectives, requirements, and evaluation criteria. Through this active engagement, learners assume a dual role: they are both evaluators of their own performance and recipients of feedback that contributes to the improvement and deepening of their knowledge (Andrade, 2019).

However, many students, particularly at the beginning of their studies, tend to inaccurately assess their own abilities. Research reveals interesting patterns: students with poorer performance often overestimate their capabilities, while academically stronger students tend to exhibit more accurate self-assessments (Haake et al., 2021; Boud et al., 2015; Carroll, 2020). This indicates that it is particularly relevant to support students working on self-assessment tasks in digital learning environments with adaptive, individualized feedback.

To address this need, we describe in this paper an extension for the SAFRAN system, a Moodle plugin designed to provide students with self-assessment tasks and deliver situational and adaptive feedback. Currently, learners receive feedback after completing and self-evaluating their tasks, with the feedback initially created by an instructor for specific error cases. While this approach has its merits, it is resource-intensive, as instructors must account for a wide range of error cases and scenarios to ensure comprehensive and helpful feedback. Otherwise, there is a risk that the feedback may remain incomplete and fail to fulfill its intended purpose (Kulhavy, 1989).

The proposed extension of the current system enhances the feedback generation process by integrating AI. AI offers a potential solution to the challenges of scalability and personalization. By leveraging AI, the enhanced system can generate feedback that is more tailored to the individual needs of learners, improving clarity and relevance. This would benefit both instructors and learners. Instructors could be relieved of the time-consuming task of manual feedback generation, allowing them to focus on other critical responsibilities. Simultaneously, learners could benefit from feedback that is better aligned with their needs, helping them achieve their learning goals more effectively.

In summary, the integration of AI into the SAFRAN system represents a significant step forward in supporting self-assessment tasks in online learning environments. By providing scalable, personalized, and efficient feedback mechanisms, this extension has the potential to address the growing demand for timely and accurate feedback, ultimately enhancing the learning experience for students and reducing the workload for instructors.

2. Requirements for the AI-Driven Feedback System

To define the requirements for the proposed AI-driven extension of SAFRAN, we use User Stories. These concise, user-focused descriptions establish a common language between developers and stakeholders, ensuring the system delivers value to both instructors and learners. As a core element of agile methodologies, User Stories provide a flexible and user-centric approach to requirement formulation (Cohn, 2004).

We developed a set of User Stories focusing on replacing static feedback, integrating AI for personalized feedback generation, and evaluating feedback quality. A summary of these stories, including their objectives and stakeholders, is provided in Tab. 1.

Table 1: User Stories

User Story	Actor	Goal
US01- Removal of Static Feedback and Creation of an Initial Prompt for Feedback Generation	Instructor	As an instructor, I want to eliminate the need for static feedback when creating self-assessment tasks, so that the process is more efficient. Instead, an initial prompt for AI-generated feedback should be available, enabling automatic feedback generation for each task and solution provided by a student.
US02 - Integration of AI and Generation of Feedback Based on the Created Prompt	Learner	As a learner, I want personalized feedback on my solution that highlights specific errors or strengths, so I can understand my performance and improve.
US03 - Customization of the Prompt for Feedback Generation	Instructor	As an instructor, I want to create my own prompt during question creation, ensuring that the AI-generated feedback aligns with my task requirements.
US04 - Storage and Management of Generated Feedback	Instructor	As an instructor, I want AI-generated feedback to be automatically saved and displayed in a user-friendly feedback history, accessible only to me, so I can track and maintain feedback quality.

3. Concept & Implementation of an AI-feedback agent

The design and implementation of the AI-driven extension for SAFRAN are based on leveraging the existing technology stack of the SAFRAN plugin. To ensure seamless integration and compatibility, no modifications were made to the current technology stack or system architecture. Instead, the extension was designed to fully integrate into the existing infrastructure, maintaining the established framework while introducing new functionalities to address the requirements outlined in the User Stories (US01–US04).

3.1 Conceptual Design

The implementation addressed these requirements through a flexible and scalable architecture, with interactions between components designed to efficiently fulfill the functional needs of instructors and learners. Below, we outline how each User Story is addressed within the system design:

1. US01: Removal of Static Feedback and Creation of an Initial Prompt

The user interface (client) was extended to remove the need for manually inputting static feedback by defining a decision tree specifying error cases and corresponding feedback texts. Instead, an initial prompt for feedback generation is stored in the backend and automatically associated with each new task. This enables AI-driven dynamic feedback generation without requiring instructor intervention.

2. US02: Integration of AI and Feedback Generation

The SAFRAN plugin was extended with an interface that communicates with the AI model. This integration ensures that feedback is generated based on the stored prompts and delivered to learners after they submit their solutions. The architecture supports on-demand feedback generation, with results delivered asynchronously and in real time to learners.

3. US03: Customization of the Feedback Prompt

Instructors are provided with the option to choose between predefined prompts or to create custom prompts during task creation. This functionality is implemented through new input fields and selection options in the SAFRAN frontend. Custom prompts are stored in a dedicated database table and linked to the corresponding task, ensuring flexibility and alignment with task specific requirements.

4. US04: Storage and Management of Generated Feedback

To enable instructors to track and manage feedback, the system stores AI-generated feedback in a user-friendly feedback management system. Feedback texts are displayed in a table-like interface, allowing instructors to review and monitor feedback for each task and student solution, ensuring quality and consistency by changing the prompt, if necessary.

3.2 Feedback Prompt Structure

The feedback generation process relies on a structured prompt system, consisting of three key message types:

- **System Message:** Defines the foundational context and role of the AI model. By default, the AI is configured as a "mentor," providing supportive guidance tailored to individual learner needs. This role was chosen to align with the feedback's purpose of supporting the learning process rather than direct instruction.
- **Assistant Message:** Contains detailed instructions, examples, and guidelines for the AI's output. This ensures consistency in feedback format and content, including linguistic guidelines such as feedback length.
- **User Message:** Represents the specific input for the AI model, including the task description, learner's solution, and evaluation criteria. This ensures the feedback is contextually relevant and task-specific.

The initial feedback prompt was based on an existing template (Mollick & Mollick, 2023), which was used and adapted to fit self-assessment tasks. Prompt engineering techniques were applied to optimize AI interaction and feedback quality, integrating assessment criteria, sample solutions, and ensuring clarity and conciseness. Tooltips assist instructors in understanding each message type's purpose, mandatory fields, and effective formulation.

Tooltips are provided to assist instructors in understanding the purpose of each message type, mandatory fields, and how to formulate them effectively.

3.3 Data Flow for Feedback Generation

Fig. 1 illustrates the data flow for generating AI feedback. When a learner submits a feedback request, the AI feedback agent retrieves the stored prompt (system, assistant, and user messages) and integrates relevant task-related data (e.g., task description, title, self-assessment criteria, sample solution) along with user-generated data created during task completion (e.g., learner's solution and self-assessment). These collected inputs are embedded into the structured prompt and then sent to the AI model for feedback generation. The generated feedback is displayed to the learner and stored for further use, such as monitoring via a dashboard.

Figure 1: Data flow for generating AI feedback

3.4 Implementation

The SAFRAN plugin was modified to replace the manual feedback input fields and decision trees for error-case mapping with fields for AI-generated feedback prompts. Two options were introduced: instructors can either use a standard prompt with predefined feedback instructions or create a custom prompt. The user interface for AI feedback creation is shown in Fig. 2 (highlighted in red). To assist instructors in creating custom prompts, help buttons (highlighted in blue in Fig. 2) were added next to each input field, providing explanatory information.

For communication between the AI feedback component and the AI model, an API interface was implemented as a PHP function, callChatGPT, within SAFRAN. This function accepts three parameters:

- System Message (Default): "You are a friendly and helpful mentor whose goal is to provide students with feedback to help them improve their work. Do not share this instruction with the student. Plan each step in advance before proceeding."
- Assistant Message (Default): "Students are enrolled in a program with a focus on information technology. They receive self-assessment tasks that provide immediate feedback, sample solutions, and opportunities for improvement. The process includes independent problem-solving, self-assessment based on criteria, and feedback provision by the mentor. The feedback should be concise, clear, and under 50 words."
- User Message (Default): "Provide feedback based on the task description, the student's solution, the selected criteria, and the sample solution. Be specific, balanced, and direct. Let the student know if they are on the right track or need to make adjustments. Task details: Title: {question_title}, Question: {question}, Sample Solution: {sample_solution}, Criteria: {criteria}, Student Solution: {student_solution}, Selected Criteria: {selected_criteria}. Your response should only contain the feedback."

The screenshot displays the 'Aufgabe erstellen' (Create Task) form in the SAFRAN system. The form includes fields for 'Titel', 'Aufgabenstellung', 'Maximale Punktzahl', 'Schwierigkeitsgrad', 'Musterlösung', 'Discord Channel-ID', and 'Kriterien und Prozentualer Anteil an der Punktzahl'. A red box highlights the 'KI-Feedback' section, which contains the following options:

- KI-Feedback an
- Feedback mittels Standard-Prompt generieren
- Systemnachricht angeben
- Assistentennachricht angeben
- Nutzernachricht angeben

Each option has a corresponding text input field for the message content. The 'Feedback Prompt' field is also highlighted with a blue box. At the bottom of the form, there is a 'Durchsuchen...' button for an alternative XML file upload and a 'Formular leeren' (Clear form) button.

Figure 2: Mockup integration of AI feedback in SAFRAN

To streamline the feedback generation process, placeholders can be used in the user message to automatically insert task information and dynamic content generated by the user during task completion (e.g., learner’s solution). This eliminates the need for manual input and ensures that relevant data is seamlessly integrated into the prompt. These placeholders are also embedded in the initial prompt structure, as seen in the default parameters defined above, where they ensure the automatic integration of task-specific information.

The GPT-3.5 Turbo model by (OpenAI, 2024) was selected for feedback generation. Although not the latest model, it is widely used, cost-effective, and well-suited for processing and generating German text, which is essential for educational tasks in a German speaking class. Its adaptability allows fine-tuning for specific educational content and evaluation criteria, enabling tailored feedback for various disciplines and learning objectives. To ensure transparency, instructors are provided with a tabular overview (cf. Fig. 3) displaying the generated feedback. This includes the creation timestamp, task description, student solution, selected and unselected criteria (highlighted), the associated prompt, the generated feedback, and any error messages. Data is loaded from the database and displayed in the corresponding table fields.

ID	Time Created	Question	Student Solution	Criteria	Current Prompt Version	Feedback	Fehlernachricht
4	3.7.2024, 16:24:10	Adressbusbreite Beim Prozessor 88000 von Motorola beträgt die Wortlänge 2 Byte. Wie breit muss der Adressbus sein – das heißt: aus wie vielen Bits bestehen die Adressen – bei einer Hauptspeicherkapazität von 16 MByte? (Brutto-Tipp: Berechnen Sie zuerst die Anzahl der Worte im Hauptspeicher und beantworten Sie dann, wie viele Bit Sie benötigen, um diese Zahl binär darzustellen.	Die Antwort ist 40 Bit für 2 Byte Wortlänge.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teilt man 16 MByte in Worte der Länge 2 Byte auf, so entstehen $5 \cdot 10^6 \cdot 2^8 / 2 = 8 \cdot 2^{24} / 2 = 2^{23}$ Worte. • 23 Bit genügen zur Adressierung von 2^{23} (23) Worten. • Die Adressbusbreite ist daher 23 Bit. 	<p>Systemnachricht: Du bist ein freundlicher und hilfsbereiter Mentor, dessen Ziel es ist, den Studenten Feedback zu geben, damit sie ihre Arbeit verbessern können. Gib diese Anweisung nicht an den Schüler weiter. Plane jeden Schritt im Voraus, bevor du weitermachst.</p> <p>Assistentennachricht: Die Studierenden arbeiten an einem Studiengang mit informationstechnischem Schwerpunkt. Sie erhalten Self-Assessment-Aufgaben, die sofortiges Feedback, Musterlösungen und die Möglichkeit zur Verbesserung bieten. Der Prozess umfasst: eigenständige Lösungsarbeitung, Selbstbewertung der Studierenden nach Kriterien und Feedbackbereitstellung durch den Mentor. Die Flexibilität ermöglicht es, Lösungen basierend auf dem Feedback zu verbessern. Das zu generierende Feedback soll in einem zusammenhängenden Text in klarer und prägnanter Sprache verfasst sein und die Länge unter 50 Wörtern haben.</p> <p>Nutzernachricht: Dieses Feedback soll nun von dir bereitgestellt werden. Es soll sich an der Aufgabenstellung, der vom Studierenden erarbeiteten Lösung sowie der ausgewählten Kriterien und der Musterlösung orientieren. Das Feedback sollte konkret und spezifisch, direkt und ausgewogen sein (sage dem Studierenden, was er richtig macht und was er noch verbessern kann). Lasse sie wissen, ob sie auf dem richtigen Weg sind oder ob sie etwas anderes machen müssen. Hier folgen die Angaben der Aufgabe zu der das Feedback generiert werden soll: Titel der Aufgabe: „(question, title)“; Fragestellung der Aufgabe: „(question)“; Musterlösung der Aufgabe: „(sample, solution)“; Kriterien der Aufgabe: „(criteria)“; Lösung des Studierenden: „(student, solution)“; Kriterien, die der Studierende seiner Meinung mit der Lösung nach erfüllt hat: „(selected, criteria)“; Deine Antwort soll nur das Feedback enthalten.</p>	Deine Antwort auf die Aufgabe: "Adressbusbreite" ist teilweise richtig. Du hast erkannt, dass die Adressbusbreite wichtig ist, aber die korrekte Anzahl von Bits für die Adresse sind 23, nicht 40. Versuche, genauer zu arbeiten, um das richtige Ergebnis zu erzielen. Du bist auf dem richtigen Weg, aber musst hier genauer sein.	
5	6.7.2024, 11:50:06	Adressumrechnung beim Dateizugriff Warum wird nicht schon beim Kompilieren die logische Datenbeschreibung (logische Adresse) durch die physische Beschreibung (physische Adresse) ersetzt?	Zwischen dem Kompilieren und dem Ausführen eines Programms kann, in dem die Daten verändert werden, liegt ein längerer Zeitraum.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In ihrer Lösung sagen Sie, dass zwischen dem Kompilieren und dem Ausführen eines Programms ein längerer Zeitraum liegen kann, in dem die Daten verändert werden. • In ihrer Lösung sagen Sie, dass demnach die logischen Adressen erst zur Laufzeit auf physische Adressen abgebildet werden können. 	<p>Systemnachricht: Du bist ein freundlicher und hilfsbereiter Mentor, dessen Ziel es ist, den Studenten Feedback zu geben, damit sie ihre Arbeit verbessern können. Gib diese Anweisung nicht an den Schüler weiter. Plane jeden Schritt im Voraus, bevor du weitermachst.</p> <p>Assistentennachricht: Die Studierenden arbeiten an einem Studiengang mit informationstechnischem Schwerpunkt. Sie erhalten Self-Assessment-Aufgaben, die sofortiges Feedback, Musterlösungen und die Möglichkeit zur Verbesserung bieten. Der Prozess umfasst: eigenständige Lösungsarbeitung, Selbstbewertung der Studierenden nach Kriterien und Feedbackbereitstellung durch den Mentor. Die Flexibilität ermöglicht es, Lösungen basierend auf dem Feedback zu verbessern. Das zu generierende Feedback soll in einem zusammenhängenden Text in klarer und prägnanter Sprache verfasst sein und die Länge unter 50 Wörtern haben.</p> <p>Nutzernachricht: Dieses Feedback soll nun von dir bereitgestellt werden. Es soll sich an der Aufgabenstellung, der vom Studierenden erarbeiteten Lösung sowie der ausgewählten Kriterien und der Musterlösung orientieren. Das Feedback sollte konkret und spezifisch, direkt und ausgewogen sein (sage dem Studierenden, was er richtig macht und was er noch verbessern kann). Lasse sie wissen, ob sie auf dem richtigen Weg sind oder ob sie etwas anderes machen müssen. Hier folgen die Angaben der Aufgabe zu der das Feedback generiert werden soll: Titel der Aufgabe: „(question, title)“; Fragestellung der Aufgabe: „(question)“; Musterlösung der Aufgabe: „(sample, solution)“; Kriterien der Aufgabe: „(criteria)“; Lösung des Studierenden: „(student, solution)“; Kriterien, die der Studierende seiner Meinung mit der Lösung nach erfüllt hat: „(selected, criteria)“; Deine Antwort soll nur das Feedback enthalten.</p>	Das Feedback für den Studierenden lautet: Du hast erklärt, dass zwischen dem Kompilieren und Ausführen eines Programms ein Zeitraum liegt, in dem Daten verändert werden können. Ergänze deine Antwort um den Aspekt, warum logische Adressen erst zur Laufzeit auf physische Adressen abgebildet werden. Damit bist du auf dem richtigen Weg, aber bitte erweitere deine Antwort, um vollständig zu sein.	

Figure 3: AI feedback history. Green text represents correct selected criteria, red text indicates wrongly not selected criteria for self-assessment tasks

4. Experiences

4.1 Methods

To address Research Question 1 (How can an AI feedback agent be implemented to provide individualized and scalable feedback for self-assessment tasks?) an AI agent was integrated into the Moodle plugin SAFRAN. A tailored prompt was designed for feedback generation, and the system was implemented to store prompts, generate feedback on-demand, and deliver personalized feedback to learners. Functional tests showed that the implementation was able to automatically create feedback for solutions and self-assessments submitted by a student. To address the research questions two and three, two investigations were conducted:

1. Quality and Utility of AI-Generated Feedback:

This investigation addressed Research Question 2 (How do instructors perceive the quality and utility of AI-generated feedback compared to their own feedback?) by evaluating feedback from five AI models (GPT-3.5 Turbo, GPT-4 Turbo, LLaMa 3, Mixtral AI 8x7b, Mixtral AI 8x22b). Two instructors assessed 45 feedback instances using a 5-point Likert scale across six criteria: accuracy, relevance, detail, language quality, appropriateness, and coherence.

2. Contextual Relevance of AI-Generated Feedback:

This investigation addressed Research Question 3 (To what extent can an AI feedback agent generate contextually relevant feedback, guided by reference texts or sample solutions, while minimizing the production of irrelevant or off-topic content?). The AI models' ability to generate contextually relevant feedback was evaluated using a structured framework. Feedback was assessed for alignment with task descriptions, sample solutions, and learner responses, with systematic ratings for relevance, precision, and contextual adherence.

Table 2 provides an example task, solution context, and feedback generated by GPT-3.5 Turbo using the standard prompt, while Appendix 1 displays the codebook used by teachers to assess the AI-generated feedback.

Table 2: Example of AI-feedback generation

task and solution context	
Title	Count-to-Infinity with BGP
Question	BGP uses the distance vector algorithm to solve the routing task between autonomous systems. Can the count-to-infinity problem arise with BGP?
Student solution	The count-to-infinity problem can arise with BGP if update messages send the costs in a cycle between routers, which can lead to infinite path costs.
Sample solution	The count-to-infinity problem can therefore arise if the update messages of the costs are sent in a cycle between routers. For example, in Figure 4.5 the update messages circle between B and C [Figure]. This problem does not exist with BGP due to the specification of the complete path in the update message, as a router sees itself on a path and concludes that it should not use this path. For example, in BGP C would receive the update message from B with the path B - C - A in Figure 4.5. Now C recognizes that it is on the path itself and ignores this message. As a result, the messages between B and C no longer circle and there is no count-to-infinity problem.
Criteria	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) In your solution, you say that the count-to-infinity problem can arise if the cost update messages are sent in a cycle between routers. 2) In your solution you say that this problem does not exist with BGP due to the specification of the complete path in the update message. 3) In your solution you give an example of how BGP avoids the count-to-infinity problem.
Selected criteria	1.)
Not selected criteria	2.), 3.)

AI feedback output: “Well done, you recognized that the count-to-infinity problem can occur with BGP when update messages with costs are sent in a cycle between routers. However, you should have also mentioned that BGP avoids this problem by specifying the complete path in the update message, since a router sees itself on a path and ignores the message. An example of this BGP mechanism would have further improved your solution. Continue like this for the next task and pay attention to concreteness and completeness.”

4.2 Results

Regarding investigation 1, Figure 4 shows that, across all AI models, the feedback achieved good accuracy (median = 4; interquartile range (IQR) = 1). The relevance of the feedback content was also high (median = 4; IQR = 1). Feedback texts were detailed (median = 4; IQR = 2), and language quality was rated very highly (median = 4; IQR = 1). The feedback was deemed appropriate (median = 4; IQR = 1) and coherent (median = 4; IQR = 1). Inter-rater reliability (Cohen’s Kappa = 0.58) indicated moderate agreement among evaluators. In the comparison between instructor-generated feedback and AI-generated feedback we see a neutral result with a Median of 3 and an IQR of 3. The neutral result (median = 3, IQR = 3) suggests that AI-generated feedback is comparable to instructor feedback in quality but exhibits significant variability. This highlights its potential for scalability in learning environments with many students, reducing instructor workload while maintaining feedback quality. However, the variability indicates room for improvement, particularly in handling complex or subjective tasks. Despite some criticisms (evident in the spread of the boxplots and outliers), the AI-generated feedback was overall rated positively by both instructors and could serve as a supportive tool

Figure 4: Results of the expert survey

When comparing the performance of individual models (Tab. 3) measured in investigation 2, GPT-4 Turbo (mean = 4.05, standard deviation (SD) = 1.09) ranked highest, followed by LLaMa 3 (mean = 4.01; SD = 1.12), Mixtral AI 8x22b (mean = 3.94; SD = 1.11), Mixtral AI 8x7b (mean = 3.84; SD = 1.12), and GPT-3.5 Turbo (mean = 3.66; SD = 1.12).

Table 3: Mean values of the results of the teacher survey divided by used AI model

AI model	accuracy	relevance	detail	language quality	appropriateness	coherence
GPT-3.5 Turbo	3.28	3.62	3.56	4.22	3.89	3.39
GPT-4 Turbo	4.06	4.22	4.06	4.28	4	3.67
LLaMa 3	3.56	4.11	3.83	4.33	4.33	3.89
Mixtral AI 8x7b	3.72	4.06	3.72	4.17	3.94	3.44
Mixtral AI 8x22b	3.67	3.83	3.67	4.28	4.22	3.94

5. Conclusion

In digital learning environments, feedback for self-assessment tasks is typically instructor-generated, potentially resulting in generic or mismatched feedback that fails to address individual learner needs. This study explored the potential of AI-generated feedback as a scalable and personalized alternative, addressing three key research questions.

First, we demonstrated the feasibility of integrating an AI agent into digital learning environments, such as the SAFRAN Moodle plugin, to provide individualized and scalable feedback. Customizable prompts and real-time feedback generation ensure accessibility for both instructors and learners. Second, our evaluation revealed that AI-generated feedback is generally accurate, relevant, and coherent, with median scores of 4 across most criteria. GPT-4 Turbo and LLaMa 3 performed best, though differences between models were minimal, indicating that even smaller or older models can produce high-quality feedback. Third, the AI agent effectively

generated context-aware feedback based on reference texts and sample solutions, with minimal instances of irrelevant or off-topic content. These findings underscore the potential of AI-generated feedback to enhance learning experiences at scale, offering personalized and timely support while reducing instructor workload. However, practical challenges, such as prompt fine-tuning and consistency across diverse tasks, must be addressed to fully realize this potential.

This study has several limitations. The evaluation involved a small sample size of two instructors and a limited number of tasks ($n = 9$), all within a course in the "STEM" domain. This may not fully represent variability across broader educational contexts. Additionally, the study focused on short-term feedback quality and did not assess long-term learning outcomes. The use of predefined prompts may also limit adaptability to dynamic learner needs, and the absence of learner perspectives leaves questions about student perceptions and actions unresolved. Future research should focus on optimizing AI models for educational use, integrating them into broader learning ecosystems, and investigating their long-term impact on learning outcomes. By addressing these challenges, AI-generated feedback can play a transformative role in scaling feedback processes, fostering more effective and personalized learning experiences.

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7. Appendix 1

Codebook for expert analysis

Purpose and scope:

This codebook is used for the systematic and consistent coding of expert ratings on AI-generated and static feedback texts for quiz tasks. It supports the analysis of the quality and comparability of the two feedback types.

Procedure:

- The feedback texts from all models are listed for each task.
- The models are anonymized for the analysis and the order is rotated.
- The samples consist of feedback texts for 9 tasks or solutions.

One solution per task type (solution status) and length was determined. The feedback texts of all 5 models were used for these 9 solutions, i.e. 5x3x3 feedback texts.

- All necessary information on the task is displayed for the evaluation.
- Before the analysis, the procedure is checked by means of a test run.

Coding scheme:

Domain1: Content quality

Correctness:

- Definition: Refers to whether the feedback is factually correct.
- Example: "The feedback was completely correct and covered all essential points."
- Coding: Yes/No

Accuracy:

- Definition: Refers to the precision of the feedback.
- Example: "The feedback was very precise and covered all the details."
- Coding: Scale 1-5 (1 = I do not agree, 5 = I agree)

Relevance:

- Definition: Refers to how well the feedback matches the answer given.

- Example: "The feedback was related to the answer/solution."
- Coding: Scale 1-5 (1 = I do not agree, 5 = I agree)

Level of detail (detail):

- Definition: Refers to how detailed and informative the feedback is.
- Example: "The feedback was very detailed and addressed all aspects of the response."
- Coding: Scale 1-5 (1 = I do not agree, 5 = I agree)

Domain 2: Linguistic and formal quality

Language quality:

- Definition: Refers to the linguistic correctness and style of the feedback.
- Example: "The feedback was grammatically correct and well formulated."
- Coding: Scale 1-5 (1 = I do not agree, 5 = I agree)

Appropriateness:

- Definition: Refers to the linguistic correctness and style of the feedback.
- Example: "The language of the feedback was appropriate and easy to understand."
- Coding: Scale 1-5 (1 = I do not agree, 5 = I agree)

Coherence:

- Definition: Refers to whether the feedback is logical and consistent.
- Example: "The feedback was logically structured and consistent."
- Coding: Scale 1-5 (1 = I do not agree, 5 = I agree)

Domain 3: Comparison with static feedback texts

Preference:

- Definition: Refers to the preferred recommendation of feedback in a specific error situation.
- Example: "Which feedback would you prefer to recommend to a learner in this error situation? AI feedback or teacher feedback?"
- Coding: AI-Feedback / Teacher Feedback

AI feedback/teacher feedback comparison (comparison)

- Definition: Refers to the comparison between AI-generated and static feedback.
- Example: "The AI-generated feedback was better than the static feedback."
- Coding: Scale 1-5 (1 = I do not agree, 5 = I agree)

Domain 4: Further information

Further comments:

- Definition: Variable area for opinions/comments not covered by the other areas.
- Example: "The AI-generated feedback repeats information unnecessarily often." - Coding: free text field

University Students' Adoption, Feedback Perceptions, and Learning with a Generative-AI Tool: A Pre–Post Study of COFFEE

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Abstract

Generative AI (genAI) promises scalable formative feedback in higher education but raises questions about uptake, perceptions, and effects on learning. We evaluated COFFEE, a lecturer-endorsed, institutionally safeguarded LLM-based feedback tool, in distance-learning modules at a German university using a two-wave, one-group design (T1 baseline $n = 612$; T2 post $n = 93$; matched pairs $n = 63$). At T2, 76% reported using COFFEE, though engagement was brief for most (<1 h; median three sessions). Perceptions were favourable: feedback quality and trust exceeded scale midpoints, with higher benevolence among ≥ 1 h users and higher encouragement among repeat (≥ 2) users. Prospectively, only intrinsic motivation to know predicted later use (OR = 1.88); prior academic genAI use, academic wellbeing, and academic/course self-efficacy and academic competences did not. In the matched cohort (users and non-users), overall pre–post comparisons showed no Holm-corrected gains on the primary academic outcomes. Complementary dose–response analyses, however, indicated small, selective improvements among users, most consistently for course self-efficacy, with tentative signals for academic competences. Taken together, findings suggest that curiosity-driven motivation underpins adoption and that LLM-mediated feedback may yield incremental, task-adjacent benefits under greater engagement. Designing for depth of use, maintaining ethical safeguards, and targeting task-proximal outcomes with stronger comparative designs are critical next steps.

Keywords

Generative AI, formative feedback, higher education, distance learning, self-efficacy, academic motivation, trust, adoption, student perceptions, learning outcomes

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming higher education, from adaptive learning to assessment design. Generative AI tools such as large language models (LLMs) have made an immediate and lasting impact on educational practice, offering new ways to scale student support (Chiu et al., 2023). At the same time, online and distance learning face persistent challenges in providing individualized formative feedback. Instructors in large or asynchronous courses often lack the time and resources to give detailed comments on every student's work (Nicol, 2010). Yet formative feedback is critical: effective feedback helps students improve knowledge and skills, fosters self-regulated learning, and supports motivation and autonomy (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Shute, 2008; Evans, 2013; Kluger & DeNisi, 1996; Wisniewski et al., 2020).

Recent advances in LLMs suggest that detailed, contextualized comments can be generated at scale. Early studies indicate that AI-powered feedback can improve revision behaviour, engagement, and student motivation (Meyer et al., 2024; Kinder et al., 2025; Dai et al., 2023). However, concerns remain about

hallucinations or inaccuracies in AI outputs (Hellas et al., 2023), shallow personalization (Zeevy-Solovey, 2024), and risks of over-reliance that might undermine critical reflection (Hadi Mogavi et al., 2024). These tensions highlight that perceived quality and trust in AI feedback are central determinants of its educational value (Hoff & Bashir, 2015; Nazaretsky et al., 2025).

To address these challenges, researchers and instructors developed COFFEE (Corrective Formative Feedback), an LLM-enabled feedback tool at FernUniversität in Hagen, a large distance-teaching university in Germany (see Hanses et al., 2025; Karolyi et al., 2025). Unlike ad-hoc uses of commercially available generative AI, COFFEE was developed according to Value Sensitive Design (Friedman & Hendry, 2019) and Trusted Learning Analytics (Spiekermann, 2021; Hansen et al., 2020), embedding values such as fairness, accountability, privacy, and transparency, data minimization and is compliant with GDPR and EU AI Regulations. The tool takes into account the assessment requirements recommended by lecturers and provides formative feedback on long written assignments within regular courses on a large scale (Hanses et al., 2025; Karolyi et al., 2025). By situating AI feedback in an institutionally governed and ethically grounded system, COFFEE aims to balance efficiency with student autonomy and foster trust.

Given this context, this study investigates students' experiences of AI-mediated feedback in real courses. Adoption and perceptions matter because students act on feedback only when they judge it credible, fair, and useful (Hoff & Bashir, 2015); even high-quality comments have limited impact without trust and perceived value. Early evaluations of LLM feedback report heterogeneous effects on learning that appear contingent on engagement patterns (e.g., whether students return to revise, how long they interact) and on learners' prior dispositions (e.g., motivation, familiarity with AI) (Dai et al., 2023; Meyer et al., 2024; Kinder et al., 2025). Thus, we first need a clear picture of who adopts COFFEE and how its feedback is perceived before exploring possible pre–post changes under authentic use.

RQ1: Adoption and perceptions. How widely is COFFEE adopted, and how do users perceive its feedback? We describe exposure among T2 respondents (any use, repeat use, time on tool) and profile users' perceptions of feedback quality (developmental feedback, encouragement, fairness) and epistemic trust (expertise, benevolence, integrity).

RQ2: Prospective predictors of use. Which baseline characteristics predict subsequent tool use? We examine whether T1 characteristics academic wellbeing, academic and course self-efficacy, academic competences, academic motivation and prior academic genAI use predict T2 COFFEE usage.

RQ3: Within-person change in outcomes. Do students show pre–post shifts in academic wellbeing, self-efficacy (general and course), competences, and motivation, and do these shifts scale with COFFEE use? Building on links between feedback and learning (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Shute, 2008; Ryan & Deci, 2017; Wisniewski et al., 2020), we: a) Primarily test a dose–response relation by regressing change scores ($\Delta = T2 - T1$) on engagement intensity (any-use and ordinal exposure); b) Secondly describe overall pre–post change in the full matched cohort; and c) Examine whether baseline academic genAI use moderates Δ , acknowledging that prior experience may shape how students interpret and act on AI-generated feedback.

In the following sections, we first describe the study context, participants, design, and measures, outlining how COFFEE was implemented and evaluated. We then present results in line with our three research questions, beginning with adoption and perceptions, followed by predictors of use, and finally consider pre–post changes and exploratory dose–response patterns. The paper closes with a discussion of key findings, limitations of the design, and implications for the future use of trustworthy AI-mediated feedback in higher education.

2. Method

2.1 Study Design

We conducted a two-wave, one-group pretest–posttest study of a digital formative-feedback tool (“COFFEE”) in higher education, see Hanses and colleagues (2025) and Karolyi and colleagues (2025). Surveys were fielded at baseline before any tool exposure (T1) and again near the end of the teaching period after exposure opportunities (T2). The design serves three objectives: (1) describe usage patterns and perceptions at T2, (2) prospectively predict later COFFEE use from T1 characteristics, and (3) estimate within-person change from T1→T2 on academic and motivational outcomes. The study is observational and not randomized; accordingly, all dose–response results are interpreted as associations, not causal effects.

2.2 Setting, participants, and recruitment

Participants were enrolled in different distance-learning modules at FernUniversität in Hagen during the summer semester 2025. Recruitment proceeded in two waves via LMS announcement and e-mail. The total number of students contacted at T1 and T2 was approximately 2600. This number refers to course registrations, not active students. In distance learning, courses are often taken early to familiarise with expectations or secure repetition in case of failure. Sample sizes by analytic set were: T1 entrants ($n = 612$), T2 respondents ($n = 93$) and a matched T1–T2 cohort ($n = 63$; matched on specific codes assessed at T1 and T2), which results in participation rates 23 % at T1 and 3% at T2. Demographic composition is summarized in Table 1; women comprised ~72% of T2 and ~78% of the matched cohort; mean age at T2 was 37.34 years ($SD = 12.90$). Module composition differed across samples (e.g., “Module 2”, the largest course, constituted 45.8% of all T1 entrants vs. 74.6% of the matched cohort), indicating selection on module in panel retention. Analyses of within-person change and prediction were restricted to matched complete pairs ($n = 63$). We did not use partial cases for change analyses. Participants provided informed consent and agreed to GDPR compliant data handling.

Table 1. Sample flow & demographics by analytic sample

Measure	T1 all	T2 all	Matched
<i>n</i>	612	93	63
Age, <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	35.43 (11.78)	37.34 (12.90)	36.25 (12.67)
Gender, % (<i>n</i>)			
Women	71.6 (419)	72.0 (67)	77.8 (49)
Men	24.6 (144)	24.7 (23)	22.2 (14)
Other / no answer	3.8 (22)	3.2 (3)	0.0 (0)
Module, %			
Module 2	45.8 (279)	50.5 (47)	74.6 (47)
Other modules	54.2 (332)	49.5 (46)	2.3 (16)

2.3 Procedure and timeline

At T1 (baseline, pre-exposure), students completed demographics and baseline measures (academic wellbeing, academic and course self-efficacy, academic competences, and academic motivation, and academic genAI use). COFFEE access was available during the term. At T2 (end of term, post-exposure window), students reported COFFEE usage (any use, frequency, session counts, time on tool) and completed feedback perception measures plus re-assessments of academic wellbeing, academic and course self-efficacy, academic

competences, and academic motivation. Feedback perception measures were administered only to users (by design) via skip-logic.

2.4 Measures

Demographics. At T1, students reported their age (years), gender (woman, man, other / prefer not to say), and study module.

Academic genAI use. Three items developed for this study assessed academic genAI use. The items covered use intensity, functional use, and perceived competence. An example item is: "I regularly use generative AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, Bard, Claude) for study-related tasks." Items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). Internal consistency: T1 $\alpha = .90$.

Academic wellbeing. Four items capturing satisfaction with knowledge acquisition and personal development in the study program (e.g., "I am satisfied with the gain in knowledge about my field of study"). 5-point Likert (1 = not at all satisfied, 5 = very satisfied). Internal consistency: T1 $\alpha = .86$; T2 $\alpha = .88$.

General academic self-efficacy. The 5-item General Academic Self-Efficacy Scale (GASE; Nielsen et al., 2018; van Zyl et al., 2022). Example: "I generally manage to solve difficult academic problems if I try hard enough." 5-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). Internal consistency: T1 $\alpha = .82$; T2 $\alpha = .76$.

Course-specific self-efficacy. Three self-developed items targeting confidence in mastering the current course (e.g., "I feel confident understanding the key concepts in this course"). 5-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). Internal consistency: T1 $\alpha = .86$; T2 $\alpha = .85$.

Academic competences. Three items capturing the ability to write reports, apply scientific methods, and analyse complex information (e.g., "I am able to apply scientific methods"). 5-point scale (1 = not at all, 5 = to a very high degree). Internal consistency: T1 $\alpha = .79$; T2 $\alpha = .78$.

Academic motivation. The Short Academic Motivation Scale (SAMS; Kotera et al., 2021; German translation: Möltner et al., 2024) using two items per subscale, on a 7-point Likert (1 = do not agree at all, 7 = fully agree) assessed academic motivation. Subscales: Intrinsic Motivation to Know (IMK; T1 $\alpha = .77$, T2 $\alpha = .83$), Intrinsic Motivation to Accomplish (IMA; T1 $\alpha = .66$, T2 $\alpha = .73$), Intrinsic Motivation to Stimulate (IMS; T1 $\alpha = .90$, T2 $\alpha = .93$), Identified Regulation (IDR; T1 $\alpha = .79$, T2 $\alpha = .86$), Introjected Regulation (IJR; T1 $\alpha = .56$, T2 $\alpha = .32$), External Regulation (ER; T1 $\alpha = .88$, T2 $\alpha = .89$), and Amotivation (AM; T1 $\alpha = .84$, T2 $\alpha = .92$). Most subscales showed good internal consistency; reliabilities for IJR were low. Given low reliability at both waves, IJR is treated as exploratory and excluded from the analyses of RQ3.

COFFEE usage (T2). We captured (a) any use (0 = never, 1 = \geq once), (b) frequency (never / once / $\geq 2\times$), (c) repeat-use session counts (asked only of repeat users), and (d) total time on tool (dichotomized as <1 h vs ≥ 1 h, with hours asked only if ≥ 1 h). This skip-logic yields different denominators by indicator (e.g., hours only among those exceeding 1 h).

Feedback perceptions

Assessment Feedback Questionnaire (AFQ). COFFEE's feedback perceptions were assessed using the AFQ, using 13 items (Lizzio & Wilson, 2008) with a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). Subscales: Developmental Feedback (e.g., "Comments helped me focus on areas I could improve", $\alpha = .81$),

Encouragement (e.g., “Acknowledged my good points or ideas”, $\alpha = .78$), and Fairness (e.g., “Feedback was inconsistent or contradictory”, reverse-keyed; $\alpha = .69$).

Münster Epistemic Trustworthiness Inventory (METI). Trust in COFFEE’s feedback was assessed using the 14 items METI (Hendriks et al., 2015) with 7-point semantic differentials with higher values reflecting greater perceived trust. Subscales: Expertise (e.g., “incompetent–competent”, $\alpha = .73$), Integrity (e.g., “dishonest–honest”, $\alpha = .79$), and Benevolence (e.g., “immoral–moral”, $\alpha = .76$).

2.5 Data preparation and missing data

T1 item nonresponse was low. Little’s MCAR test was borderline ($\chi^2(50) = 67.56, p = .050$). We proceeded under plausible MAR given block-forced completion and covariate coverage. At T2, there was no item-level missingness on administered items; any “missing” reflects planned skips (e.g., AFQ/METI only for users; hours only if ≥ 1 h). Panel matching yielded $n = 63$ complete pre–post pairs; change and prediction analyses therefore use complete-case pairs. To address module imbalance in the matched panel, we (a) report module-stratified descriptives, (b) repeat key estimates within modules, and (c) apply post-stratification weights to T1 module margins where indicated.

2.6 Statistical analysis

RQ1: Adoption and perceptions (T2 cross-section; $n = 93$ overall; AFQ/METI among users, $n = 71$)

We describe adoption and usage intensity in the full T2 sample and compare perception means (AFQ, METI) among users across pre-specified two-level contrasts (e.g., ≥ 1 h vs < 1 h; > 1 use vs once). Group comparisons used independent-samples t-tests (Welch’s correction when Levene’s test indicated heteroscedasticity). Because RQ1 involves multiple related comparisons, we report Hedges’ g with 95% CIs and apply Holm correction within each perception family (AFQ $m = 3$; METI $m = 3$). Module-stratified estimates are presented as robustness (sensitivity) analyses.

RQ2: Prospective predictors of use (matched cohort, $n = 63$)

We modelled the ordinal usage outcome (never / once / $\geq 2\times$) via proportional-odds (ordered logistic) regression. The primary predictor set comprised T1 demographics, academic genAI use, seven motivation subscales, Academic and Course self-efficacy, Academic Well-being, and Academic Competences. Given module selection, we applied post-stratification weights to align the matched cohort with the T1 module distribution. Analyses used post-stratification to T1 module margins; unweighted results were comparable. Model diagnostics included Pearson and deviance goodness-of-fit and the test of parallel lines. Odds ratios are presented, with key continuous predictors (e.g., IMK) standardized per 1-SD for interpretability. We estimated several a-priori variants (full theory-driven; reduced by construct families) and report the most parsimonious specification that preserved the substantive conclusion while avoiding overfitting.

RQ3: Within-person change in outcomes (matched cohort, $n = 63$)

Dose–response with usage. We regressed change scores ($\Delta = T2 - T1$) on COFFEE use with two a-priori codings: any-use (0/1) and an ordinal trend (1 = never, 2 = once, 3 = $\geq 2\times$). We report unadjusted p with 95% CIs and R^2 , interpret as associations, and prioritize consistency across codings as the robustness criterion. Non-users are retained as the never-exposure group to preserve the full gradient.

Pre–post change. For four prespecified academic outcomes, we ran paired t-tests on T2–T1 differences, reporting mean change, 95% CIs, Cohen’s d_z , and Holm-adjusted p -values within the family ($m = 4$).

Moderation by baseline academic genAI use. Given $n = 63$, moderation was limited to a single predictor: centered baseline academic genAI use. Models test its moderation of Δ and report unadjusted p -values with 95% CIs. Non-users are retained.

2.7 Software and reporting

Analyses were performed in IBM SPSS Statistics 29. Two-tailed $\alpha = .05$ was used throughout. We report exact p -values, 95% CIs, and unstandardized estimates.

3. Results

3.1 Students' adoption and perceptions of the COFFEE tool at T2 (RQ1)

At the second wave (T2, $n = 93$), most students (76.3%) reported using the COFFEE feedback tool at least once, with the remainder (23.7%) reporting no use (Table 2). Among users ($n = 71$), use frequency was skewed: 38.0% used it only once and 62.0% used it multiple times (median 3 sessions, range 2–30). Session counts and total time were right-skewed: 76.1% of users spent under 1 hour using the tool (median 2h for those above 1h). Use frequency (one vs multiple uses) did not differ by duration ($<1h$ vs $\geq 1h$; $\chi^2(1) = 1.99, p = .158$). In summary, COFFEE was widely tried but generally used sparingly (most students < 1 h), with a long tail of heavier use.

Table 2. COFFEE adoption & usage intensity at T2 (N = 93; users $n = 71$)

Domain	Measure	Value
Adoption (all T2)	Any use, n (%)	71 (76.3%)
	No use, n (%)	22 (23.7%)
Use frequency (among users)	1x, n (%)	27 (38.0%)
	> 1x, n (%)	44 (62.0%)
Repeat-use distribution (repeat users only)	Sessions, M (SD)	5.50 (5.57)
	Sessions, median [range]	3 [2–30]
	2–3 sessions, n (%)	25 (56.8%)
Time on tool (among users)	< 1 h, n (%)	54 (76.1%)
	> 1 h, n (%)	17 (23.9%)
Hours (among > 1 h only)	Hours, M (SD)	3.00 (1.58)
	Hours, median [range]	2 [2–8]

Notes. Repeat-use counts were only asked of repeat users; hours were only asked of those reporting > 1h total.

Students' perceptions of the feedback quality were generally positive. On AFQ (1–5), encouragement was rated highest ($M = 4.23, SD = 0.72$), with developmental feedback ($M = 3.60, SD = 0.79$) and fairness ($M = 3.39, SD = 0.99$) also above midpoint. Trust was likewise high: on METI (1–7) means were 5.14 ($SD = 1.13$) for expertise, 5.11 ($SD = 1.40$) for integrity, and 5.01 ($SD = 1.26$) for benevolence.

We examined whether intensive use was associated with different perceptions (Table 3). Using time on tool ($\geq 1h$ vs $< 1h$) as the primary intensity marker, longer-duration users reported higher METI benevolence ($g = -0.84, p_{Holm} = .009$). No other METI or AFQ subscale differences by duration survived Holm. Using repeat use (> 1 vs once), AFQ encouragement remained higher among repeat users ($g = -0.63, p_{Holm} = .033$); developmental feedback and fairness did not survive Holm, and no METI repeat-use contrasts were reliable. Finer splits (e.g., 2–3 vs ≥ 4 sessions) yielded no additional reliable differences, and module-stratified analyses mostly preserved these patterns. In summary, heavier time investment was associated with higher

benevolence, and repeat use was associated with higher encouragement; all other contrasts were non-significant after Holm correction.

3.2 Predictors of COFFEE use based on T1 measures (RQ2)

We fitted a post-stratified proportional-odds (ordinal logistic) regression predicting COFFEE use frequency (never / once / ≥ 2) from baseline (T1) variables (matched $n = 63$). The model was significant overall ($\chi^2(5) = 18.15, p = .003$) and showed acceptable fit: Pearson and deviance goodness-of-fit tests were non-significant (all $p > .40$), and the test of parallel lines did not reject proportional odds ($\chi^2(5) = 4.81, p = .44$). Nagelkerke's pseudo- $R^2 = .28$ indicated moderate explanatory power.

Table 4 shows that the only robust predictor was T1 intrinsic motivation to know (IMK). In the weighted model, a 1-SD higher IMK at T1 was associated with 88% greater odds of being in a higher usage category (OR = 1.88, 95% CI [1.12, 3.16]). Other predictors (age, gender) had positive point estimates but were not statistically reliable across model specifications. None of the other variables (academic genAI use, module indicators, academic outcomes) were significantly related to COFFEE use. Unweighted analyses replicated the IMK effect and yielded the same substantive conclusion: higher baseline IMK predicted greater subsequent COFFEE use; other effects were not significant or were inconsistent. Among several pre-specified model variants, we report the most parsimonious specification; IMK's effect was stable across alternatives.

3.3 Within-person change from T1 to T2 and association with COFFEE use (RQ3)

In the matched subsample ($n = 63$), we first described overall pre–post change (T2–T1) on the four primary academic outcomes—academic wellbeing, academic self-efficacy (ASE), course self-efficacy (CSE), and academic competences (Table 5). After Holm adjustment within this primary family ($m = 4$), no outcome showed a statistically significant mean change. Small increases were observed (e.g., $\Delta ASE = +0.15, d_z = 0.28$; $\Delta CSE = +0.19, d_z = 0.27$), but these were non-significant after correction (all $p_{\text{Holm}} \geq .12$). Prior to adjustment, ASE and CSE had nominal $p \approx .03$. Motivation was treated as exploratory. The confirmatory set excluded IJR a priori due to low reliability; no motivation subscale showed a change that survived correction (e.g., IMA and IMS nominal p s = .02–.03; $p_{\text{Holm}} > .11$). Exploratorily, IJR increased ($\Delta = +0.40, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.11, 0.70], t(62) = 2.78, p = .007$); given the low reliability at T2 ($\alpha = .32$), we report this without inferential emphasis.

Our primary test of RQ3 examined whether change scaled with COFFEE use. We regressed change scores ($\Delta = T2-T1$) on engagement using two a priori codings: (a) any use (0/1) and (b) an ordinal exposure trend (1 = never, 2 = once, 3 = ≥ 2) (Table 6). Course self-efficacy gains were positively associated with use: any-use $B = 0.60$ (95% CI [0.16, 1.04], $p = .009, R^2 = .11$) and an ordinal trend $B = 0.26$ ($p = .026$). Academic competences were higher among any-use students ($B = 0.42, p = .039, R^2 = .07$), with a marginal linear trend ($p = .067$). Academic wellbeing showed marginally positive associations in both codings (any-use $p = .056$; trend $p = .059$), whereas ASE showed small, non-significant associations (all $p \geq .23, R^2 \leq .06$). Among motivation subscales, only intrinsic motivation to accomplish was higher for any-use ($B = 0.89, p = .028, R^2 = .08$); other subscales showed no reliable links (all $p > .13$). Non-users were retained as the “never” exposure group to preserve the full gradient.

Table 3. Perception & trust scales (T2 users $n = 71$; groups: $< 1 \text{ h } n = 54, \geq 1 \text{ h } n = 17$) and T2 age (total $N = 93$)

Measure	T2 total $M (SD)$	use time $< 1 \text{ h}$ $M (SD)$	use time $> 1 \text{ h}$ $M (SD)$	Hedges' $g (>, < 1 \text{ h})$ [95% CI]	sensitivity	use frequency $= 1 \times M (SD)$	use frequency $> 1 \times M (SD)$	Hedges' $g (>1 \times, 1 \times)$ [95% CI]	sensitivity
AFQ developmental feedback	3.60 (0.79)	3.60 (0.77)	3.60 (0.88)	0.01 [-0.53, 0.54]		3.35 (0.68)	3.75 (0.82)	-0.52 [-1.00, -0.03]	1 [†]
AFQ encouragement	4.23 (0.72)	4.15 (0.72)	4.49 (0.70)	-0.47 [-1.01, 0.08]	1 [†]	3.95 (0.67)	4.40 (0.71)	-0.63* [-1.12, -0.15]	1 ^{†,2†}
AFQ fairness	3.39 (0.99)	3.42 (0.97)	3.31 (1.06)	0.11 [-0.43, 0.65]		3.36 (1.01)	3.42 (0.98)	-0.06 [-0.53, 0.42]	
METI expertise	5.14 (1.13)	5.13 (1.15)	5.19 (1.11)	-0.05 [-0.59, 0.49]		5.02 (0.95)	5.21 (1.24)	-0.16 [-0.64, 0.31]	
METI benevolence	5.01 (1.26)	4.76 (1.26)	5.78 (0.93)	-0.84** [-1.40, -0.28]	1*,2**	5.12 (1.34)	4.94 (1.22)	0.14 [-0.33, 0.62]	
METI integrity	5.11 (1.40)	4.95 (1.48)	5.62 (0.98)	-0.48 [-1.02, 0.07]	2 [†]	4.94 (1.48)	5.22 (1.36)	-0.20 [-0.67, 0.28]	
T2 age (years)	37.34 (12.90)	36.20 (12.71)	40.59 (11.30)	-0.35 [-0.89, 0.19]		35.63 (11.61)	38.25 (12.97)	-0.21 [-0.69, 0.27]	

Notes. Two-tailed tests. Welch used if Levene $< .05$ (not applicable here). Holm correction applied within families: AFQ ($m = 3$), METI ($m = 3$). Hour-based: only METI Benevolence survives ($p_{\text{Holm}} = .009$). Repeat-use: only AFQ Encouragement survives ($p_{\text{Holm}} = .033$). CI = confidence interval. In sensitivity analysis, if the significance level of the effect is shown as 1 = in all other modules, 2 = in module 2. Significance markers on g : ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$, [†] $p < .10$.

Table 4. Ordered logistic regression predicting frequency of coffee use (weighted analysis, $N = 63$).

Predictor	OR [95% CI]
Age (years T1)	1.87 [0.98, 3.59] [†]
Academic genAI use (T1)	1.24 [0.72, 2.16]
Intrinsic motivation to know (IMK, T1)	1.88 [1.12, 3.16]*
Gender (Female vs. Male, T1)	3.32 [0.91, 12.16] [†]
Module 2 (vs. other modules, T1)	2.29 [0.76, 6.88]

Note. * $p < .05$, [†] $p < .10$.

Table 5. Paired-samples t-test results for primary outcomes and motivation subscales at Time 1 (T1) and Time 2 (T2).

Variable	T1 <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	T2 <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Δ (T2-T1)	95% CI	<i>t</i> (62)	<i>d_z</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>p</i> _{Holm}
Primary outcomes (<i>m</i> = 4)								
Academic wellbeing	3.69 (0.78)	3.80 (0.83)	0.11	[-0.06, 0.29]	1.27	0.16	.208	.208
Academic self-efficacy	3.93 (0.70)	4.08 (0.61)	0.15	[0.01, 0.29]	2.20	0.28	.031	.124
Course self-efficacy	3.43 (0.81)	3.62 (0.80)	0.19	[0.01, 0.37]	2.17	0.27	.034	.124
Academic competences	3.54 (0.70)	3.67 (0.72)	0.13	[-0.02, 0.29]	1.72	0.22	.091	.182
Motivation subscales (<i>m</i> = 6)								
Intrinsic motivation to know (IMK)	5.71 (1.18)	5.85 (1.22)	0.14	[-0.07, 0.35]	1.37	0.17	.177	.516
Intrinsic motivation to accomplish (IMA)	4.37 (1.59)	4.74 (1.54)	0.37	[0.06, 0.68]	2.40	0.30	.019	.114
Intrinsic motivation to stimulate (IMS)	4.15 (1.70)	4.49 (1.49)	0.34	[0.03, 0.65]	2.23	0.28	.030	.150
Identified regulation (IDR)	5.26 (1.62)	5.31 (1.53)	0.05	[-0.26, 0.36]	0.31	0.04	.758	.758
External regulation (ER)	4.37 (1.90)	4.63 (1.73)	0.27	[-0.02, 0.56]	1.86	0.23	.068	.272
Amotivation (AM)	1.40 (1.09)	1.52 (1.11)	0.11	[-0.05, 0.27]	1.38	0.17	.172	.516

Note. *n* = 63. Δ = T2 - T1. Holm-adjusted *p* values control familywise error within the confirmatory motivation family (*m* = 6; IJR excluded a-priori due to low reliability). None of the confirmatory subscales survive Holm at α = .05.

Table 6. Exploratory dose–response regressions of COFFEE usage on pre–post change scores in academic outcomes and motivation ($n = 63$).

Outcome (Δ)	Model	B (Usage Effect)	95% CI for B	p	R^2
Academic Outcomes					
Academic Well-Being	Any use (0/1)	0.437	[-0.012, 0.887]	0.056	0.058
	Usage trend (0–2)	0.218	[-0.009, 0.445]	0.059	0.057
Academic Self-Efficacy	Any use (0/1)	0.229	[-0.134, 0.591]	0.212	0.025
	Usage trend (0–2)	0.111	[-0.072, 0.294]	0.231	0.023
Course Self-Efficacy	Any use (0/1)	0.598	[0.157, 1.039]	0.009**	0.108
	Usage trend (0–2)	0.258	[0.032, 0.484]	0.026*	0.079
Academic Competence	Any use (0/1)	0.417	[0.022, 0.813]	0.039*	0.068
	Usage trend (0–2)	0.188	[-0.013, 0.389]	0.067	0.054
Motivation					
Intrinsic Mot. – Knowledge	Any use (0/1)	0.393	[-0.047, 0.833]	0.155	0.033
	Usage trend (0–2)	0.06	[-0.220, 0.340]	0.669	0.003
Intrinsic Mot. – Accompl.	Any use (0/1)	0.892	[0.099, 1.686]	0.028*	0.077
	Usage trend (0–2)	0.296	[-0.114, 0.706]	0.154	0.033
Intrinsic Mot. – Stim.	Any use (0/1)	0.358	[-0.451, 1.168]	0.379	0.013
	Usage trend (0–2)	-0.093	[-0.504, 0.317]	0.651	0.003
Identified Regulation	Any use (0/1)	0.608	[-0.193, 1.410]	0.134	0.036
	Usage trend (0–2)	0.268	[-0.139, 0.674]	0.192	0.028
External Regulation	Any use (0/1)	0.437	[-0.173, 1.046]	0.156	0.024
	Usage trend (0–2)	0.206	[-0.190, 0.602]	0.300	0.014
Amotivation	Any use (0/1)	-0.251	[-0.673, 0.171]	0.239	0.023
	Usage trend (0–2)	-0.146	[-0.359, 0.066]	0.172	0.030

Note. B = unstandardized regression coefficient; CI = confidence interval; R^2 = model R-squared. Any use (0/1) contrasts non-users with users (once or $\geq 2\times$); usage trend (1–3) codes intensity as never, once, $\geq 2\times$. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$.

Finally, we tested moderation by baseline academic genAI use (centered), limited to this single moderator for parsimony given $n = 63$. Baseline academic genAI use did not moderate pre–post change (all interaction $p > .10$), including models controlling for COFFEE use, indicating that initial academic genAI familiarity did not systematically shape outcome changes.

4. Discussion

This study examined usage patterns, perceptions, and short-term within-person changes associated with COFFEE, an LLM-based formative feedback tool, in distance-learning modules. Three findings stand out. First, uptake was broad but engagement depth was typically light. Second, intrinsic motivation to know (IMK) was the only robust prospective predictor of later COFFEE use; neither prior academic genAI use nor baseline global academic outcomes (academic wellbeing, academic and course self-efficacy, academic competences) predicted subsequent engagement. Third, mean pre–post gains on global academic outcomes did not survive multiplicity control in the matched cohort; nonetheless, dose–response analyses suggested selective, small benefits, most consistently for course self-efficacy, among students who engaged with the tool. We interpret these patterns in light of recent evidence on LLM-mediated feedback, motivation, and technology use in higher education, noting that effects should be read as associative given attrition and the absence of a control group.

4.1 RQ1: Adoption and perceptions: high trial, shallow use, encouragement and trust focused on benevolence

The fact that 76% of respondents used COFFEE indicates substantial openness to AI-mediated formative feedback in an authentic course context. Yet most users invested little time (≥ 1 h was uncommon) and many engaged only once, indicating that initial curiosity does not automatically translate into sustained, regular, repeated use. This ‘broad but thin’ engagement pattern may also reflect an as-yet underutilized depth of didactic integration within modules. By contrast, the exercises are substantial and paired with comprehensive feedback; once learners attain an appropriate level of proficiency, they typically do not repeat them for practice. In addition, LLM-generated formulations often skew positive, which may yield overly favourable feedback or dampen students’ critical appraisal.

Students appraised the feedback as encouraging and modestly developmental and fair, and overall trust (expertise, integrity, benevolence) was positive. After controlling for multiple comparisons, two contrasts remained: learners who spent ≥ 1 h reported higher benevolence, and repeat users reported higher encouragement. These patterns align with evidence that acceptance of AI feedback hinges not only on accuracy but also on relational qualities (e.g., care, fairness, tone), and that transparency about an AI source can both bolster and dampen trust. For example, Zhang et al. (2025) showed that explicitly labelling feedback as ‘AI’ reduced perceived authenticity even when usefulness was unchanged under hidden-source conditions. Taken together, our results suggest that benevolence and encouragement are the most responsive trust levers under deeper or repeated engagement with COFFEE. Practically, this implies designing for sustained interaction, e.g., structured revision cycles and prompts that invite reflection and re-submission, to strengthen the relational qualities that support ongoing use.

4.2 RQ2: Predictors of use: curiosity beats familiarity

Only intrinsic motivation to know prospectively predicted later COFFEE use, whereas prior academic genAI use, academic wellbeing, academic and course self-efficacy, and academic competences did not. This points to curiosity and anticipated value as the key levers for continued engagement, rather than simple familiarity. COFFEE use hinged on curiosity/learning-oriented interest rather than simple familiarity with academic genAI use. Put differently, feeling that “this will help me learn something I want to know” mattered more than already having used genAI for study purposes before. This pattern fits our RQ1 perception data: heavier/repeat users rated encouragement higher (AFQ) and perceived greater benevolence (METI), suggesting that a supportive, value-visible experience can reinforce the motivational pathway from curiosity to continued use.

4.3 RQ3: Pre–post change: selective, dose-dependent signals amid small overall effects

Across the matched cohort ($n = 63$), the overall pre–post estimate, which summarises change for both COFFEE users and non-users, did not yield Holm-corrected gains on the primary academic outcomes. This cohort-level stability is consistent with brief exposure for many students and the course/study-wide (rather than task-proximal) nature of the outcomes. Complementing this descriptive picture, the dose–response analyses focused on variation in engagement and indicated small, selective gains among users, most consistently in course self-efficacy, with tentative patterns for academic competences and wellbeing. In other words, while the cohort as a whole showed little average movement, students who engaged with COFFEE exhibited signals of improvement, especially on outcomes closest to the feedback’s purpose. This pattern aligns with controlled evaluations of LLM-mediated feedback, which tend to find small-to-modest improvements when feedback is task-proximal and iterative, for example, increases in revision quality and motivation in secondary students (Meyer et al., 2024) and gains on writing-related outcomes for pre-service teachers (Kinder et al., 2025). Overall, the results suggest that (i) cohort-level averages can remain stable

when exposure is heterogeneous, and (ii) engagement intensity and outcome specificity matter: course-specific efficacy appears more responsive to formative AI feedback over a single semester of mostly light use.

4.4 Limitations

The study is observational and non-randomized; all dose–response associations are non-causal. Usage is self-reported rather than log-verified; matched $n=63$ limits power after multiplicity control; outcomes are broad and may miss task-level learning; and the context (adult distance learners) tempers generalizability. We addressed module imbalance via post-stratification and controlled familywise error within outcome families, but unmeasured confounding and measurement constraints remain.

4.5 Implications and future directions

To move beyond initial trial use, COFFEE should be embedded in structured revision cycles where students submit drafts, receive AI feedback, revise, and then re-engage, ideally with assessment alignment so benefits are immediate and visible. Because intrinsic motivation to know predicted uptake, framing COFFEE as an exploration tool that supports mastery rather than compliance may be most effective; short on-ramp activities that showcase concrete gains can help students internalize its value and shift motivation toward more autonomous forms. Trust also requires careful design: students responded most to benevolence and encouragement, qualities that can be reinforced through polite, specific, non-controlling language, just-in-time rationales, and transparent limitations with opportunities to query or contest feedback, while making instructor endorsement and institutional safeguards visible in the tool. Finally, evaluation should incorporate system logs and task-proximal outcomes such as rubric scores or revision quality, and future studies should employ randomized or quasi-experimental designs across multiple feedback cycles to provide stronger evidence of learning effects.

4.6 Conclusion

In an authentic distance-learning environment, COFFEE was widely adopted and positively perceived, yet its benefits remained modest and selective under brief exposure. Students with higher curiosity-driven motivation were more likely to engage, and those who engaged more reported small gains in course self-efficacy. These patterns are consistent with contemporary findings: recent trials show that LLM feedback can enhance revision quality, motivation, and engagement when task-aligned and iterative (Meyer et al., 2024; Kinder et al., 2025; Thomas et al., 2025), but broad learning gains are unlikely without sustained depth of engagement (Escalante et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2025). The path forward is clear: preserve ethical safeguards and instructor endorsement to maintain trust, design for sustained interaction through structured feedback cycles (Carless & Boud, 2018; Hattie & Timperley, 2007), and evaluate with task-proximal metrics and stronger designs such as randomized trials (Wisniewski et al., 2020). Under those conditions, LLM-enabled feedback can become a credible complement to human instruction in higher education.

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Digital Student & Staff Services

Beyond assessment: How AI Becomes a Mentor, Evaluator, and Career Coach

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming distance education, evolving from a tool for automating grading and administrative tasks into a mentor, evaluator, and career coach. This study explores how AI fosters intellectual growth, critical thinking, and career readiness by supporting personalized and adaptive learning. AI-powered mentorship systems use adaptive algorithms and natural language processing (NLP) to offer individualized academic support. These systems assess student performance, recognize learning patterns, and provide tailored feedback, cultivating an interactive and student-centered environment. Virtual tutors simulate human-like conversations, helping students build problem-solving and ethical reasoning skills. This personalization deepens understanding and fosters autonomy in complex subjects. As Göçmez and Okur (2023) note, AI-based student support includes real-time chatbots, course recommendation systems, automated assessments that enhance feedback, and emotion recognition tools that monitor engagement. Additionally, AI profiling helps identify at-risk students, enabling early interventions and more effective support strategies.

As an evaluator, AI transcends traditional assessment methods focused on memorization. AI-based evaluations analyze student input in real time, incorporating written responses, project-based tasks, and simulations (Du Plessis, 2025; Vlachopoulos & Makri, 2024). Platforms like Gradescope identify patterns in answers for consistent grading. In the humanities, NLP-based tools such as Cognii and E Cree offer immediate feedback on written responses, helping students strengthen their arguments and critical thinking (Vlachopoulos & Makri, 2024). Similarly, Turnitin's Draft Coach and Revision Assistant assist with structure and originality in academic writing. Adaptive systems like Knewton Alta customize assessments to student progress, while Century Tech applies neuroscience-informed analytics for real-time learning insights (Du Plessis, 2025). However, as Bozkurt et al. (2024) caution, AI assessments must be designed to promote higher-order thinking and avoid reinforcing superficial learning or algorithmic bias.

AI also creates new opportunities for educators' professional development. In schools, it provides data-driven insights, intelligent feedback, and support for instructional decisions (Copur-Gencturk et al., 2024). Training aligned with the TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) framework strengthens teachers' digital competencies through hands-on, collaborative learning (Zulianti et al., 2024; Celik, 2022; Yang et al., 2024). Beyond teaching, AI acts as a career coach by aligning student competencies with industry demands. Using predictive analytics, AI identifies skill gaps, suggests personalized learning paths, and connects learners to employment opportunities. AI chatbots simulate interviews, review resumes, and provide strategic career advice, improving workforce preparedness.

Despite these advances, ethical and practical concerns remain. Algorithmic bias, lack of transparency, and unequal access can perpetuate inequalities. Therefore, ethical guidelines, faculty training, and safeguards that maintain learner independence are essential to ensure fair and inclusive AI integration.

This study proposes a forward-looking framework where AI acts as a partner in students' intellectual and professional growth. In alignment with Bozkurt et al. (2024), it advocates for human-centered, ethical AI use to enhance equity, creativity, and agency in the evolving landscape of distance education.

Keywords

Distance Learning, Assessment, Career Readiness, Ethical Implications

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming distance education, moving from an administrative tool to a key driver of personalized learning, assessment, and professional development. Recent studies highlight AI's role in creating adaptive environments where students receive tailored feedback, develop critical thinking, and engage in more autonomous learning (Göçmez & Okur, 2023; Bozkurt et al., 2024).

In learning support, AI-powered tutors and mentoring systems simulate human-like interaction, providing real-time guidance and emotional reinforcement. In assessment, AI shifts evaluation away from memorization toward authentic, project-based, and adaptive approaches that foster higher-order thinking (Du Plessis, 2025; Vlachopoulos & Makri, 2024). At the same time, AI applications extend to career readiness, aligning student competencies with labor market demands through predictive analytics, interview simulations, and personalized skill development (Topping et al., 2025).

Despite these opportunities, concerns about bias, transparency, and unequal access raise ethical and pedagogical challenges. Scholars emphasize the need for human-centered AI integration that enhances equity and learner agency while avoiding overreliance on automated systems (Bozkurt et al., 2024).

This study explores AI's evolving role in distance education through the following research questions:

- How does AI foster intellectual growth and critical thinking in distance learning environments?
- In what ways do AI-driven assessments reshape evaluation practices?
- How can AI support students' career preparedness and professional development?
- What ethical challenges accompany AI integration, and how can they be addressed?

By addressing these questions, the study aims to propose a framework for integrating AI as tutor, evaluator, and career coach in distance education.

Literature Review

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in educational contexts is reshaping the dynamics of teaching and learning. AI systems, such as Knewton Alta and Century Tech, adaptively adjust assessments based on student progress and provide insights into learning behaviors (Du Plessis, 2025). These adaptive learning environments encourage engagement and responsiveness that traditional assessments often lack, moving beyond rote memorization to support deeper understanding of subject matter (Vlachopoulos & Makri, 2024).

One of the critical advantages of AI in education is its potential to enhance higher-order thinking among students. However, it is essential to design AI assessments carefully to avoid reinforcing superficial learning or perpetuating algorithmic biases (Bozkurt et al., 2024). By utilizing evaluative systems that focus on higher-level cognitive skills, AI can analyze complex student input in real time, including assessments of written responses

and project-based tasks, providing a more comprehensive view of a student's abilities and learning trajectory (Topping et al., 2025).

AI's capabilities also extend to providing immediate feedback and consistent grading, as demonstrated by platforms like Gradescope, which identify patterns in student responses. In the humanities, natural language processing (NLP) tools such as E Cree and Cognii facilitate direct feedback on written materials, fostering the development of arguments and critical thinking skills (Vlachopoulos & Makri, 2024). Similarly, Turnitin's Draft Coach and Revision Assistant assist learners in refining the structure and originality of their academic writing, creating interactive experiences that enhance essential academic skills (Du Plessis, 2025).

AI's transformative role has led to a framework that advocates for the responsible use of technology to foster equity, creativity, and student agency, particularly in distance education contexts (Bozkurt et al., 2024). The literature suggests a vision where AI acts as a partner in students' intellectual and professional growth. This paradigm shift necessitates ongoing discussions about the ethical implications of AI, ensuring that it enhances educational standards rather than diminishes them (Göçmez & Okur, 2023).

Additionally, AI promotes new pathways for educators' professional development. Providing data-driven insights and feedback on instructional practices facilitates informed decision-making regarding teaching strategies. Aligning training with the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework is critical for strengthening educators' digital competencies (Copur-Gencturk et al., 2024; Zulianti et al., 2024). Collaborative professional development sessions help educators navigate the digital landscape, fostering continuous learning and adaptability (Yang et al., 2024).

The evolution of AI in education has led to personalized learning modalities. AI-powered mentorship systems utilize adaptive algorithms and NLP to deliver tailored academic support, encouraging deep understanding and autonomy among learners, particularly in complex subjects (Göçmez & Okur, 2023). Furthermore, the development of virtual tutors simulating human-like interactions illustrates AI's potential to improve ethical reasoning and problem-solving skills through engaging, personalized support systems (Vlachopoulos & Makri, 2024).

These innovations allow AI to play a crucial role in identifying at-risk students through profiling tools, enabling timely and effective intervention measures that enhance learning outcomes (Göçmez & Okur, 2023). Additionally, monitoring student engagement through emotion recognition technology further underscores AI's multifaceted approach to enriching educational experiences, promoting both academic success and emotional well-being (Bozkurt et al., 2024).

As the literature on AI in education continues to evolve, it becomes evident that the collaboration between educators and AI can fundamentally transform pedagogical practices. These changes encourage schools to embrace AI's potential while remaining aware of the ethical implications associated with its use. Maintaining a focus on developing higher-order thinking skills and competencies aligned with contemporary educational needs is essential for maximizing AI's benefits in diverse learning environments (Vlachopoulos & Makri, 2024).

In summary, the literature underscores the transformative potential of AI in education. With effective implementation and ethical considerations, AI can enhance assessments, support professional development, customize learning experiences, and improve educational outcomes for both students and educators, marking a significant milestone in the advancement of innovative educational practices (Du Plessis, 2025; Bozkurt et al., 2024).

Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology used for the current literature review on the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in distance education. The study followed the guidelines of the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) framework to ensure the transparency, completeness, and reproducibility of the process.

1. Search Strategy

A systematic literature search was conducted across electronic databases, including Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science. The keywords used, either individually or in combination, were: "Artificial intelligence" or "AI", "Distance education" or "Distance learning", "Assessment", "Personalized learning" or "Adaptive learning", "Professional development", "Ethical challenges". The search was limited to articles published from 2023 onwards to include the most recent developments and studies in the field.

2. Study Selection Criteria

The inclusion criteria adopted were, first of all studies that were published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. Secondly, studies that were examining the role of AI in distance education and studies related to at least one of the four research areas: (a) intellectual growth, (b) assessment, (c) professional development, and (d) ethical challenges. The studies selected were written in Greek and English language.

The exclusion criteria, on the other hand, that were adopted were articles that are not in full text (e.g., conference abstracts), studies focusing on traditional, in-person educational environments, unrelated studies (e.g., general articles on AI without educational application). Another exclusion criterion was the focus on proctoring systems and supervision as well as technical matters.

3. Study Selection Process

The selection process followed the stages of the PRISMA framework. Initially, the titles and abstracts of articles resulting from the search strategy were screened for their relevance. Subsequently, the full texts of the selected articles were examined in detail based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. All decisions were documented to ensure transparency.

4. Data Extraction and Synthesis

From each final study, the following data were extracted: Identification details (author, year of publication), purpose of the study, key findings regarding the role of AI in distance education as well as thematic category (e.g., assessment, professional development).

This data was then thematically synthesized, grouping similar findings and highlighting central trends and debates in the literature. This synthesis formed the basis for writing the literature review.

Findings and Discussion

The findings of this study are presented and interpreted in relation to the four research questions (RQ1–RQ4). Each subsection combines empirical evidence from the reviewed literature with a discussion of its implications for distance education.

RQ1: AI as a Mentor – Intellectual Growth and Critical Thinking: The findings show that AI-driven mentorship systems foster personalized learning experiences that promote intellectual growth and autonomy. Virtual tutors, adaptive platforms, chatbots, and recommendation systems provide real-time feedback, simulate human-like conversations, and identify at-risk learners through profiling tools. These applications support higher-order thinking by encouraging problem-solving and ethical reasoning skills. In line with Göçmez and Okur (2023), such systems enhance learner engagement and independence. Bozkurt et al. (2024) emphasize that while AI can facilitate autonomy, its integration must remain human-centered to safeguard critical thinking and agency. Thus, AI's mentoring role lies not in replacing educators but in complementing them, creating environments where students develop reflective and ethical capacities.

RQ2: AI as an Evaluator – Rethinking Assessment: AI-based assessment platforms expand evaluation beyond rote memorization. Gradescope ensures consistent grading through pattern recognition, while NLP-based tools such as Cognii and E Cree offer formative feedback on written work. Turnitin's Draft Coach and Revision Assistant improve academic writing, and adaptive systems such as Knewton Alta and Century Tech adjust difficulty levels to match student progress. The Artificial Intelligence-Based Assessment in Education (AIBA) framework (Fang, Roscoe, & McNamara, 2023) highlights the multidimensionality of these systems across purposes, constructs, data sources, computational methods, and visibility. These findings confirm Vlachopoulos and Makri's (2024) claim that authentic assessments are essential for 21st-century competencies. Similarly, Du Plessis (2025) stresses the potential of project-based, AI-supported assessment to enhance deeper learning. At the same time, concerns raised by Bozkurt et al. (2024) about algorithmic bias and the risks of "stealth assessment" underscore the need for carefully designed frameworks. The evidence suggests that AI reshapes evaluation practices, but its effectiveness depends on balancing innovation with transparency and pedagogical responsibility.

RQ3: AI as a Career Coach – Professional Development and Employability: Findings highlight AI's role in aligning academic learning with labor market demands. Predictive analytics identify skill gaps and generate personalized learning pathways, while AI chatbots simulate job interviews and provide resume feedback. Platforms such as Thunai extend career guidance to include leadership skills, networking, and emotional well-being (Charanya et al., 2025). Conceptual models like MentorAI (Bagai & Mane, 2023) further suggest AI's potential to support holistic professional growth, including work-life balance. These insights resonate with Tan (2024), who shows how AI mentorship systems can guide early-career researchers, and with Karwa (2023), who demonstrates their value in refining domain-specific competencies. Topping et al. (2025) also note AI's role in enhancing reflective practices and peer assessment. Nevertheless, while AI offers strategic advantages for career preparedness, it lacks the empathetic and relational dimension of human mentoring. A hybrid model that combines AI efficiency with human empathy appears to be the most effective approach.

RQ4: Ethical Challenges and Policy Implications: The findings reveal that AI integration raises complex ethical and institutional challenges. Issues such as algorithmic bias, unequal access, and risks to data privacy demand transparent and equitable policies. Universities are beginning to revise their strategies to include clear guidelines on AI use, ensure data protection, and promote faculty training. Professional development aligned with the TPACK framework (Copur-Gencturk et al., 2024; Zulianti et al., 2024) is essential to equip educators with the competencies to use AI ethically and effectively. This aligns with Bozkurt et al. (2024), who caution against uncritical reliance on AI, and emphasizes that AI integration is not merely a technological shift but also an institutional and cultural transformation. Without clear safeguards, there is a risk that AI could undermine rather than enhance educational equity.

Synthesis

Overall, the findings and their interpretation suggest that AI holds transformative potential as a mentor, evaluator, and career coach in distance education. However, its effectiveness depends on careful design, ethical safeguards, and supportive institutional frameworks. The dual nature of AI—innovation coupled with risk—reflects the current state of its integration: a powerful enabler of personalized learning and professional development, yet one that requires deliberate governance to ensure inclusivity, transparency, and human-centered practice.

Conclusions

This study examined the evolving role of artificial intelligence in distance education, highlighting its potential to act simultaneously as a mentor, evaluator, and career coach, while also addressing the ethical challenges and institutional implications of its integration. The findings indicate that personalized mentorship systems, virtual tutors, and profiling tools can foster student autonomy, engagement, and critical thinking, while AI-based assessment platforms expand evaluation beyond memorization by offering authentic, formative, and adaptive feedback that supports higher-order learning. At the same time, predictive analytics and AI-powered guidance systems contribute to career preparedness by bridging academic learning with employability and responding to labor market demands. Despite these opportunities, significant ethical challenges remain: generative AI raises questions of reliability, academic integrity, and transparency in grading (Xia et al., 2024), while algorithmic bias, data privacy, and unequal access continue to pose risks. Addressing these issues requires robust institutional policies, professional development for educators, and a human-centered approach that ensures AI strengthens equity, creativity, and learner agency rather than undermining them.

Universities are called upon to take a leading role in the responsible integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI). They must develop clear AI policies that address issues of equity, transparency, and data governance, and ensure equitable access for all students to AI tools and digital infrastructure. Furthermore, they must establish professional development programs, aligned with frameworks such as TPACK, to empower educators to integrate AI in an ethical and effective manner. Finally, a revision of assessment policies is required to incorporate authentic methods supported by AI while ensuring academic integrity.

Similarly, educators can utilize AI to improve teaching and learning. They can use AI-driven feedback tools to enhance students' critical thinking and personalize their learning trajectories. Additionally, they can leverage AI data analytics to identify at-risk students and design timely interventions. AI can also function as a tool for reflective practice, improving their instructional strategies through data.

In turn, students themselves have an active role. They should engage with AI tutors and adaptive platforms as partners in learning and not as substitutes for human judgment and initiative. They must also use AI-powered career tools strategically to develop employability skills while always maintaining an awareness of ethical issues.

In conclusion, AI has the potential to act as a transformative partner in distance education when applied responsibly. The challenge for institutions is to balance innovation with ethics, ensuring that AI enhances equity, creativity, and learner agency. By fostering a human-centered approach, universities can harness AI not only as a technological tool but as a catalyst for meaningful educational change.

Limitations and Future Research

While this study provides valuable insights into the role of AI in distance education, several limitations must be acknowledged. Primarily, the scope of analysis was limited, examining AI as a mentor, evaluator, and career coach, while other dimensions—such as its role in fostering collaboration or supporting accessibility for learners with disabilities—were beyond the research's scope. Additionally, the study's dependence on secondary sources, rather than extensive primary data, may limit the generalizability of its findings. The rapid technological change within the field of AI in education also raises questions about the longevity of the current findings, as tools and practices that appear transformative today may quickly become outdated. Finally, contextual variability means that the results may not apply equally across all educational systems, cultural contexts, or disciplines, as the impact of AI depends on institutional resources, digital infrastructure, and policy environments.

Given these limitations, future research should focus on several key areas. Empirical validation is needed through large-scale, mixed-methods, and longitudinal designs to measure the actual impact of AI on learning outcomes, critical thinking, and employability. Cross-cultural comparisons are also essential to reveal how contextual factors shape AI adoption and effectiveness. Furthermore, more work is required to explore how AI can support inclusive education, particularly for students with disabilities or those with limited digital access. Continued investigation into the development of transparent, equitable, and accountable policies for AI integration in universities is necessary, along with studies that examine educator perspectives, their adaptation to AI tools, and the support they require.

In sum, while this study highlights the transformative potential of AI in distance education, further research is crucial to ensure that its integration is evidence-based, equitable, and responsive to the needs of diverse learners and educators.

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Development of meta classification of competencies at the University of Maribor

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Abstract

Rapid technological and societal changes are transforming the competencies required in the labour market and higher education. In response, the European Union introduced a common framework for micro-credentials to promote flexible and competency-based lifelong learning. Building on this policy, the University of Maribor has developed an institutional approach that integrates study programmes and short courses through a digital, AI-supported Curriculum Management System (CMS). The CMS enables the mapping of learning outcomes to multiple competence frameworks and classifications, accreditation, quality assurance, and interoperability. Central to this development is the University of Maribor Competencies Classification (UMCC), designed to promote the development of ESCO, which lacks sufficient coverage of higher-education competences and proficiency levels. The paper presents the concept of a meta classification of competencies, integrating diverse frameworks and discipline-specific models, into a unified structure with DigComp, GreenComp, and other EU frameworks. This approach enhances alignment between education and societal needs and contributes to the evolution of a common European competence language for lifelong learning.

Keywords

lifelong learning, competence classification, competence framework, short course, micro-credential, curriculum management system, quality assurance

1. Introduction

According to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2023), only 40 % of adults in Europe currently participate in lifelong learning, while the World Economic Forum (WEF, 2025) estimates that 44 % of the global workforce will require additional training or reskilling by 2030, as two-fifths of existing competencies will be transformed or rendered obsolete. Higher education is undergoing a paradigm shift, driven by rapid technological, economic, and societal changes that demand a more flexible and competency-driven approach to learning. These developments highlight the urgent need to complement traditional education with lifelong learning, with competencies taking precedence over specific job roles. To address these challenges, the European Union adopted the Council Recommendation on a European Approach to Micro-Credentials for Lifelong Learning and Employability (Council of the EU, 2022), establishing a framework for integrating micro-credentials into national qualification systems.

In Slovenia, the launch of university-level pilot projects under the NextGenerationEU Recovery and Resilience Plan in 2022 marked the beginning of a coordinated transformation of higher education. At the University of Maribor (UM), the Agile Development of Education and Micro-Credentials project laid the groundwork for an institutional ecosystem that integrates formal study programmes and micro-credentials into a coherent framework supported by digital infrastructure. In 2025, micro-credentials were included in the Higher Education Act (Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation, 2025).

At UM, we are developing a university-wide support platform for all forms of education, backed by competence frameworks and classifications. The accreditation process, development monitoring, and quality assurance of study programs and short courses are supported. The agile development of higher education programmes and short-term education and training to obtain the micro-credential will depend on effective collaboration with external stakeholders. The approach should be based on explicitly defined credentials linked to assessed learning outcomes. Therefore, we have developed the Curriculum Management System (CMS), an AI-supported platform designed to facilitate the mapping of learning outcomes to multiple competence frameworks and classifications, ensuring transparency, quality assurance, and cross-border recognition.

The aim is to address the labour market and societal needs, fostering a more agile and competency-driven education ecosystem. We present our approach to managing the diverse landscape of competencies to provide a systematic approach to developing European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) (European Commission, 2017) with the introduction of meta classification of competencies at the University of Maribor that is based on multiple competence frameworks, classifications, and input from the university professors. The Common European Higher Education Area can reach its full potential only with a common approach based on competencies.

2. Lifelong Learning at University of Maribor

The Slovenian Qualifications Framework (SQF) (Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation, 2015) and the Higher Education Act of the Republic of Slovenia define the procedures and responsibilities related to the accreditation of higher education institutions and their educational offerings. The national system of quality assurance and regulatory development is aligned with broader European policy frameworks and standards. The new Higher Education Act defines a micro-credential as a public document that certifies the completion of a short course or training programme. It represents a formal record of the learning outcomes achieved by an individual, expressed in terms of the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) (European Commission, 2015). Officially recognised short educational and training programmes leading to micro-credentials are delivered by accredited higher education institutions and are considered to be in the public interest.

Each micro-credential comprises a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 9 ECTS credits. Such programmes do not constitute parts of formal study programmes nor the fulfilment of obligations within them. Importantly, micro-credentials are not formally included in the Slovenian Qualifications Framework (SQF), and discussions regarding their integration are still ongoing. At the institutional level, micro-credentials are approved by the university senate upon the proposal of the competent faculty body. Each higher education institution establishes its own internal procedures for designing, approving, and delivering micro-credentials, ensuring consistency with institutional and national quality assurance frameworks. Institutions are also required to maintain a self-evaluation system that regularly reviews the implementation, structure, content, revision, and potential discontinuation of micro-credentials as part of the overall quality-assurance cycle. The National Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (NAKVIS 2019) periodically evaluates these procedures as part of the regular renewal of institutional accreditation.

The Guidelines for the Development of Micro-Credentials (UM 2024) are aligned with UM's lifelong learning strategy and internal procedures (UM 2017). Short courses are categorised as follows:

1. Non-accredited, without assessment → certificate of attendance;
2. Non-accredited, with assessment → certificate of attendance;
3. Accredited, with assessment → micro-credential.

Non-accredited courses without assessment are mainly used for staff training or employer-specific programmes and support broader lifelong learning participation. Non-accredited short courses with assessed learning outcomes result in a certificate of attendance and are implemented by UM member institutions using a standardised certificate template. Micro-credentials are issued exclusively for accredited short courses with verified learning outcomes. All accredited short courses are published in the UM Lifelong Learning Catalogue. Participants will be registered in the Academic Information Subsystem (AIPS), ensuring data management consistent with university standards and access to institutional infrastructure.

Quality assurance and reporting follows national legislation and UM guidelines for micro-credentials. The minimum scope of a short course eligible for a micro-credential is 1 ECTS, typically at EQF level 6 or higher. Learning outcomes must be measurable, achievable, and aligned with recognised taxonomies (e.g., Bloom's). Each accredited short course includes mandatory metadata—provider, coordinator, participating institutions, description, related competencies, qualification level (SQF, EQF, EHEA), KLASIUS and ISCED classifications, grading system, and a unique identifier. Accreditation follows established institutional procedures.

3. Learning Outcomes and Competences

Linking learning outcomes and competencies is essential for designing transparent, comparable, and quality-assured educational offerings, particularly when developing micro-credentials that are public document. Within the European Qualifications Framework (EQF), competence is defined as the demonstrated ability to use knowledge, skills, and personal, social, and methodological abilities in work or study situations, as well as in professional and personal development. In this sense, competencies are broader than skills: whereas skills typically denote the ability to use specific methods, tools, or instruments in defined contexts, competencies describe a person's capacity to act effectively in novel or complex situations by mobilising a combination of knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

Learning outcomes are statements describing what a learner knows, understands, and is capable of doing upon completion of a specific learning process. They represent results of learning and are expressed in terms of knowledge, skills, and competencies at a defined qualification level. Learning outcomes serve as the measurable link between education and assessment: each learning outcome must be verifiable through appropriate methods of evaluation, which confirm the acquisition of the corresponding competencies.

In curriculum design, competencies form the conceptual foundation, while learning outcomes operationalise these competencies into assessable units that guide teaching, learning, and evaluation. We aim to ensure that the learning outcomes of all short courses and study programmes are aligned with relevant competence frameworks and classifications. However, we identified a central challenge: the fragmented and heterogeneous nature of existing competence frameworks and classifications.

We have identified hundreds of competence frameworks spanning diverse disciplines. Some originate from traditional professional associations (IEEE 2025, ACM 2012), while others result from national or international initiatives. Their scope and structure vary—certain frameworks comprehensively describe entire professions, whereas others focus on specific training needs or domains such as tourism. Frameworks like DigComp also define proficiency levels, providing an additional layer of granularity. However, most frameworks remain non-machine-readable and lack international standardisation, which hinders interoperability and data integration. Although artificial intelligence can assist in harmonising classifications, the development of coherent and reliable frameworks continues to rely on expert human judgment.

ESCO was developed by the European Commission’s Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion, and provides a multilingual reference describing over 3,000 occupations and 13,000 skills across 28 languages. ESCO serves as a common European language for employment, education, and training, promoting transparency and mobility within the labour market. The system is publicly accessible online and via API, with its first full version released in 2017. Comparable taxonomies, such as the Lightcast Open Skills Library in the United States, offer larger datasets but focus primarily on market-driven applications.

Testing within the European University project in 2022 revealed that ESCO remains incomplete for higher education and focuses on lower-level skills. To address these gaps, UM initiated the University of Maribor Competencies Classification (UMCC) and is developing the CMS to map learning outcomes across multiple frameworks systematically. This approach has the potential to provide comparability and recognition of acquired learning within the institution and across the European Higher Education Area.

4. University of Maribor Competencies Classification

Although international systems such as ESCO, Lightcast, and discipline-specific frameworks provide valuable references, their inconsistent structure, coverage, and level descriptors limit interoperability and comparability across disciplines. Building on ESCO, UM is now extending its efforts toward the meta classification of competencies, designed to integrate multiple frameworks and enable harmonised mapping across diverse educational contexts. We plan to use UMCC for the formal description of the learning outcomes. Additionally, we plan to develop a Job Description Editor for a formal connection of labour needs to the UMCC. This represents a systematic attempt to integrate and harmonise multiple frameworks into a unified, hierarchical structure based on the development of ESCO.

UMCC will include only competencies that are actually used in the learning outcomes by the education offering of UM. Each member of the UM, e.g., the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, can select additional competence frameworks that are included in the CMS. Mapping of Learning Outcomes and Competencies can begin at any group of competencies, but the selection of competencies from ESCO is mandatory. This links the learning outcome to an appropriate position within the ESCO structure (Figure 1). User is supported by the artificial intelligence based on the description of the learning outcome and already selected competencies. The better the description, the better suggestions can be offered. Suggestions are updated after a new competency is selected, regardless of the tab used, e.g., if a competency is selected from the IEEE, suggestions for the ESCO are updated.

Figure 1: Selection of competencies from ESCO with the help of AI.

Selected competence frameworks can be used to define learning outcomes in greater detail. A framework can be presented in a separate tab or included under the competencies group "Other", based on the importance and available data format of the framework. As shown in Figure 2, the competencies included in the competence frameworks of IEEE and ACM are considerably more detailed than those available in ESCO.

Figure 2: Selection of competencies from ACM and IEEE.

The Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp) represents a specific subset of competencies formally developed and maintained by the European Commission. While DigComp is conceptually and structurally aligned with the ESCO, it provides a more detailed and operational model focused on digital literacy and proficiency levels. DigComp defines competencies across five dimensions and eight proficiency levels, ranging from basic to highly specialised digital skills. Similar competence frameworks include GreenComp (the European Sustainability Competence Framework), LifeComp (the European Framework for Personal, Social and Learning to Learn Competence), and EntreComp (the European Entrepreneurship Competence Framework). Together, these frameworks constitute formalised subdomains within ESCO, representing targeted and policy-driven approaches to competence development across key European priority areas and are supported by the UM CMS (Figure 3).

Figure 3: DigComp and support for proficiency levels.

Within national and international projects and networks, domain-specific competence frameworks are developed to address the needs of particular industries and research areas. Competence frameworks are also developed by sectoral associations such as the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia (GZS) and by the Strategic Research and Innovation Partnerships (SRIPs), which operate as coordinated clusters between academia, research institutions, and industry. SRIPs are currently covering key strategic domains, e.g., Smart Cities and Communities, Factories of the Future, Smart Buildings (Government of the Republic of Slovenia, 2025). Each SRIP develops or adapts competence catalogues relevant to its domain. For example, the SRIP Circular Economy produced the Catalogue of Competences that defines required skills and knowledge for sustainable production and business models (SRIP – Circular Economy, 2023). The SRIP GoDigital partnership focuses on the digital transformation of industry and the development of ICT-related competence profiles, aligned with the European Digital Skills Agenda (SRIP GoDigital, 2025). All such frameworks can be included under the tab "Other" (Figure 4). Each selected competency is automatically added to the UMCC and becomes a candidate for the proposed update of the ESCO.

Figure 4: Selection of competencies from other competence frameworks with the help of AI.

5. Discussion

The review process and the procedures for proposing updates to the ESCO have not yet been formally established. In the next phase, we will assess the adequacy of the proposed technical solution through systematic testing of competence mapping in short courses leading to micro-credentials.

Following the completion of pilot projects, the development activities will be extended to the level of accredited regular study programmes. In this phase, we anticipate additional challenges related to the large number of courses and the complexity of associated learning outcomes and competencies. The expansion of the system to full-scale academic programmes will therefore require enhanced automation and improved methodological support for the aggregation, mapping, and hierarchical structuring of competencies.

Further challenges are expected in defining and calibrating the levels of proficiency across different frameworks and in providing comprehensive training for academic staff. These trainings will focus on the systematic linking of learning outcomes to competencies to ensure consistency and prevent redundancy that could obscure distinctions between learning outcomes or diminish the interpretability of awarded micro-credentials. A coherent and scalable approach will be essential to maintain transparency, comparability, and the overall integrity of competency-based education within both short and degree-oriented programmes.

Slovenia is introducing advanced labour-market forecasting tools. The Skills Forecasting Platform aims to identify future competence needs and anticipate occupational trends over a 30-year horizon, combining national data with methodologies from Cedefop's European Skills Forecast (Cedefop, 2024). Complementing this effort, the Labour Market Platform of the Employment Service of Slovenia (ESS) integrates real-time data

on job vacancies, professions, and competence demands to support evidence-based policy, education planning, and career guidance (Employment Service of Slovenia, 2024). Earlier initiatives, such as the GZS Career Platform, already provided medium-term forecasts of skills needs to guide both employers and educational institutions (Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia, 2020). The European competence framework for researchers ResearchComp could be used to assess and develop researchers' transferable skills and foster career development (European Commission, 2024). Together, these sector-based frameworks and forecasting platforms can be used to develop the University of Maribor's meta classification of competencies, providing an evidence-based foundation for aligning educational outcomes with evolving labour-market demands.

In Slovenia, all companies are required to maintain a job classification system that includes formal descriptions for each position, outlining what is expected from the worker. We could map those descriptions to the expected skills, knowledge, and competencies of employees, the same way we do for the learning outcomes. We plan to develop a Job Description Editor—a digital tool designed to simplify the creation and updating of job descriptions while enabling their integration with the University of Maribor Competencies Classification (UMCC) and ESCO frameworks. Connected to the foresight, these integrations will allow both acquired and required competencies to be represented in a structured, comparable, and internationally recognisable format, strengthening the link between education, employability, and workforce development.

6. Conclusions

The development of the meta classification of competencies at the University of Maribor represents a systematic effort to bridge the gap between higher education and the evolving needs of the labour market. By combining institutional, national, and European frameworks, the proposed model introduces an integrated approach to competence management across diverse educational contexts. Through the CMS and the UMCC, learning outcomes can be mapped to multiple competence frameworks, facilitating the development of ESCO, thus enabling interoperability, comparability, and scalability of competency-driven education.

The pilot implementation within short courses leading to micro-credentials demonstrates the feasibility of using AI-supported systems to automate and harmonise competence mapping, quality assurance, and accreditation processes. As the approach expands to accredited study programmes, it will contribute to a more agile and responsive higher-education ecosystem that aligns educational offerings with real-world demands.

Future work will focus on validating the methodology through cross-institutional and international cooperation, refining the taxonomy of proficiency levels, and strengthening the feedback loop between education, labour-market foresight, and policy development. The meta classification thus serves as a cornerstone for advancing the European Skills Agenda and supports the vision of a coherent and data-driven European framework for lifelong learning and employability.

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European Universities initiative and University Networks

Pedagogical Innovation for Open and Online Teaching: The EUNICE Alliance Approach

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Abstract

The European Universities Initiative aims to foster deeper transnational cooperation in higher education. Within this framework, the EUNICE (European University for Customised Education) alliance -comprising ten partner universities – has launched the *Pedagogical Innovation* initiative to strengthen digital teaching capacity. This initiative responds to the growing need for high-quality open, online, and blended education by equipping academic staff with contemporary pedagogical skills and digital tools. A collaborative, cross-institutional approach was adopted to design and implement open and online training modules. These include synchronous and asynchronous workshops, curated digital resources, and peer-to-peer exchanges, all hosted within the alliance’s virtual learning environment. Participants are faculty members from all ten EUNICE institutions, and activities are delivered in an open-access format to promote inclusivity and transferability. Preliminary results show high levels of engagement among teaching staff and increased awareness of digital pedagogies. Early feedback from participants indicates improved confidence in designing learner-centered, online learning experiences. The initiative has also led to the creation of a shared repository of open teaching resources, promoting reusability and institutional collaboration. The *Pedagogical Innovation* initiative demonstrates the potential of university alliances to serve as incubators for educational transformation. By promoting openness, digital fluency, and pedagogical collaboration across borders, EUNICE advances the European Universities Initiative’s broader goals of innovation, inclusion, and sustainability in higher education. Lessons learned from this model may inform future strategies for capacity building in university networks across Europe.

Keywords

Pedagogical innovation, open education, digital competence, collaborative learning, EUNICE Alliance

1. Introduction

The rapid digital transformation of higher education has underscored the urgent need for new pedagogical approaches and professional development models that empower educators to design meaningful online and blended learning experiences. The European Universities Initiative, launched by the European Commission, responds to this challenge by encouraging universities to form alliances that promote innovation, inclusion, and transnational cooperation.

The *EUNICE – European University for Customised Education* alliance represents a strong network of ten universities from Germany, Spain, Italy, France, Sweden, Belgium, Greece, Poland, Finland, and Portugal. Founded in 2020, EUNICE seeks to transform higher education by promoting flexibility, inclusion, and collaboration between universities, industries, and societies. Within this context, the *Pedagogical Innovation*

initiative was created to enhance teaching quality, support digital transformation, and strengthen the pedagogical competences of academic staff.

2. The EUNICE Alliance and its pedagogical vision

EUNICE – *European University of Customised Education* aims to provide customised learning pathways at a European scale and to enhance both students' and teaching staff's experience through innovative, open, and flexible learning opportunities. Its key objectives focus on fostering good practices in knowledge sharing, interdisciplinary research, and innovative educational approaches that can effectively address global challenges. At the same time, it seeks to ensure that education, research, and innovation are closely aligned with regional socio-economic needs, while actively promoting collaboration that connects academia with society and the labour market.

Although the partner universities of the EUNICE Alliance are traditional, campus-based institutions, they have joined forces to create a collaborative transnational network that extends beyond the boundaries of conventional higher education. This cooperation allows them to share resources, expertise, and pedagogical innovations in ways that transcend geographical and institutional limits.

The alliance currently brings together ten universities across Europe:

- Poznań University of Technology (Poland) – coordinator of the Alliance
- Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus–Senftenberg (Germany)
- University of Cantabria (Spain)
- University of Catania (Italy)
- Université Polytechnique Hauts-de-France (France)
- University of Mons (Belgium)
- University of Vaasa (Finland)
- Karlstad University (Sweden)
- University of the Peloponnese (Greece)
- Polytechnic Institute of Viseu (Portugal)

Together, these institutions represent 136 407 students and 11.661 staff (52 departments), forming a vibrant European academic community. Within this network, pedagogical innovation has become a strategic pillar for transforming how teaching and learning are designed and experienced—bridging the gap between traditional university education and the emerging needs of a digitally connected, global society.

3. Pedagogical Innovation within the EUNICE Alliance: A collaborative and constructivist approach to professional learning

The *Pedagogical Innovation* programme, developed within the framework of the EUNICE Alliance, aims to enhance teaching excellence through knowledge sharing, inclusive digital learning experiences, and the exchange of innovative educational practices among partner institutions. Built on a collaborative model, EUNICE has designed a comprehensive training programme that includes:

- synchronous and asynchronous workshops,
- curated open educational resources,
- peer-to-peer exchanges, and
- cross-institutional learning communities.

The EUNICE *Pedagogical Innovation* programme is conceptually grounded in constructivist and socio-constructivist learning theories, which emphasise that knowledge is actively constructed rather than passively received. According to Vygotsky (1978), learning is inherently social, emerging through interaction and collaboration within the *zone of proximal development*. Bruner (1996) further conceptualised learning as a process of meaning-making through discovery and scaffolding, while Jonassen (1999) described technology-enhanced environments as contexts that enable learners to build, test, and refine their own understanding. In the EUNICE context, these perspectives translate into learner-centred, participatory, and reflective professional learning activities—such as peer mentoring, collaborative design workshops, and digital communities of practice.

A second theoretical strand is Open Education, which highlights the values of accessibility, participation, and knowledge sharing. Weller (2014) argued that openness in higher education has evolved from a technological affordance into a pedagogical commitment, while Cronin (2017) framed Open Educational Practices (OEP) as the intersection between openness, collaboration, and praxis. The European Commission's *Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027* (European Commission, 2020) reinforces this perspective by promoting digital inclusion, interoperability, and the development of open learning ecosystems.

Within the EUNICE context, these principles of openness and collaboration are translated into concrete pedagogical practices that support professional learning and cross-institutional exchange. Drawing also from Communities of Practice theory (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998), the initiative views professional learning as situated, collaborative, and identity-forming. Through shared inquiry and reflection, educators gradually move from peripheral participation to active membership in a European professional community.

This multidimensional framework integrates constructivism, openness, and professional collaboration as complementary forces driving pedagogical innovation in open and online higher education. The following sections illustrate how these theoretical principles are enacted through the initiative's key actions.

4. Digital Thursdays: Empowering educators through practice

Building on the principles of constructivism and openness outlined above, the *Digital Thursdays* series represents one of the flagship actions of the EUNICE Pedagogical Innovation Initiative. Grounded in theories of social constructivism (Vygotsky, 1978) and communities of practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998), these short, interactive online sessions provide a space for educators to experiment with digital tools, share innovative teaching approaches, and engage in reflective dialogue across institutions.

Each session focuses on a specific theme—such as *gamification* (Gee, 2003; Deterding et al., 2011), *interactive video learning*, or *inclusive assessment* (Boud & Molloy, 2013)—and is led by guest speakers from partner universities. The format encourages hands-on exploration and peer exchange, aligning with contemporary research that highlights the importance of *active, collaborative professional learning* in digital education (Laurillard, 2012; Beetham & Sharpe, 2019).

Feedback collected from participants indicates that the sessions not only enhanced their technical and pedagogical confidence but also fostered a sense of belonging within a European community of educators, reflecting findings from studies on cross-institutional professional networks (Carvalho & Goodyear, 2014). The initiative's motto, "*Empower your classroom!*", encapsulates its broader aim: to cultivate creative, digitally fluent, and pedagogically reflective teachers across the EUNICE Alliance.

5. The Teachers' Hub: A transnational community for collaborative learning

A central component of the EUNICE Pedagogical Innovation Initiative is the *Teachers' Hub*, a digital environment designed to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange among educators across partner universities. Rooted in the theoretical frameworks of Open Education (Cronin, 2017; Weller, 2020) and Communities of Practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998), the Hub functions as a dynamic professional network where teachers share experiences, co-create pedagogical resources, and engage in collective reflection on innovative teaching practices. It facilitates both synchronous and asynchronous interaction through online discussions, webinars, and repositories of open educational materials, reflecting the shift from individual professional development to *networked collaborative learning* (Dron & Anderson, 2014; Lieberman & Mace, 2010).

All training and capacity-building actions within the Initiative are supported by the Teachers' Hub, which operates simultaneously as a repository of resources and as a collaborative learning community. Rather than a static collection of materials, the platform constitutes a *living ecosystem of professional learning* where knowledge emerges through participation, dialogue, and co-construction—key characteristics of *socially situated learning* (Vygotsky, 1978; Wenger, McDermott, & Snyder, 2002). This process contributes to the gradual formation of a shared professional identity among educators as *European teachers* committed to openness and pedagogical renewal.

Beyond the development of digital and pedagogical competences, the Teachers' Hub promotes reflection, personal growth, and lifelong learning—core dimensions of academic professionalism in a rapidly evolving educational landscape (Avalos, 2011; Stoll et al., 2006). Its open-access and multilingual structure ensures inclusion, accessibility, and transferability of knowledge across institutional and linguistic boundaries, aligning with the European Universities Initiative's principles of collaboration and diversity (European Commission, 2024). Overall, the Teachers' Hub exemplifies EUNICE's vision of cross-institutional collaboration and sustainability in higher education, providing a model for continuous professional learning that transcends national borders.

6. Open Networked Learning course (ONL): An international model for collaborative and reflective teaching practice

Another significant action within the same pedagogical framework is the Open Networked Learning (ONL) course, coordinated by Karlstad University (Sweden)—a member of the EUNICE alliance—and Arcada University of Applied Sciences (Finland), which collaborates as an external partner. The course extends the principles of openness and collaboration to an international community of practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998). ONL represents an international, open, and collaborative online learning experience for educators, researchers, and educational developers worldwide, including both institutional learners (affiliated with partner universities) and open learners (independent participants joining freely from outside the consortium).

The course's distinctive feature lies in its open participation model, which brings together participants from diverse geographical, institutional, and disciplinary backgrounds to address authentic challenges in online and blended learning. Grounded in the principles of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) (Hmelo-Silver, 2004; Savery, 2006), ONL is structured through the FISH (Focus–Investigate–Share) framework—a scaffold that supports participants in defining their inquiry, investigating collaboratively, and sharing outcomes and reflections openly (Nerantzi & Beckingham, 2015).

This pedagogical approach fosters transparency, inclusivity, and community building, aligning with EUNICE's commitment to open, networked, and innovative higher education. It reflects the view that professional learning is most powerful when it is socially constructed and grounded in authentic inquiry (Laurillard, 2012; Dron & Anderson, 2014). Participants engage in critical reflection on their practice while developing digital,

pedagogical, and collaborative competences in real-world contexts, consistent with current models of networked professional development (Poortman et al., 2022).

Moreover, outcomes of ONL—such as digital lesson designs, case studies, and reflective artefacts—are integrated into EUNICE’s Open Educational Resources (OER) repository, further reinforcing the alliance’s core principles of openness, sustainability, and reusability in higher education (Cronin, 2017; Weller, 2020).

7. Language and Intercultural Competence

Building on EUNICE’s broader vision of openness and collaboration, another major strand of the alliance’s pedagogical innovation concerns multilingualism and intercultural competence. Through its *Work Package 2 – Language Steering Committee*, EUNICE promotes language learning and intercultural awareness among students and staff, aiming to expand access to the languages of all partner universities. This initiative reinforces the alliance’s vision of a multilingual and interconnected European university, where communication across linguistic and cultural boundaries becomes a core educational value (Beacco et al., 2016; Kramsch, 2011).

Within this framework, language learning is not conceived merely as a technical skill, but as a means of inclusion, empowerment, and professional mobility (Byram, 1997; Piccardo et al., 2018). It enables students and staff to collaborate effectively across borders and disciplines, fostering empathy, mutual understanding, and a sense of European belonging (Risager, 2007; Zarate et al., 2008). This intercultural dimension reinforces the European Universities Initiative’s core values of diversity, openness, and shared European identity (European Commission, 2024; European Commission, 2025).

As part of its immediate plans, the *Language Steering Committee* is developing a structured programme of language courses for staff—both academic and administrative—across all partner universities. These courses will provide opportunities for employees to learn the languages spoken within the alliance, thereby enhancing cross-institutional communication and supporting a culture of multilingual collaboration within EUNICE. In doing so, the alliance follows the guidelines of the European Commission, which emphasise that multilingualism is not only a pedagogical instrument but also a cornerstone for employability, intercultural competence, inclusivity, and social cohesion within the European Education Area (European Commission, 2025, pp. 188–189).

8. Conclusions

The EUNICE Pedagogical Innovation Initiative demonstrates that meaningful educational transformation in higher education emerges from sustained collaboration, openness, and reflection rather than isolated technological adoption. Across its different strands—the Digital Thursdays series, the Teachers’ Hub, the Open Networked Learning (ONL) course, and the Language and Intercultural Competence actions—the alliance has cultivated a growing community of educators committed to rethinking teaching and learning through shared practice.

Evidence from these activities shows increased pedagogical confidence, cross-institutional engagement, and a richer culture of openness in teaching. Educators have not only developed digital and methodological competences but have also begun to form a shared professional identity as European teachers. The integration of outputs such as open educational resources, reflective case studies, and collaborative lesson designs illustrates how the alliance translates pedagogical innovation into tangible and transferable results.

Beyond these outcomes, several lessons can be drawn. The first concerns the power of communities of practice: when educators learn together, they also shape collective professional meaning and long-term sustainability. Second, the alliance highlights the importance of multilingualism and intercultural understanding as enablers of collaboration across borders. Finally, the EUNICE experience suggests that

pedagogical innovation flourishes when openness is not treated as a technical choice but as a cultural and ethical commitment embedded in everyday academic life.

Taken together, these developments signal a shift toward a more integrated, reflective, and inclusive model of higher education—one where European collaboration becomes both a driver and a manifestation of pedagogical renewal.

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Micro-credentials for Continuing Education

Enhancing trust in construction education with blockchain-based micro-credentials

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Abstract

In the construction sector, the trend of digitalization is growing. Additionally, the recognition and verification of professional competencies are becoming increasingly necessary.

However, certification systems are often characterized by fragmentation, inefficiency, and a reliance on paper-based processes. This situation leads to a decreased level of trust between educational providers and employers.

A six-week pilot program in DevOps was conducted at the University of Ljubljana, involving twenty participants engaged in software-related training. Furthermore, a second pilot was implemented in collaboration with the University of Bologna to assess the effectiveness of cross-border credential verification. The results showed an impressive 97% satisfaction rate among learners and confirmed the interoperability of credential exchanges across institutions.

This study illustrates the feasibility and pedagogical value of trusted micro-credentials in enhancing workforce mobility and promoting lifelong learning. The paper integrates both pedagogical and technological perspectives, contributing to ongoing research on decentralized trust frameworks within digital education ecosystems.

Keywords:

blockchain, micro-credentials, verifiable credentials, digital education, construction

1. Introduction

The construction industry is currently undergoing a significant transformation, characterized by advancements in digital technology and environmental practices, particularly through Building Information Modeling (BIM), data-driven planning, and sustainability initiatives. These developments necessitate a workforce that persistently enhances its expertise in digital tools, project management, and collaborative methodologies. However, the education and training landscape within this sector remains fragmented and slow to adapt. Certificates are frequently issued in the form of paper documents, which can pose challenges for verification across borders or institutions. Meanwhile, emerging job profiles require agile and verifiable learning pathways.

Micro-credentials have emerged as an effective solution to this challenge. They allow learners to document specific skills gained through focused, short training experiences. This enables employers to assess demonstrated abilities instead of relying only on broad qualifications. However, the credibility of micro-credentials depends on the reliability, interoperability, and transparency of the systems that issue and verify them.

This paper presents a hybrid framework that integrates educational innovation with trust mechanisms based on technology. The EDUxCERT platform, together with the blockchain infrastructure, enables universities and training centers to issue verifiable digital credentials that are tamper-proof, portable, and compliant with European standards, including the Electronic Identification and Trust Services (eIDAS 2.0) and the European Digital Identity (EUDI) wallet.

The study includes insights from two pilot implementations: one at the University of Ljubljana, where students utilize the EDUxCERT platform within the entire ecosystem to create courses, track grades, and receive certification; and another at the University of Bologna, which focuses on interoperability between two countries with different regulations. These implementations demonstrate how verifiable micro-credentials can enhance transparency, interoperability, and increase accessibility for learners.

2. Background and related work

2.1. Micro-Credentials in lifelong learning

Micro-credentials are modular, competency-based units of learning that can be collected to form more comprehensive qualifications or recognized individually by employers. According to the European Commission (2022), these credentials provide evidence of learning outcomes gained through brief, transparent, and quality-assured educational experiences. They play a crucial role in the European Union's strategy for lifelong learning and workforce mobility. Research indicates that micro-credentials enhance learner engagement and offer flexible pathways for both upskilling and reskilling (Brown et al., 2021).

However, the widespread adoption of micro-credentials faces challenges such as fragmentation, limited interoperability due to varying regulations and paperwork, and a lack of verifiable digital trust mechanisms (Jirgensons & Kapenieks, 2018). Many initiatives remain confined within institutional silos, complicating efforts for cross-border recognition.

2.2. Digital trust and blockchain technologies in education

Emerging technologies, such as blockchain and Verifiable Credentials (VCs), provide a strong foundation for the decentralized and tamper-proof verification of academic records. The European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI)¹ pilot project, along with related EU projects such as ESSA², EBSI-VECTOR, and BuildChain³, demonstrates the ability to store credentials as cryptographic proofs, thereby eliminating the need for vulnerable documents. This method enables learners to take ownership of their achievements and share them securely.

Research highlights the need to align technological innovation with governance and pedagogy. A purely technical approach cannot replace quality assurance or institutional validation. Therefore, it is crucial to develop hybrid models that integrate semantic interoperability, policy frameworks, and educational design.

2.3. Construction education and digital transformation

Vocational and higher education programs in the construction sector face distinct challenges, including the rapid pace of technological advancements, stringent safety regulations, and growing demands for sustainability. According to the European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (CEDEFOP, 2021), there are persistent skill mismatches between industry requirements and the training available. It is crucial to integrate digital competencies, project management skills, and principles of green construction into curricula; however, this integration is often implemented at a sluggish pace.

The case study presented herein examines the application of micro-credentials within this framework, showcasing the use of blockchain-based verification to enhance both educational transparency and industry credibility.

3. Challenges in construction education and skills recognition

The construction industry, despite its importance, faces three significant structural challenges.

First, there is fragmentation and obsolescence in training systems. Curricula and certification frameworks vary widely across institutions and countries, limiting the portability of qualifications. Additionally, emerging technologies such as Building Information Modeling (BIM), digital twins, and sustainability management are evolving more rapidly than existing educational programs, resulting in persistent skills gaps.

¹ <https://www.ebsi-vector.eu/en/>

² <https://softwareskills.eu/>

³ <https://buildchain-project.eu/>

Second, there is a lack of transparent and verifiable credentials. Certifications are often issued in paper or PDF formats and stored in isolated databases that lack standardized verification procedures. As a result, employers must manually verify these credentials, and the prevalence of unverified certificates undermines trust in their authenticity.

Finally, the alignment between education and industry is weak. There is limited collaboration among universities, training providers, and construction firms, resulting in graduates who often lack the practical digital and managerial competencies expected in modern projects.

These challenges highlight the need for an interoperable, verifiable, and industry-connected credentialing framework. The EDUxCERT–BuildChain approach directly addresses these issues by integrating modular learning pathways with decentralized verification and governance aligned with industry standards.

4. Methodology and framework design

Figure 1: Methodology and framework design

4.1 System architecture

This case study utilizes a design-based research methodology to evaluate an innovative technological solution within a real-world educational context (Figure 1). The pilot initiatives explored the potential of blockchain-verified micro-credentials to enhance trust, transparency, and learner engagement in university-level construction-related courses. Data was collected through platform analytics and participant feedback.

The framework incorporates the EDUxCERT platform, which handles learning management, course development, and credential issuance, alongside the BuildChain trust layer to ensure the verifiability and integrity of credentials. The architecture consists of the following components:

- **Issuer Module:** Managed by accredited instructors, this module is responsible for generating and signing Verifiable Credentials using institutional Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs).
- **Holder Wallet:** This prototype digital wallet complies with EUDI standards and allows learners to securely store and share their credentials.
- **Verifier Service:** This service is used by employers or partner institutions to authenticate credentials via blockchain hashes, ensuring that personal data remains inaccessible and private.

4.2 Workflow Integration

The implementation of the six-week course was strategically designed to encompass a complete credential lifecycle, thereby integrating educational, technological, and governance processes into a cohesive workflow. This workflow is structured in three successive stages: learning design, issuance, verification, and sharing. Each stage builds upon the

outcomes of the preceding one, illustrating how micro-credentials can effectively transition from learning activities to verified digital evidence in a transparent and auditable manner.

Stage 1: Learning Design

In this initial phase, instructors utilized the EDUxCERT platform to establish learning outcomes, develop assessment titles, and create digital credential templates. Each credential template was designed to incorporate structured metadata, including:

- Issuer information (institution name, accredited instructor Decentralized Identifier)
- Competence descriptors aligned with European frameworks such as ESCO or DigComp
- Assessment criteria and grading methodologies
- Validity period and issue date

This systematic approach ensured that the credentials maintained semantic interoperability and conformed to recognized standards for lifelong learning. Through the standardization of credential templates, EDUxCERT facilitated consistency across diverse training sessions and institutions, thus mitigating ambiguity in skill definitions.

Stage 2: Credential Issuance

Following the completion of the course and fulfillment of assessment requirements, instructors activated the issuance process through the EDUxCERT platform (Figure 2).

The learner received a digital certificate, which included a QR code linked to the blockchain transaction, enabling third parties to validate its authenticity.

Figure 2: Glance of applications

Stage 3: Verification and Sharing

In the concluding phase, learners used their EUDI-compatible digital wallets to store, manage, and share their credentials (Figure 3). Verification can be conducted by:

- **Employers**, who can verify authenticity through the public Verifier portal.
- **Partner institutions**, which can cross-validate credentials during mobility or recognition processes.
- **Peers or recruiters**, who can use the QR code to access real-time validation without intermediaries.

When the QR code or verification link is utilized, the system compares the credential hash in the database with the hash recorded on the blockchain. A successful match confirms that the credential has not been altered and was issued by a reputable institution.

This decentralized verification model eliminates the need for manual confirmations or centralized databases, thereby fostering trust among learners, issuers, and verifiers. It ensures that each step—from the achievement of learning to credential validation—remains transparent and independently auditable.

Figure 3: Verification and sharing process

4.3 Governance Model

The governance model supporting the proposed framework aims to build and sustain trust among all stakeholders in the micro-credential ecosystem, which includes learners, issuers, verifiers, and policymakers.

At the first level, institutional trust ensures that only accredited and legitimate educational providers are authorized to issue verifiable credentials. Each participating university or training center is listed in the EDUxCERT institutional directory, with its identity verified through Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) linked to official domain records or national education registries. This mechanism ensures that every credential issued on the platform can be traced back to a reputable and accountable institution. Additionally, institutional policies specify who within the organization—such as instructors, department heads, or administrators—has the authority to issue or revoke credentials.

The second layer, network trust, governs the interactions among the institutions involved in the broader EDUxCERT ecosystem. In this layer, BuildChain trust anchors serve as root authorities, validating and cross-referencing issuer DIDs. Before adding a new institution to the network, its DID is compared against the trust anchor registry to minimize the risks of duplication, impersonation, or fraudulent involvement. Periodic audits are conducted through automated smart contracts that monitor credential issuance patterns and identify irregularities, such as duplicate credential hashes or inconsistent metadata.

The third layer, policy trust, guarantees long-term interoperability and sustainability by aligning the platform with established European regulatory and technological frameworks. EDUxCERT and BuildChain comply with key initiatives, including the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI), Authentication and Trust Services (eIDAS 2.0)⁴, and the European Digital Education Area (EDEA)⁵. Compliance with these initiatives ensures that credentials issued within

⁴ <https://www.european-digital-identity-regulation.com/>

⁵ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/focus-topics/digital-education>

the system are recognized across European borders and can be incorporated into future European Digital Identity (EUDI)⁶ wallets.

This multi-layered approach transforms the micro-credential system into a trustworthy digital ecosystem—where verification is both a technical process and an institutional as well as societal responsibility.

5. Pilot Implementation

Two pilot implementations were conducted to evaluate the EDUxCERT framework in academic settings, with the goal of assessing its effectiveness in enabling trusted micro-credentialing across both institutional and national boundaries. The pilots aimed to test both pedagogical effectiveness and technical interoperability, using consistent evaluation methods to ensure the results could be compared effectively.

Pilot 1 – University of Ljubljana: Local Implementation

The first pilot program was conducted at the University of Ljubljana, specifically within the Faculty of Computer and Information Science, as part of the DevOps Programme. This program focuses on digital and software engineering tools and was selected for its integration of theoretical learning with applied project-based activities, creating an ideal environment for assessing blockchain-enabled credentialing.

- **Participants:** The pilot involved 20 employees from companies, all with at least a bachelor's degree in relevant IT fields.
- **Duration:** The program lasted 6 weeks, from April to May 2024.
- **Location:** The sessions were held onsite.
- **Language:** All instruction was conducted in English.
- **Learning Areas:** The curriculum covered software development lifecycle management, agile methodologies, version control, and digital project coordination.

During the pilot, participants engaged in a blended educational model that combined lectures, collaborative assignments, and continuous assessment. The EDUxCERT platform was used to create micro-credentials representing specific competencies, such as “Version Control and CI/CD Automation” and “Agile Project Coordination.”

Upon completing each module, participants automatically received a Verifiable Credential (VC) containing metadata, which included descriptions of competencies, the issuer's identity, timestamps, and cryptographic proof.

Feedback was collected through surveys and interviews (Figure 4). Learners reported a 97% satisfaction rate, indicating that the immediate recognition of their achievements significantly enhanced their motivation to complete assessments. Instructors noted improvements in grading transparency and better traceability of learning outcomes compared to traditional grading systems.

This pilot confirmed the technical reliability of the integration and highlighted its pedagogical relevance as a motivational tool. Additionally, it demonstrated that credential issuance could be seamlessly integrated into existing university workflows with minimal training requirements or changes to infrastructure.

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/eudi-regulation>

Figure 4: Student Feedback

Pilot 2 – University of Bologna: Cross-Border Interoperability

The second pilot expanded the experiment to include a cross-institutional and cross-border context by collaborating with the University of Bologna, utilizing the EBSI-vector infrastructure⁷. The objective was to determine whether micro-credentials issued in Slovenia could be recognized and validated in Italy, and vice versa, by utilizing decentralized verification instead of manual communication between institutions. Each institution acted simultaneously as both the issuer and verifier, facilitating bidirectional testing of the credential flow.

During this pilot:

- The University of Ljubljana issued digital credentials to participants in a DevOps course.
- The University of Bologna issued credentials for a short course on Digital Skills for Sustainable Construction.

Each credential contained a blockchain-anchored hash and a QR code. When a credential from Ljubljana was submitted to Bologna's verification portal, the system retrieved its hash from EBSI-vector, verified the match, and confirmed authenticity within seconds. This process worked seamlessly in reverse as well.

The test achieved a 100% success rate in cross-verification, with no false positives or unverified credentials. These results confirmed full technical interoperability across institutional nodes and established that cross-border credential recognition could be achieved without centralized databases or third-party validation services.

This interoperability test aligned with the principles and specifications of the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI)⁸ and the eIDAS 2.0⁹ regulation, confirming the platform’s readiness for potential integration with European data and identity frameworks.

⁷ <https://www.ebsi-vector.eu/en/overview/>

⁸ <https://hub.ebsi.eu/blockchain>

⁹ <https://www.european-digital-identity-regulation.com/>

Figure 5: Cross-Border Interoperability

Overall, the pilot programs affirmed the feasibility and sustainability of decentralized trust infrastructures for higher education credentialing. They provided concrete evidence that blockchain-enabled micro-credentials can support the European goal of portable, learner-owned, and verifiable skills recognition.

6. Results and Analysis

The pilots demonstrated both the feasibility and the perceived value of decentralized credentialing within academic contexts. Quantitative satisfaction scores, along with qualitative feedback, suggest that trust mechanisms have significantly enhanced learners' accessibility and supported institutional interoperability.

From a technological perspective, the blockchain layer functioned reliably, with no occurrences of credential duplication or validation errors identified.

Pedagogically, the implementation of micro-credentials has led to increased learner engagement by providing rapid recognition of achievements and visual feedback via the digital wallet interface. The verifiability feature has promoted transparency between instructors and students, which aligns effectively with the principles of open and distance education.

Nevertheless, some participants highlighted usability challenges related to wallet configuration and expressed a desire for integration with existing university authentication systems. These insights will be pivotal in guiding future enhancements to both the interface and interoperability of the system.

7. Discussion

The findings confirm that trusted micro-credentials can effectively bridge the gap between education and employment in the construction sector.

Three key implications arise from this:

1. **Enhancing Transparency and Quality Assurance** – Blockchain-based credentials provide immutable audit trails of course design and evaluation, which strengthens institutional accountability.
2. **Facilitating Workforce Mobility** – The learner-controlled wallet allows for cross-border recognition of competencies, supporting initiatives like Erasmus+ and the European Qualifications Framework (EQF)¹⁰.
3. **Strengthening Industry Partnerships** – Construction companies can trust verified credentials without the need for intermediary validation, streamlining the recruitment process and compliance checks.

These benefits align with the broader objectives of the European Education Area 2030, which promotes digital credential ecosystems and encourages learners to own their data. However, the case study also highlights some adoption barriers, including the need for clearer policies on issuer accreditation, sustainable infrastructure funding, and staff training on micro-credential design.

The integration of EDUxCERT with BuildChain demonstrates that technical trust must be paired with institutional governance and pedagogical coherence—a balance that is essential for scalability.

¹⁰ <https://europa.eu/europa/en/european-qualifications-framework-eqf>

8. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper presents a case study regarding the implementation of blockchain-based micro-credentials within the DevOps Program at the University of Ljubljana, extended by a cross-border interoperability pilot in collaboration with the University of Bologna. This study makes a significant contribution to the field of digital education by illustrating how decentralized trust infrastructures can enhance transparency, promote learner autonomy, and facilitate cross-sector recognition within the domain of construction education.

The pilot initiatives achieved an impressive satisfaction rate of 97% and validated the technical feasibility of integrating verifiable credentials into conventional university workflows. By merging educational innovation with blockchain technology, the proposed framework strengthens the principles of lifelong learning and enhances employability in an increasingly digitized labor market.

Future research initiatives will aim to broaden the scope of the pilot programs to include additional faculties and vocational centers, incorporate semantic skill descriptors such as ESCO¹¹, and establish links to European data spaces related to education and employment. Furthermore, the following studies will investigate policy mechanisms aimed at standardizing credentials and optimizing user experience to ensure the large-scale adoption of this initiative.

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¹¹ <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en>

Diversity and Inclusion in Open and Online Education

Development of a MOOC for empowering migrants' and refugees' vocational training through learning Greek as an additional language: The PROGRESs Project Approach

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Abstract

The global refugee crisis has transformed Greece into a major host country for migrants and refugees. Language acquisition emerges as critical for integration and labour market participation, yet educational materials must be specifically designed to address the diverse needs of these learners. This paper presents the development of a MOOC, i.e. of a comprehensive Moodle learning platform and educational materials created as part of the PROGRESs project (acronym; full title of the project "Provision of the Greek language for the Integration of the Refugee Population into the Labour Market"), implemented by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) in collaboration with the Ministry of Migration and Asylum, Hellenic Open University, and Odysseya NGO, funded under the Recovery and Resilience Facility (R.R.F., European Commission).

The educational material consists of five units designed for levels A1-A2 (according to C.E.F.R.), delivered through both printed and online formats to accommodate different learning preferences and circumstances. The material integrates vocabulary, grammar, and communicative activities based on everyday situations crucial for refugee and migrant integration, including personal introduction, workplace communication, public service navigation, transportation, and health-related contexts. The online platform (www.edulearn.eap.gr) provides synchronous and asynchronous learning opportunities, featuring interactive exercises, forums, and multimedia resources that enable flexible, self-paced study alongside structured classroom instruction.

This study contributes to research on intercultural education by demonstrating that effective language education platforms must combine pedagogical flexibility, cultural sensitivity, and technological accessibility to support both traditional print-based and digital learning modalities for diverse refugee and migrant populations.

Keywords: *Greek as an additional language; refugee education; adult refugees; educational materials; digital learning; MOOC/Moodle learning platform; vocational training*

1. Introduction

The last decades have been crucial for many nations due to unstoppable migrant and refugee flows. Greece is a major point of entrance for these populations, coming from African countries such as Egypt and Sudan, and Asian countries such as Iran, Syria, Afghanistan, Palestine, China, and the Philippines. Forty years ago, Greece was a country of origin for many migrants; now, due to wars, poverty, and the erosion of human rights, it has become a host country for many migrants and refugees seeking a better future. This crisis presents two main challenges: humanitarian aid and integration. These populations have urgent needs, such as food, clothing, and access to healthcare, not only for physical health issues but also for psychological support.

Even when basic needs are covered, there remains the urgent need for integration into the new environment. Migrants and refugees need to seek employment; however, the language barrier is significant. Education is crucial for these populations, but circumstances differ from person to person. Different individuals have different needs regarding language acquisition. For example, there are migrants and refugees who are illiterate in their L1, while others are literate and bilingual. Also, due to the fact that many of these people work in the technical sector, they do not have time to participate in face-to-face Greek lessons.

Taking all of the above into consideration, the PROGRESs project was developed within the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), a European initiative designed to help member states strengthen resilience, inclusiveness, and sustainable growth. The programme is implemented by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) in close cooperation with the Ministry of Migration and Asylum, the Hellenic Open University (HOU), and the NGO Odyssea.

The aim of the PROGRESs project is to enhance the social and economic integration of adults over 18 years old who belong to the following groups: Beneficiaries of International Protection (BIPs), Beneficiaries of Temporary Protection (BTPs), Third-Country Nationals (TCNs) legally residing in Greece and asylum seekers. The project addresses significant barriers to employment, ranging from limited language skills to lack of recognized vocational qualifications, through structured pathways that combine language acquisition, vocational skills development, and practical work experience.

As part of this comprehensive integration strategy, the Hellenic Open University developed educational materials for teaching Greek as a second and/or foreign language to the target group. The materials were designed to be used in printed and/or online formats, supporting the needs of all students, even those who prefer self-study or cannot attend regular face-to-face classes due to work commitments. The educational material consists of five core units covering everyday situations and communication needs, delivered through a specially designed Moodle learning platform (www.edulearn.eap.gr) that enables both synchronous classroom use and asynchronous independent study (see Appendix 1, screenshots from the Moodle learning platform).

2. Literature Review

2.1 Teaching Greek as a Second or Foreign Language

The constant movement of refugees and migrants around the world is a commonly accepted fact that has changed various aspects of every country. Multicultural and multilingual societies have replaced mono-cultural and monolingual ones. The same happened to Greece, but the refugee flows of 2015

were a game changer, especially for education and educational policies. According to Kantzou et al. (2017), there is an urgent need for Greece, as a host country for numerous refugees, migrants, and asylum seekers, to provide literacy in Greek language, either as a foreign language or as a second language.

It is accepted that students face many difficulties in learning the Greek language. For example, adult refugees have to learn the local language as a necessary tool that will improve their socio-economic and professional status, helping them, at the same time, to integrate harmoniously into the country (Androulakis et al., 2016). The great number of people with refugee or migrant backgrounds, who seek to learn Greek rapidly as a second or a foreign language, have turned many language classrooms into heterogenous environments, as these populations differ in age, gender, sociocultural background, language competence, and prior exposure to any educational setting (Long, 2014). Recent research demonstrates that Modern Greek language education contexts substantially alter requirements for materials, teacher training, and instructional practices across different learner populations (Mattheoudakis & Maligkoudi, 2024).

2.2 Importance of Language Acquisition for Labour Market Integration

Greece has become a host country for many migrants and refugees. These people have experienced the loss of relatives and their fortunes, and they try to become members of a new sociocultural environment while simultaneously seeking pathways to economic independence and labour market participation (Palaiologou & Prekate, 2023).

Language acquisition is particularly crucial for successful integration into the labor market. Without proficiency in the host country's language, refugees and migrants face severe barriers to employment, often being restricted to informal or low-skilled jobs regardless of their educational background or professional qualifications (European Commission, 2020). Research demonstrates that language competence significantly increases employment opportunities and enables migrants to access positions commensurate with their skills and experience (Baker et al., 2019). Moreover, language proficiency facilitates professional networking, understanding of workplace culture and expectations, and the ability to advocate for workers' rights and fair treatment. The integration process is fundamentally intertwined with language learning, as linguistic competence enables not only economic participation but also social inclusion and civic engagement (ILO, 2024).

The PROGRESs project recognizes that language is the essential gateway to both employment and social interaction. Beyond basic communication, refugees and migrants need language skills specific to their vocational pathways, whether in tourism, agriculture, technical and construction fields, or other employment sectors. Language education within vocational training contexts must therefore address both general communicative competence and sector-specific terminology and discourse patterns.

2.3 Importance of Intercultural Education

Intercultural education is characterized as an educational movement with the main purpose of ensuring equal opportunities in school and society. At the same time, it seeks to empower non-native speaker students to develop skills and knowledge comparable to those of native students (Giavrimis & Dimitriadou, 2023). According to many researchers, intercultural education follows four main principles: a) empathy, b) solidarity, c) elimination of prejudices, and d) respect for cultural diversity. All these

principles must be reflected not only by educators but also in educational materials (Banks, 2002; Michael & Rajuan, 2009).

At the heart of intercultural education lies the fundamental recognition and respect for cultural, linguistic, and social differences as valuable resources rather than obstacles to overcome (Palaiologou, 2023). This approach requires educators and educational systems to actively acknowledge the diverse backgrounds, experiences, and knowledge that migrant and refugee students bring to the classroom, viewing these differences as assets that enrich the learning environment for all students. Intercultural education promotes dialogue, mutual understanding, and the development of intercultural competence, enabling students from different backgrounds to coexist peacefully and contribute constructively to pluralistic societies (Palaiologou & Dietz, 2012).

Given that many refugee students have suffered from psychological traumas, post-traumatic stress, loss, and exhaustion, it is essential that educators, educational materials, and the educational system in general promote intercultural education, because these populations need to belong somewhere (Palaiologou & Prekate, 2024). The intercultural education model promotes the necessary principles that help, especially refugee students, to become active members of the classroom and, subsequently, of society (Liu, 2024).

2.4 Needs for New Educational Materials and Digital Platforms

There are numerous educational materials for teaching Greek as a second or a foreign language; however, according to Dafkou (2023), these materials do not always address students' needs. More specifically, each refugee or migrant student has different linguistic and educational needs. According to recent research by Gkaintartzi et al. (2021), many books designed to help non-native speakers learn Greek language mainly include basic vocabulary, small phrases, and cover the same contexts, which are not always appropriate (Dafkou & Gkaintartzi, 2023). Innovative platforms such as the Digital School in Greece (launched in 2024) offer interactive learning systems and digital tutoring that provide more personalized learning pathways (CEDEFOP, 2024), yet accessibility for refugee and migrant populations remains limited.

Furthermore, it is evident that in classrooms with refugee students, each one has different linguistic needs. For example, a non-native speaker may be characterized as having A1 level proficiency in Greek; however, due to constant interaction with Greek people, his or her speaking skills may be higher, but his or her writing skills remain at a lower level. This example shows that educational materials have difficulty meeting various literacy levels simultaneously. This fact leads some educators to create their own materials; however, educators are not necessarily positioned or trained to develop appropriate educational materials (Gkaintartzi et al., 2021; Mogli et al., 2021). Research on teaching Modern Greek as L2 emphasizes the importance of addressing learners' diversity and varying profiles in instructional design (Mattheoudakis & Maligkoudi, 2024).

The development of online learning platforms specifically designed for refugee and migrant populations addresses several critical needs. First, such platforms provide flexibility for learners who work irregular hours or have family responsibilities that prevent regular class attendance. Second, digital platforms enable self-paced learning, allowing students to review materials as needed and PROGRESs according to their individual capabilities. Third, online environments can incorporate multimedia elements—images, audio recordings, videos—that support multimodal learning and accommodate different learning styles. Finally, well-designed platforms can provide immediate feedback on exercises, enabling autonomous learning while tracking PROGRESs (UNESCO, 2023).

2.5 Main Principles for Assessing Educational Materials

The assessment of educational materials is possible through the main principles of intercultural education and the informed perspectives of experienced educators. Any educational material needs to be adapted to students' needs, not vice versa. It is important that a textbook or any educational material meets students' needs and should be designed in a way that promotes not only linguistic needs but also addresses aspects that concern the audience (Barghamadi, 2020).

Furthermore, teaching an audience that speaks another language and is completely unfamiliar with the target language requires visualization; images and colors promote easier understanding (Saborío-Taylor & Rojas Ramírez, 2023). Educational materials for refugees and migrants must be carefully designed so as not to trigger sensitive aspects of their lives. Any image, text, sketch, table, or activity must be culturally sensitive (Diamani & Agrusti, 2018).

It is of great importance for students from different sociolinguistic backgrounds to feel accepted and respected not only by educators but also by the educational materials used. Therefore, it is important for any educational material to be based on multimodality. In other words, according to Dimitriadou, Tamtelen, & Tsakou (2011), students understand the target language differently via images, videos, and special effects compared to texts and rules alone. Therefore, visual stimulation is necessary for student engagement and interaction (Chamberlin-Quinlisk, 2013).

Regarding texts, images, and sketches, educational materials must realistically reflect students' lives and respect their language, religion, country of origin, and culture (Bundsgaard & Hansen, 2011). Another important factor in evaluating educational materials for refugees and migrants is the level of adaptability they offer. In other words, each educational material is considered effective when it takes into consideration adapting learning experiences and tools to suit learners' needs and making sure they are interacting and engaged (Koutzeklidou, Manousou, Karantrantou, 2025). Finally, intercultural education reflects principles such as respect, multilingualism, inclusion, and empowerment; therefore, any educational material must be created according to these principles to be deemed appropriate for refugees and migrants. Recent scholarship emphasizes that effective Greek language teaching materials must incorporate intercultural competence and mutually empowering interactions (Gogonas et al., 2024, in Mattheoudakis & Maligkoudi).

3. The PROGRESs Project Structure

3.1 Project's Overview and Target Groups

The PROGRESs project represents a comprehensive approach to integration that combines language education, vocational training, and practical work experience. Funded under the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), the project is implemented through a multi-stakeholder partnership involving the International Organization for Migration (IOM), the Ministry of Migration and Asylum, the Hellenic Open University, and Odysseya NGO.

The project targets adults over 18 years old from four main categories: Beneficiaries of International Protection (BIPs), Beneficiaries of Temporary Protection (BTPs), Third-Country Nationals (TCNs) legally residing in Greece, and asylum seekers. All of these groups face significant barriers to employment, including limited language skills, lack of recognized vocational qualifications, cultural differences, limited access to information about the labour market, and difficulties in navigating bureaucratic procedures. These challenges often result in exclusion, underemployment, or precarious working conditions.

3.2 Project's Pathways: Paid Traineeship and Vocational Training

The programme offers two main modalities designed to respond to diverse participant needs and create tangible pathways into the labour market:

1. Paid Traineeship: Participants begin with 80 hours of Greek language instruction, ensuring they acquire basic linguistic skills necessary for everyday communication and workplace interaction. This is followed by 270 hours of paid on-the-job training, which provides not only practical experience but also a source of income. Training sectors include tourism, agriculture, technical and construction fields, as well as projects specifically designed to enhance women's employability. The paid nature of this traineeship is particularly important, as it allows participants to support themselves financially while simultaneously building professional skills and confidence.

2. Vocational Training: This pathway also starts with 80 hours of Greek language instruction, followed by up to 70 hours of specialized vocational training. The focus areas include tourism, agriculture, technical and construction, as well as targeted support for vulnerable groups. This option is ideal for those who wish to strengthen their technical knowledge and gain certifications that can improve their employability.

Participants are encouraged to combine both modalities—traineeship and vocational training—in order to maximize their skills, broaden their opportunities, and enhance their long-term employment prospects. The Greek language component is mandatory for all participants, as language serves as the essential gateway to both employment and social interaction. However, exemptions are provided for those who already hold a high school diploma or an official certificate of Greek language proficiency.

4. Development of Educational Materials and Moodle Platform

4.1 Design Principles and Pedagogical Framework

The educational materials developed by the Hellenic Open University for the PROGRESS project were designed according to three main principles: a) adaptability to diverse learner profiles and needs, b) realistic content that addresses authentic communicative situations participants encounter in daily life and workplace contexts, and c) availability in both printed and digital formats to accommodate different learning preferences, technological literacy levels, and access to technology.

Recognizing that refugees and migrants often work irregular hours and have family responsibilities that prevent regular class attendance, the materials were specifically designed to support flexible learning pathways. The dual format approach ensures that learners can engage with content through traditional print materials when preferred or necessary, while also providing digital access through the Moodle platform for those who have the skills and resources to benefit from online learning.

4.2 Content Structure and Curriculum Organization

The educational material consists of five core units designed to cover levels A1, with some extension to A2 level content where appropriate. The material was organized to correspond initially to A1 level Greek proficiency; however, it became evident that a broader and more linguistically advanced approach would better serve the diverse target audience. Thus, the material was given a more extensive and complex form, incorporating activities of graded difficulty to respond to linguistic levels beyond complete beginners.

The five units address everyday situations crucial for refugee and migrant integration (as shown in Figures 3-7, Appendix 1):

Unit 1: "Me, Every Day" (Εγώ κάθε μέρα): This unit focuses on personal introduction and daily routines. It covers the Greek alphabet, personal pronouns, the verb "to be," articles, and vocabulary related to family and friends. The unit enables learners to introduce themselves, talk about their families, and describe basic daily activities.

Unit 2: "From Home to Work" (Από το σπίτι στη δουλειά): This unit addresses the transition between home and workplace contexts. It introduces numbers, basic verb conjugations, and vocabulary related to money, time, home, and work environments. Learners develop the ability to discuss work schedules, describe their homes, and handle basic financial transactions.

Unit 3: "Communication Everywhere" (Επικοινωνώ παντού): This unit focuses on communication in various public spaces. It covers irregular verbs, interrogative pronouns, subjunctive mood, and vocabulary for contexts such as markets, banks, restaurants, and schools. Learners acquire skills for navigating essential public services and commercial environments.

Unit 4: "Going Out and Moving Around" (Βγαίνω και πηγαίνω): This unit addresses transportation and movement. It introduces past tenses, passive voice, and vocabulary related to transportation means and giving/receiving directions. Learners develop the ability to use public transportation, ask for and give directions, and describe past events.

Unit 5: "Diet, Health, and Nature" (Διατροφή, υγεία & φύση): This comprehensive unit covers topics related to food, health, and the environment. It addresses adjectives, colors, more complex syntax, and vocabulary for cooking, vacation activities, medical contexts, and nature. This unit is particularly important as it enables learners to communicate about health issues and access medical services.

Each unit combines vocabulary acquisition, grammar instruction, reading comprehension, writing practice, listening activities, and speaking exercises, always linked to the real communicative needs of participants. The material covers basic and significant communicative needs as defined by the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages and the Curriculum for Teaching Greek as a Foreign Language of the University of Athens.

4.3 The Moodle Platform: Technical Features and Pedagogical Dimensions

The Hellenic Open University developed a dedicated Moodle platform (www.edulearn.eap.gr) specifically designed for teaching Greek as a second or foreign language to immigrants and refugees (see Figure 1, Appendix 1 for platform interface). The platform constitutes a central component of the PROGRESS project's educational approach and can be utilized as primary or supplementary material, in combination with printed textbooks, by both educators and learners. Importantly, the platform enables learners to use the material for self-study, accommodating those who cannot attend regular classes.

This particular platform represents a significant advancement in Greek language education for refugees and migrants, as it is organized specifically to address their unique circumstances and needs. The platform's primary distinction lies in its interactive nature: the correctness of answers in the majority of activities is checked automatically and simultaneously at the moment they are completed (see Figure 2,

Appendix 1 for example of interactive exercise). This immediate feedback mechanism is crucial for autonomous learners who may not have regular access to instructors.

The platform supports both synchronous and asynchronous learning modes. For synchronous learning, educators can use the platform materials during face-to-face or online classes, projecting exercises and activities for whole-class participation and discussion. For asynchronous learning, students can access the platform independently at times convenient to their work schedules and family responsibilities, PROGRESs through materials at their own pace.

Key features of the platform include: interactive exercises with automatic correction; multimedia resources including audio recordings of native Greek speakers for listening comprehension and pronunciation modeling; discussion forums that enable learners to communicate with instructors and fellow students, fostering a sense of community even in distance learning contexts; PROGRESs tracking that allows both learners and instructors to monitor advancement through the curriculum; and flexible access that accommodates different devices (computers, tablets, smartphones), recognizing that many refugees and migrants may only have mobile phone access to the internet.

The design is structured to include activities of graded difficulty, ensuring that it responds to and serves linguistic levels that do not exclusively concern complete beginners. The overall and primary objective of the material's construction is familiarity with and immediate use of Greek at a very basic communicative level, enhancing, as much as feasible, the self-confidence of foreign speakers in the new language and society. It focuses on all four basic skills—comprehension and production of oral discourse, and the corresponding written skills—within a simple and friendly framework, with realistically appropriate texts adapted within various communicative contexts.

4.4 Multimodal Design and Cultural Sensitivity

The educational materials incorporate multimodal design principles, recognizing that students understand and engage with the target language differently through various modes of representation. The materials integrate text, images, audio recordings, and interactive activities to accommodate different learning styles and preferences. Visual elements are carefully selected to be culturally inclusive and sensitive, avoiding imagery or content that might be triggering for individuals who have experienced trauma.

The texts, dialogues, and scenarios presented in the materials realistically reflect the lives and experiences of refugees and migrants in Greece, while respecting their diverse linguistic backgrounds, religions, countries of origin, and cultures. Situations and contexts are chosen to be relevant to participants' actual communicative needs, whether in seeking employment, accessing healthcare, interacting with public services, or building social connections in their new communities.

5. Discussion and Implications

5.1 Integration of Language Education within Vocational Training

The PROGRESS project represents an innovative model that integrates language education directly within vocational training and labour market integration pathways. This integration recognizes that language learning in isolation is insufficient for successful professional integration; rather, language skills must be developed in conjunction with vocational competencies and practical work experience. The 80-hour Greek language component that precedes both the paid traineeship and vocational training

pathways ensures that all participants have a foundation of communicative competence before entering workplace contexts.

This approach aligns with research demonstrating that language acquisition is particularly effective when embedded in meaningful, authentic contexts relevant to learners' goals and needs (Long, 2014). By connecting language instruction directly to employment pathways in specific sectors—tourism, agriculture, technical and construction fields—the project enables learners to develop both general Greek language proficiency and sector-specific communicative competencies.

5.2 Addressing the Digital Era

The dual format approach—printed materials alongside the digital Moodle platform—addresses a critical challenge in contemporary refugee and migrant education: the digital divide. While digital platforms offer significant advantages in terms of flexibility, interactivity, and accessibility, not all learners have equal access to technology or possess the digital literacy skills necessary to benefit from online learning environments.

Research indicates that refugees and migrants demonstrate widely varying levels of technological familiarity. Some are highly skilled users of digital technologies and readily embrace online learning platforms; others have limited experience with technology and prefer traditional print-based materials that provide greater confidence and accessibility (Gros, 2016; UNESCO, 2023). By providing both formats, the PROGRESS project ensures inclusivity, allowing each learner to engage with materials in ways that match their skills, preferences, and circumstances.

The Greek education system has begun implementing digital platforms such as the Digital School (e-school.gov.gr), which offers interactive textbooks and learning management systems; however, ensuring equitable access for refugee and migrant learners remains challenging (CEDEFOP, 2024). The PROGRESS project's commitment to dual-format materials represents an important step toward equity in educational access.

5.3 Scalability and Sustainability

The development of the Moodle platform and associated materials represents a sustainable investment in refugee and migrant education infrastructure. Unlike one-time training interventions, the platform and materials remain available for continuous use, enabling ongoing cohorts of learners to benefit from these resources. The digital platform can accommodate large numbers of users simultaneously, providing scalability that would be difficult to achieve through face-to-face instruction alone.

Furthermore, the materials are designed to be adaptable, allowing educators to modify and supplement content to address specific learner needs or emerging contexts. This adaptability ensures that the materials remain relevant and responsive over time, even as the profiles and needs of refugee and migrant populations evolve.

5.4 Contribution to Intercultural Education and Social Inclusion

Beyond language instruction, the PROGRESS project and its educational materials embody principles of intercultural education. The materials are designed with cultural sensitivity, respecting the diverse backgrounds, experiences, and identities of refugee and migrant learners. The project recognizes participants not merely as beneficiaries of aid but as active contributors to Greek society, economy, and culture. This perspective shift—from viewing refugees and migrants as problems to be managed to

recognizing them as valuable human capital and cultural resources—is fundamental to successful integration.

The project's emphasis on dignity, confidence, and social inclusion alongside economic integration reflects a holistic understanding of what integration entails. Language proficiency enables not only labour market participation but also civic engagement, social networking, and the development of a sense of belonging in the host society. By providing pathways to employment, professional development, and economic independence, the project empowers refugees and migrants to rebuild their lives with dignity and contribute meaningfully to their new communities.

6. Conclusions

This paper has presented the development and implementation of educational materials and a Moodle platform for teaching Greek as a second/foreign language within the PROGRESS project. The project represents a comprehensive, multi-stakeholder approach to refugee and migrant integration that combines language education, vocational training, and practical work experience.

The educational materials developed by the Hellenic Open University address critical needs in Greek language education for refugees and migrants. By providing content in both printed and digital formats, the materials ensure accessibility for learners with varying levels of technological literacy and access. The five-unit curriculum covers essential communicative situations that refugees and migrants encounter in daily life and workplace contexts, from personal introduction to health-related communication. The specially designed Moodle platform enables flexible, self-paced learning alongside structured classroom instruction, with interactive exercises, multimedia resources, and immediate feedback mechanisms that support autonomous learning.

The PROGRESS project demonstrates that effective language education for refugees and migrants must be grounded in intercultural education principles, cultural sensitivity, and pedagogical flexibility. Educational materials must accommodate diverse learner profiles, including variations in prior education, linguistic backgrounds, literacy levels, and technological skills. The integration of language instruction within comprehensive pathways to labour market integration represents an innovative approach that recognizes language acquisition as fundamentally connected to economic and social inclusion.

The project's dual-format approach addresses the digital divide while leveraging the advantages of technology for those able to benefit from online learning. This inclusive strategy ensures that no learners are excluded due to limited technological access or skills, while also providing enhanced learning opportunities through digital platforms for those who can utilize them.

Integration is a multi-dimensional process that cannot be achieved through legislation alone. It requires holistic approaches that combine legal frameworks with targeted educational and vocational initiatives. It requires opportunities that empower people to build their own futures, to stand on their own feet, and to contribute meaningfully to the societies in which they live. The PROGRESS project embodies this vision by placing emphasis on language acquisition, skills development, and professional experience, offering a model that is both practical and transformative.

Looking forward, the PROGRESS project and its educational components offer valuable lessons for other contexts facing similar integration challenges. The collaboration between the International Organization

for Migration, the Ministry of Migration and Asylum, the Hellenic Open University (HOU), and Odyssea NGO demonstrates the power of multi-stakeholder partnerships in addressing complex social challenges. The materials and platform developed by the scientific team of HOU represent sustainable educational infrastructure that can continue to serve successive cohorts of learners, making this not just a temporary intervention but a long-term contribution to Greece's capacity to support refugee and migrant integration.

Ultimately, the success of integration efforts depends on recognizing refugees and migrants not as problems to be managed but as individuals with dignity, agency, and potential to contribute to their host societies. By providing pathways to language proficiency, vocational skills, and labour market participation, the PROGRESs project empowers refugees and migrants to rebuild their lives and become active members of Greek society, enriching the social fabric and contributing to economic vitality.

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Appendix 1: Screenshots from the Moodle Learning Platform for Teaching Greek as a Foreign Language

Figure 1. Presentation of MOOC– Main Interface and Units/Contents of the Material

The screenshot displays the Moodle Learning Platform interface for teaching Greek as a Foreign Language. The main content area is titled "Provision of Greek language courses in Greece (mainland)". The page is organized into several sections:

- Γενικές πληροφορίες (General Information):** This section provides details about the courses. It includes a "Νέα - Ανακοινώσεις" (New - Announcements) section and three course listings:
 - Αίθουσα διδασκαλίας (δομή Κορίνθου):** The course is held daily from 16:30 to 21:30 via Microsoft Teams. A lock icon indicates it is unavailable, with a note: "Μη διαθέσιμο (κρυφό) εκτός και ισχύει ένα από τα: Ανήκετε στην ομάδα Kor250707 ...".
 - Αίθουσα διδασκαλίας (δομές Πύργου και Πάτρας):** The course is held daily from 16:30 to 21:30 via Microsoft Teams. A lock icon indicates it is unavailable, with a note: "Μη διαθέσιμο (κρυφό) εκτός και ισχύει ένα από τα: Ανήκετε στην ομάδα Pyrgos250918 ...".
 - Αίθουσα διδασκαλίας (δομή Κυλλήνης):** The course is held daily from 16:30 to 21:30 via Microsoft Teams. A lock icon indicates it is unavailable, with a note: "Μη διαθέσιμο (κρυφό) εκτός και ισχύει ένα από τα: Ανήκετε στην ομάδα Kilini250918 ...".
- Navigation Menu (Left Sidebar):** The menu includes categories such as "Γενικές πληροφορίες", "Γλωσσική εκπαίδευση" (Language Education), and "Διαπολιτισμική εκπαίδευση" (Intercultural Education). Under "Γλωσσική εκπαίδευση", there are five units: "Χώρος συζητήσεων", "1. Εγώ, κάθε μέρα", "2. Από το σπίτι στη δουλειά", "3. Επικοινωνιού παντού", "4. Θγαίνω και πηγαίνω", "5. Διατροφή, υγεία και φύση", "Αλληλεπίδραση", "Διαπολιτισμική εκπαίδευση", and "Γλωσσάρι - Ορολογία".
- Bottom Section:** Three cards are displayed, each with a pie chart icon and a label: "Γλωσσική εκπαίδευση", "Διαπολιτισμική εκπαίδευση", and "Γλωσσάρι - Ορολογία".

Note: The platform interface displays the five core units designed for A1-A2 level Greek language instruction, accessible through www.edulearn.eap.gr. Each unit is clearly labeled and provides access to vocabulary, grammar, reading, writing, listening, and speaking activities.

Figure 2. Multiple Choice Exercise with Automatic Correction from Unit 1

Note: Example of interactive exercise demonstrating the platform's automatic correction feature, which provides immediate feedback to learners, supporting autonomous study.

Figure 3. Unit 1: "Me, Every Day" (Εγώ κάθε μέρα) – Content Overview

Note: This unit consists of 4 sub-units covering the Greek alphabet, personal pronouns, the verb "to be," articles, and vocabulary related to family and friends.

Figure 4. Unit 2: "From Home to Work" (Από το σπίτι στη δουλειά) – Content Overview

Note: This unit consists of 4 sub-units focusing on numbers, basic verbs, and vocabulary related to money, time, housing, and work contexts.

Figure 5. Unit 3: "Communication Everywhere" (Επικοινωνώ παντού) – Content Overview

Note: This unit consists of 4 sub-units addressing irregular verbs, interrogative pronouns, subjunctive mood, and vocabulary for markets, banks, restaurants, and schools.

Figure 6. Unit 4: "Going Out and Moving Around" (Βγαίνω και πηγαίνω) – Content Overview

Note: This unit consists of 4 sub-units covering past tenses, passive voice, and vocabulary related to transportation and directions.

Figure 7. Unit 5: "Diet, Health, and Nature" (Διατροφή, υγεία & φύση) – Content Overview

Note: This unit consists of 5 sub-units addressing adjectives, colors, syntax, and vocabulary for cooking, vacation, medical contexts, and nature.

Note: The complete PROGRESs platform is developed by Hellenic Open University in collaboration with IOM, the Ministry of Migration and Asylum, and Odyssea NGO; it contains five core units covering A1-A2 level Greek language competencies, designed specifically for autonomous and facilitated learning by refugee and migrant populations participating in the Recovery and Resilience Facility-funded programme for labour market integration.

Empowering Migrants through Education: The PIPE Project's Approach to Social Inclusion

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Abstract

The Programme of Inclusion for Migrant People at Risk of Social Exclusion (PIPE) is an Erasmus+ project launched in November 2023. It aims to support the integration of migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers through tailored education, vocational training, and mentorship programs. By promoting intercultural awareness and developing digital learning tools, PIPE fosters social cohesion and empowers migrants to actively participate in their host communities.

Key outcomes of the PIPE project include the development of a digital platform offering a toolbox for professionals, volunteers, and institutions working with migrants. This platform promotes collaborative learning experiences, builds intercultural competencies, and supports the emergence of migrant citizenship grounded in social justice and community participation.

This presentation evidences the main outcomes of the project, combined with the main initiatives of the International Telematic University Uninettuno about migrants and refugees.

Keywords

Migrants, Inclusion, Crisis response

1. Introduction

Migration has become one of the most pressing social phenomena in Europe, reshaping demographic patterns and challenging established systems of education, labour, and welfare. According to Eurostat, in 2023, approximately 5.9 million people migrated to EU countries, including about 4.3 million arriving from non-EU countries and 1.5 million moving from one EU country to another (intra-EU migration). This represented anyway a drop from 2022 (when inflows had peaked around 6.2 million, boosted by refugees from Ukraine). Also, one analysis finds that the EU's foreign-born population grew by only 2.5 million in 2024. This implies net immigration remained positive in 2024 but far less pronounced than the year before. Notably, the majority of immigrants continue to come from outside the EU – for example, roughly 77% of 2023's immigrants were non-EU citizens. Additionally, European asylum requests remained high in 2024, since 1.01 million asylum applications were registered across EU countries. The main countries of origin remained Syrians, Afghans, Venezuelans, Turks, and Colombians, although most major applicant groups saw fewer claims in 2024 than in 2023. Despite the slight decline, pressure on asylum systems persisted, as nearly half of 2024's applicants were from nationalities with low recognition rates (i.e. likely to be eventually rejected).

These movements are not temporary episodes but part of a long-term trend: as of 2021, people with a migrant background accounted for over 23% of the total EU population, and in countries such as Germany this share rises to more than one in four inhabitants. Migrants contribute significantly to the social and economic fabric of their host societies, bringing skills, cultural diversity, and human capital. Yet, their path toward integration is often marked by systemic barriers. Data from the OECD indicate that migrants are, on average, twice as likely to be unemployed as the native-born population, and they are disproportionately represented in precarious

and low-paid sectors. Educational inequalities are also evident: language barriers, interruptions in schooling due to displacement, and limited recognition of prior qualifications restrict their opportunities to access further education or vocational training. These obstacles translate into a persistent skills gap that hinders both individual empowerment and broader social cohesion [Dragostinova, 2016].

Beyond the economic dimension, the challenges of integration have deep cultural and social implications. Surveys across European countries reveal high levels of mistrust and “social distance” towards certain migrant groups, particularly those perceived as culturally different. This climate can fuel marginalization, social exclusion, and, in some cases, radicalization. At the same time, communities hosting large numbers of newcomers face pressure on local resources such as housing, healthcare, and education, which can exacerbate tensions if not managed with inclusive and sustainable strategies [Buonanno, 2017].

In this context, education plays a key role in bridging divides and enabling mutual understanding. For migrants, it provides essential tools for empowerment: acquiring the host country’s language, developing transversal and professional skills, and gaining access to pathways that enhance employability. For host societies, education fosters intercultural awareness, reduces prejudice, and supports the construction of inclusive environments where diversity is seen as an asset rather than a burden. The intersection of these two dimensions makes education not only a personal right but also a structural necessity for fostering resilient, equitable, and cohesive communities in an era of unprecedented human mobility [Osler, 2020].

2. European initiative supporting inclusions and integration of migrants and refugees

The European Union has long viewed migration not merely as a challenge to be managed but as a structural reality requiring coordinated, humane, and forward-looking responses [Stalker, 2002; Balzacq, 2005; Brady, 2008]. Rooted in its founding values of solidarity, human rights, and respect for diversity, the EU seeks to balance effective border management with the promotion of inclusion and equal opportunities for those who arrive on its territory. Central to this vision is the idea that migration, when properly governed, can strengthen Europe’s social fabric, address demographic and labor market needs, and foster intercultural dialogue, while also ensuring protection for those fleeing war, persecution, or hardship [Papagianni, 2014; Crawley, 2016; Scipioni, 2018].

The European Union implements its migration and refugee inclusion strategy through a multifaceted policy framework anchored in both regulatory instruments and operational coordination mechanisms. At the core lies the "*Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021–2027*", which provides a comprehensive roadmap to remove barriers and promote active participation of migrants and those with a migration background across key domains such as education, employment, housing, and healthcare. The Plan emphasises intersectionality, gender equality, anti-discrimination, and leverages digital tools and data-driven monitoring to ensure progress—though a mid-term review in 2025 noted uneven implementation, with only ~25% of housing measures and ~15% of education/training actions completed so far.

Parallely, the EU’s *New Pact on Migration and Asylum*, approved in 2024, represents a major overhaul of the *Common European Asylum System (CEAS)*. Encompassing a suite of legislative instruments—including the Reception Conditions, Qualification, Asylum Procedures, Screening, Eurodac, Resettlement and Humanitarian Admission, Return Border Procedures, and Migration Management Regulations—the Pact aims to introduce uniform asylum procedures, expedited processing timelines, and a mandatory solidarity mechanism. Under this mechanism, Member States must either host asylum seekers or contribute via financial support, personnel, or infrastructure support; non-compliance can trigger a fixed monetary levy. These reforms are

slated to take effect from 2026, though some aspects—such as the Union Resettlement and Humanitarian Admission Framework—are already operational.

The EU also maintains funding instruments to support policy implementation on the ground. The *Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund* (AMIF) provides resources to Member States and EU-managed projects to enhance the Common European Asylum System, support legal migration and integration, facilitate returns, and foster solidarity across countries. Supporting the implementation of these norms is the European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA)—an operational body tasked with coordinating Member States, offering technical assistance, and bolstering capacities across the EU to manage asylum and migration flows effectively

In crisis scenarios, the EU has an additional tool: the *Temporary Protection Directive* (2001/55/EC). This directive, invoked for the first time in 2022 in response to the war in Ukraine, enables swift, collective protection—aiding in granting residence rights, work eligibility, and social welfare to large groups of displaced persons without individual asylum procedures

2.1 The initiatives of the Internationale Telematic University UNINETTUNO for migrants and refugees

In such a context, the International Telematic University UNINETTUNO, has carried out several initiatives to help promote the inclusion and integration of migrants and refugees, in line with EU policies. A central element of UNINETTUNO's institutional mission is the democratization of knowledge through digital innovation, multilingual education, and the promotion of intercultural dialogue. This vision is rooted in the belief that education must be a universal right and that digital technologies can serve as powerful equalizers, granting access to learning opportunities even to the most marginalized groups. In this perspective, the University has long placed migrants and refugees at the center of its internationalization strategy, developing tools, programs, and partnerships that directly respond to their educational and social needs [Garito, 2016].

The most emblematic initiative in this regard is the *University for Refugees* (www.universitaperrifugiati.it), a global platform designed to give refugees access to higher education without geographical or bureaucratic barriers. Accessible in four languages—Italian, English, French and Arabic—it enables refugees to pursue university studies, enroll in professional training and retraining programs, or simply improve their linguistic skills to facilitate integration into host societies. What makes this initiative unique is its dual focus: on the one hand, it provides tools for the recognition of prior academic qualifications and professional competences obtained in the country of origin; on the other hand, it supports host communities by offering courses on Arabic language and culture, thereby promoting mutual understanding and cultural exchange. In this way, the platform embodies UNINETTUNO's commitment to building bridges between communities and transforming education into a driver of social cohesion [Garito, 2017; Garito, 2020]. The initiative has been officially presented at the United Nations, which recognized its importance for achieving the 2030 SDGs, in particular Goal 4 (Quality Education) and Goal 10 (Reduce Inequalities).

Beyond this flagship project, UNINETTUNO has coordinated and participated in numerous EU-funded research and innovation projects addressing migration and inclusion from different angles. UNINETTUNO embraced a strong technological approach through the leading of the Horizon 2020 project *REBUILD*, which co-created digital platforms and ICT solutions with the active involvement of both migrants and local authorities in Italy, Spain, and Greece. By adopting a participatory design model, the project ensured that integration strategies reflected the lived experiences of migrants while equipping public administrations with innovative tools for more effective management [Garito, 2021; Pollini, 2021; Garito, 2022].

Also, through *VIEWS* (Erasmus+), the University supported the professional development of educators working with migrant learners, designing competence self-assessment tools and open educational resources to better meet the needs of diverse classrooms. The *Destinazione Comune* project took a territorial perspective, focusing on holders of international protection in the Lazio region of Italy, and implemented integrated pathways combining housing, employment, and socio-cultural activities to foster autonomy and long-term inclusion. In the field of youth and vulnerable groups, *RE-FUTURE* (Erasmus+) provided unaccompanied refugee minors with a voice, training them to use video and digital media as storytelling tools. The project culminated in a documentary created directly by the minors, offering an authentic perspective on their hopes, fears, and integration pathways.

Taken together, these initiatives illustrate UNINETTUNO's holistic and systemic approach to migrant and refugee inclusion. Rather than treating migrants as passive recipients of aid, the University positions them as active agents of knowledge production and social change, while also working with educators, policymakers, and local communities to create more resilient and inclusive societies. From digital platforms and ICT innovation to community-based integration and higher education reforms, UNINETTUNO's work demonstrates how an academic institution can extend its role beyond teaching and research, acting as a true laboratory of social innovation at the European and global level.

3. The PIPE project

Against this backdrop of structural migration challenges and ambitious EU policy frameworks, the *PIPE Project* (*Programme of Inclusion for Migrant People at risk of social Exclusion*) emerges as a concrete response aimed at translating principles into practice. Conceived as a collaborative European initiative in the framework of the Erasmus+ programme, PIPE reflects the vision that education and mentorship are not only tools for integration but also pathways to empowerment. The project seeks to go beyond emergency support or short-term interventions, instead fostering sustainable mechanisms of inclusion in which migrants themselves take on an active role.

At its core, PIPE adopts a circular model of integration: migrants who have already established themselves in host societies are trained to become mentors and facilitators for newcomers. In this way, the project builds a self-sustaining community of support, where experience, resilience, and cultural knowledge are shared horizontally rather than imposed from above. The objectives are threefold: first, to equip professionals and educators with practical tools to better accompany migrant learners; second, to strengthen the soft skills, cultural awareness, and employability of migrants themselves; and third, to create digital resources—such as an online guide and gamified learning pathways—that ensure access to knowledge, rights, and opportunities.

The strength of PIPE lies in its multinational partnership, which brings together six institutions from five European countries, each contributing complementary expertise. EVM (Spain), the project coordinator, offers long-standing experience in education and social innovation. The Institut für Roma und Minderheiten (Germany) brings a focus on vulnerable communities and intercultural mediation. Aalborg University (Denmark) contributes its tradition of problem-based learning and educational technology. Universidad de La Laguna (Spain) provides academic expertise on migration and inclusion processes. Hellenic Mediterranean University (Greece) engages through its laboratories of social work and community development. Finally, MAG-UNINETTUNO (Italy) extends the legacy of the International Telematic University UNINETTUNO, ensuring the availability of multilingual e-learning platforms and digital tools tailored to migrant learners.

Together, these partners embody PIPE's vision: to create an inclusive ecosystem where knowledge, skills, and community bonds converge, enabling migrants not just to adapt to European societies, but to thrive as full and active participants. The main objectives of the project include to:

- offer more help, service and training to migrants, as well as accreditation through Europass or microcredentials
- work together with partners across Europe to solve the greatest immigration issues of the century
- enable migrants to use their skills to contribute to the receiving society and acclimate to the culture
- help make the arrival of migrants less traumatic for the migrants and the receiving society to promote harmony and inclusion
- raise awareness in schools and societies to diminish fear and hatred.

The project has started at the beginning of 2025 and it is now halfway through implementation. The following sections describe the products developed so far and those expected to be developed by the end of the project.

3.1 Early outcomes

In the context of the project, several key products were developed to support the inclusion of migrants. The main results already achieved by the project are detailed below, together with their contents and objectives.

Toolbox for Professionals

The Toolbox for Professionals is a multilingual digital platform that serves as a collection of resources for practitioners, volunteers and institutions working with migrants. Designed to be easy to use and translated into several languages. This toolbox takes a multidimensional (linguistic, cultural and behavioural) approach to support the integration and empowerment of migrants. The aim is to provide practical materials, guides and tools to help create inclusive and culturally aware environments, while strengthening the skills of those working in the reception sector. The platform, which is constantly updated, also helps to build a European network for sharing good practices and raises awareness on inclusion and diversity through training of public bodies and volunteers involved. Within it, resources are organised in three main thematic areas:

- **Language:** a comprehensive guide for teaching the national language to migrants, which can also be used by educators and volunteers without specific training. This section provides accessible teaching methodologies that facilitate migrants' language acquisition and promote intercultural communication, thus contributing to stronger and more inclusive communities.
- **Culture:** an in-depth cultural guide, accompanied by a practical action plan, designed to support professionals in developing intercultural awareness and competence. This section also includes information on the host country (geography, history, politics, traditions) to help newcomers orient and adapt to the local context.
- **Diversity:** a strategic plan dedicated to diversity education, aimed in particular at institutions, public authorities and local communities. This part of the toolbox promotes more inclusive and conscious welcoming practices, encouraging empathy, reflection and institutional change in the approach towards migrants. Tools are offered to detect diversity training needs and to monitor progress over time in order to continuously improve inclusion policies

Through these components, the Toolbox for Professionals (accessible on the project's official website) represents an open repository of resources to support those working in migrant integration. It provides

standardised guidelines for the non-formal training of practitioners and helps to standardise competences across Europe, while creating a space for transnational cooperation and knowledge exchange.

Guide for Teaching National Language for Migrants

The Guide for Teaching National Language for Migrants is a comprehensive handbook developed to support organisations, teachers and volunteers in teaching the language of the host country to migrants. This result is a collaboration of experts from Spain, Denmark, Greece, Italy and Germany and thus reflects diverse perspectives on language teaching in multicultural contexts. The overall objective of the guide is to provide effective language learning tools that foster not only the acquisition of language skills, but also the social inclusion and autonomy of migrants in the new context. The main contents of the Guide are:

- International approach: The guide amalgamates contributions and good practices from five countries, offering a rich, multicultural view of national language teaching methods for migrants. This comparative perspective helps to understand different realities and to adopt flexible teaching strategies.
- Eight-chapter structure: the handbook is organised into eight thematic chapters covering a wide range of topics. It starts with an analysis of why it is important to teach the local language to migrants and then addresses the best pedagogical strategies, a critical analysis of existing teaching materials and the integration of modern technologies in the learning process. Highly topical cross-cutting issues such as gender equality and environmental sustainability are also addressed in order to contextualise language teaching in contemporary challenges.
- Innovative and inclusive methods: the guide provides practical teaching methodologies and operational suggestions for effectively teaching language to migrants, even in vulnerable situations. Different pedagogical approaches are illustrated, from intercultural education to strategies for language empowerment of learners, in order to create more inclusive and culturally sensitive learning environments.
- Intercultural dialogue and 'pedagogy of hospitality': at the heart of the work is the concept of learning as mutual exchange. The guide encourages trainers to adopt a pedagogy of hospitality, in which language teaching becomes a two-way process: migrants are not merely passive recipients, but actively participate by bringing their own experience. This intercultural approach fosters a climate of mutual respect and understanding, where the host community also learns and grows through interaction.
- Richness of resources: in addition to theoretical and methodological content, the guidebook provides a vast repertoire of practical resources. There are numerous links to teaching materials, online tools, educational kits and information content on the topic of migration, which facilitate teachers' work and allow lessons to be expanded with additional activities and insights. This ensures that teachers have the necessary resources at their fingertips to adapt teaching to the needs of their migrant students.

The language guide provides both a solid theoretical basis and concrete tools for teaching the language in an effective and culturally sensitive manner. Its ultimate goal is to promote the active integration of migrants through language, understood not only as a means of communication but also as a bridge to social inclusion. By adopting the proposed strategies, educators can contribute to making language learning a mutually enhancing experience that empowers migrants and strengthens cohesion with the local community. The guide

is available for free download on the PIPE platform and has been translated into six languages (English, Spanish, Italian, Greek, Danish and German) so that it can be used in all project partner countries.

Guide and Action Plan for Cultural Training for Professionals

This guide with an integrated action plan is therefore essential for anyone involved in the field: it is intended for a wide range of users, including local policy-makers, public managers, trainers, educators, non-profit organisations and even researchers interested in innovative methodologies in the field of inclusion. Each of these actors can find in the document targeted guidance for their own field, with the common aim of improving their practices and coordinating their efforts towards a more inclusive society. The Guide and Action Plan for the Cultural Education of Professionals is available for download on the official project website (Toolbox for Professionals) and is actively promoted for its contents to be applied in the field. Indeed, all partners and practitioners are encouraged to use it and to put the recommendations provided into practice by integrating them into their own training programmes and policies. This deliverable represents a shared European reference point designed to harmonise and improve approaches to intercultural training for integration practitioners. The Guide and Action Plan for Cultural Training for Professionals is a comprehensive document designed to improve the intercultural competences of those working with migrants, refugees and asylum seekers. Published as Deliverable 2.4 of the project, this guide is a key resource that helps professionals and stakeholders (public bodies, NGOs, trainers, etc.) to address in a structured way the challenges related to the cultural inclusion of migrants. In other words, it offers a framework and practical tools to design and implement effective intercultural training pathways within organisations and communities working in integration. Its key contents and objectives are outlined below:

- **Analysis and methodologies:** The guide presents a detailed analysis of the challenges and opportunities related to migrant integration, providing insights into current trends, recurring obstacles and possible policy solutions that have emerged at the European level. On this theoretical basis, step-by-step operational methodologies are then described that enable the different actors (e.g. reception centres, associations, institutions) to implement the project's intercultural strategies in a clear and confident manner. This combination of analysis and practice helps to understand the "why" of problems and at the same time the "how" to intervene.
- **Best practices and case studies:** to make the concepts concrete, the document includes numerous best practice examples and case studies from real experience. Successful approaches adopted in different European contexts are illustrated and lessons learnt from these experiences. These practical cases offer replicable models and useful insights, helping readers to understand what works in the field of cultural education and inclusion.
- **Practical tools:** the guide also provides an operational toolkit to facilitate the daily work of practitioners. Templates, checklists and digital solutions are provided that practitioners can use directly in their activities. For instance, there are templates to plan training sessions, checklists to assess acquired intercultural competences, and indications on platforms and online resources to be used to improve migrants' involvement.
- **Wide range of topics covered:** The document covers a broad spectrum of topics relevant to intercultural training. Among the main topics addressed are strategic frameworks for setting up effective cultural training programmes, guidelines for collaboration between the various actors involved (in order to create strong partnerships and share knowledge), the use of innovative solutions - e.g. digital tools and modern methodologies - to increase the active involvement of migrants in training, and finally, monitoring and evaluation techniques to measure the impact of activities and

ensure continuous improvement. This thematic richness ensures that the guide addresses all critical aspects needed to build well-calibrated cultural integration programmes.

- **Impact and objectives pursued:** The adoption of this guide enables various stakeholders to achieve several strategic benefits. In particular, practitioners who follow its recommendations can deepen and adopt existing best practices on intercultural competence, strengthen their own strategies for engaging migrants (thus achieving a greater impact of their actions), foster greater collaboration between agencies and organisations (creating an interconnected network of mutually supportive practitioners), and ensure the long-term sustainability of initiatives launched. In essence, the guide aims to professionalise and make inclusion efforts more effective, creating synergies and continuity over time.

This integrated action plan guide is therefore essential for anyone involved in the field: it is intended for a wide range of users, including local policy-makers, public managers, trainers, educators, non-profit organisations and even researchers interested in innovative methodologies in the field of inclusion. Each of these actors can find in the document targeted guidance for their own field, with the common aim of improving their practices and coordinating their efforts towards a more inclusive society. The Guide and Action Plan for the Cultural Education of Professionals is available for download on the official project website (Toolbox for Professionals) and is actively promoted for its contents to be applied in the field. Indeed, all partners and practitioners are encouraged to use it and to put the recommendations provided into practice by integrating them into their own training programmes and policies. This deliverable represents a shared European reference point designed to harmonise and improve approaches to intercultural training for integration practitioners.

3.2 **Expected future outcomes**

In addition to the outcomes described above, the PIPE project is producing or has planned further significant outputs consistent with its goals of socio-cultural inclusion of migrants:

- **Strategic Plan for Diversity Education:** as mentioned, a key component of the toolbox is a strategic plan aimed at institutions and local communities to strengthen a culture of inclusion. This output provides guidelines on how public bodies and organisations can train their staff in diversity management. In practice, the plan offers tools to analyse internal training needs, implement more inclusive policies and monitor progress over time regarding diversity awareness. The adoption of this plan at the institutional level aims to encourage changes in organisational procedures and behaviour to make the reception of migrants more efficient and equitable.
- **Training programmes on soft skills and mentoring for migrants:** As part of Work Package 3, PIPE is developing innovative training programmes aimed directly at adult migrants. These programmes focus on the development of so-called soft skills (e.g. effective communication, teamwork, problem solving, emotional intelligence) and also include cultural awareness modules and mentoring initiatives. The idea is to improve the employability and social integration of migrants by providing them with skills useful in the world of work and everyday life, as well as peer support networks. For example, the project plans to create mentorship opportunities in which already well-integrated migrants mentor newcomers to facilitate their orientation in the host society. These training programmes - currently under development and testing - are designed to be flexible and adaptable to different national contexts in order to meet the specific needs identified in each partner country.
- **Mobile application for migrants:** A further planned output (under Work Package 4) is the development of a smartphone app for migrants. This digital application will serve as a practical tool to provide migrants with immediate and user-friendly access to training resources and support services. In line

with PIPE's focus on technological innovation, the app will include features that allow recipients to find out about available services, take courses or training modules independently (e.g. language modules or basic skills tutorials) and receive useful updates for their integration. In addition, the app is expected to adopt gamification elements (playful approach) to encourage active participation of users. The importance of this tool is underlined by the fact that the results of the preliminary research conducted by the project are guiding precisely the development of this app, in order to respond in a targeted manner to the needs that have emerged in the different national realities. Once completed, the mobile app will be an essential complement to the other PIPE resources, ensuring that migrants can benefit from the support offered by the project on the move and at any time.

4. Conclusions

The PIPE project is progressively building a comprehensive ecosystem of resources and practices that address the multifaceted dimensions of migrant inclusion. By combining the Toolbox for Professionals—with its structured guides on language teaching, cultural awareness, and diversity management—with tailored training programmes and forthcoming digital solutions for migrants themselves, PIPE demonstrates a holistic approach to integration. Each output is designed to be open, free, and easily accessible, ensuring that both practitioners and beneficiaries can adopt and adapt the tools in their specific national and local contexts.

This openness is not merely a technical feature but reflects the project's underlying philosophy: inclusion cannot be achieved through isolated actions, but requires collaborative, replicable, and scalable models that foster long-term change. By offering resources in multiple languages, grounded in real European contexts, PIPE lowers barriers to participation and creates opportunities for migrants to engage actively in their host societies, rather than being positioned as passive recipients of aid.

Moreover, the project's emphasis on cultural training, mentoring, and the development of soft skills signals a shift in perspective. Integration is not understood only in terms of economic self-sufficiency, but as a process of mutual adaptation and empowerment, where communities learn to value diversity and migrants gain the tools to become active contributors. In this sense, PIPE is not simply producing educational materials; it is contributing to a European narrative of inclusion, one that links innovation in digital education with the fundamental values of solidarity, equity, and respect for human rights.

By bridging the gap between research, policy, and practice, PIPE also provides transferable models that can inspire future initiatives at both national and European levels. Its integrated ecosystem demonstrates how EU-funded projects can catalyze innovation in social inclusion, strengthen transnational cooperation, and promote resilient and welcoming communities across Europe. Ultimately, the project's long-term legacy will not only lie in its individual outputs, but in its capacity to inspire institutions, educators, policymakers, and migrants themselves to work together towards a more inclusive and cohesive society.

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Fostering Inclusive Digital Education: The BERTL Certificate Program for Accessibility Awareness in Higher Education

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Abstract

The project *BERTL – Barrierfree Design for Teaching and Learning*, based at the University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien and funded by the City of Vienna, aims to raise awareness and build practical competencies around digital accessibility in higher education. As part of this initiative, a modular certificate program was developed to engage academic staff and educators in inclusive teaching practices and empower them to reduce barriers for students with disabilities.

The *BERTL Certificate* consists of three workshops: (1) an interactive awareness module exploring everyday challenges faced by students with impairments, using simulations and reflection exercises; (2) a hands-on technical workshop focusing on accessible digital documents (Word, PowerPoint, PDF); and (3) a Moodle-focused session where participants directly apply accessibility principles to their course environments. The curriculum blends legal, pedagogical, and technical perspectives to offer a holistic training experience.

Starting in September 2025, the BERTL Certificate will be integrated into our internal professional development program at the University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien. The program offers academic staff a comprehensive and hands-on introduction to digital accessibility—not just as a technical requirement, but as a mindset that actively shapes inclusive teaching practices. What I particularly value is the modular structure that combines personal reflection with legal, pedagogical, and technical expertise, culminating in practical application within Moodle. Feedback from the pilot phase clearly shows: even small adjustments in course design can have a significant impact for students with disabilities. At the same time, the BERTL Certificate sends an important institutional signal. It aligns with our quality assurance efforts and reflects our commitment to embedding accessibility into everyday university life—not just individually, but systemically and sustainably.

This talk will present the conceptual framework, pilot implementation, and initial feedback from the certificate program, which is currently being integrated into the university's professional development and quality assurance processes. The initiative builds upon insights published in the *FNMA Magazine (4/2023)* [1] and presented at the *Austrian Research Forum 2024* [2], where the institutional responsibilities and structural challenges of higher education for students with disabilities were analysed.

The presentation also explores how institutional strategies for digital accessibility can be operationalized through targeted training programs, and how advisory boards, peer groups, and cross-departmental collaboration support sustainable implementation.

Keywords

Universal Design for Learning (UDL), Inclusive Higher Education, Barrier-Free Design, Accessibility Certificate, Simulation-Based Learning

1. Introduction :

While digital accessibility in higher education has long been discussed through the lenses of technology and pedagogy, its relevance as a strategic institutional concern is often overlooked. The BERTL project (Barrierfree Design for Teaching and Learning), based at the University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien and funded by the City of Vienna, seeks to close this gap. It positions accessibility not merely as a compliance issue or technical challenge, but as a holistic quality indicator for inclusive education and a marker of institutional maturity.

In this context, the BERTL Certificate emerges as more than a continuing education offer for academic staff—it functions as a strategic lever for implementing inclusion across multiple layers of university life. Combining experiential learning, legal frameworks, and technical skill-building, the certificate aims to foster a shift in mindset: from accessibility as an individual responsibility to accessibility as an institutional value.

Higher education institutions (HEIs) across Europe are increasingly challenged to demonstrate how they meet legal obligations and uphold societal responsibilities related to inclusion, equality, and accessibility. Legal instruments such as the European Accessibility Act (Directive (EU) 2019/882) [3], which has entered into force in Austria in January 2025, require organizations with over 400 employees to appoint an Accessibility Officer—highlighting the growing recognition of accessibility as a governance issue. At the same time, frameworks such as the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities reinforce the obligation of HEIs to ensure equitable participation not only for students but also for staff, researchers, and external partners.

These policy shifts are mirrored at the national level, where accessibility and diversity are increasingly embedded in quality assurance processes, accreditation procedures, and funding calls. In Austria, initiatives such as the family-friendly university certification [4] and the integration of an Employer Value Proposition (EVP) reflect the growing importance of institutional identity, inclusiveness, and employer branding. The BERTL Certificate contributes to this broader transformation in several ways.

First, it offers a modular, practice-oriented training program that builds awareness and applied skills among teaching and administrative staff. Second, it is embedded into the internal professional development framework of the university, where it acts as a structured pathway to promote inclusive teaching practices. Third, it directly supports institutional strategies in Human Resources (HR), Diversity, Equity & Inclusion (DEI), and Quality Assurance by translating abstract policy objectives into actionable training formats. In doing so, it not only enhances the digital and pedagogical accessibility of learning environments but also strengthens the university's internal culture and external reputation.

This paper presents the conceptual foundations, implementation process, and initial experiences with the BERTL Certificate. While a structured evaluation has not yet been conducted, early feedback and pilot-phase observations suggest promising engagement and institutional relevance. The paper discusses how accessibility training can be integrated into institutional structures, how strategic alignment with HR and DEI goals can be achieved, and what lessons can be drawn for the wider European higher education community. Ultimately, it argues that digital accessibility must be re-framed as a strategic opportunity for universities to demonstrate leadership, foster innovation, and truly embody the values of equity and participation.

2. Methodology:

The development and implementation of the *BERTL Certificate* is embedded within a broader institutional strategy to integrate digital accessibility into human resources, professional development, and organizational culture. The methodological approach combines modular training design, structural integration in HR processes, and iterative development based on continuous feedback loops.

The BERTL Certificate is composed of three independent workshop modules, each targeting key competencies for inclusive digital teaching. These modules are:

- Awareness Workshop (90 minutes): Introduces foundational concepts of accessibility in higher education, including legal frameworks, types of impairments, and self-experience simulations designed to foster perspective-taking and empathy.
- Digital Accessibility Workshop (120 minutes): Focuses on the practical creation of accessible documents (Word, PowerPoint, PDF) using institutional templates and widely available tools. Participants apply accessibility standards directly to their own teaching materials.
- Inclusive Moodle Workshop (90 minutes): Addresses the design of accessible digital learning environments, with hands-on activities to adapt Moodle courses in terms of structure, navigation, contrast, and assessment tools.

All modules are offered as stand-alone sessions to ensure low-threshold access and flexibility for participants. In addition, bundled formats are offered on key awareness-raising occasions such as the *International Day of Persons with Disabilities*, enhancing visibility and institutional engagement.

Integration into HR and DEI Strategy

Starting in September 2025, the BERTL Certificate will be fully integrated into the university's internal professional development framework, coordinated by the HR department. This integration allows accessibility training to become part of routine staff development and connects DEI objectives with standard HR processes such as recruitment, appraisal interviews, and individual development planning.

Key aspects of this strategic embedding include:

- Institutional anchoring of Equality Management within the HR department, ensuring that accessibility and diversity are seen as core components of organizational development rather than peripheral concerns.
- Inclusion of DEI-related goals in annual planning cycles and institutional strategy setting.
- Operational rollout via standard HR channels, including training initiatives, internal communications, and legal instruments.
- Framing DEI as a functional responsibility, encouraging leadership and staff to adopt accessibility as part of their regular duties rather than an optional or additional task.
- Positioning accessibility as an element of the university's employer branding, aligning inclusion with talent recruitment and retention strategies.

Dynamic Development and Quality Assurance

The certificate program is embedded in the university's continuous improvement process (KVP). Evaluation mechanisms—including participant feedback and peer reviews—inform the annual refinement of training content and delivery formats. This ensures that the workshops remain current, relevant, and tailored to the evolving needs of both educators and learners.

Furthermore, the BERTL project maintains strong collaboration with the university's Teaching and Learning Center, the Equality & Diversity Office, and a cross-sectoral BERTL Advisory Board consisting of stakeholders from academia, industry, and user advocacy groups. This network provides feedback, identifies new challenges, and supports the co-development of tools such as the BERTL Accessibility Toolbox and the BERTL Simulation Lab.

3. Results: Preliminary Findings and Institutional Impact

Although a full-scale evaluation of the BERTL Certificate is still forthcoming, a number of structural and cultural impacts have already become visible since the program’s initial rollout. Initial evidence is based on a pre-implementation needs assessment, systematic tracking of training activities, and cross-departmental observations from those involved in accessibility and inclusion initiatives.

Baseline Needs and Strategic Design

A university-wide needs assessment conducted prior to the launch revealed widespread interest in accessibility-related training among academic and administrative staff (Figure 1). Respondents cited low familiarity with current standards and expressed a strong desire for practical tools, institutional support, and peer exchange. These findings directly informed the modular structure of the certificate, including its focus on self-experience, hands-on application, and standalone accessibility of each workshop.

Figure 1: Responses to the statement “For the following cases, I lack information or advisory support for implementation”. The radar charts show perceived knowledge and support gaps across different accessibility dimensions, differentiated by type of impairment (A) visual impairments, (B) motor impairments and (C) neurodivergent conditions (e.g. autism, ADHD). Higher values indicate a stronger perceived lack of information or institutional guidance at that time.

Institutional Uptake and Visibility

Since the BERTL project launch in 2022, a dual-track approach to accessibility capacity building has emerged at the University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien.

On the other hand, the integration of accessibility and inclusion topics into the official HR-led internal training program has led to a marked increase in participation and visibility. Over the academic years 2023/2024 and 2024/2025, 16 additional workshops were delivered under the university’s internal professional development program, offering a combined 243 training hours and reaching 251 participants. These formats covered topics such as digital accessibility, inclusive communication, and universal design for learning.

This collaborative effort between the BERTL project team and the Human Resources department has resulted in the establishment of a sustainable training ecosystem that links hands-on expertise with strategic HR and DEI objectives. Together, these developments illustrate the BERTL Certificate’s dual function: as both a direct intervention and a strategic enabler of systemic institutional change.

Organisational and Institutional Impact

The introduction of the BERTL Certificate generates visible impact across multiple levels of the university:

- **Individual Level:** Academic staff acquire concrete competencies for designing accessible materials and digital learning environments. Although a full evaluation is pending, early feedback and baseline data suggest that DEI-related offerings are well-attended and valued. Informal teaching evaluations and anecdotal evidence point to tangible improvements in the learning experience for students with disabilities.
- **Organisational Level:** The certificate fosters cross-functional collaboration between key stakeholders—including Human Resources, the BERTL project team, the Teaching & Learning Center, IT services, quality assurance, and student representatives. This interdepartmental approach contributes to the development of a more inclusive and coherent organizational culture.
- **Institutional Level:** By embedding accessibility and diversity in the remit of HR and Equality Management, and by aligning workshop content with faculty-level initiatives and quality processes, the BERTL Certificate supports the long-term integration of accessibility into the university's strategic operations. Its contribution to initiatives such as employer branding, internal capability-building, and diversity certification reinforces its role as a structural component of institutional development.

In this way, the BERTL Certificate exemplifies how targeted training can evolve into a strategic HR instrument—shaping not just individual awareness, but institutional priorities and systems.

4. Discussion: Opportunities and Challenges

The implementation of the BERTL Certificate has highlighted both opportunities and structural challenges in embedding digital accessibility within higher education institutions. It offers practical insights into what it takes to move beyond isolated awareness-raising efforts toward a systemic, HR-driven approach to inclusion.

Opportunities:

- **Low-threshold Access:** By offering its three modules as stand-alone sessions, the BERTL Certificate lowers the entry barrier for participation and fosters broader engagement across departments and staff roles.
- **Quick Wins, High Impact:** Even small improvements—such as accessible PDF formatting or more inclusive Moodle course structures—can significantly enhance the experience of students with disabilities. These “quick wins” create momentum and reinforce the value of inclusive design.
- **Reputation and Visibility:** The project has contributed to the university's external profile through international conference contributions (e.g. IHE 2025) and related publications, positioning UAS Technikum Wien as an active voice in the discourse on inclusion and educational innovation.
- **Strategic Alignment:** The certificate is not a stand-alone initiative but is woven into existing DEI and HR strategies—such as the university's re-certification as a family-friendly university, the development of inclusive recruiting standards, and the annual planning of staff training programs.

Challenges

- **Resource Demands:** Sustained implementation requires long-term investment in time, personnel, and budget—particularly for updating content, maintaining partnerships, and expanding capacity.
- **Cultural Change:** For accessibility to be more than a matter of legal compliance, it must be embraced as a core cultural value. This requires continuous communication, leadership buy-in, and opportunities for reflection and dialogue.

- Structural Embedding: Pilot initiatives risk fading out if they are not institutionalized. Ensuring long-term impact means translating projects into permanent structures and workflows within the university.

5. Conclusion

From both a Human Resources and DEI perspective, digital accessibility is not merely a technical detail—it is a critical marker of institutional maturity and educational quality. Universities that treat accessibility as a core element of their personnel and organizational strategies enhance not only equity for students, but also their competitiveness and attractiveness as employers.

The most effective lever in this context is the structural anchoring of equality and accessibility within the HR department. This integration ensures that inclusion is not handled as an optional discourse, but rather as an embedded component of professional development, strategic planning, and quality assurance.

The BERTL Certificate exemplifies how continuing education, when strategically designed and institutionally supported, can act as a transformative force. By combining modular training, cross-departmental collaboration, and long-term structural commitment, the program contributes meaningfully to a culture of inclusion—showing that accessibility must not only be taught but lived as a guiding principle of academic and organizational life.

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Student Dropout Rates in Higher Distance Education: An Empirical Investigation at the Hellenic Open University (HOU)

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Abstract

The study examines student dropout rates at the Hellenic Open University (HOU), Greece's largest institution offering exclusively Distance Education (DE). Focusing on demographic factors and programme structures over the period 2016-2022, the study analyses data from 69,077 enrolled students, including 17,675 withdrawals across HOU's four faculties. The findings reveal that dropout rates are higher among male and undergraduate students, as well as among those enrolled in programmes with annual articulation. Also, geographic distribution shows that regions with high enrolment experience high dropout rates, and certain special categories—such as prisoners, Roma, and dependent individuals—exhibit disproportionately higher dropout tendencies. Age was not found to influence dropout rates significantly. Moreover, passive withdrawal, where students discontinue studies without formal notification, constituted the majority of cases. The study underlines the complexity of dropout as a multifaceted phenomenon influenced by institutional, demographic, personal, and socioeconomic factors, emphasizing the necessity for targeted interventions to improve student retention in distance education contexts.

Keywords

distance higher education, dropout, Hellenic Open University

1. Introduction

Dropout in the context of DE refers to the phenomenon where students make the final decision to discontinue their studies and fail to complete their academic programme (Bağrıacık Yılmaz & Karataş, 2022). Dropout rates in DE have a crucial impact on student outcomes, institutional finances, and accreditation (Rahmani et al., 2024). Research over the years has shown that dropout rates in DE programmes are considerably higher—often double or more—than those in traditional, face-to-face academic settings, fluctuating from 20% to as high as 80% (Appavoo et al., 2023; Radovan, 2019; Simpson, 2008; Xenos et al., 2002). Distance learners confront several barriers that contribute to higher dropout rates, including feelings of isolation, difficulties in balancing work, family, and studies, and inadequate institutional support (Bağrıacık Yılmaz & Karataş, 2022).

Monitoring dropout rates in DE is important for several reasons. Firstly, the identification of dropout patterns can help universities to focus on at-risk student groups and implement targeted interventions (Bağrıacık Yılmaz & Karataş, 2022). Secondly, dropout affects both students—who lose time, resources, and opportunities—and universities, which face challenges in terms of reputation and operations (Pierrakeas et al., 2020). Subsequently, high dropout rates often indicate poor academic performance and undermine human capital development (Stylianou & Milidis, 2024). Analysing the causes of dropout allows institutions to improve their

services, such as counselling and educational assistance, and to address institutional and administrative barriers (Appavoo et al., 2023; Radovan, 2019).

The primary objective of this study was to conduct an empirical investigation into dropout rates at the HOU, the largest institution in Greece that offers DE exclusively. Over the years, HOU has represented a critical setting to investigate and understand dropout dynamics in higher DE. The HOU offers both undergraduate and postgraduate Study Programmes (SPs), comprised of Thematic Units (TUs) and implemented under an annual or semester-based schedule. More specifically, the study aimed to investigate dropout phenomena at the HOU by examining data collected from 2016 to 2022, with particular focus on the following research questions (RQs):

- RQ1: Is students' demographic profile (i.e., age, gender, geographic region, and other personal characteristics) related to dropout rates?
- RQ2: Is the structure of distance education programmes (i.e., annual and semestrial SPs, graduate and postgraduate SPs) related to dropout rates?

By examining these RQs, the study intends to contribute to the development of systemic improvements and targeted support mechanisms designed to reduce dropout rates and enhance student retention within the context of distance higher education.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1. Defining Dropout

Dropout is generally defined as abandoning one's studies before completing a programme. However, dropout is a multi-dimensional and complex phenomenon, and there are notable differences in how universities define and measure dropout. For example, some studies focus on non-enrolment in consecutive semesters, while others focus on academic non-completion. Additionally, dropout is often used interchangeably with concepts such as attrition and non-completion, which in turn are juxtaposed with antonyms like retention, persistence, continuance, completion, etc., thus, the specific term is often surrounded by a degree of ambiguity (Xavier & Meneses, 2020). Generally speaking, definitions of dropout vary according to the administrative and educational policies of the universities in question, and their multitude makes it difficult to standardize the measurement of dropout rates (Appavoo et al., 2023). What is more, every distance learning programme may have unique dropout causes and patterns, implying that “dropout” is a relative term highly dependent on context (Budiman, 2018; Elibol & Bozkurt, 2023). According to Radovan (2019), it is necessary first to adequately define dropout before analyzing its causes and introducing measures to reduce it. This is because the definition strongly influences the identification of causes leading to dropout.

2.2. Dropout factors in DE

The abandonment of DE programmes is not the result of a single cause, but rather a combination of institutional, personal, demographic, and socioeconomic factors. At the institutional level, inadequate support systems and inflexible programme structure contribute significantly to dropout rates, considering that in DE, we are dealing with working adults who need flexible learning paths. Also, poor interaction with teachers and inadequate academic guidance make it difficult for students to meet programme requirements (Appavoo et al., 2023; Simpson, 2008). In addition, according to Simpson (2008), the open-door admission policy adopted by several universities can lead to higher dropout rates. Since in such cases no previous qualifications are required for enrollment, students who lack the necessary preparation are more likely to drop out than their qualified peers.

Financial and employment factors can contribute significantly to dropout rates and create barriers to persistence. For example, financial constraints such as tuition fee increase and sudden loss of income can affect students, forcing them to prioritize immediate survival over education (Bağrıacık Yılmaz & Karataş, 2022; Pierrakeas et al., 2020). In addition, professional obligations such as transfers, increased workload, or unexpected promotions have been found to disrupt study habits (Pierrakeas et al., 2004).

At the personal level, Pierrakeas et al. (2004) have shown that one of the reasons that can lead to dropping out of studies is the wrong programme choice. In this sense, the misalignment between students' expectations and programme content plays a critical role, as students who enroll in programmes that are not consistent with their professional or academic goals are more likely to drop out. Also, students with insufficient prior knowledge find it difficult to self-regulate their learning, which leads to discouragement and ultimately withdrawal (Pierrakeas et al., 2020). Furthermore, in DE environments with limited interaction, factors such as anxiety, self-doubt, and feelings of isolation further undermine uninterrupted learning (Appavoo et al., 2023; Ranasinghe et al., 2025).

Demographic factors also influence dropout rates. For example, in terms of age, younger students are more likely to drop out due to family obligations, while older students may face difficulties in balancing work and study (Appavoo et al., 2023; Ranasinghe et al., 2025). Gender also appears to have a significant impact. For example, Bağrıacık Yılmaz & Karataş (2022) report that female students confront greater hindrances in balancing caregiving roles with their academic pursuits. Finally, technological barriers—such as low digital literacy, inadequate infrastructure, and connectivity problems—also influence students' decisions to drop out or continue their studies (Rahmani et al., 2024).

The above presentation of the factors that influence dropout is not exhaustive. Numerous other factors are mentioned in the literature, which are included in specific dropout models that can be explored in depth. What we want to make clear in this section is that dropout is a multifaceted phenomenon that must be carefully investigated in the academic DL contexts in which it is applied.

2.3. Dropout conceptualisation in the HOU

In the HOU, dropout is defined as the percentage of enrolled students who withdraw per year of admission (note that if a student chooses to withdraw in the fifth year of his/her studies, his/her decision will be counted in the dropout rate for the year of admission). It is noted that HOU's students have the right to temporarily withdraw for some years from their studies without any penalty in order to overcome temporary barriers in their studies, but our focus is on those who are no longer students.

It is important to define here the distinction between active and passive withdrawal. Active withdrawal refers to cases where a student explicitly informs the university that he/she intends to leave a programme. Passive withdrawal, on the other hand, occurs when a student stops engaging with the programme but does not officially inform the university that he/she is no longer studying (Sánchez Román V. et al., 2024).

3. Methodology

3.1. Population and Sample

The study population included all students enrolled at the HOU during the period 2016-2022. This amounted to a total of 69,077 students. Of these, 17,675 had withdrawn from their studies. The students came from all four HOU Schools: the School of Science and Technology (SST), the School of Social Sciences (SSS), the School of Humanities (SHU), and the School of Applied Arts and Sustainable Design (SAASD).

3.2. Data Collection

The data were collected from the university's student registry. The variables collected for each student included: enrolment year, School, SP and its articulation (i.e., annual or semestrial SP), educational level (i.e., undergraduate or postgraduate SP), gender, age, year of withdrawal, and type of withdrawal (i.e., active or passive). Geographical data on the students' region of residence were also collected. Furthermore, the data included indicators for specific categories, such as prisoners, Roma, and persons with disabilities, as well as persons belonging to social support institutions, such as child protection structures, homeless, and dependent individuals.

It is notable that the HOU is supporting students through the tutors' facilitating role, the right to temporarily withdraw for some years from their studies, and the provision of advisement from the Counselling and Psychological Support Office. So, students get all the help they can before deciding to quit their studies.

3.3. Data Analysis

The data analysis primarily involved descriptive statistical methods to examine dropout rates across various aspects at the HOU from the amount of data collected over the period 2016- 2022. Percentages of enrolment and withdrawal were compared within the abovementioned data to identify disproportionate dropout trends. Differences between withdrawal and enrolment percentages were calculated to highlight cases with higher or lower dropout. Overall, the analysis focused on identifying patterns and disparities in dropout rates using summary statistics and comparative differences between withdrawn and enrolled percentages.

4. Results

Looking for a general trend within the dataset collected for the aforementioned period, it is observed that dropout rates decreased between 2016 and 2022 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dropout fluctuation of HOU's Study Programmes from 2016 to 2022

4.1. Gender Differences in Dropout

In terms of gender, Table 1 depicts a gender gap in dropout rates. Specifically, male students tend to dropout at a disproportionately higher rate than their enrolment rate ($D = +9.5$). In contrast, female students show dropout rates lower than their enrolment rates, indicating greater retention ($D = -9.5$).

Table 1: Dropout Rates by Gender (2016-2022)

Gender	% Enrolled	% Withdrawn	Difference (% Withdrawn – % Enrolled)
Male	35.8	45.3	+9.5
Female	64.2	54.7	-9.5
Total	100	100	0

4.2. Geographic Distribution of Dropout

The geographical distribution of dropout rates indicates that regions with higher enrollment rates tend to have higher dropout rates. For example, the region of Attica, with 41.3% of enrolled students, also has the highest dropout rate (44.0%). A similar trend is observed in other large regions, such as Thessaloniki and Achaea. Nevertheless, there are divergences in smaller regions. For example, the region of the Ionian Islands, which accounts for only 1.8% of enrolments, also accounts for 2.2% of dropouts and, on average, 32% of enrolled students from that region quit their studies. In all other regions, 23%-27% of enrolled students quit their studies on average, rising up to 28% for the enrolled students living abroad.

4.3. Dropout Among Special Categories

With regard to special categories of students, higher dropout rates are observed for some categories compared to others (Table 2). In particular, prisoners, Roma, dependent individuals, and students from child protection institutions have higher dropout rates compared to their enrollment rates. In contrast, students with disabilities show greater persistence, with dropout rates much lower than their enrolment rates (D= -21.7).

Table 2: Dropout Rates Among Special Categories at HOU (2016-2022)

Category	% Enrolled	% Withdrawn	Difference (% Withdrawn – % Enrolled)
Students with Disabilities	34.80	13.10	-21.7
Prisoners	26.90	35.70	+8.8
Released Prisoners	6.90	6.00	-0.9
Roma	8.90	12.60	+3.7
Dependent individuals	12.30	20.60	+8.3
Child Protection Institutions	8.10	10.60	+2.5
Homeless	2.00	1.50	-0.5
Total	100	100	0

4.4. Age and Dropout Trends

With regard to the investigation of age as a factor contributing to drop out, the almost identical average ages in both groups, together with the comparable standard deviations, suggest that age does not play a significant role in dropout trends at HOU (Table 3).

Table 3: Mean Age of Enrolled and Withdrawn Students

Population Group	Mean Age (Years)	Standard Deviation
Enrolled Students	35.6	8.3
Withdrawn Students	35.8	8.4

4.5. Dropout by Withdrawal Type

Passive withdrawals appear to account for the vast majority of student withdrawals in comparison to active withdrawals, a fact that shows that most withdrawals occur passively — through non-compliance with institutional requirements (e.g., failure to re-enrol or meet academic standards) — rather than through decisions officially communicated to the university (Table 4).

Table 4: Withdrawals by Type at HOU (2016–2022)

Withdrawal Type	Number of Withdrawals	Percentage (%)
Passive Withdrawal	15,487	88
Active Withdrawal	2,088	12
Total	17,575	100

4.6. Dropout Rates by Faculty and SP Articulation

Among the schools (Table 5), SST and SSS exhibit higher differences between their withdrawal and enrollment rates, with SST showing a particularly pronounced difference. In contrast, SHU and SAASD exhibit lower dropout rates compared to their enrolment rates, with SHU showing a remarkably low dropout rate (D= -9.8).

Table 5: Dropout Rates by Faculty (2016-2022)

Category	% Enrolled	% Withdrawn	Difference (% Withdrawn – % Enrolled)
Faculty			
School of Science and Technology (SST)	16.9	24.8	+7.9
School of Social Sciences (SSS)	41.7	43.7	+2
School of Humanities (SHU)	39.8	30	-9.8
School of Applied Arts & Sustainable Design (SAASD)	1.6	1.4	-0.2
Total	100	100	0

With regard to the SP articulation (Table 6), there is a clear dropout divergence between annual and semestrial articulation. More specifically, students in annual articulation drop out at a disproportionately higher rate than their enrollment rate (D= +10), while those in semestrial articulation show a significantly lower dropout rate (D= -10).

Table 6: Dropout Rates by SP Articulation (2016-2022)

SP articulation	% Enrolled	% Withdrawn	Difference (% Withdrawn – % Enrolled)
Annual	63.2	73.2	+10
Semestrial	36.8	26.8	-10
Total	100	100	0

4.7. Dropout Rates by Education Level

Regarding the education level, a divergence between undergraduate and graduate students is detected (Table 7). More specifically, undergraduate students exhibit a higher dropout rate compared to their enrolment rate (D= +15.8), while postgraduate students exhibit dropout rates proportionally lower than their enrolment rates, indicating greater persistence (D= -15.8).

Table 7: Dropout Rates by Education Level (2016-2022)

Education Level	% Enrolled	% Withdrawn	Difference (% Withdrawn – % Enrolled)
Undergraduate	32.6	48.4	+15.8
Postgraduate	67.4	51.6	-15.8
Total	100	100	0

5. Discussion

The aim of the study was to investigate dropout rates at the HOU. Descriptive statistical research was conducted for the period 2016-2022. The sample consisted of 69,077 enrolled and 17,675 withdrawn students from HOU's four faculties. Two RQs were investigated: the relation between students' demographic profile and dropout rates (RQ1), and the relation between SP structure and dropout rates (RQ2). The findings both confirm and expand upon prior literature and the concerns raised in the introduction.

More specifically, with regard to RQ1, the findings show that gender is an important demographic factor associated with dropout rates at the HOU. Specifically, male students seem to drop out at higher rates than female students. This is consistent with the findings of Xenos et al. (2002), who report that female students tend to show greater commitment to their studies. Similarly, Appavoo et al. (2023) detect greater persistence among female students and, therefore, greater academic resilience. In his research, Ranasinghe et al. (2025) report that external factors, such as professional obligations and financial pressures, significantly affect male students' continuation of their studies, especially in social contexts where they are the main breadwinners of the family.

However, in the studies by Pierrakeas et al. (2004) and Utami & Winarni (2022), no statistically significant differences between the sexes were found in dropout rates. It is noteworthy that Pierrakeas et al. (2020) reported a change over time in the previous trends found in the research by Xenos et al. (2002), which shows that male and female students now have similar persistence rates. It is equally interesting that the research by Stoessel et al. (2015) shows that female students are at greater risk of dropping out of distance learning programs, which can be explained by the smaller benefits they derive from their career-related goals and their strong dissatisfaction with the lack of social support in these programmes. Overall, the above findings show that the contribution of gender to dropout is not predetermined but is always subject to specific contexts related to the conditions of DE and the broader social conditions that determine the course of study.

Regarding special categories, vulnerable groups such as prisoners, Roma, and dependent individuals had significantly higher dropout rates. This finding partially aligns with the existing literature. For example, Díaz-Vicario et al. (2019) mention structural and cultural barriers faced by Roma youth, including community skepticism and institutional insensitivity, which undermine educational persistence. It is interesting that, while the current study found people with disabilities to exhibit stronger retention, the research of Bulut & Bulbul (2024) mentions that male students with disabilities show a higher tendency to drop out of higher education compared to female students, a finding that is explained partially by socio-demographic and behavioral factors.

As far as age is concerned, there is no evidence of a tendency to drop out, given that the average age of enrolled and withdrawn students was almost the same. This finding contrasts with the existing literature, which suggests that different age groups face different issues that affect the likelihood of dropping out of university. For example, students in the 30-39 age group often find it difficult to balance their professional and family obligations, which contributes to higher dropout rates. Younger students (<30) are also vulnerable due to a lack of academic preparation and pressure in balancing academic studies with work obligations (Pierrakeas et al., 2004; Ranasinghe et al., 2025). What is more, students aged 50 and over have lower dropout rates, likely due to stronger motivation for personal development goals (Stoessel et al., 2015). These findings indicate that age does indeed play a role in dropout, but not on its own, only in combination with a number of other factors such as those mentioned above. Therefore, the absence of a link between age and dropout in the present study needs further investigation and cross-referencing with respect to factors such as those mentioned above.

With regard to the geographical distribution of HOU students, the areas with the highest enrolment rates also have proportionally high dropout rates. However, some smaller areas, such as the Ionian Islands, show disproportionately higher dropout rates in relation to their enrolment rates. In the study by Pierrakeas et al. (2020) with HOU students, it appears that students in smaller Greek cities tend to drop out of the institution at a significantly higher rate than students in large urban centres. Of course, it should be noted that these regional differences were not statistically significant, and therefore, city size does not appear to be a strong influencing factor in student dropout rates.

The great percentage of passive withdrawal shows that HOU students choose simply to disappear and do not communicate their decision to stop their studies. The reasons for dropping out can be various and be indirectly inferred through engagement data, such as no attendance at student-tutor meetings or failure to submit assessments, although the exact reasons behind this withdrawal remain unknown.

With respect to RQ2, the analysis showed that the structure of an SP affects dropout rates. More specifically, students who enrolled in annual SPs had higher dropout rates compared to those enrolled in semester-based SPs. This finding has to be further investigated in order to identify the set of reasons that may explain this trend. On the part of the four HOU Schools, the SST and SSS had higher dropout rates compared to the SHU and SAASD. The particularly high dropout rate observed in SST could be further examined in conjunction with factors such as the potentially demanding nature of its SPs, increased student workload, quality of teaching support, etc.

A more reliable interpretation can be attempted in relation to the graduate/postgraduate level of the SPs. More specifically, the relevant findings showed a higher dropout propensity among undergraduate students compared to postgraduate students. This finding is also supported by the literature. The research of Pierrakeas et al. (2004) shows that dropout rates are significantly higher in HOU's undergraduate SPs, mostly due to the limited prior exposure of undergraduate students to university-level academic demands and the difficulties they confront in balancing academic work with other life obligations. In contrast, postgraduate students are often equipped with prior academic experience and clearer professional goals, so they tend to present lower dropout tendencies.

6. Conclusion and future work

This empirical investigation into student dropout rates at the HOU revealed that dropout in higher DE is a multifaceted phenomenon influenced by demographic, institutional, and personal factors. Gender differences were detected, with male students exhibiting higher dropout rates, while age did not appear to play a decisive role in dropout trends at the HOU. Programme articulation also affected dropout, with annual SPs showing

higher dropout rates compared to semestrial SPs. Additionally, undergraduate SPs demonstrated greater dropout tendencies than postgraduate SPs.

The study is limited by its reliance on administrative data, which may not capture the full complexity of dropout causes, particularly in cases of passive withdrawal where students do not communicate their decision. The analysis does not include qualitative insights from students, which could provide a deeper understanding of personal and contextual factors influencing dropout.

Future research should adopt mixed-method approaches to integrate qualitative data, such as student interviews or surveys, to more comprehensively explore motivations behind dropout decisions and the lived experiences of distance learners. Investigations into the causal mechanisms linking programme structure, academic support, and dropout rates would be valuable, especially regarding the observed higher dropout in annual SPs. To this end, appropriate learning analytics systems that monitoring student dropout should be further exploited (e.g. Samaras et.al, 2024). Lastly, focused studies on vulnerable student groups, including prisoners and Roma students, are essential to develop targeted interventions that effectively address the unique barriers they face in DE.

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Innovation in Research and Technology

Beyond Silos: Functional Requirements for Next-Generation Educational Data Architectures in Higher Education

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Abstract

This contribution investigates why existing educational data architectures in higher education (HE)—educational data management (EDM), learner record stores (LRS), educational data warehouses (EDW), learning-analytics platforms (LAP)—fail to meet researchers and users needs and identifies the functional requirements that a “next-generation” educational data architecture must satisfy to close this gap.

The digital transformation in HE allows learners to access their materials and results from anywhere, receive feedback in real time, tailor their learning experience to individual needs and open up new opportunities for personalized learning (de Witt et al., 2020; Hanses et al., 2025). Learning analytics (LA) and artificial intelligence (AI) are key enablers of this, yet their institution-wide adoption remains limited. Educational data management forms the foundation for learning-analytics research and its practical adoption because well-structured, interoperable, and ethically governed data repositories enable researchers to run robust, reproducible analyses while giving institutions the reliable, real-time insights needed to improve teaching and learning. The fact that the adoption of these solutions remains limited across institutions highlights the discrepancy and underpins the rationale for our analysis (Tsai et al., 2021; Viberg et al., 2018).

The literature names many contributing factors that limit the adoption of LA (user involvement, project management, organizational fit, software system design). This contribution focuses on three data-centric obstacles:

Prototype-to-production gap: Most scientific advances remain at the prototype stage and rarely achieve institution-wide adoption in HE. Among several contributing factors, the access to high-quality educational data and the absence of common data-handling and software standards are often mentioned (Márquez et al., 2024)

LA research does not measure learning: Many LA studies do not measure learning outcomes, and a lot of studies do not use data from learners in actual education systems. Instead research focuses on “found data” - data collected by technology that was not designed to measure learning. (Motz et al., 2023) Which means, even when data is available, it is often the wrong data or poorly suited for understanding learning.

Data-preparation workload: Research in HE spends high resources on data cleaning, integration and access, which reduces the time available for the main research (Nunn et al., 2016; Stojanov & Daniel, 2024).

This suggests that not all the data-related requirements are fulfilled and the different EDM solutions are currently not viewed as a path to solve the data-related issues. To examine this mismatch, we (i) synthesised the data-centric hurdles in recent literature and derived a list of functional requirements for data architectures in HE, and (ii) mapped this list of functional requirements against publications with concrete data architectures in HE. Seven data architectures published between 2018 and 2025 met our inclusion criteria.

Our analysis uncovers a series of systematic functional gaps that run through currently published architectures—namely: inconsistent data formats; missing links between course-, programme- and institution-level data; inadequate mechanisms for data consolidation; limited cataloguing and self-service access; and insufficiently granular security and access-rights management.

By revealing where current EDM solutions fall short and specifying the capabilities required, we provide a roadmap for designing next-generation educational data architectures. This can accelerate LA/AI adoption in HE and increase capabilities for core research activities.

Keywords

Learner Record Store, Educational Data Warehouse, Learning Analytics, Learning Analytics Architecture

1. Introduction

Learning analytics (LA) adoption in higher education remains limited, with few institutions achieving sustainable deployment beyond pilot projects (Alzahrani et al., 2023; Márquez et al., 2024). While digital transformation in HE promises personalized learning and data-driven decision-making, a gap persists between available technologies and their practical implementation at scale.

Educational data management (EDM) solutions—learner record stores (LRS), educational data warehouses (EDW), and learning analytics platforms (LAP)—were developed to handle growing volumes of educational data. However, these systems often do not meet the needs of researchers and practitioners who require integrated, accessible data for analysis. This disconnection can be observed in three main aspects: research prototypes that cannot scale due to data access limitations, LA studies that rely on readily available "found data" rather than purposefully collected learning indicators, and research teams spending substantial time on data preparation rather than analysis (Motz et al., 2023; Nunn et al., 2016; Stojanov & Daniel, 2024).

Although various factors limit LA adoption—including user involvement, organizational fit, and project management (Tsai et al., 2021; Viberg et al., 2018)—data infrastructure problems create a foundational barrier. Without properly structured, interoperable data repositories, institutions cannot develop reproducible analyses to support broader adoption or provide timely insights for educational decision-making. This creates a cycle where limited infrastructure restricts successful implementations, which in turn reduces institutional investment in data systems.

This paper addresses two research questions: (1) What functional requirements must educational data architectures fulfil to enable LA/AI adoption in higher education? (2) To what extent do current EDM architectures meet these requirements? We synthesized data-centric challenges from recent literature to derive a requirements framework, then mapped these requirements against seven data architectures published between 2018 and 2025.

Our analysis reveals functional gaps across the examined architectures. These gaps help to explain why current EDW-solutions struggle to support sustainable LA initiatives. By identifying these specific shortcomings and defining necessary capabilities, this research provides guidance for developing next-generation educational data architectures that can better support LA/AI adoption and research activities in higher education.

2. Data-Centric Obstacles

2.1 Educational Data Management Landscape

HE institutions generate and collect data through multiple systems, creating a complex ecosystem. Bringing these systems together requires specialized management solutions. Three primary EDM approaches have emerged as solutions to these needs. Learner Record Stores (LRS) collect and store learning activity statements using specifications like xAPI, capturing detailed interactions across various learning platforms (Labba et al., 2020). Educational Data Warehouses (EDW) serve as centralized repositories that integrate data from multiple sources for reporting and analysis, typically following traditional business intelligence architectures (Amo et al., 2021). Learning Analytics Platforms (LAP) provide analytical tools and visualizations specifically designed for educational data, often combining storage, processing, and presentation layers (Dondorf et al., 2021).

While these solutions have seen increasing deployment, adoption patterns remain uneven. Recent surveys indicate that although 70% of higher education institutions report having some form of learning analytics initiative, fewer than 20% have achieved institution-wide implementation (Tsai et al., 2021). Most implementations remain departmental or course-specific, limiting their potential impact on institutional decision-making and educational improvement.

The limited adoption of EDM solutions can be traced to several data-centric challenges that persist across institutions. We focus on three obstacles that directly impact the ability to conduct meaningful LA research and practice.

2.2 Prototype-to-production Gap.

Educational technology research produces numerous innovative LA approaches, yet most of these remain confined to experimental settings. Márquez et al., 2024 found that over 80% of published LA interventions never progress beyond pilot implementations. Two data-related factors contribute to this gap: limited access to fully integrated data, and the absence of common data standards that would enable solutions to work across different institutional systems. Researchers often develop prototypes using datasets that differ substantially from real institutional data in structure, quality, and scale, making deployment challenging when faced with actual operational constraints.

2.3 LA Research does not Measure Learning.

A systematic review by Motz et al., 2023 revealed that many LA studies do not actually measure learning outcomes or use data from learners engaged in authentic educational activities. Instead, research often relies on "found data"—information collected by systems not designed for learning measurement. While such data is accessible, it provides limited insight into actual learning processes. This reliance necessitates for more meaningful educational data, which may be scattered across systems, restricted by privacy concerns, or simply not collected.

2.4 Data-Preparation Workload.

Researchers and practitioners report spending 60-80% of their project time on data preparation tasks rather than analysis (Nunn et al., 2016). This includes locating relevant data sources, gaining access permissions,

cleaning inconsistent formats, resolving quality issues, and integrating different datasets. (Stojanov & Daniel, 2024) documented cases where data preparation for a single research project required months of effort across multiple technical and administrative units. This overhead not only delays research but also limits the number of studies that can be conducted with available resources, reducing the evidence base for LA effectiveness.

2.5 Current Literature Gaps

While previous research has examined LA adoption challenges from organizational, pedagogical, and functional perspectives (Tsai et al., 2020), less attention has been paid to the specific architectural requirements of educational data systems. Existing literature tends to treat data infrastructure as a technical implementation detail rather than a foundational element that shapes what analyses are possible. Studies that do address data architecture often focus on single institutions or specific technologies, lacking comparative analysis across different approaches.

Furthermore, although standards have developed specifications for educational data interoperability there is limited research on how these standards translate into architectural requirements for institutional data systems. The literature lacks a systematic framework for evaluating whether EDM architectures adequately support the data needs of modern LA applications.

This gap is particularly problematic given the increasing emphasis on data-driven decision-making in higher education. Without clear architectural guidelines, institutions continue to implement EDM solutions that may address immediate needs but fail to provide the foundation necessary for sustainable, scalable learning analytics. This study addresses this gap by systematically identifying functional requirements and evaluating how current architectures meet these needs.

3. Methodology

Our study employed a two-phase approach: (1) deriving functional requirements through literature synthesis, and (2) evaluating existing EDM architectures against these requirements. We conducted a systematic literature review to identify data-related challenges and needs in learning analytics implementations. Starting with LA adoption studies, we extracted functional requirements. Through iterative thematic analysis, we consolidated these findings into functional requirement categories. To identify relevant EDM architectures, we searched Scopus and EBSCOhost using the following query:

```
TITLE("Learner Record Store" OR "Learning Record Store"
OR "Learning Analytics Platform" OR "Educational Data Lake"
OR "Educational Data Warehouse" OR "Learning Analytics Data")
OR
((TITLE("Higher Education")
AND (ABS("architecture", "database"))))
AND PUBYEAR > 2017 AND PUBYEAR < 2026
```

Figure 1 Search String

The search yielded 115 initial results. Two publications have been added from other sources. We applied inclusion criteria requiring: (1) detailed technical architecture description, (2) implementation in higher education context, and (3) focus on LA use cases. Exclusion criteria removed conceptual frameworks without implementation details, vendor white papers, and duplicate reports of the same system. Figure 1 illustrates the selection process, resulting in seven architectures meeting all criteria.

Figure 2 Selection Process

Each selected architecture was systematically coded against the requirements framework to examine whether each requirement was fully addressed, partially addressed, or not addressed, using evidence from architecture descriptions, system diagrams, and reported capabilities. We classified a gap as "systematic" when it appeared in five or more of the seven architectures, indicating a field-wide challenge rather than implementation-specific limitations.

4. Functional Requirements

Our literature synthesis revealed 41 functional requirements. These requirements address the complete data lifecycle from collection through analysis and governance, organized into nine categories that reflect distinct architectural capabilities.

Data Integration encompasses capabilities for collecting data from heterogeneous sources. Modern HE institutions operate dozens of systems—from learning management systems to student information systems—requiring architectures to support multiple import formats and standards.

Data Management addresses storage and organization of diverse educational data types. Requirements span multiple granularity levels: macro-level institutional data (enrolments, programs), meso-level course data (assessments, grades), and micro-level interaction data (clickstreams, learning activities). Architectures must handle both structured relational data and unstructured content while maintaining raw data for reproducibility.

Data Transformation covers processing capabilities needed to convert raw data into analytically useful formats. This includes quality assurance through timestamping and validation, schema harmonization across sources and derivation of key performance indicators. Traceability of transformations ensures reproducible analyses and regulatory compliance.

Data Provisioning enables controlled data access for various stakeholders. Requirements include comprehensive data cataloguing for discoverability, flexible export schemas to support different analytical tools, and standardized APIs for programmatic access.

Data Analysis specifies built-in analytical capabilities from basic descriptive statistics to advanced predictive modelling for applications like dropout prediction.

Data Protection and Compliance ensures appropriate data governance through authentication, fine-grained authorization, role-based access control, and privacy-preserving techniques including pseudonymisation. Audit logging supports both security monitoring and regulatory compliance.

Data Lifecycle Management addresses long-term data stewardship, including retention policies, selective deletion for privacy rights, and archiving strategies.

Visualisation and Reporting covers presentation layer requirements, supporting different stakeholder needs through customisable dashboards and report generation.

System Reliability ensures operational sustainability through monitoring, scalability, and maintainability features.

Table 1 Functional requirements for Learning Analytics Platforms

Data Integration	
A-01	The platform must be able to store educational data from various data sources.
A-02	The platform must support data import via xAPI.
A-03	The platform must support data import via common formats (e.g., XML, JSON, CSV).
A-04	The platform must be able to merge educational data from various data sources.
A-05	The platform must support periodic data integration (e.g., daily, weekly).
A-06	The platform must support (near) real-time data integration (e.g., minute-accurate).
Data Management	
A-07	The platform must support structured (e.g., relational) and unstructured data (e.g., text, images, audio, video).
A-08	The platform must be able to store educational data with personal reference.
A-09	The platform must be able to store macro-level data (e.g., enrolment data, course information).
A-10	The platform must be able to store meso-level data (e.g., assessments, exam performance).
A-11	The platform must be able to store micro-level data (e.g., learning activities, clickstream).
A-12	The platform must store educational data in raw format.
Data Transformation	
A-13	The platform must timestamp all data to enable quality checks and tracking.
A-14	The platform must support configurable data quality checks.
A-15	The platform must enable transformation of educational data into unified schemas.
A-16	The platform must ensure that all data transformation steps are traceable for the system administrator.
A-17	The platform must derive and store predefined indicators (KPIs) from educational data.
A-18	The platform must enable creation and calculation of new custom indicators (KPIs).
A-19	The platform must support mappings to source system IDs.
Data Provisioning	
A-20	The platform must provide a data catalogue that documents information of contained data.
A-21	The platform must enable output of educational data in configurable schemas.
A-22	The platform must support data export via common formats (e.g., XML, JSON, CSV).
A-23	The platform must provide a REST API with versioning and documentation.
Data Analysis	
A-24	The platform must provide simple descriptive statistics about stored educational data.
A-25	The platform must provide a configurable interface for data analysis.
A-26	The platform must support predictive analytics (e.g., prediction of learning success, dropout risks).
Data Protection and Compliance	
A-27	The platform must provide authentication for users and their applications.

A-28	The platform must ensure that only authorised users can access specific data (authorization system).
A-29	The platform must support role-based permissions with configurable access rights (role system).
A-30	The platform must provide configurable security policies for access (e.g., encryption, protocols).
A-31	The platform must be able to provide educational data in pseudonymised and/or anonymised form.
A-32	The platform must be able to log access to educational data.
Data Lifecycle Management	
A-33	The platform must support configurable retention periods for different data types.
A-34	The platform must enable deletion of data for individual persons.
A-35	The platform must enable automated archiving of older data.
Visualization and Reporting	
A-36	The platform must provide configurable dashboards for different user groups (e.g., students, teachers).
A-37	The platform must support interactive data visualisations.
A-38	The platform must enable creation and export of reports.
System Reliability	
A-39	The platform must provide system monitoring and performance metrics.
A-40	The platform must be scalable to process growing data volumes and user numbers.
A-41	The platform must include an update function that enables regular security updates for system components.

5. Gap Analysis of Current Architectures

The analysis examined seven architectures implemented in higher education institutions between 2018 and 2025. These included three learning record stores with xAPI focus, two comprehensive educational data warehouses, one hybrid cloud-based data lake solution, and one integrated LAP. All architectures were operational systems serving actual institutional needs, ranging from single-department deployments to campus-wide implementations.

Table 2 presents the detailed requirements mapping, revealing 21 requirements that were inadequately addressed across most architectures. Five systematic gaps emerged, each appearing in at least five of the seven systems.

Table 2: Detailed Requirement Mapping

No	Short Form	RWTH Analytics ¹	SibFu ED ²	Kyushu LAP ³	OpenLAP ⁴	eDWaaS ⁵	EXCALIBUR ⁶	POLARIS ⁷
A-01	Multiple Data Sources	+	0	0	0	0	+	+
A-02	xAPI Import	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A-03	Standard Format Import	+	+	0	0	0	0	+
A-04	Data Source Merging	0	0	-	-	-	0	0
A-05	Periodic Data Integration	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A-06	Near Real-time Integration	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A-07	Structured/Unstructured Data	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
A-08	Personal Educational Data	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
A-09	Macro-level Data	0	+	-	-	-	0	0
A-10	Meso-level Data	+	+	-	+	0	+	+
A-11	Micro-level Data	+	+	0	+	0	+	+
A-12	Raw Format Storage	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A-13	Timestamp Assignment	0	+	-	-	-	-	0
A-14	Configurable Quality Checks	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
A-15	Schema Transformation	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A-16	Transparent Data Transformation	+	0	0	0	0	0	+
A-17	Result Store	0	+	0	+	+	+	+
A-18	Custom KPIs	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A-19	Source System Traceability	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A-20	Data Catalog	-	0	0	0	0	-	-
A-21	Configurable Schema Output	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
A-22	Standard Format Export	+	+	-	-	-	0	0
A-23	REST API	-	-	-	-	-	-	0

A-24	Descriptive Statistics	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A-25	Configurable Analysis Interface	o	+	o	o	o	o	+
A-26	Predictive Analytics	+	+	o	o	o	+	+
A-27	User Authentication	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A-28	Access Permissions	+	o	o	o	o	o	+
A-29	Role System	o	+	o	o	o	+	+
A-30	Security Policies	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A-31	Pseudonymization/Anonymization	+	o	o	o	o	o	o
A-32	Access Logging	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A-33	Retention Periods	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
A-34	GDPR-compliant Deletion	o	o	o	o	o	o	o
A-35	Automated Data Archiving	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
A-36	User Group Dashboards	+	+	o	+	+	o	o
A-37	Interactive Visualizations	o	o	+	o	o	o	o
A-38	Report Generation	+	+	o	o	+	+	+
A-39	System Monitoring	o	o	o	o	o	o	o
A-40	Scalability	o	+	+	+	+	o	o
A-41	Security Updates	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

¹(Dondorf et al., 2021; Dondorf, 2022) ²(Kustiitskaya et al., 2023) ³(Flanagan & Ogata, 2018) ⁴(Chatti et al., 2017) ⁵(Khan et al., 2018) ⁶(Judel & Schroeder, 2022) ⁷further development based on 6

Legend: + = requirement fully met; o = requirement partially met; - = requirement not met.

Gap 1: Inconsistent data formats. While all architectures could import data from multiple sources, none fully implemented unified schema transformation (A-15). Six architectures lacked configurable output schemas (A-21), forcing consumers to adapt to fixed formats. Source system ID mappings (A-19) were partially implemented in only two systems, complicating data lineage tracking. This creates significant barriers for researchers needing to combine data from different systems or time periods.

Gap 2: Missing cross-level data links. Data merging capabilities (A-04) were limited to predefined relationships in all architectures. Five systems stored macro-level institutional data (A-09) separately from micro-level learning data without mechanisms to connect organisational hierarchies. This separation prevents analyses that require linking individual learning behaviours to program-level outcomes or institutional metrics.

Gap 3: Inadequate consolidation mechanisms. Only one architecture supported near real-time data integration (A-06) with others limited to batch processing. Basic requirements like comprehensive timestamping (A-13) were often not implemented, appearing fully in just three systems. Configurable quality checks (A-14) and transformation traceability (A-16) were absent in five architectures, making it difficult to identify and correct data issues.

Gap 4: Limited cataloguing and self-service access. Data catalogues (A-20) existed in only two architectures. REST APIs (A-23) with proper versioning and documentation lacked in all systems. In addition, configurable analytical interfaces (A-25) are often not provided. This forces researchers to request data extracts through IT departments, creating bottlenecks and delays.

Gap 5: Insufficient security granularity. While all architectures included basic authentication, fine-grained authorization (A-28) was limited to table or schema level rather than row or column level. Pseudonymisation capabilities (A-31) were manual processes many systems, lacking automated transformations. Data lifecycle management was particularly weak: configurable retention (A-33) appeared in only two systems, GDPR-compliant deletion (A-34) required manual database operations, and automated archiving (A-35) was entirely absent in five architectures.

Additional gaps in supporting infrastructure were notable. Interactive visualisations (A-37) were limited to predefined charts in five systems. System monitoring (A-39) focused on technical metrics rather than data

quality or usage patterns in all cases. Support for unstructured data (A-07) was minimal, with despite to the growing importance of text, audio, and video in educational contexts.

These systematic gaps explain why institutions struggle to scale LA beyond pilots. Without unified schemas and proper cataloguing, researchers cannot efficiently access needed data. Missing cross-level links prevent holistic analyses. Inadequate security and lifecycle management raise compliance risks, making institutions hesitant to expand data collection. The cumulative effect forces continued reliance on manual, ad-hoc data preparation—perpetuating the problems these architectures were meant to solve.

6. Discussion, Limitations and Roadmap

This paper sets out to explain why widely used EDM solutions— LRS, EDW, and LAP —have not enabled institution-wide LA adoption in HE. The ‘Requirement Mapping’ across seven architectures (2018–2025) illuminates a coherent pattern of functional gaps.

Three findings stand out. First, current architectures struggle with semantic interoperability. Although most systems ingest multiple formats and support xAPI, they rarely perform robust schema harmonization, configurable output, or systematic source-ID mapping. In practice, this forces researchers to build ad-hoc bridges across datasets and time periods. Second, architectures remain siloed across macro (institution), meso (course), and micro (interaction) levels. Without principled links across these layers, institutions cannot connect individual learning behaviors to program outcomes or strategic KPIs, limiting both research validity and decision-making relevance. Third, core “production-grade” capabilities are limited or absent: near real-time ingestion, comprehensive timestamping and quality checks, data catalogues with lineage, and self-service APIs. The net effect is persistent dependence on manual data extracts and ad-hoc preparation pipelines—precisely the pattern that limits scale and generalizability.

Several limitations exist. First, the requirement analysis was conducted by a single rater; inter-rater reliability was not established. Without a second rater and agreement statistics, coding decisions may reflect subjective judgment. Second, the coding relies on published descriptions of seven architectures; documentation gaps may lead to under- or over-estimation of capabilities. Third, inclusion criteria focused on HE publications and excluded vendor white papers; findings may not generalize to widely deployed commercial systems with proprietary features.

Toward a proper educational architecture, future work should (a) repeat the requirement mapping with multiple raters; (b) develop a LA architecture with cross-functional teams (IT, researchers, instructional designers, data protection officers) with open standards to avoid lock-in. Addressing the identified gaps calls for a reference architecture that is explicitly designed to (i) measure learning, (ii) reduce data-preparation workload, and (iii) sustain production-grade operations at institutional scale. Institutions should consider these requirements when planning future investments in educational data infrastructures.

A next-generation educational data architecture can close the prototype-to-production gap, reduce data-preparation burdens and make LA both scalable and enhance impact for higher education.

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Mapping Augmented Reality Tools for Digital Learning in STEM Education: A Scoping Review of English, Spanish, and German Products

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Abstract

The integration of Augmented Reality (AR) into digital learning holds considerable significant promise for enhancing learner engagement, particularly in STEM disciplines (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). AR applications provide immersive and interactive learning experiences that can actively stimulate students' curiosity and foster deeper understanding, making them promising tools for rethinking engagement in higher education. However, effectively leveraging AR for remote learning environments remains challenging, especially across diverse linguistic and educational contexts. This scoping review systematically identifies and maps available AR tools aimed at supporting digital learning in STEM fields, accessible in English, Spanish, or German, between 2019 and 2025. Following the PRISMA guidelines, a structured search was conducted across digital distribution platforms (Apple App Store, Google Play Store). Inclusion criteria targeted AR applications with a clear educational focus on STEM, available in at least one of the three specified languages, and compatible with mobile devices. The search strategy employed natural language search terms tailored to Spanish, English, and German, reflecting the absence of Boolean operators in mainstream mobile app distribution platforms. The app titles and descriptions were manually screened to ensure their relevance. Data extraction captured core attributes, including educational level, device compatibility, cost model, language availability, and the geographical origin of the developers. The scoping review is expected to provide insights into the current landscape of AR tools for STEM digital learning. By identifying strengths and gaps in existing offerings, the study will inform educators, developers, and policymakers on how to better harness AR technologies to promote engagement, adapt teaching to diverse needs, and foster inclusive learning environments. Particular attention will be given to the accessibility of AR tools across different educational levels and linguistic groups, supporting the broader goal of rethinking higher education through engagement, adaptation, and inclusion.

Keywords

Augmented Reality, Digital Learning, STEM Education, Scoping Review, Educational Technology, Higher Education

1. Introduction

The integration of digital technologies has served to complement existing educational practices, particularly in response to the demand for more accessible and flexible learning environments (Valverde et al., 2021; Kerimbayev et al., 2023; Marienko et al., 2020). Augmented Reality (AR), in particular, has gained prominence for its ability to create immersive and interactive experiences by overlaying digital elements onto the physical world. This technology enhances student engagement, conceptual understanding, and motivation, offering new ways to approach complex content across various disciplines (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2017; Bujak et al., 2013).

At the same time, STEM education (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) presents unique challenges in digital learning due to its experimental and abstract nature. The rapid shift to online education, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighted both the limitations of traditional instruction and the need to adopt innovative pedagogical strategies (Means et al., 2013; Bao, 2020). Teaching STEM in digitally mediated environments requires tools that support visualisation, experimentation, and student interaction in the absence of physical labs and materials. In this context, AR emerges as a promising resource to bridge these gaps. By enabling virtual simulations of scientific processes and interactive manipulation of 3D content, AR can enrich digital STEM education and improve learning outcomes.

Given the growing number of AR applications available on digital platforms, this review distinguishes between commercial and non-commercial tools to better understand the diversity of resources and their accessibility. Commercial AR tools often benefit from professional development, robust design, and technical support, but they may pose financial barriers for institutions or learners (Radianti et al., 2020). In contrast, non-commercial tools, often developed by educational institutions or open-source communities, can increase equity and support inclusive education, although they may face limitations in scalability or user experience (Klopfer & Sheldon, 2011; Santos et al., 2014). This distinction allows for a more comprehensive analysis of the educational potential of AR in different usage contexts.

In addition, the selection of English, Spanish, and German as target languages for this review was based on practical and linguistic considerations. These languages reflect the linguistic competencies of the research team, ensuring accurate interpretation and analysis of the available tools. English, as the world lingua franca in science and technology, dominates the field of educational technology (Montgomery, 2013; Ammon, 2012). Spanish and German, although not as dominant globally, represent language communities in Europe and Latin America, where educational innovation, including the use of AR, is actively expanding (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2023). This multilingual scope allowed for a manageable inclusion of applications from diverse educational and cultural contexts.

1.1. Augmented Reality (AR)

AR has emerged as an educational technology, garnering significant interest over the past two decades due to its potential to enhance teaching and learning outcomes (Chadeea & Prinsloo, 2022). AR overlays digital content onto the physical world, creating interactive and immersive learning experiences that combine virtual and real elements. Studies such as those by Cheng and Tsai (2013), Gittinger and Mulders (2024), Dede (2009), Wu et al. (2013), and Akçayır and Akçayır (2017) indicate that AR enhances student engagement, motivation, and achievement across various academic settings.

By allowing individuals to visualise and interact with virtual objects in a real-world setting, AR helps bridge the gap between abstract concepts and tangible understanding. It enables the representation of phenomena, objects, and content that are typically invisible to the naked eye, thereby enhancing both comprehension and knowledge retention. According to Bujak et al. (2013), AR supports learning by transforming abstract information into perceptible experiences and facilitating the visualisation of processes that would otherwise remain inaccessible to students.

However, this visualisation requires mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets that are compatible with AR applications. The widespread availability of mobile devices allows a broader and more diverse group of learners to engage with AR-enhanced educational content, regardless of their geographic or institutional context. The proliferation of mobile devices has facilitated access to AR, enabling learners from different locations and educational environments to participate in enriched learning experiences (Itransition, 2023).

By leveraging the ubiquity of mobile technology, AR tools reduce access barriers and make immersive, interactive learning experiences more inclusive and scalable (Del Cerro & Morales, 2018). The accessibility of AR is strengthened by the use of standard mobile devices, allowing a greater number of students to participate in AR-enhanced educational activities (Itransition, 2023).

In particular, technological advances have lowered the barriers to integrating AR. Unlike early implementations that required expensive headsets, modern AR can be accessed via ordinary smartphones and tablets. This increased accessibility has led to a growing number of commercial and non-commercial AR tools and platforms for educational use, making the exploration of AR-supported learning more feasible on a large scale (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2017; Garzón & Acevedo, 2019)

1.2. STEM subjects (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) in digital learning

STEM education (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) plays a fundamental role in fostering innovation, problem-solving, and scientific literacy in contemporary society. However, teaching these disciplines in a digital learning context presents unique challenges due to their inherently practical, abstract, and often experimental nature.

Digital education itself has evolved with the advancement of digital technologies, becoming a key educational modality in contexts marked by unequal access, reduced mobility, or global health crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Bao, 2020). This model allows students to access educational content from virtually anywhere, removing the geographical

and temporal barriers associated with traditional face-to-face instruction (Means et al., 2013). Nonetheless, the effectiveness of remote instruction in STEM fields depends on several factors, such as access to stable internet connections, the availability of appropriate technological devices, and the adequate preparation of both teachers and students to function in digital learning environments. Instructional design must also prioritise interaction, continuous feedback, and active student participation to ensure quality learning experiences outside the physical classroom (Garrison et al., 1999).

Recent scholarship has emphasised that digital learning is not simply a substitute for traditional classroom instruction, but a transformative modality that redefines the nature of learning itself. According to Basak et al. (2018), digital learning represents a comprehensive framework that encompasses e-learning, mobile learning, and blended approaches, uniting them under a pedagogical model driven by technology-enhanced engagement. Vaicondam et al. (2022) further argue that digital learning supports the personalisation of instruction, accessibility for diverse learners, and the integration of emerging tools such as artificial intelligence and extended reality.

In STEM education, these benefits become particularly salient. Zou et al. (2025) note that digital learning environments offer opportunities to integrate flexible, student-centered approaches, including flipped classrooms and gamified activities, which are well-suited to the problem-solving and experimental ethos of STEM fields. This theoretical foundation underscores that digital learning is not merely about remote access, but about fostering meaningful, technology-mediated experiences that extend the reach and depth of STEM instruction across varied educational contexts.

These challenges become even more pronounced in STEM disciplines, where students must grasp complex spatial concepts, conduct virtual experiments, and engage with abstract content, often requiring tools that extend beyond traditional theory and practice. A promising response to these challenges is the integration of AR into digital STEM education. AR enables the virtual simulation of laboratory experiments and scientific phenomena, helping to overcome the physical limitations of remote learning environments. Through various applications, students can perform scientific practices or explore three-dimensional structures without the need for expensive lab equipment, thereby bringing interactive learning experiences into the home or classroom through digital simulations.

Studies have shown that these AR-based visualisations can support deeper conceptual understanding and foster the development of key skills in STEM education, such as critical thinking and problem-solving (Garzón & Acevedo, 2019), autonomous learning and self-regulation (Garzón & Acevedo, 2019), as well as spatial and visual reasoning skills (Bujak et al., 2013).

In fields such as mathematics and engineering, AR-based educational interventions have been shown to enhance both academic performance and student motivation compared to traditional approaches, including textbooks (Ibáñez & Delgado, 2018; Petrov & Atanasova, 2020). By enabling "authentic exploration" and encouraging inquiry in virtually enriched real-world contexts, AR helps bridge the gap between theory and practice. Ultimately, the incorporation of AR into STEM education holds considerable potential to enhance both

digital and in-person learning, providing students with immersive, practical, and meaningful experiences that were previously difficult to achieve outside of physical laboratories.

To address this need, the present review sets out to identify and analyse available AR applications that support STEM education across all educational levels. The guiding research question is: What AR tools are commercially and non-commercially available in English, Spanish, or German that support digital learning in STEM disciplines across all educational levels? Thereby, we aim to describe their main characteristics, including platform compatibility, cost model, target education level, and STEM discipline focus.

2. Methods

2.1. Study Design

This scoping review was conducted in accordance with the methodological framework outlined by Tricco et al. (2018) and the PRISMA-ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews) guidelines. The purpose of the review was to identify and map AR tools aimed at supporting digital learning in STEM disciplines, focusing on tools accessible in English, Spanish, or German between 2019 and 2025.

2.2. Eligibility criteria

Tools were included based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria (see Table 1). Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.

Criteria	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
a) Availability	AR applications launched or actively updated between 2019 and 2025	Applications originally launched before 2018, with no recent updates, are not functional/do not exist anymore, even when they were launched after 2019
b) Educational focus	Aimed at learning or educational support in STEM disciplines (natural sciences, mathematics, technology, engineering)	General-purpose or entertainment AR apps without a clear educational STEM focus.
c) Supported languages	Available in at least one of the target languages (Spanish, English, or German), either in the user interface, content, or documentation	Tools available only in other languages
d) Device compatibility	Compatible with mobile, tablet, or computer devices	Applications not compatible with mobile devices, tablets, or computers

e) Commercial and non-commercial availability	Commercially and non-commercially available (Apple App Store, Google Play Store)	Tools that are no longer available or accessible to the public
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2.3. Information sources

Information sources included mainstream mobile app distribution platforms. Specifically, the following platforms were searched: Apple App Store and Google Play Store.

The search was conducted using mainstream mobile app distribution platforms, specifically the Apple App Store and Google Play Store. These sources were selected to reflect real-world conditions of how users search for and access educational AR tools.

2.4. Search strategy

Due to the limitations of app stores, which do not support Boolean operators or advanced search filters, natural language phrases were used in three languages:

- English: “Augmented Reality Learning”
- German: “Augmented Reality Lernen”
- Spanish: “Realidad Aumentada Aprendizaje”

App titles and descriptions were manually reviewed to assess relevance. The search strategy focused on identifying tools aligned with five conceptual categories: AR technology, STEM focus, educational level, language availability, and platform compatibility.

Searches were conducted by trained student research assistants using their personal mobile devices to simulate authentic user experiences across different operating systems and device types.

2.5. Selection process

A total of 592 applications were identified through initial searches across both app stores. After applying the eligibility criteria and removing duplicates, 212 unique AR applications were included in the final synthesis. The selection process is summarised in the PRISMA flow diagram (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Flow diagram for scoping review (adapted after Haddaway et al., 2022).

The flow diagram (see Figure 1) shows the retrieval of 592 records identified from two sources, the Apple App Store in English (n=181), German (n=35), and Spanish (n=3), and the Google Play Store in English (n=69), German (n=62), and Spanish (n=242). After the initial screening, 374 applications were excluded for not meeting the predefined inclusion criteria.

Following the screening, 592 applications were retained for eligibility assessment. During this phase, several were excluded based on specific criteria such as not being AR technology (n=194), not corresponding to the educational level defined in our inclusion criteria (n=76), use of a language other than English, Spanish, or German (n=2), or no focus on STEM areas (n=102). No records were excluded based on outdated versions prior to 2019, 2, or unavailability for mobile platforms.

After reviewing the exclusion process and the reasons mentioned, a total of 217 applications were initially included. However, some duplicates were identified, as certain applications appeared in both the Apple App Store and the Google Play Store. After removing these five duplicates, the final number of applications included in the analysis was 212.

The final 212 applications were categorised and analysed using a system based on a structured ontology, adapted for this scoping review. All data processing and classification were

conducted using Excel spreadsheets, ensuring consistency and traceability throughout the analysis. No manual annotation was performed. The full dataset, including the criteria used for inclusion and exclusion, is available in the online [Supplementary Material](#).

2.6. Data collection

A standardised data extraction form was developed to capture key characteristics of each tool, including:

- Platform compatibility (iOS, Android)
- Language availability (English, Spanish, German)
- Developer and country of origin
- Cost model (free, freemium, paid)
- Target educational level mapped using the International Standard Classification of Education: ISCED (2012) classification

Data were charted manually in a structured spreadsheet, with each entry double-checked for accuracy.

3. Results

The results were synthesised in a descriptive manner, highlighting frequency counts and representative examples to provide insights into the identified apps.

3.1. Devices

Of the 212 apps analysed, 99 (46.7%) were available on both iOS and Android, 94 (44.3%) were iOS-only, and 19 (9.0%) were Android-only. This suggests a strong preference for iOS support among developers.

3.2. Language

Our analyses reveal a clear predominance of English as the primary language of distribution. In comparison, a significantly smaller number of applications are available in German and Spanish. Out of the total applications reviewed, 198 apps are available in English (82.2%), 64 apps in German (26.6%), and 43 apps in Spanish (17.8%). It is important to note that many of these applications are multilingual, appearing in more than one language category.

For example, in English, there are several notable applications that utilise the language as a primary medium of interaction. *Quiver Education* brings coloring pages to life using interactive AR, promoting creativity and engagement. The interface and all instructions are in English. Similarly, *Ocean 4D+* provides an English-language immersive educational journey through underwater ecosystems, offering detailed 3D models of marine life.

In Spanish, *Aventura Aumentada* is a gamified learning platform that employs AR storytelling to reinforce educational content in Spanish. Here, Spanish is not just the interface language but an integral part of the educational experience. *Head Atlas*, on the other hand, is a 3D anatomy visualisation app designed for Spanish-speaking students in biology and

health sciences. While it does not teach Spanish, it is fully localised to make complex scientific content accessible to Spanish speakers.

In the case of German, apps like *simpleclub – Die Lernapp* and *Caro!AR* illustrate how the language can be used both as a medium and as part of the content itself. *Caro!AR* also supports German education in subjects like science, using AR to create interactive experiences. It is especially geared toward enhancing comprehension in the German language, making it more than just a translated interface.

In terms of linguistic diversity, 140 apps are available in only one language (58.0%), while 42 apps support two languages (17.4%), and even 27 apps are trilingual (11.2%). This distribution shows that although most apps are monolingual, a significant portion is accessible to broader audiences through multilingual support.

3.3. Country of development

Based on the analysis of developer origins, the top three countries leading the development of educational AR applications are the United States, with 43 apps (24.0%), India, with 35 (19.6%), and Germany, with 20 (11.2%). These countries show strong involvement in educational technology, reflecting both technological capacity and market orientation (Table 2).

Table 2: Distribution of the Top Five Countries Developing AR Applications by Price Type.

Country	Total Apps	Free	Freemium	Paid
United States	50	73%	0%	27%
India	35	60%	25%	15%
Germany	20	67%	17%	16%
Spain	8	86%	0%	14%
Indonesia	8	57%	29%	14%

Note. The table 2 represents the five countries with the highest number of registered AR applications in the dataset. Each circle shows the relative proportion of free, freemium, and paid applications developed in each country.

The United States has the highest volume, likely due to its well-established industry, while India is experiencing rapid growth in this sector (Kapoor et al., 2024). Germany, although smaller in volume, makes notable contributions with content tailored to its local educational standards.

3.4. Price level

The pricing analysis of educational AR applications reveals that the majority are offered at no cost, with 150 apps classified as free (70.8%). Meanwhile, 47 apps fall under the paid category (22.2%), indicating a moderate presence of monetised content. Additionally, 15 apps use a freemium model (7.1%), providing basic features for free while charging for premium content (see Table 2). This distribution suggests a strong emphasis on accessibility, with developers favouring low-barrier entry points to reach broader educational audiences.

3.5. Educational level

The analysed apps span a wide range of educational contexts, with many addressing multiple levels simultaneously. While our analysis initially focused on applications relevant to digital learning, it quickly became evident that only a small fraction of the identified studies tools are explicitly designed for digitally mediated learning contexts. Instead, most applications are tailored to K-12 education, particularly elementary and middle school levels. The distribution is as follows:

- **Preschool:** 21 apps (10.9%), e.g., *Montessori Preschool*: This app offers interactive AR activities that support early childhood learning in numeracy, literacy, and practical life skills through playful exploration.
- **Kindergarten:** 20 apps (10.4%), e.g., *AR Flashcards*: This app is designed for young learners. It uses AR flashcards to present animated 3D models that help develop vocabulary, recognition, and imagination.
- **Elementary School:** 98 apps (51.0%), e.g., *BuchTaucher*: This app augments textbooks with videos, audio, and animations to support learning in subjects like math, language, and science.
- **Middle School:** 98 apps (51.0%), e.g., *AR-Physics – Physik lernen*: With this app, students can conduct interactive experiments, simulate forces and motion, and deepen their understanding of physics concepts through AR.
- **High School:** 50 apps (26.0%), e.g., *Die Klima App*: This app uses AR to immerse learners in climate-related scenarios such as floods and wildfires and encourages reflection through interactive simulations and narrative experiences.
- **University/College:** 55 apps (28.6%), e.g., *BioDigital Human – 3D Anatomy*: This app provides interactive 3D and AR visualisations of human anatomy and health conditions, supporting life science and medical education at the university level.
- **Vocational Education:** 26 apps (13.5%), e.g., *INNIO Learning Experiences*: Tailored for vocational learners in the energy sector, this app uses AR to simulate technical procedures and safety training in realistic work environments.
- **Adult Education:** 37 apps (19.3%), e.g., *Augmented Instructor*: This app provides AR-enhanced training for adults, offering instructional support across various STEM-related topics in continuing education.

These numbers reveal a strong focus on K-12 education, particularly at the elementary and middle school levels, which together account for more than half of all analysed apps. At the same time, a substantial number of apps target higher education, vocational training, and adult learning, highlighting the versatility of AR technology in STEM education. Nevertheless, the overall low visibility of digital learning-specific implementations raises critical questions about the extent to which AR is currently leveraged to support flexible, location-independent learning experiences.

4. Discussion

This scoping review offers a systematic mapping of both commercial and non-commercial AR applications designed to support digital learning in STEM education across English, Spanish, and German-speaking contexts. Our findings provide critical insights into the

accessibility, linguistic diversity, educational levels, and pedagogical relevance of these tools, thereby informing future integration efforts of AR in digital learning environments.

First, our data highlights a promising level of accessibility. More than 70% of the identified applications are available free of charge, with additional tools offered under freemium models. This finding reinforces earlier research suggesting that mobile AR technologies can support equitable learning opportunities when cost barriers are minimised (e.g., Del Cerro & Morales, 2018). Nonetheless, the discoverability of high-quality educational tools remains an issue. For instance, prominent applications like *Merge Cube* were not identified through standard app store searches due to limitations in platform indexing. This suggests a need for improved metadata, categorisation, and searchability mechanisms on mainstream mobile app distribution platforms to facilitate effective adoption by educators, particularly those with limited technical expertise.

Second, our review demonstrates a clear predominance of English-language AR applications, while Spanish and German are significantly underrepresented. Although some tools are multilingual, the majority support only one language, potentially reinforcing educational inequalities for non-English-speaking learners. This underscores the need for culturally and linguistically adaptive AR content to ensure meaningful learning across diverse contexts. Expanding localisation efforts remains critical for inclusive and globally relevant AR-based education. As Nye (2015) and Eppard et al. (2021) emphasise, the cultural and linguistic adaptation of educational technology is essential not only for usability but also for learner engagement and comprehension. Language and culture shape how users interact with digital tools, and ignoring this dimension may hinder the pedagogical effectiveness of AR interventions.

Moreover, the decision to include English, Spanish, and German as target languages in this review was based not only on the linguistic competence of the research team but also on methodological and cultural considerations. Limiting a review to English-only sources can introduce language bias and exclude regionally relevant tools or practices (Rasmussen & Montgomery, 2018).

English, spoken by over 1.4 billion people worldwide, serves as the dominant global language in science, technology, and education, and is officially used in more than 50 countries (Crystal, 2003; Eberhard, 2021). Spanish, with approximately 483 million native speakers and over 558 million total users, is the second most spoken native language globally and holds official status in 20 countries across Latin America and Europe (Instituto Cervantes, 2023; Eberhard, 2021). German, in turn, is the most widely spoken native language within the European Union, with an estimated 90 to 95 million native speakers and up to 220 million total users worldwide, making it a key language for identifying tools developed in regions with a strong educational and technological tradition (European Commission, 2023).

The inclusion of Spanish and German enabled the review to capture educational tools developed in culturally diverse regions such as Latin America and Central Europe, where AR is increasingly being adopted for pedagogical innovation (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation, 2023). Furthermore, incorporating multiple languages aligns with international best practices in systematic reviews, which recommend minimising

language bias by including non-English sources whenever possible (Glanville et al., 2021). In this way, the multilingual scope of the review supports a broader and more inclusive understanding of the development and implementation of AR tools across diverse linguistic and cultural educational ecosystems.

Third, although AR tools span all educational levels, there is a particularly strong emphasis on K-12 contexts, with over 50% of the tools targeting elementary and middle school. In contrast, applications explicitly designed for higher education or vocational contexts are comparatively fewer, despite growing interest in leveraging AR for professional and academic training. The scarcity of AR tools for advanced STEM topics may limit the potential of immersive learning at higher cognitive levels. Future development should therefore aim to address this gap by creating tools tailored to university curricula and complex scientific concepts.

The review identified 55 applications (28.6%) specifically designed for university and higher education contexts, particularly in fields such as anatomy, engineering, and medical education. These tools highlight the potential of AR to enhance advanced STEM learning by enabling the visualisation of complex structures, simulating laboratory experiments, and facilitating training in professional practices. Such applications are particularly relevant to higher education institutions, where the demand for flexible, technology-enhanced learning has increased following the COVID-19 pandemic (Bao, 2020; Radianti et al., 2020). Strengthening the integration of these tools into university curricula would help bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application at higher cognitive levels, thereby better preparing students for both academic and professional challenges.

In contrast, although the prevalence of AR tools for K–12 levels suggests strong potential for early engagement with STEM concepts, their adaptation to digital learning contexts remains limited and often ambiguous (Zhang & Wang, 2021). Many of the applications aimed at younger students, especially in preschool and elementary education, depend on adult supervision or classroom interaction, which complicates their independent use in digitally mediated settings without the support of a caregiver or teacher (Ibáñez & Delgado, 2018).

This presents a significant challenge for equitable implementation in home-based environments, particularly when parents may lack the time or digital literacy to facilitate learning. As highlighted by Means et al. (2013), the effectiveness of digital tools in digital learning is closely tied to the surrounding instructional infrastructure and support systems. Therefore, although the availability of AR tools for young learners is promising, their deployment in fully remote contexts may require additional scaffolding or the development of pedagogically integrated AR experiences specifically designed for self-directed learning. Future research should explore how these tools can be adapted or complemented with digital learning-appropriate methodologies to ensure meaningful learning across all age groups in virtual environments.

This is particularly relevant in digital learning, where AR has demonstrated positive effects on the comprehension of abstract and experimental content, especially in STEM disciplines (Iqbal et al., 2022; Eldokhny & Drwish, 2021). By simulating laboratories, 3D models, and interactive experimentation, AR can bridge the gap between theory and practice even in

remote environments, supporting the development of spatial reasoning, critical thinking, and autonomous learning (Garzón & Acevedo, 2019).

Finally, during our analysis, we also recognised that the current landscape of mobile app-based AR tools lacks systematic pedagogical frameworks guiding the design and implementation of AR for digital learning. As Akçayır and Akçayır (2017) argued, effectiveness is not inherent to technology itself but depends on thoughtful integration into instructional design. We therefore would suggest that while the technological infrastructure exists, pedagogical guidance for educators remains limited.

In the context of digital learning, where teacher-student interaction is often asynchronous and mediated by technology, clear instructional design becomes even more essential. Literature recommends that AR content for digital learning be usable, goal-aligned, and contextually relevant to avoid cognitive overload and ensure learner autonomy (Eppard et al., 2021). Moreover, the combination of AR with artificial intelligence and virtual agents has been identified as a promising avenue for enhancing guidance and feedback in self-directed learning scenarios (Iqbal et al., 2022), particularly when physical presence and real-time facilitation are not feasible.

5. Limitations

This review has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the search strategy was constrained by the limitations of mainstream mobile app stores, which do not support Boolean operators or advanced filters. As a result, some relevant applications, especially those with non-standardised titles or less optimised metadata, may have been overlooked. This is exemplified by the exclusion of widely used tools such as *Merge Cube*, which were not detected through our natural language-based search.

Second, while our multilingual approach covered English, Spanish, and German, it excluded other major world languages, potentially omitting AR tools used in regions such as East Asia or the Middle East. Similarly, apps available only on less commonly used platforms such as the *Microsoft Store* or *Amazon App Store* were not included due to accessibility constraints and limited adoption among educators, particularly in mobile-first environments.

Third, our classification relied on app store descriptions and screenshots rather than in-depth testing of each tool's functionality. While this reflects the typical experience of educators browsing these platforms, it may not fully capture the pedagogical quality or usability of the applications. Additionally, the absence of user analytics or long-term usage data limits our ability to assess sustainability and real-world impact.

Finally, the dynamic nature of mobile app marketplaces means that app availability, pricing, and functionality are subject to frequent change. The results of this review represent a snapshot within the defined time frame (2019 to 2025) and may not reflect future developments or trends in AR-enhanced digital learning.

6. Conclusion

This scoping review provides a timely and systematic overview of the current landscape of both commercial and non-commercial available AR tools for STEM digital learning education in English, Spanish, and German-speaking contexts. The findings highlight a growing number of accessible applications, particularly for younger educational levels, with a strong emphasis on English-language content and mobile compatibility.

While the reviewed tools show great potential to enhance engagement, visualisation, and conceptual understanding in STEM subjects, important gaps remain. These include limited language diversity, inconsistent pedagogical alignment, and concerns about long-term sustainability. Educators and developers should therefore consider not only the technical features of AR applications but also their fit with curricular goals, language accessibility, and visibility within app marketplaces.

Future research should explore the classroom use of these tools in real-world settings and examine how AR can be integrated into teacher education and institutional strategies. Only through such combined efforts can the full educational potential of AR be realised, promoting more inclusive, engaging, and adaptive learning environments in STEM education.

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Competing interests

We have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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V-Lab: VR Simulation for Science Lab Training

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Abstract

Lab training has always been a challenge to science university faculties due to a number of factors. Such are the fragility of the equipment and the resulting repair or replacement cost, the risk of accidents and the congestion of the physical labs due to the high number of students, which, combined with each other, hinder the overall training process. The problem is aggravated in the case of distance universities, where students visit their lab facilities en masse and only a few times in a year, thereby having a very short time-frame to make use of the equipment. For this reason, Hellenic Open University (HOU) has developed its own virtual biology and physics laboratories for its science undergraduate program, simulating various experiments. In those, students can make unlimited free use of the simulated lab equipment and learn with trial and error without the risk of accidents or damages that can happen in a physical lab. HOU's most recent virtual lab version, V-Lab, simulating the biology lab, comes in two versions; one PC version, which, like the older releases of HOU's virtual labs, has a mouse and keyboard User Interface; and one VR version, whose User Interface consists of VR headset and handles. Upon V-Lab, two online courses have been designed; a short course for teaching how to successfully conduct experiments within the virtual lab; and a five-week MOOC for the programming development under Unity game engine of both PC and VR versions of V-Lab. These courses attempt to make virtual lab use and development accessible to universities and institutions with the ultimate purpose of reducing the overall cost of lab training.

Keywords

Virtual Labs, Virtual Reality, Extended Reality, Simulation, Distance Education

1. Introduction (Calibri, 11 pt, bold)

Onlabs is an educational platform created by the Hellenic Open University (HOU) to provide virtual replicas of its physical science laboratory facilities. As HOU operates a distance education model, students enrolled in natural science programs have limited access to the physical labs - typically for a few days annually for examination purposes. This brief access window constrains opportunities for adequate familiarization with the equipment and safety protocols, resulting in suboptimal training and elevated risk of damage to vulnerable instruments.

Onlabs mitigates these issues by offering HOU's science students the opportunity for unrestricted practice with 3D simulated instruments within a safe, digital environment. This allowance for learning by trial and error aims to ensure that students can operate the on-site equipment safely and proficiently when they visit the on-site laboratories. Obviously, Onlabs's purpose is not to replace on-site lab education but to complement it.

Onlabs has been mainly developed under the Unity game engine and C# as its scripting language. While Onlabs supports Virtual Reality (VR) and touch user-interfaces, its core development focuses on a PC version where navigation is controlled by arrow keys and object interaction is managed via the mouse. Its primary

developmental focus has been on biology, implementing procedures and instruments related to photonic microscopy, TBE 10X solution preparation, agarose gel preparation, electrophoresis and centrifugation, but it has also been extended to physics (oculus, cosmic ray observation) and chemistry (titration).

Figure 1 shows a screenshot of Onlabs with the instruments of microscopy and 10X TBE solution preparation.

Figure 1. Screenshot of Onlabs.

Onlabs's later generation, V-Lab, developed since 2023 within the "XR2Learn" Horizon European programme, incorporates new state-of-the-art graphics and a new, optimized user-interface and will be presented in detail in Section 3.

1.1 Play modes in the Virtual Lab

Onlabs incorporates three distinct play modes to support diverse pedagogical goals:

- *Instruction Mode*: A guided learning environment with voice and text prompts, enforcing a specific, non-divergent experimental workflow.
- *Evaluation Mode*: An assessment environment where users freely perform a procedure using specific instruments and receive performance-based scoring.
- *Experimentation Mode*: A free-form sandbox environment granting unrestricted access to all integrated instrumentation and procedures, without any evaluation.

There has also been another mode (yet for research purposes only), namely *Machine Learning Mode*, for the optimization of the scoring algorithm incorporated in the Evaluation Mode, with the use of various machine learning methods such as genetic algorithms, artificial neural networks and reinforcement learning.

Onlabs's various versions are available for download for free from its website¹.

¹ <http://onlabs.eap.gr/>

Onlabs has been repeatedly evaluated by students from HOU and other Greek universities, and has been consistently assessed as a useful complementary tool for laboratory education. The reader may find the full list of our publications about the various implementations and evaluations of Onlabs in its website, too.

2. Background and Related Work

The integration of Virtual Reality (VR) into educational settings has a history spanning over half a century, with early applications, such as flight simulators for training purposes, dating back to the 1960s (Kavanagh et al., 2017). The core principles that define the educational value of VR are Immersion, Interaction and User Involvement (Freina & Ott, 2015). Immersion refers to the degree to which the technology approximates a real-world experience, leading to a psychological sense of "presence" or "being there" for the user (Freina & Ott, 2015; Tian et al., 2023).

For decades, the widespread adoption of VR in education was hindered by limitations in technology, high costs and logistical challenges (Kavanagh et al., 2017). However, the commercial release of affordable and high-quality Head-Mounted Displays (HMDs), such as the Oculus Rift, around 2012 marked a significant turning point, making immersive VR more accessible for a wider range of educational applications (Freina & Ott, 2015; Smutny et al., 2019).

Contemporary literature highlights numerous pedagogical benefits of using VR across various disciplines, including science, engineering and art (Muzata et al., 2024; Smutny et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2023). Key advantages identified through systematic reviews and studies include:

- *Enhanced Engagement and Motivation*: VR creates highly engaging and motivating learning experiences, which positively impacts student mood and enthusiasm for learning (Freina & Ott, 2015; J. Li & Liang, 2024, 2024; Smutny et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2023).
- *Improved Conceptual Understanding and Visualization*: VR provides an unparalleled ability to represent abstract concepts (e.g., in physics and mathematics) and allows for the close-up examination and manipulation of 3D models and environments, which is often difficult or impossible with conventional methods (Campos et al., 2022; Smutny et al., 2019).
- *Safe and Cost-Effective Simulations*: VR environments offer a controlled and safe space to practice complex or hazardous procedures, such as chemical experiments or surgical operations, which can be repeated as frequently as needed without resource or safety constraints (Ali et al., 2022; Muzata et al., 2024).
- *Support for Diverse Learning Styles*: The interactive, visual and kinesthetic nature of VR-enhanced learning appeals to a variety of learning preferences, which can lead to more stable and long-lasting knowledge gain (Freina & Ott, 2015).

Despite the optimism, researchers note that the full potential of VR in education is yet to be realized, with challenges remaining in developing specific pedagogical practices for its implementation and ensuring accessibility for all learners (Muzata et al., 2024).

2.1 The Evolution and Role of Virtual Laboratories

A primary application of VR and simulation technology in education is the Virtual Laboratory, particularly in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) fields (Y. Li et al., 2024; Sellberg et al., 2024). Virtual laboratories are generally defined as technology-mediated learning contexts, which can be delivered through PC simulations or fully immersive VR environments via HMDs, allowing students to conduct scientific

investigations, simulate experiments, test hypotheses and collect data in a digital realm (Rosli & Ishak, 2024; Sellberg et al., 2024).

The emergence and growing adoption of Virtual Labs, accelerated significantly by the demand for remote and flexible learning during events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, address several inherent limitations of traditional hands-on labs (Ali et al., 2022; Reyes et al., 2024). These traditional limitations include high costs for equipment and chemicals, safety risks associated with hazardous materials, limited access to resources and the inability to repeat costly or time-consuming experiments (Ali et al., 2022; Gunawan et al., 2023).

Key findings from the literature on virtual laboratories include:

- *Comparable Learning Outcomes:* Systematic reviews comparing Virtual Labs with traditional hands-on laboratories have shown that students can achieve similar or even better learning outcomes, depending on the specific knowledge or skill being measured (Sellberg et al., 2024).
- *Strengths in Affective Outcomes:* Virtual Labs are particularly effective in enhancing non-cognitive outcomes, with meta-analyses showing high effect sizes for improving students' learning motivation and learning engagement (J. Li & Liang, 2024).
- *Focus on Practical and Procedural Skills:* Virtual Labs, especially immersive virtual labs, have become a critical tool for familiarizing students with laboratory procedures and equipment, helping them develop practical skills in a risk-free environment before entering a physical lab (Gunawan et al., 2023; Reyes et al., 2024).
- *Complementation, Not Replacement:* A recurring consensus in the research, particularly in engineering and science education, is that while virtual laboratories are a powerful and effective supplement for instruction, they currently do not have the capacity to completely replace hands-on laboratory experiences (J. Li & Liang, 2024; Y. Li et al., 2024; Reyes et al., 2024). Virtual Labs are most effective when integrated into a hybrid learning strategy that combines their interactive, immersive advantages with the foundational knowledge provided by conventional education (Muzata et al., 2024).

The continuous technological advancements in immersive VR are now pushing the development of "Immersive Virtual Labs" which create multi-sensory, interactive learning environments that transcend physical limitations, setting the stage for more complex and engaging digital practical work (Y. Li et al., 2024).

3. V-Lab: new generation of Hellenic Open University's virtual labs

V-Lab, short for "Virtual Lab", as mentioned in the introduction, is the new generation of HOU's Onlabs. It has been being developed since 2023 within "XR2Learn: Leveraging the European XR Industry Technologies to Empower Immersive Learning and Training", a Horizon EU framework programme (2023-2026) in which several other European universities and companies participate².

V-Lab has been released for both PC and VR, with both of releases simulating the microscopy experimental procedure and incorporating high-end graphics and realistic functionalities.

The user interface of the PC version of V-Lab builds upon the latest user interface of Onlabs, with crucial modifications towards a more realistic interaction. Such improvements have been the discarding of the user's inventory (present in all previous versions of Onlabs) and a more realistic movement of lab objects within the virtual lab by the user by enabling the latter to pick up and carry the actual 3D objects instead of dragging their

² <https://xr2learn.eu/>

respective 2D icons with the mouse, which had been the norm since Onlabs version 1.0. Moreover, the application of immersion oil on the microscopy specimen has been implemented, which is a necessary prerequisite for focusing with microscope's 100X objective lens, missing from previous versions.

Figures Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrate two screenshots of V-Lab's PC version.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the lab bench in V-Lab.

Figure 3. Screenshot of photonic microscopy simulation in V-Lab.

On its behalf, V-Lab's VR version (Figure 4) manages to combine the immersion of VR with user-friendly functionalities which overcome several of its inherent caveats. Such is the functionality of the combination of looking through the ocular lenses of the microscope and simultaneously being able to handle the microscope's knobs and adjust the focus; while in the PC version the problem is solved by dividing the screen in two parts,

the left one having the 3D microscope and the right one showing the 2D microscoping image of the examined specimen (Figure 3), in the VR version the 2D microscoping image is projected onto a 3D simulation of a tablet while the user is supposedly looking through the oculars, allowing them that way to view the microscope's knobs and therefore manipulate them at the same time (Figure 5).

Figure 4. View inside V-Lab VR version.

Figure 5. Viewing the microscoping image on a tablet while manipulating the microscope knobs in V-Lab VR version.

3.1 Virtual Lab Standard Development Kit

Apart from the stand-alone implementations for PC and VR, V-Lab offers a Standard Development Kit (SDK) for the development of virtual laboratories in Unity game engine. With the V-Lab SDK, an inexperienced user in game programming can develop their own functionalities in existing virtual labs with a minimum amount of coding – or even not coding at all. In essence, the SDK consists of a modular, component-based development framework, which reads the inputs that sensors (e.g., a switch, a knob, etc.) receive from the user interface (e.g., from the pressing/dragging of the mouse button), feeds them into variables and then to effectors (e.g., a light bulb, a mechanical part, etc.), and the properties of particular features of the latter is being modified (e.g., the color of the light bulb changes, the mechanical part moves, etc.).

4. Virtual Lab Massive Open Online Courses

Apart from the development of virtual laboratories, two different Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have also been designed within V-Lab.

The first MOOC is a short one-hour course which equips educators with the knowledge and practical skills to effectively integrate Extended Reality (XR) technologies, including Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR) and Mixed Reality (MR) into educational settings. It offers a comprehensive exploration of XR's potential to enhance teaching and learning, grounded in instructional design principles like the ASSURE model (Smaldino et al., 2019) and the TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Through engaging modules, real-world case studies and a hands-on final project, participants learn to analyze learner needs, select appropriate XR technologies and design immersive learning experiences that align with curriculum goals.

The second MOOC is five-week course of 1 ECTS aiming to train participants in developing virtual laboratories modeled after V-Lab. Development takes place in the Unity game engine environment using the C# programming language. Upon completing the course, participants are supposed to be able to simulate laboratory instruments and objects as well as corresponding experimental procedures, leveraging their prior knowledge of programming techniques. The first 3 weeks revolve around the core aspects around the programming development of a virtual lab, that is, setting up the lab scene, programming the user character and its navigation in the scene and the user's interaction with the various lab objects and instrument components with the use of the mouse; the 4th week concerns the development of the virtual lab's VR version; and finally, in the 5th week the learner is being initiated into the use of V-Lab SDK which allows for virtual lab development in a little-to-no-code fashion. The MOOC provides the learner with both video tutorials and a text developer's guide.

Both MOOCs are publicly accessible from the XR2Learn project's website.

5. Conclusions

In order to facilitate lab training for its natural science students, HOU has developed its own virtual laboratories, simulating various lab instruments and experimental procedures in biology, physics and chemistry. The latest generation of HOU's virtual labs (V-Lab), developed around the "XR2Learn" Horizon European programme and currently focusing on biology's microscopy procedure, includes two releases, one for PC and another for VR, and incorporates state-of-the-art graphics and improved functionalities that enhance the realism and the user-friendliness of the simulation. It also includes an SDK for the development of virtual labs on a little-to-no-code basis.

Moreover, around V-Lab, two MOOCs have been designed; a short one-hour MOOC for teaching the use of virtual labs in education and a 5 weeks MOOC (1 ECTS) for the programming development of virtual labs for both PC and VR and the use of the V-Lab SDK.

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Course and Curriculum Design

AI and Universities. Critical Thinking, Personalised Pathways, Recognised Skills

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Abstract

As higher education continues to evolve, universities rethink how they should support innovation, creativity and critical thinking. So, some important questions arise: Which teaching methods best foster creativity and critical thinking? Which educational tools (both traditional and modern) serve this purpose effectively and how might artificial intelligence enhance them? This paper addresses these questions through a human-centred approach, focusing on adaptive pedagogy, personalised learning pathways, the recognition of skills through digital micro-credentials and last but not least the meaningful use of digital tools (UNESCO, 2019; European Commission, 2022).

Erasmus+ collaborative projects provided useful data and practical examples from related pilot tests in many EU Universities that supported our research. For example, EDDIE was a four-year (2020-2024) project creating a Sector Skill Alliance (SSA) to develop a long-driven Blueprint for the digitalization of the European Energy sector (EDDIE Project, 2023a).

Insights from the project include AI-driven learning simulations, real-time dashboards and visual tools that helped learners identify progress and skill gaps. A major outcome was the development of a blockchain-secured Digital Credential Marketplace, allowing learners to safely store and share their achievements (EDDIE Project, 2023d). These tools proved valuable not only for students, but also for institutions, many of which used the project to review internal practices, update their curricula, and pilot credential frameworks such as EQF, DigComp, Europass and micro-credential system (European Training Foundation, 2023; EDDIE Project, 2023b). By using and analysing data from the project's pilot testing, outputs and evaluation reports (such as learner performance, engagement metrics, institutional feedback, integration of various digital tools and AI), HE institutions can enhance the design of their curricula and teaching methods. Thus, a highly realistic educational strategy and an improved learning framework will evolve in the future.

The paper also reflects on Salman Khan's book *Brave New Words* (2024), which offers a vision of education where learners are recognised not only for what they know, but for what they can do. The author explores how artificial intelligence can help shift education away from rote learning and towards approaches that value practical skills, personal growth, and meaningful progress. He imagines a future where AI supports more tailored teaching, fairer assessment and wider access to opportunity, while also highlighting the ethical and social responsibilities that must guide its use in education.

In line with this Salman Khan's perspective, the findings from EDDIE and related studies, we suggest a model of higher education that is inclusive, adaptable and ethically grounded (UNESCO, 2021; The Guardian, 2023). A model where personalised learning and recognised skills go hand in hand. Under this model learners will be continuously supported throughout their learning process by a tailored mentorship program which will be adapted to learners' needs and current circumstances. A model where innovation is driven by both technology and pedagogy.

Keywords

AI, personalised learning, skills recognition, higher education adaptive learning, critical thinking

1. Introduction

Higher education across Europe is undergoing structural change that extends beyond short-term technological cycles. The long-standing model of three or four year degrees delivered in standardised formats is giving way to more flexible, learner-centred provision that blends formal, non-formal and work-based learning.

Several forces drive this shift. Europe's population is ageing and adults are returning to education at multiple career stages (Eurostat, 2023a, 2023b). Labour markets are being reshaped by the green and digital transitions, with CEDEFOP estimating that close to half of the workforce will require substantial up or reskilling by 2030 (CEDEFOP, 2023). At the same time, only 46.6 % of adults aged 25–64 participated in any education or training during the previous year, and just 56 % of adults aged 16–74 possess at least basic digital skills, well below the 80 % target for 2030 (Eurostat, 2023c; Joint Research Centre, 2025). **These figures highlight the need for systems that support lifelong learning at scale while maintaining quality and inclusion.**

European policy points in the same direction. The European Strategy for Universities emphasises interconnected, inclusive and resilient institutions. The Council Recommendation on micro-credentials sets a shared definition and quality elements and the Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027 prioritises effective digital ecosystems and advanced skills development (Council of the European Union, 2022; European Commission, 2021, 2022). Together, all these initiatives outline a European skills-and-trust ecosystem in which learning must be portable and verifiable and adaptable.

In this context, three trends emerge as particularly important and guide the present study. Universities are expected to foster creativity and critical thinking while using AI-enhanced tools to make learning more interactive and reflective (UNESCO, 2019). Personalised learning pathways are gaining ground through adaptive systems that respond to pace, interests and goals (Khan, 2024). Micro-credentials recognise competences in smaller, stackable units that can be combined across disciplines and sectors (CEDEFOP, 2023).

Two Erasmus+ projects illustrate how these priorities translate into practice. EDDIE (Education for the Digitalisation of the Energy Sector) identified skill gaps in areas such as data analytics, cybersecurity and AI, and piloted modular training and micro-credentials. HYBOT (Enhancing Hybrid Teaching in Higher Education through Chatbots) which was presented during **I-HE2024** developed an ECTS-accredited micro-credential for academic staff and documented hybrid-teaching practices and chatbot use cases across Europe. Both projects show how technology, pedagogy and recognition can be combined, while also exposing challenges around infrastructure, assessment and data protection.

This paper examines how micro-credentials, personalised pathways and AI interact to create opportunities and risks for European higher education. Using a sociotechnical lens and an embedded comparative case design, it analyses evidence from EDDIE and HYBOT against current European initiatives to clarify the conditions under which digital innovation expands opportunity, strengthens trust and preserves academic values. As Khan (2024) argues, the promise of AI lies not in replacing teachers but in empowering them to nurture curiosity and meaningful learning progress. Evidence from UNESCO (2019) and the OECD (2023) likewise stresses that AI should serve human development rather than technological efficiency alone.

2. Methods

This study adopts an embedded comparative case-study design drawing on evaluation data from the Erasmus+ **EDDIE** project (2020–2024). EDDIE was a Sector Skills Alliance of more than fifty partners across seventeen European countries. Its pilots tested AI-enabled learning tools, modular training programmes and cross-border micro-credential frameworks, providing a rich evidence base for analysing the intersection of artificial intelligence, personalised learning and skills recognition.

Case selection and scope

Two strands of EDDIE activity were selected because they combine technological innovation with documented pedagogical outcomes.

The first is the **Digital Credential Marketplace** and its associated modular courses, which explored the design and portability of verifiable micro-credentials across national systems.

The second is the **Creativity and AI in Energy Education** pilots, which examined how AI-supported simulations and real-time feedback could stimulate problem solving, creativity and critical thinking in university settings.

Data sources

The analysis draws on three main types of evidence:

1. **Project documentation** – internal evaluation reports, public deliverables and technical specifications produced by the EDDIE consortium (2023, 2024).
2. **Participant feedback** – post-course online surveys capturing learner engagement, perceived creativity gains, satisfaction with AI tools and the usability of micro-credentials.
3. **Qualitative insights** – transcripts and summaries from semi-structured focus groups and interviews with students, academic staff, institutional coordinators and industry mentors.

Participants and instruments

Across the two strands, more than 1,000 learners and approximately 120 academic staff engaged in pilot activities. Surveys used five-point Likert scales and open-ended questions to capture both quantitative ratings and qualitative reflections. Creativity was assessed through self-ratings and peer/instructor comparative creativity scores on a ten-point scale. Eighteen focus groups (six to ten participants each) and twenty-four follow-up interviews explored themes such as learner autonomy, interdisciplinary collaboration and the perceived ethical risks of AI.

Analytical procedure

Quantitative survey data were analysed using descriptive statistics to identify patterns in creativity ratings, adoption of AI tools and satisfaction with micro-credentials. Qualitative material was coded inductively to surface recurring themes and to compare experiences across partner universities. Triangulation of survey metrics, focus-group narratives and project documentation strengthened validity and reduced the risk of bias from any single source.

Ethical considerations

All evaluation activities followed Erasmus+ ethical guidelines. Participation was voluntary, informed consent was obtained and all data were anonymised prior to analysis. The study complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and with institutional review procedures at participating universities.

Limitations.

Although the mixed-methods design provides a robust empirical foundation, findings are based on pilot activities of limited duration and cannot be generalised without caution.

Key empirical insights

A central finding was that creativity can be cultivated through experiential, collaborative and technologically

augmented teaching. Problem-based learning, AI-assisted modelling, capstone challenges and immersive simulations were consistently rated highly by students and faculty for their creativity-promoting effects.

University	Course Title	Creativity Rating (1–10)	AI Tools Used
NTUA (Greece)	Digital Energy Labs	8.7	Simulation, ML feedback
RWTH Aachen (Germany)	Smart Grid Automation	8.4	Predictive analytics
POLIMI (Italy)	AI-Enhanced Urban Design	9.2	Generative design tools
KTH (Sweden)	Digital Twin City Planning	9.1	AR/VR, simulation
FOSS – Univ. of Cyprus	Integrated Systems Lab	8.5	Real-time monitoring

Table 1 summarises comparative creativity ratings from selected pilot activities.

Figure 1. Comparative effectiveness of teaching methods based on EDDIE pilot evaluations.

Educational tools and the role of AI

Across the pilots, AI was not treated as a stand-alone solution but as a catalyst for learner autonomy and critical thinking. For example, NTUA used AI-supported simulation platforms that allowed students to create smart-building models and test energy-saving interventions in real time, while POLIMI deployed generative design tools enabling students to explore multiple urban-development scenarios and refine solutions against sustainability metrics. KTH used digital-twin VR environments to let urban-planning students walk through simulated neighbourhoods, adjust infrastructure variables and receive immediate feedback on system efficiency and emissions.

These technologies were integrated with inquiry-driven pedagogies that emphasised experimentation, iterative processes, and dialogue, helping to make abstract concepts more concrete and strengthening students’ confidence in decision-making.

Contextual insights drawn from the diversity of EDDIE partners highlighted how national and institutional contexts shape creative practice. At NTUA, project-based energy audits encouraged student ownership and heightened social awareness. RWTH Aachen promoted interdisciplinary collaboration spanning engineering, data science and policy. POLIMI combined architecture, sustainability, and digital technologies to stimulate

innovation. KTH explored future sustainable cities through immersive design. The University of Cyprus employed scenario-based training with AI forecasting to prepare learners for real-world energy challenges.

Structured evaluations across these pilot activities confirmed positive effects on creative engagement, interdisciplinary interaction, and the quality of project outcomes. Figure 2 presents student ratings of how different methods supported creative thinking, while Table 2 reports the frequency of AI-assisted tool use.

Table 2: Frequency of AI-supported tool use in selected partner institutions during EDDIE pilot activities

Country	Institution	AI Tool Type	Course Area	Use Frequency (%)
Greece	NTUA	Predictive Modelling	Smart Buildings	85
Germany	RWTH	ML Grid Simulations	Smart Grids	78
Italy	POLIMI	Generative Design	Architecture	92
Sweden	KTH	Digital Twins (VR)	Urban Planning	88
Cyprus	University of Cyprus	Sensor-Driven AI	Energy Systems	81

Figure 3. Increase in learners’ confidence using AI-supported tools before and after the pilot modules.

Framework for creativity-driven AI education

- **Problem-based learning** for authentic engagement;
- **Digital tools enabling exploration and manipulation** of complex systems;

- **Interdisciplinary collaboration** to broaden perspectives;
- **Embedded ethical reflection** on data use and algorithmic bias; and
- **Iterative, student-led project cycles** supported by adaptive AI.

3. Micro-credentials and the Recognition of Skills

Recognition of learning is evolving as quickly as labour-market demands. For decades, long-form degrees and diplomas served as the primary proof of competence. Today, that model is complemented by micro-credentials: short, digital certifications that document specific competences. Unlike traditional degrees, they allow learners to progress in smaller, stackable steps and adapt more rapidly to technological and economic change (Oliver, 2019; CEDEFOP, 2023).

Micro-credentials offer immediacy, flexibility and measurable labour-market responsiveness—qualities increasingly valued by professionals who must update their skills repeatedly across a working life. At the same time, participation in adult learning and basic digital skills remain below European targets, highlighting the need for qualifications that are portable, trustworthy and straightforward to use.

European policy now provides a shared definition and quality elements for micro-credentials. The detailed governance and trust mechanisms are analysed in the following section. Here, the focus is on how micro-credentials operate in practice and on the learner experience of earning and using them.

The aforementioned projects illustrate the potential of this approach. HYBOT demonstrated the feasibility of micro-credentials by aligning modular staff-training courses with recognised European competence frameworks, allowing academic staff to document specific digital-teaching competences in a form that can be transported across institutions and national systems. EDDIE piloted a blockchain-enabled credential marketplace to issue and store micro-credentials, strengthening portability and learner agency. These pilots show that human-centred design is both feasible and scalable when technology serves clearly articulated educational aims.

Figure 4 : HYBOT in Numbers

A bar chart summarising the number of participants, completed chatbot prototypes and key learning outcomes.

Figure 5: EDDIE Outputs and Marketplace

An infographic showing key quantitative outputs (occupational profiles, training programmes, pilot participants) and the architecture of the blockchain-enabled marketplace.

Taken together, these initiatives demonstrate that micro-credentials are more than a technical innovation. They represent a shift in the social contract of higher education, enabling learners to build verifiable evidence of competence in smaller, cumulative steps; providing employers with more precise indicators of skills and challenging universities to develop new mechanisms of quality assurance, equity and recognition. When anchored in trusted European frameworks and supported by transparent governance, micro-credentials can reconcile flexibility with rigour and learner agency with institutional accountability

Figure 6 : European Skills and Trust Ecosystem

European Frameworks and Governance for Trusted Digital Learning

The credibility of micro-credentials, personalised pathways and artificial intelligence in higher education depends not only on the quality of individual projects but also on the institutional and regulatory ecosystems in which they operate. Over the past decade, Europe has progressively constructed a *multi-layered*

governance architecture that provides the normative, technical and legal foundations for trusted digital learning. This architecture combines outcome frameworks, quality mechanisms and secure infrastructures into what can be described as a **European trust infrastructure for credentials and data**.

At the heart of this emerging system sits the **European Qualifications Framework (EQF)**, which sets out eight reference levels of knowledge, skills and responsibility and provides a common language for describing learning outcomes across national contexts. The EQF serves not only as a classificatory tool but also as a meta-framework that enables comparability and cross-border portability of qualifications. Complementing the EQF is **ESCO (European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations)**, a multilingual taxonomy cataloguing thousands of occupations and skills (European Commission, 2023). Together, EQF and ESCO allow micro-credentials to be expressed in outcome-based terms that can be readily understood by employers, institutions and learners throughout Europe.

Credit systems reinforce this outcome-oriented architecture. **The European Credit System for Vocational Education and Training (ECVET)** and **the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS)** provide mechanisms for quantifying workload and for transferring and accumulating credits across institutions and borders. Their integration into micro-credential design ensures that short-form learning carries recognised credit value and can be stacked towards larger qualifications. Quality assurance is further supported by the **European Quality Assurance in Vocational Education and Training (EQAVET)** indicators, which offer benchmarks for transparency and continuous improvement.

Digital competence frameworks add another essential layer. The **DigComp framework** specifies levels of digital competence for citizens, while **DigCompEDU** focuses on educators' digital teaching capabilities (Carretero et al., 2022). By articulating competences for both learners and educators, these frameworks enable universities to benchmark the digital skills addressed in micro-credential programmes and to align assessment methods with recognised standards.

These content and quality frameworks rest on secure digital infrastructures that guarantee verifiability and legal validity. The **Europass Digital Credentials** service issues credentials as digitally signed electronic documents, ensuring long-term authenticity and machine-readable portability. Combined with the **eIDAS Regulation**, which establishes the legal force of electronic signatures across the European Union, this infrastructure allows a micro-credential awarded in one country to be authenticated and trusted in another without further verification. The EDDIE project's blockchain-enabled Digital Credential Marketplace extends these capabilities by issuing and storing credentials on a decentralised ledger. At the same time it remains fully compliant with Europass and eIDAS standards, illustrating how emerging technologies can strengthen the permanence and cross-border integrity of digital credentials.

Recent policy initiatives further consolidate this governance landscape. **The Council Recommendation on micro-credentials (2022)** sets out shared definitions, quality elements and implementation guidelines to steer national adoption. **The Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027** calls for high-performing digital education ecosystems supported by robust infrastructure and digitally skilled educators (European Commission, 2021). The forthcoming **Artificial Intelligence Act** introduces a risk-based regulatory framework for AI applications, including those used in education, requiring transparency, human oversight and safeguards against discrimination (European Commission, 2024). Collectively, these instruments establish not only technical standards but also normative expectations of fairness, accountability and human agency.

Analytically, this governance constellation represents a polycentric model of digital regulation. Authority is distributed across European institutions, national governments, credential issuers and technology providers. Such a model fosters innovation while maintaining a common floor of trust, but it also raises challenges of coordination, compliance and continual updating as technologies evolve. Scholars of digital governance note

that sustaining interoperability and legal certainty in such a rapidly changing environment demands ongoing policy learning and active stakeholder engagement.

The experience of projects such as EDDIE highlights both the opportunities and the demands of this environment. By designing micro-credentials aligned with EQF levels, embedding DigComp competences and issuing credentials through Europass-compliant blockchain platforms, EDDIE operationalised the European trust infrastructure in a concrete sectoral setting. At the same time, it exposed the practical complexities of cross-border implementation, from divergent national accreditation practices to variations in institutional digital capacity.

In sum, the European frameworks outlined here provide more than administrative scaffolding. They form the enabling conditions for a human-centred digital university. They ensure that micro-credentials can circulate across borders without loss of value, that AI-enabled learning systems remain accountable to human oversight, and that personalised learning pathways are recognised within a coherent and legally secure qualification space. The next challenge is to maintain this delicate balance between innovation and regulation, ensuring that the governance mechanisms themselves remain adaptable to future technological and societal change.

Personalised Pathways

Designing learning that is both rigorous and responsive has become a defining challenge for contemporary higher education. For much of the twentieth century, universities relied on standardised curricula to guarantee fairness and comparability. While this model offered clarity, it is increasingly ill-suited to a world in which students arrive with diverse prior knowledge, change careers multiple times and expect study routes that adapt to their personal circumstances (OECD, 2023). **Personalised learning pathways represent a necessary evolution: instead of requiring every learner to follow a single route, adaptive approaches recognise different starting points, goals and rhythms.**

Advances in artificial intelligence and learning analytics have brought large-scale personalisation within practical reach. Adaptive platforms can monitor engagement, detect difficulties and recommend targeted support, yielding measurable gains in persistence and performance (Frontiers in Education, 2024). AI-enabled systems extend these capabilities from reactive adjustment to proactive guidance, using predictive indicators and recommender algorithms to suggest next steps and uncover latent skill gaps. Yet technology alone is not sufficient. Meaningful personalisation depends on thoughtful instructional design, human oversight and the institutional capacity to act on the insights generated. European pilot projects illustrate how these principles operate in practice. EDDIE applied adaptive dashboards to offer tailored feedback, and HYBOT provided modular pathways for educators, illustrating different modes of personalisation.

Personalisation, however, raises important ethical and practical questions. Adaptive systems may reproduce bias if trained on incomplete data, and an excessive focus on efficiency risks narrowing rather than broadening learning opportunities. UNESCO (2019) and the OECD (2023) call for transparency, explainability and safeguards against discrimination in all AI-supported educational systems. Recent frameworks for Responsible AI in Learning Analytics translate these principles into operational requirements such as explicable model behaviour, documented human-in-the-loop decision points and continuous bias monitoring. Universities must ensure that personalised pathways empower learners to explore, create and take intellectual risks, rather than confining them to predefined tracks. Recognition frameworks provide the institutional scaffolding that lends personalised learning credibility. When outcomes are expressed in the language of the European Qualifications Framework and secured via Europass Digital Credentials, achievements can be verified and transported across institutions and national systems. Combined with

responsible AI practices, these mechanisms show that personalised pathways can reconcile flexibility with rigour and learner agency with institutional accountability.

AI’s Role in Education

Artificial intelligence has moved from a peripheral tool to a structural capability in higher education, enabling personalisation, predictive analytics and real-time feedback at scales traditional curricula cannot match. Instead of replacing educators, AI **augments** their capacity to design learning that is rigorous and responsive—supporting dialogue, creativity and higher-order thinking while relieving them of routine tasks.

Evidence from European pilots reinforces this perspective. In both projects, AI was embedded within recognised competence and credential frameworks. Adaptive dashboards and tutoring systems proved effective only when linked to explicit outcomes and mediated by active teaching. These cases show that algorithmic recommendations gain educational value only when translated into actionable interventions that respect academic standards and learner agency.

The growing use of AI raises pressing **governance and ethical** issues. Algorithms may perpetuate bias, opaque models obscure decision logic, and large-scale data collection heightens privacy concerns. UNESCO (2019, 2021) and the OECD (2023) call for transparency, explainability and safeguards against discrimination, while the forthcoming EU AI Act establishes a risk-based framework requiring human oversight and continuous monitoring for high-risk applications. Recent proposals for Responsible AI in Learning Analytics operationalise these principles through bias auditing, explicable model behaviour and documented human-in-the-loop checkpoints.

Figure 7 : Conceptual Layers of AI Impact in Higher Education

Figure 7 illustrates three nested layers of AI’s impact in higher education: pedagogy and human oversight at the core, technical systems in the middle, and governance and policy on the outer ring. It shows that integration depends less on technical novelty than on pedagogical design and institutional responsibility. When aligned with trusted recognition frameworks and transparent governance, AI can enhance learning, support personalisation and preserve academic values—laying the foundation for a human-centred digital university.

Towards a Human-Centred Digital University

The rapid uptake of AI, micro-credentials and personalised learning has created major opportunities for innovation in higher education, while also exposing pedagogical and ethical tensions. Evidence shows that AI-enabled personalisation supports persistence, engagement and achievement only when embedded in well-designed curricula and governed by transparent frameworks. In this role, **AI strengthens rather than replaces educators**.

Meta-analyses of adaptive learning (2024–2025) report uneven but significant gains, strongest when AI is paired with mentoring and formative feedback rather than used in isolation (Frontiers in Education, 2024). Reviews of responsible-AI frameworks stress that fairness, explainability and bias auditing are prerequisites for long-term trust (Morales Tirado et al., 2024). Overall, success depends as much on institutional culture and governance as on algorithms.

The pilot applications illustrate this principle. Their contribution does not lie in specific platforms but in demonstrating how AI and micro-credentials can be orchestrated within recognised European frameworks to balance flexibility with accountability. By linking adaptive tools to explicit competences and portable credentials, these projects show that human-centred design is both feasible and scalable when technology serves clearly articulated educational aims.

Salman Khan's *Brave New Words* (2024) envisions intelligent systems relieving teachers of routine tasks so they can focus on dialogue, mentoring and higher-order thinking. Khanmigo exemplifies this through a Socratic mode that provides personalised prompts while keeping the educator in the loop. Khan also warns of risks—bias, hallucinations, unequal access and opaque data—and calls for explainability, bias auditing and human oversight. His conclusions echo this paper: learning gains from AI depend less on novelty than on pedagogical purpose, professional development and strong governance.

A human-centred digital university is defined not by technology itself but by an **architecture of trust** (see **Figure 7**), where technology remains subordinate to educational purpose and democratic accountability.

Looking ahead, universities must combine AI investment with professional development, robust data governance and participatory mechanisms that involve students in decisions about data use. European frameworks such as the EQF, Europass Digital Credentials and the forthcoming AI Act provide regulatory scaffolding, but their effectiveness depends on active engagement by academic communities. Only by foregrounding human agency and institutional responsibility can the digital university become not just efficient, but equitable, creative and resilient.

Conclusions

The central question posed in the abstract—Which teaching methods best foster creativity and critical thinking, and how AI might enhance them—is answered by evidence from Erasmus+ pilots, meta-analyses and European policy frameworks. Creativity thrives in **problem-based and collaborative settings** supported by **formative feedback** and explicit competence goals. Traditional formats such as studios, laboratories and capstones remain effective when centred on authentic problems and iterative design cycles, not when adopting technology for its own sake.

Artificial intelligence strengthens these environments only when it is treated as a **pedagogical instrument** rather than a stand-alone solution. Intelligent simulations, generative design tools and adaptive dashboards can widen the design space, surface misconceptions early and provide rapid first-pass feedback, but their educational value depends on thoughtful instructional design and active human mediation. The most

consistent gains appear when algorithms are transparent, recommendations are explainable and teachers remain central in guiding interpretation and next steps.

Recognition mechanisms complete the cycle. **Micro-credentials**, aligned with frameworks such as the EQF and Europass Digital Credentials, translate creative work into **portable, trustworthy evidence of competence**. In the pilots, portability motivated learners and enabled cross-border verification without diluting standards. Governance arrangements—quality assurance, competence frameworks and lawful digital credentialing—are not bureaucratic afterthoughts but the enabling conditions linking pedagogy to social and labour-market recognition.

The implications for universities are clear. Lasting impact requires curriculum design that integrates AI tools with problem-centred learning, professional development that equips educators to interpret and act on AI feedback, and data-governance policies that protect privacy while supporting evidence-based improvement. Where these conditions are met, AI frees educators to focus on mentoring, questioning and cultivating judgement: it **serves as a scaffold for human judgement, not a substitute**.

Glossary

Artificial Intelligence (AI) – Computer systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as pattern recognition, decision-making and natural language processing.

Council Recommendation on a European Approach to Micro-credentials (2022) – EU policy document establishing a shared definition, quality criteria and implementation guidelines for micro-credentials across Member States.

Creativity Ratings – Comparative scores (self-, peer- and instructor-rated on a 10-point scale) used in the EDDIE pilots to evaluate the perceived creativity of student outputs.

DigComp / DigCompEDU – The European Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp) and its educator version (DigCompEDU), which define levels of digital literacy and teaching competence.

ECVET / ECTS – European Credit systems for vocational education and training (ECVET) and higher education (ECTS) that allow transfer and accumulation of learning credits.

EDDIE (Education for the Digitalisation of Energy) – A 2020–2024 Erasmus+ Sector Skills Alliance that developed AI-enabled training, creativity pilots and a blockchain-secured Digital Credential Marketplace.

EQF (European Qualifications Framework) – An eight-level reference framework describing learning outcomes in terms of knowledge, skills and responsibility to promote cross-border recognition of qualifications.

ESCO – European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations; a multilingual classification of jobs and skills used to map occupational profiles.

Europass Digital Credentials (EDC) – EU infrastructure that issues verifiable, digitally signed credentials compliant with the eIDAS Regulation.

Hybrid Teaching – A pedagogical model that combines on-campus and online students in the same synchronous or asynchronous learning environment.

HYBOT – Erasmus+ project “Enhancing Hybrid Teaching in Higher Education through Chatbots,” which developed an ECTS-accredited micro-credential for chatbot design.

Micro-credential – A short, targeted qualification that certifies specific competences or learning outcomes, typically issued in digital form.

Sector Skills Alliance – An Erasmus+ partnership type that brings together education providers, industry and policy makers to address sectoral skill needs.

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Empowering TESOL Student Teachers Through Generative AI. A Course-Based Study on Digital Lesson Design in Higher Education

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Abstract

This study investigates how TESOL student teachers integrate generative artificial intelligence (AI) into lesson design within a higher education course. Conducted at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (October 2024–January 2025), the study involved 38 undergraduate student teachers who worked in pairs to produce 19 digital lesson projects using tools such as ChatGPT, Canva, Grammarly, and Padlet. A qualitative thematic analysis of the projects and reflections revealed that student teachers perceived AI as a supportive tool for generating content, scaffolding skills, and personalizing tasks. Generative AI use enabled innovative practices, including escape rooms, role-play scenarios, and multimodal lessons, while also raising concerns around accuracy, originality, and dependency. Findings highlight the dual role of AI as both a catalyst for creativity and a source of ethical and professional challenges. The study underscores the importance of embedding AI literacy into TESOL teacher education to balance innovation with critical pedagogy, preparing pre-service teachers for responsible integration of AI in language learning contexts.

Keywords

Generative AI; TESOL; Teacher Education; Critical Digital Pedagogy; Lesson Design; AI Literacy; Pre-service Teachers

1. Introduction

The rapid emergence of generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming educational practice and raising new challenges for teacher education. Far from being a supplementary tool, AI is increasingly viewed as part of a paradigm shift in education, reshaping how learning materials are produced, personalized, and delivered (Gentile, Citta, Perna, and Allegra, 2023).

ChatGPT, Canva, and other AI-powered applications allow teachers to generate texts, design visuals, scaffold vocabulary and grammar tasks, and create interactive learning experiences at unprecedented speed and scale.

These developments are particularly significant for the field of TESOL (Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages) (Mavridi, 2025). Language learning requires not only exposure to content but also interaction, scaffolding, and cultural awareness—areas where the teacher’s role remains central (Zawacki-Richter, Marin, Bond, and Gouverneur, 2019). While AI can support efficiency and creativity in lesson preparation, it cannot replace the pedagogical judgment and interpersonal skills that define effective language teaching. This duality creates both opportunities and responsibilities for teacher education programs.

Research to date highlights two key insights. First, teachers and student teachers often perceive AI positively as a time-saving and creativity-enhancing partner (Holmes et al., 2022; Balatero, Jayno, & Miranda, 2024), but they also recognize its limitations, including risks of plagiarism, bias, and dependency (Li and Wu, 2025).

Second, generative AI is already being used in classrooms to support content generation, scaffolding, gamification, and personalization, though its effectiveness depends on how teachers adapt and mediate these outputs (Dwivedi, Hughes, Baabdullah, Ribeiro-Navarrete, Giannakis, Al-Debei, and Wamba, 2023; Ghadimi and Griffiths, 2025; Mavridi, 2025).

Despite this growing body of work, little is known about how pre-service TESOL teachers—who are still forming their professional identities—engage with generative AI in authentic course contexts. Do they view AI as supportive or problematic? What kinds of pedagogical applications do they attempt? And how do they balance innovation with concerns over quality and ethics?

This study addresses these questions by analyzing 19 lesson design projects created by 38 undergraduate TESOL student teachers. The research focuses on three guiding questions:

1. How do TESOL student teachers perceive the integration of generative AI in lesson design?
2. What types of pedagogical applications do they develop using AI?
3. How does AI integration affect the quality, personalization, and innovation of their teaching materials?

By addressing these questions, the study contributes to the growing field of AI in teacher education, offering insights into how generative tools can be responsibly embedded into TESOL curricula to empower future teachers while cultivating critical AI literacy.

2.1 AI in Education: A Paradigm Shift

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has often been described as a paradigm shift that redefines the roles of teachers and learners. Gentile et al. (2023) argue that AI is reshaping the classroom from a teacher-centered model toward more adaptive, learner-centered approaches. Kalantzis and Cope (2025) similarly conceptualize this shift as a transformation in literacy practices, where human–AI collaboration redefines meaning-making and the role of teachers as designers of digital learning ecologies. With the ability to generate instructional content, automate feedback, and create personalized learning pathways, AI offers unprecedented opportunities for educational innovation. However, these advances also

demand a reconfiguration of the teacher’s role, positioning educators as facilitators, mentors, and designers of learning experiences rather than as the sole transmitters of knowledge (Cope, Kalantzis, and Searsmith, 2021).

For TESOL, this shift is particularly significant. Language learning depends heavily on interaction, scaffolding, and affective support—dimensions that AI cannot fully replicate. While AI can enhance efficiency and provide access to diverse resources, it cannot replace the human teacher in cultivating intercultural awareness, communicative competence, and critical thinking (Zawacki-Richter, Marín, Bond, & Gouverneur, 2019). This tension underscores the importance of examining how TESOL student teachers perceive AI, how they incorporate it into practice, and how they navigate its benefits and limitations.

2.2 TESOL Student Teachers’ Perceptions of AI

Teacher perceptions play a pivotal role in determining whether AI tools are adopted meaningfully or resisted in practice. Research suggests that many teachers and student teachers view AI tools such as ChatGPT as supportive partners capable of saving time, reducing cognitive load, and providing inspiration for lesson

planning (Holmes et al., 2022). For pre-service teachers who are still developing their pedagogical repertoire, AI can act as a scaffold that enhances creativity and builds confidence in lesson design.

Nevertheless, perceptions of AI are often balanced rather than uncritically positive. Concerns have been raised about the accuracy of AI-generated content, the risk of plagiarism, and the danger of over-reliance on automated outputs (Li and Wu, 2025). For this reason, TESOL scholars emphasize the necessity of cultivating AI literacy—the ability to evaluate, refine, and ethically integrate AI outputs into teaching practice (Kohnke & Zou, 2025). Exploring how student teachers negotiate this balance between opportunity and risk provides valuable insight into how teacher education programs can prepare them for responsible AI integration.

2.3 Pedagogical Applications of AI in TESOL

The literature identifies a wide range of pedagogical applications of generative AI in language education. One of the most common is content generation, with AI being used to produce reading passages, dialogues, vocabulary lists, and grammar exercises (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Karakaya, Alpat, Uçar, Karakaya, Özlem, and Bozkurt, 2025). In addition, AI can support the scaffolding of language skills, helping teachers simplify texts, adapt grammar explanations, or model pronunciation for learners at different proficiency levels (Ghadimi and Griffiths, 2025).

Another emerging application is gamification and interactivity, where AI-generated prompts and materials are integrated into platforms such as Padlet, Wordwall, Kahoot, and Genially. These combinations can create interactive and motivating tasks that go beyond traditional formats (Kohnke, Moorhouse, and Zou, 2023). Finally, AI's potential for CEFR alignment should be highlighted, since teachers can adapt AI outputs to specific proficiency levels and ensure consistency with international benchmarks.

In teacher education, these applications are particularly valuable. They allow pre-service teachers to experiment with blended and online pedagogies, to test innovative lesson formats, and to combine established scaffolding strategies with new digital tools. Importantly, research stresses that AI is most effective when embedded within clear pedagogical frameworks and when teachers act as mediators who adapt AI outputs to context rather than using them uncritically (Gentile et al., 2023; Karakaya et al., 2025).

2.4 Impact of AI on Lesson Quality, Personalization, and Innovation

A recurring theme in the literature is the potential of AI to improve the quality and adaptability of teaching materials. By automating routine tasks and reducing preparation time, AI enables teachers to devote greater attention to higher-order design and pedagogy (Holmes et al., 2022; Chan, 2025). Teachers report that AI can facilitate personalization, allowing them to tailor vocabulary, texts, and activities to the needs of different learner profiles, thereby enhancing inclusivity and responsiveness.

At the same time, AI supports innovation in lesson design. Studies have documented the rise of multimodal projects, role-play simulations, and gamified activities that were previously difficult to create within limited preparation timelines (Heydari, 2025). These affordances are particularly relevant to TESOL, where engagement, authentic communication, and learner autonomy are central pedagogical aims.

However, scholars also caution that these benefits come with risks (Li and Wu, 2025). AI systems may generate fabricated references, biased content, or homogenized outputs, all of which

undermine quality if not carefully monitored. Likewise, Dooly and O’Dowd (2018) emphasize that genuine innovation requires embedding AI within a framework of critical digital pedagogy that promotes reflection, collaboration, and critical awareness, rather than passive adoption.

2.5 Ethical Considerations in AI Integration

The ethical dimension of AI use in education has gained growing attention. Principles of transparency, accountability, and originality as essential safeguards for academic and pedagogical uses of generative AI (Li and Wu, 2025; Heydari, 2025). Without such measures, there is a risk of undermining academic integrity, encouraging dependency, and eroding trust in educational practices.

These concerns are particularly pressing for TESOL teacher education. Student teachers need to learn to verify the accuracy of AI-generated materials, distinguish between their own contributions and those of AI, and reflect critically on issues such as bias, fairness, and the implications of relying on proprietary systems. Embedding these dimensions within teacher education ensures that future TESOL professionals use AI responsibly and are equipped to guide their learners in navigating AI-mediated environments.

2.6 Synthesis and Research Gap

Taken together, the literature converges on three central insights. First, teachers generally perceive AI as a supportive tool, but they also recognize challenges related to accuracy, originality, and the risk of over-reliance (Holmes et al., 2022; Li and Wu., 2025). Second, AI is being applied in diverse ways—including content generation, scaffolding, gamification, and CEFR alignment—yet these applications require careful adaptation by teachers to suit specific learning contexts (Dwivedi et al., 2023; Kohnke et al., 2023; Xeri, 2025). Third, AI has the potential to enhance quality, personalization, and innovation, but only when used critically and ethically (Gentile et al., 2023; Dooly & O’Dowd, 2018).

Despite these insights, a notable gap remains in the research. While much of the existing work focuses on practicing teachers or theoretical explorations of AI in education, relatively little is known about how TESOL student teachers—who are at the earliest stages of their professional development—perceive, apply, and reflect on AI when designing lessons. This study seeks to address that gap by analyzing lesson design projects from undergraduate TESOL teacher education, providing empirical evidence of how pre-service teachers engage with AI in ways that both harness its creative affordances and acknowledge its limitations.

Figure 1. Literature review synthesis: Generative AI and TESOL

Responsible & Reflective AI Integration in TESOL (Critical Digital Pedagogy)

3. Research Methodology

This study employed a qualitative course-based research design, drawing on principles of design-based inquiry in teacher education. A qualitative approach was selected because the research questions focused on perceptions, practices, and pedagogical applications of

generative AI, rather than standardized outcomes. The study was conducted at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens between October 2024 and January 2025, as part of the undergraduate course 'Language Skills Development and Digital Media'. A total of 38 TESOL student teachers participated, working in pairs to complete a summative assignment that produced 19 digital lesson design projects. Since the projects were embedded in normal coursework, they provided ecological validity by capturing authentic pedagogical practices rather than simulated tasks.

Each project included educational scenarios, AI-generated and student-adapted materials, references to tools used (e.g., ChatGPT, Canva, Padlet, Wordwall), and embedded reflections, thereby constituting holistic units of analysis that combined pedagogical design with reflective commentary. The dataset was systematically organized, anonymized, and coded using a thematic framework aligned with the three research questions: (1) perceptions of AI in lesson design, (2) pedagogical applications, and (3) impact on quality, personalization, and innovation. Sub-themes were derived both deductively (from existing literature, such as AI for scaffolding or ethical concerns) and inductively (emerging from student projects, such as escape rooms or AI-generated role-play scenarios).

Coding proceeded through several stages: familiarization with the dataset, development of the coding matrix, line-by-line coding of each project, clustering of codes into themes, and triangulation of results. To strengthen credibility, both qualitative depth (illustrative excerpts) and quantitative breadth (frequency counts) were

considered, and results were visualized through bar charts and consolidated figures. This process ensured that common patterns were identified alongside unique and innovative practices.

Diagram 1. The stages of data processing (qualitative analysis)

The research adhered to the ethical guidelines of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens and international standards for educational research. Students were informed that anonymized assignments could be used for research purposes, identifiers were removed, and projects were coded numerically (Project 1–19). Findings are presented in aggregate to preserve confidentiality. The use of authentic coursework imposed no additional burden or grading bias, while academic honesty was safeguarded by acknowledging AI-generated contributions and incorporating student reflections on their ethical use. These measures ensured rigor, transparency, and trustworthiness while modeling responsible engagement with AI for future TESOL professionals.

4. Results

4.1 Perceptions of Generative AI in Lesson Design

Analysis of the 19 projects revealed that student teachers generally perceived generative AI as a supportive and empowering tool, though their perspectives were nuanced (Figure 2). A large majority (16/19, 84%) described AI as time-saving, creativity-enhancing, and useful for CEFR- appropriate activity design. Students emphasized AI’s ability to generate quizzes, texts, and prompts, suggest varied formats and visuals, and increase their confidence in lesson planning. At

the same time, more than half of the projects (11/19, 58%) flagged limitations such as inaccuracies, vague definitions, or over-generalized outputs that required teacher refinement. Ethical concerns also emerged in 7/19 projects (37%), with reflections on issues of originality, dependency, and bias. One project captured this

dual stance by noting that “ChatGPT gave us a useful starting vocabulary set for B2 learners, but we had to refine it to match context and accuracy.” Collectively, these findings suggest that student teachers viewed AI not as a replacement for their professional judgment but as an assistive partner that complemented their pedagogical decision-making.

Figure 2. Perceptions of Generative AI in Lesson Design (n=19)

Figure 3. Pedagogical Applications of AI in Lesson Design

4.2 Pedagogical Applications of AI

AI was employed across multiple domains of lesson design (Figure 3). The most common application was content generation, with 15/19 projects (79%) using AI to create reading passages, dialogues, gap-fill tasks, comprehension questions, vocabulary lists, and quizzes. In 13/19 projects (68%), AI was exploited to scaffold language skills, such as grammar practice, vocabulary development, reading comprehension, and pronunciation, covering levels from A2 to C2. Gamification and interactivity were also prominent, with 12/19 projects (63%) embedding

AI-generated content into platforms like Wordwall, Padlet, Kahoot, and Genially, sometimes designing digital escape rooms or collaborative activities. Finally, 9/19 projects (47%) explicitly addressed CEFR alignment, checking AI outputs for consistency with learner proficiency levels. For instance, one reading-focused project embedded AI-generated comprehension questions into a Genially escape room, while another used AI prompts to design role-play scenarios for modal verb practice. Vocabulary lessons also integrated AI-generated slang lists into Padlet discussions, encouraging collaboration and reflection. Across cases, AI was rarely used in isolation; rather, it was combined with established digital tools such as YouTube, Google Forms, and Canva to produce multimodal, learner-centered lessons.

4.3 Impact on Lesson Quality, Personalization, and Innovation

Findings indicate that AI contributed to improvements in lesson quality, personalization, and innovation, while also raising challenges that required critical oversight (Figure 4). Fourteen projects (74%) highlighted efficiency and quality gains, reporting that AI reduced preparation time and allowed teachers to focus more on design and pedagogy. Eleven projects (58%) emphasized personalization, noting that AI helped adapt content to different proficiency levels, age groups, or learner interests. A further 10 projects (53%) demonstrated innovation, introducing multimodal projects, escape rooms, role-play simulations, and marketing campaigns based on real-world data (e.g., Statista, Admango). At the same time, 8/19 projects (42%) pointed to challenges, including the need for refinement of AI outputs and ethical concerns over originality and dependency. For example, one project on advertising campaigns combined AI-generated slogans with Statista data and Padlet discussions, requiring learners to critique and adapt outputs collaboratively. Another integrated AI-generated texts into Padlet-based group reflections, reinforcing student agency and critical engagement.

4.4 Synthesis of Findings

Taken together, the results demonstrate that TESOL student teachers balanced enthusiasm for AI's creative affordances with critical awareness of its limitations (Figure 5). Specifically, they perceived AI as supportive (16/19), though concerns about accuracy and ethics were common (11/19); they applied AI most frequently for content generation (15/19), scaffolding (13/19), gamification (12/19), and CEFR alignment (9/19); and they reported improvements in lesson quality (14/19), personalization (11/19), and innovation (10/19), while nearly half of the projects acknowledged persistent challenges (8/19). Overall, the findings highlight how student teachers integrated AI in ways that supported learner engagement, adaptability, and reflective pedagogy.

Figure 4. Impact of AI on Lesson Quality, Personalization & Innovation

Figure 5. Synthesis of Findings across RQ1-RQ3

5. Discussion and Implications

This study explored how TESOL student teachers integrated generative AI into digital lesson design. The findings demonstrate that participants generally perceived AI positively, applied it across diverse pedagogical contexts, and leveraged it to improve lesson quality, personalization, and innovation. At the same time, they displayed critical awareness of AI's limitations, particularly in relation to accuracy, ethical use, and the risk of overreliance. These results confirm and extend insights from the literature, underscoring the dual role of AI as both a catalyst for pedagogical creativity and a source of ethical and professional challenges.

Importantly, the findings resonate with the framework summarized in Figure 1 (see Literature Review), which conceptualized AI integration in TESOL through four interrelated dimensions: paradigm shift, perceptions, pedagogical applications, and ethics. The student teachers' projects illustrated how these theoretical pillars translated into authentic practice.

One of the most consistent findings was that student teachers positioned AI as an assistive tool rather than a replacement for professional judgment. AI was used to support brainstorming, generate exercises, and adapt tasks to CEFR levels, thereby reducing cognitive load and freeing time for creative design. This reflects Holmes et al. (2022) and Chan (2025), who highlighted AI's role as a scaffolding mechanism that enhances productivity while maintaining pedagogical oversight. AI can empower pre-service teachers to experiment with lesson design, provided they remain active evaluators of outputs. These practices echo the paradigm shift dimension of Figure 1, where teachers transition from transmitters of knowledge to facilitators and designers of adaptive learning experiences (Gentile et al., 2023).

The study also highlights AI's potential to foster innovation and learner-centered pedagogy in TESOL. Student teachers incorporated interactive escape rooms, role-play scenarios, and multimodal tasks that enriched traditional lesson formats. These practices resonate with

research on digital pedagogy, which identifies AI's capacity to promote personalization, interactivity, and multimodality (Heydari, 2025). This corresponds directly to the pedagogical applications dimension of Figure 1, showing how AI can be mobilized not only for efficiency but also for creative, multimodal, and collaborative approaches.

Despite this enthusiasm, participants also expressed critical awareness and ethical concerns. Projects frequently reported that AI-generated exercises required editing and verification, while others cautioned against over-reliance or raised issues around originality and academic integrity. This critical stance reflects calls in the literature for developing AI literacy as both a technical and ethical competence (Li and Wu, 2025). It also aligns with the ethics dimension of Figure 1, where transparency, accountability, and originality were identified as essential for responsible use. As Heydari (2025) agrees, critical digital literacy requires teachers and learners alike to interrogate and contextualize digital outputs. The findings of this study show that pre-service teachers are already beginning to enact such dispositions.

These insights carry important implications for TESOL teacher education. Embedding AI tasks within authentic coursework enabled student teachers to develop both technical competence and reflective awareness of AI's affordances and limitations. This supports arguments that AI literacy must be integrated into teacher education alongside digital pedagogy, ensuring that future educators can use AI critically and responsibly. The course model employed in this study

— combining generative AI, collaborative digital tools, and CEFR-based task design — provides a replicable framework for other programs seeking to integrate AI without compromising educational rigor. Seen through the lens of Figure 1, this integration requires not only innovative applications but also constant reflection on the paradigm shifts and ethical imperatives shaping TESOL education.

At the same time, the study is not without limitations. Conducted within a single undergraduate course at one university, with 38 participants and 19 projects, the findings may not be generalizable to all TESOL contexts. Future research could extend this work by investigating the longitudinal impacts of AI on teacher identity and professional practice, examining learners' perspectives on AI-mediated lessons, and comparing experiences across institutions or cultural contexts. In addition, future studies could explore AI's role in areas not directly addressed here, such as assessment, feedback, and inclusive pedagogy. Such research would contribute to a fuller understanding of how AI shapes both pre-service teacher development and learner experiences in diverse TESOL environments.

6. Conclusion

This study set out to explore how TESOL student teachers integrated generative AI into digital lesson design within the context of a higher education course. Analysis of 19 projects produced by 38 participants revealed that pre-service teachers consistently perceived AI as a supportive and empowering tool. AI generated content, scaffolded grammar and vocabulary activities, and adapted materials to CEFR levels. Beyond these efficiency gains, it also facilitated innovation, enabling the design of escape rooms, multimodal presentations, role-play scenarios, and other interactive tasks that enriched traditional lesson formats.

At the same time, student teachers demonstrated a dual stance that balanced enthusiasm with caution. While they embraced AI's capacity to save time and enhance creativity, they were equally attentive to its limitations. Many participants noted the need to refine outputs, verify accuracy, and address ethical concerns related to originality, dependency, and fairness. This combination of openness and critical reflection illustrates the emergence of what the literature terms AI literacy: the capacity not only to use AI tools effectively, but also to evaluate, adapt, and embed them responsibly in pedagogical practice.

The findings underscore that generative AI should not be viewed as a substitute for pedagogical expertise but rather as a catalyst for reflective practice and creativity. When integrated into authentic coursework, AI enabled student teachers to experiment with new pedagogical approaches while remaining mindful of professional standards and ethical responsibilities. This balance aligns with current scholarship in digital pedagogy and critical TESOL education, which stresses the need for teachers to act as mediators who adapt technology to context rather than adopting it uncritically.

Taken together, the study contributes to ongoing debates about the role of AI in education by showing how future TESOL professionals engage with it at the formative stage of their training. By situating the results within the broader dimensions outlined in the literature (see Figure 1), the study demonstrates that meaningful AI integration requires balancing creativity with caution, opportunity with responsibility, and innovation with ethics. The evidence suggests that, with appropriate scaffolding, pre-service teachers can harness AI to design adaptive, inclusive, and engaging lessons while cultivating the reflective dispositions needed for responsible use.

More broadly, the study highlights how AI integration in teacher education can foster both technical competence and critical awareness, equipping the next generation of language educators to navigate the challenges and opportunities of an evolving digital landscape responsibly.

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The Role of Open Educational Resources in the Teaching Community: A Case Study of ENCORE

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Abstract

Open Educational Resources (OER) are fundamental to fostering innovation and digital equity in the globalized educational landscape. The ENCORE platform, developed under the Erasmus+ programme, aims to facilitate the sustainable and circular use of OER, promoting educators' digital and green competencies. This study investigates the perceptions of the teaching community regarding the ENCORE platform and assesses its potential as an effective enabler of open education practices. We employed a mixed-methods survey, distributed to 54 educators (N=54) participating in a teacher training activity across various Greek higher education institutions (results refer only to the Greek pilot study). The instrument measured perception, infrastructure readiness, and behavioral intention using both open-ended questions and a 5-point Likert scale. The quantitative results reveal a consistently high level of positive acceptance and perceived utility for ENCORE. The highest scores were related to the interest of participants, the usefulness of the solution (ENCORE platform) and clarity of interaction. Crucially, participants also expressed strong positive behavioral intentions, planning to use and recommend the platform to colleagues. However, the study identified areas for refinement: scores related to institutional support and user proficiency were moderate, suggesting room for improvement in organizational backing and targeted user training. The findings affirm ENCORE's strong promise as an effective, user-endorsed tool for integrating OER into higher education. The study underscores that while individual user acceptance is high, wider, long-term adoption hinges on strengthening systemic institutional support and addressing technical integration challenges.

Keywords

Open Educational Resources, Educational Technology, Open Data

1. Introduction

In the digital era, Open Educational Resources (OER) have emerged as a transformative force in education. Defined by UNESCO (2002) as "teaching, learning and research materials in any medium that reside in the public domain or have been released under an open license," OER provide a flexible, accessible, and cost-effective means to foster innovation in pedagogy and lifelong learning (Butcher, 2011; Wiley & Hilton, 2018).

As the educational landscape adapts to the challenges of globalisation, remote learning, and digital equity, the integration of OER has gained increasing importance (de los Arcos et al., 2016). Within this context, the ENCORE platform, developed under the Erasmus+ programme, aims to enrich education by promoting the circular use of open educational resources. This study explores how educators perceive ENCORE and assesses its potential as an enabler of sustainable, open education.

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2. What are Open Educational Resources?

OER encompass a variety of digital learning tools: open textbooks, curricula, lecture notes, tests, software, and multimedia. Their defining feature lies in the 5R framework proposed by Wiley (2007): retain, reuse, revise, remix, and redistribute.

The pedagogical value of OER lies not only in cost savings, but also in the promotion of open pedagogies that empower both educators and learners (Hilton, 2016). Moreover, OER have proven to support innovation in instructional design, enhance learner engagement, and facilitate international collaboration (Kimmons, 2015).

Platforms like ENCORE contribute to these efforts by curating high-quality, domain-specific resources aligned with educational and sustainability goals. It serves as a repository and toolkit for educators aiming to enhance their digital and green competencies.

3. Methodology

The current study utilized a mixed-methods survey distributed to participants of a teacher training activity within the ENCORE project. The instrument included both open- and closed-ended questions. Quantitative items were measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree) to assess perception, infrastructure readiness, and behavioural intention.

Fifty-four (N=54) valid responses were collected. Participants represented a variety of Greek higher education institutions, including the Hellenic Open University (EAP), International Hellenic University (DIPAE), and the University of Ioannina.

4. Results

Participant Demographics and Motivation

Regarding participant's perceptions about Encore project, all of them answered positively in the question whether ENCORE can improve education (short text). Two participants coined the need researchers to collaborate closer with educators.

Most respondents were aged between 20 and 25 years (Figure 1), indicating strong interest in OER among younger educators. Participants cited reasons such as interest in open learning, pedagogical innovation, and the novelty of ENCORE as motives for their involvement.

Figure 1: Age distribution of the study participants

Quantitative Summary on Perception of OERs and the ENCORE platform

The survey results indicate an overall positive perception of the ENCORE platform among respondents. The highest mean score was observed for the question “Overall, how interesting did you find the ENCORE project?” (M = 4.29, SD = 0.71), suggesting that participants found the project engaging and appealing. Similarly, high mean values were recorded for items related to usefulness (M = 4.18, SD = 0.82), clarity of interaction (M = 4.18, SD = 0.72), and the ability of ENCORE to facilitate learning with OERs efficiently (M = 4.14, SD = 0.70). These findings imply that users generally view ENCORE as a supportive and effective tool for engaging with open educational resources.

Moderate mean values were obtained for items assessing user proficiency and ease of use (e.g., “I am proficient in using ENCORE,” M = 3.89, SD = 0.87; “It’s easy for me to drive ENCORE to do what I want,” M = 3.92, SD = 0.94), indicating that while participants found the system manageable, there is room for improvement in usability and user confidence. Items related to social influence and organizational support produced slightly lower averages, with “Seniors in my organization are supportive of using ENCORE” receiving one of the lowest mean scores (M = 3.52, SD = 0.99), suggesting that institutional endorsement may not yet be fully established.

The lowest mean score was found for “ENCORE is not compatible with other systems I use” (M = 2.81, SD = 1.12), which, being a negatively worded item, further reinforces the generally positive evaluation of ENCORE’s compatibility and integration. Finally, participants expressed positive behavioral intentions, as reflected in the relatively high means for “I plan to use ENCORE in the future” (M = 3.92, SD = 0.90) and “I would recommend ENCORE to my colleagues” (M = 3.96, SD = 0.96). Overall, the results suggest that users hold favorable attitudes toward ENCORE in terms of interest, usefulness, and future adoption potential, though further efforts to strengthen institutional support and user training could enhance uptake.

The following table summarizes the average ratings and standard deviations across key constructs (Table 1).

Table 1: The responses of study participants to the closed questions

Questions	Mean	SD
1. Overall, how interesting did you find the ENCORE project?	4.29	0.710
2. How satisfactorily have you achieved your goals?	4.00	0.816
3. I find ENCORE useful for my learning about OERs	4.18	0.818
4. Using ENCORE could allow me to complete educational activities with OERs more quickly.	4.14	0.704
5. Using ENCORE increases my productivity in learning on OERs.	4.03	0.744
6. My interaction with ENCORE is clear and understandable.	4.18	0.721
7. I am proficient in using ENCORE.	3.888	0.874
8. Learning to use ENCORE is easy for me.	4.00	0.902
9. It's easy for me to drive ENCORE to do what I want.	3.92	0.939
10. The people I consider important believe that I should use OERs/ENCORE.	4.00	0.902
11. People who influence me believe that I should use OERs/ENCORE.	3.81	0.944
12. Seniors in my organization are supportive of using ENCORE.	3.518	0.995
13. In general, the University has supported the use of OERs and ENCORE could be a platform to consider for use.	4.03	0.881
14. I have the necessary resources to use ENCORE.	4.07	0.766
15. I have the necessary knowledge to use ENCORE.	4.03	0.744
16. ENCORE is not compatible with other systems I use.	2.81	1.123

17.I plan to use ENCORE in the future.	3.92	0.899
18.I would recommend ENCORE to my colleagues.	3.96	0.961

Overall, these findings reveal a consistently high level of acceptance and perceived utility, with the only notable reservation concerning system compatibility. More specifically, the survey findings indicate that ENCORE is perceived positively by users, who find it engaging, useful, and compatible with their learning activities involving OERs. Participants generally feel capable of using the platform, and most express intentions to continue using it and recommend it to others. However, moderate scores on proficiency and social support highlight areas for improvement, particularly in enhancing user confidence and strengthening institutional backing. Overall, the results suggest that ENCORE has strong potential as an effective tool for facilitating learning with OERs, with minor refinements likely to further increase adoption and user satisfaction.

5. Conclusions

The findings of this study affirm the viability and relevance of OER, and specifically the ENCORE platform, in enhancing the quality of higher education. Participants exhibit high readiness and willingness to integrate OER into their professional practice, echoing findings from previous research (de los Arcos et al., 2016; Hilton, 2016). Systemic institutional support, availability of technical infrastructure, and training remain critical to long-term adoption. Similar surveys, such as the Open Education Research Hub (2014), have also highlighted the importance of peer collaboration and community support as enablers of OER use.

Moving forward, scaling the impact of ENCORE requires addressing technical integration challenges and fostering policy frameworks that recognize OER as core to educational transformation (UNESCO, 2021). Given the strong user endorsement and pedagogical relevance demonstrated here, ENCORE holds promise as a model for OER adoption in Greece and beyond.

Acknowledgment

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Transforming Greek Classrooms: Fostering the 4Cs through Innovation

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Abstract

The Erasmus+ 4C-Future project explores the integration of 21st-century competencies—critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication (4Cs)—into Greek secondary education. Within the framework of this project, a study was carried out that employed a qualitative research design, utilizing focus group discussions with secondary school teachers to gather insights on teaching practices, barriers, and resource needs.

Findings indicate a strong emphasis on student-centered, inquiry-based, and technology-enhanced learning approaches. Teachers identified methods such as inquiry-based learning, gamification, and digital storytelling as effective in fostering active learning and critical thinking. Digital tools and collaborative platforms are also highlighted as enhancing classroom interactivity and engagement.

Despite progress, the study reveals implementation challenges, including curriculum rigidity, limited resources, and insufficient teacher training. Teachers recommend ongoing professional development, improved technological infrastructure, increased access to digital resources, and more flexible curricula to support the effective integration of the 4Cs.

In conclusion, the 4C-Future project demonstrates the potential of innovative pedagogies to transform learning environments and align education with the demands of the digital age. However, addressing systemic challenges through policy alignment, investment, and professional support is crucial for sustainable educational transformation.

Keywords

4Cs, digital literacy, Greek Education, educational innovation, Erasmus+

1. Introduction (Calibri, 11 pt, bold)

As education around the world shifts towards equipping learners with 21st-century skills, Greece is embracing this shift by reforming its educational policies and pedagogical strategies. Central to these reforms is the promotion of the 4Cs - critical thinking, creativity, collaboration and communication. The Erasmus+ 4C Future project provides a framework for embedding these competencies in secondary education in Greece. The rapid technological, economic, and societal changes of the 21st century are transforming the landscape of education. In the context of these transformations, Greece has launched a series of educational reforms aimed at aligning its educational system with these evolving demands. While traditionally characterized by content-heavy curricula and teacher-centered instruction, the Greek education system is currently undergoing a paradigm shift toward learner-centered methodologies, digital integration, and competency-based instruction. These reforms are supported by initiatives such as the 'Skills Labs' (Ergastiria Dexiotiton), which seek to promote cross-curricular learning and student engagement.

2. Theoretical Framework and Context

The cultivation of transversal competencies—particularly critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication—has become a central focus in international education policies, recognized as essential competencies for students' success in the knowledge-based economy (OECD, 2018; World Economic Forum, 2020). These competencies, collectively referred to as the 4Cs, form a core pillar in international education policies and are progressively integrated into national curricula across Europe (Voogt & Roblin, 2012).

The 4C-FUTURE project directly addresses the need for these competencies by aiming to develop a comprehensive methodology and tools for their cultivation. This methodology will be grounded in gamified learning experiences and experiential learning strategies. The project also emphasizes the importance of fostering information and media literacy skills.

In the context of these transformations, Greece has launched a series of educational reforms aimed at aligning its educational system with these evolving demands. While traditionally characterized by content-heavy curricula and teacher-centered instruction, the Greek education system is currently undergoing a paradigm shift toward learner-centered methodologies, digital integration, and competency-based instruction. These reforms are supported by initiatives such as the "Skills Labs" (Ergastiria Dexiotiton), which seek to promote cross-curricular learning and student engagement.

The Erasmus+ 4C-Future project provides a structured framework for embedding the 4Cs within secondary education in Greece. The project's core objective is to empower teachers to effectively convey these 21st-century competencies to their students, creating a more engaging and impactful learning environment that prepares them for the challenges of the 21st century. This will be achieved through the development of an innovative framework that seamlessly integrates gamification into the educational process, motivating students and facilitating deeper learning.

The 4C-FUTURE project will be implemented through several key activities:

- Development of a tailored methodology based on research and teacher feedback
- Creation of a comprehensive toolset and guide for instructional resources
- Establishment of an online training platform for teachers' professional development
- Pilot training sessions to ensure effective implementation.

3. Method

This study employed a "qualitative research design", specifically adopting a "focus group discussion" methodology, as it allows for rich, interactive dialogue that reveals participants' experiences, perspectives, and insights on pedagogical practices (Krueger & Casey, 2014). The focus group methodology allowed for interactive, dynamic discussions, adding depth to the data collected and enabling the researchers to observe not only explicit verbal responses, but also group dynamics and consensus-building processes (Morgan, 1997). The design follows a constructivist paradigm, which emphasizes context-specific understanding and meaning-making (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). This approach was deemed appropriate for exploring the dynamic implementation of the 4Cs in Greek secondary education and the nuanced perspectives of teachers involved in this transformation.

3.1. Research Group (Sampling)

A purposive sampling strategy was employed to select a group of seven secondary school teachers (highly qualified, holding a position of responsibility and with many years of experience) representing a range of disciplines (mathematics, literature, physical education, biology, foreign languages, and computer science). Purposive sampling ensures that participants are particularly knowledgeable about or experienced with the phenomenon under study (Patton, 2015). Their diversity enabled a comprehensive view of the integration of the 4Cs into different educational contexts and pedagogical practices. This diversity facilitated also a

comprehensive exploration of innovative teaching methods, digital literacy integration and strategies to combat misinformation, ensuring robust and diverse perspectives, which are essential for triangulation and enhance the credibility of qualitative research (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

3.2. Data Collection (and Tools)

Data were gathered through a **90-minute structured focus group discussion** conducted online and guided by a semi-structured protocol covering themes such as digital literacy, pedagogical innovation, and challenges in addressing misinformation. The session was **audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim**, consistent with qualitative data collection best practices (Morgan, 1997). Field notes were also taken to record non-verbal cues and emerging themes during the interaction.

3.3. Research Procedures (Validity, Reliability, Trustworthiness)

Thematic analysis was conducted using Braun and Clarke's (2006) framework, ensuring a systematic and transparent approach to coding and theme development. To enhance trustworthiness, the study applied: (a) Credibility: Member checking was employed by sharing summary interpretations with participants for feedback. (b) Transferability: Thick descriptions of the educational context and participant background were provided. (c) Dependability: The research process was documented in detail, allowing for potential replication and (d) Confirmability: Researcher bias was minimized through reflexivity and peer debriefing during the coding process.

Ethical considerations included informed consent, anonymity, and voluntary participation.

4. Innovative pedagogical practices in Greek Schools

Analysis of recent education policy shows a shift from traditional teacher-centred approaches to interactive, student-centred pedagogical practices such as STEM education, digital storytelling, gamification and project-based learning. The new Greek national curricula emphasise learning outcomes, inclusivity and differentiated pedagogy to meet the diverse needs of learners.

Greek education reforms have increasingly promoted a shift from traditional teacher-centred models to student-centred methodologies, reflecting broader global trends in education. In particular, these methodologies include STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) education, which integrates interdisciplinary, hands-on learning experiences known to increase student engagement and develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Bybee, 2013). Digital storytelling has emerged as a powerful pedagogical approach, enhancing literacy and language skills while fostering creativity and emotional engagement (Robin, 2008). Similarly, gamification, the use of game-based elements in education, has proven effective in increasing motivation and learning outcomes (Dicheva et al., 2015).

The new Greek national curricula further emphasize inclusivity, differentiated pedagogy and clear learning outcomes, in line with international best practice to meet the diverse needs of students (Tomlinson & Moon, 2013). These curriculum reforms reflect broader pedagogical shifts towards personalized and active learning environments that actively engage students in the learning process (Prince, 2004).

The following figure 1 is illustrating the relative emphasis on key innovative practices and skills of the 4Cs in Greek education.

Figure 1. Indicative representation of the integration level and pedagogical emphasis on the 4Cs and related innovative pedagogical practices in Greek secondary education, based on national curricula, educational policies, and focus group insights from the 4C-Future project.

5. Key Findings

Teachers identified several student-centered pedagogical practices as particularly effective: inquiry-based learning, gamification, problem-based learning, STEM integration, and digital storytelling. These methods were praised for fostering active learning, critical thinking, and creativity.

Below is a visual summary of Greek teacher strategies. The figure 2 highlights the prevalence of active learning and digital engagement.

Figure 2: Strategies and methods implemented by Greek secondary school teachers as reported in the 4C-Future focus group.

5.1. Pedagogical Innovations

Teachers identified inquiry-based learning, gamification, problem-based learning, STEM integration, and digital storytelling as particularly effective in promoting student engagement and learning. These methods align with existing research indicating their effectiveness in supporting critical thinking, creativity, and active learning (Hmelo-Silver, 2004; Dicheva et al., 2015; Robin, 2008).

5.2. Digital Literacy

The integration of digital tools such as Arduino, collaborative platforms (Google Docs, Padlet), and interactive applications (Kahoot, Quizizz) significantly enhances classroom interactivity and student engagement.

Teachers emphasized the value of integrating digital tools to enhance learning. For instance, Arduino supports practical STEM activities, collaborative platforms (Google Docs, Padlet) facilitate interactive teamwork, and applications like Kahoot and Quizizz increase student engagement. This supports literature findings indicating digital technologies significantly improve educational outcomes and student motivation (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2010).

5.3. Collaboration and Communication

Collaboration and communication skills are effectively developed through various interactive strategies. Collaboration is promoted through group projects, digital collaborative tools, and discussions, while communication skills are nurtured through peer teaching, debates, role-playing, and scientific presentations. These methods are widely documented as effective practices for fostering essential communication and collaboration skills necessary in the modern workplace (Johnson & Johnson, 2009).

5.4. Educational Policy Challenges

While recent educational policies support innovation theoretically, practical implementation is inconsistent due to curriculum rigidity, limited resources, and inadequate professional development for teachers. Teachers expressed concerns about the 'tyranny of content,' which restricts flexibility and innovation.

Teachers reported significant challenges in implementing innovative pedagogical practices, primarily due to rigid curricula, limited resources, and insufficient professional development opportunities. This aligns with broader educational research highlighting similar barriers in the implementation of innovative pedagogical practices (Cuban, 2013).

5.5. Recommendations from Teachers

Teachers highlighted the need for ongoing professional development, enhanced technological infrastructure, access to digital educational resources, and more flexible curricula to effectively integrate the 4Cs.

Participants recommended enhanced ongoing professional development, improved technological infrastructure, increased access to digital educational resources, and more flexible curricular structures. These recommendations resonate with international best practices advocating systemic support and resource provision to facilitate educational innovation (Fullan, 2007).

6. Conclusions

The 4C-Future project underscores notable strides in embedding 21st-century competencies into Greek secondary education, particularly through the structured promotion of the 4Cs. The empirical findings drawn from a diverse group of teachers validate the potential of inquiry-based, digitally enriched, and collaborative pedagogies to significantly transform learning environments. These approaches support deeper learning, increased student agency, and a curriculum that resonates with the demands of the digital age (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020).

However, systemic challenges such as rigid curricular frameworks, inadequate resources, and insufficient teacher training hinder the widespread adoption of these innovative practices. To address these challenges and foster sustainable change, several policy implications emerge:

- Curriculum Reform: Implement flexible curricular frameworks that allow for the integration of 4Cs-focused activities and project-based learning.
- Resource Allocation: Increase investment in technological infrastructure and provide access to digital educational resources to support digitally enhanced learning environments.
- Professional Development: Provide ongoing, high-quality professional development for teachers, focusing on pedagogical innovation and effective integration of the 4Cs.
- Community Building: Foster professional learning communities to encourage collaboration, knowledge sharing, and ongoing support for teachers and educators.

Addressing these issues requires coherent policy alignment, sustained investment in infrastructure and capacity building, and the cultivation of a professional learning community culture (Timperley, 2011). Effective implementation of innovative practices is not merely a function of access to tools and frameworks but also of sustained professional support and leadership (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012).

Ultimately, the 4C-Future project offers a valuable model for educational transformation in Greece and beyond. By addressing the identified challenges and implementing the recommended strategies, educational systems can better equip students with the essential 21st-century skills needed to thrive in an increasingly complex and digital world. The project's methodology and tools provide a concrete framework for teachers, educators and policymakers seeking to foster critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication in the classroom. As Greece continues to modernize its educational agenda, the insights from 4C-Future provide a robust roadmap for aligning pedagogical practices with contemporary educational imperatives.

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Code words: Cracking the lexical secrets of Maths and Computer Science through a custom-built corpus

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Abstract

As in all STEM fields, international projects are an integral part of the curricula in Maths and Computer Science, thus necessitating the need for students not only to be fluent in English, but also to be in possession of the disciplinary vocabulary needed to facilitate fruitful collaboration with their overseas peers. In a distance learning setting where incoming students have disparate skill sets, it is particularly important to make available an assortment of bridging courses so that students might improve their proficiency in English before delving into their degree.

In the English Learning Support unit at the FernUniversität in Hagen, we have introduced an innovative, self-paced advanced English course utilising a custom-built corpus to enhance vocabulary acquisition and independent learning for students of Mathematics and Computer Science. A specialised corpus was created using articles and editorials from the Journal of Universal Computer Science (1995-2024). Initially created on Sketch Engine, it is comprised of over 19.8 million words or 27 million tokens. Vocabulary-building activities were designed around this corpus, and the course has been implemented on Moodle with optional oral online assessments.

Referring to a specialised corpus for authentic language offers a reliable alternative to large language models, providing abundant, authentic concordance lines without the risk of hallucinations, biased output or made up sources as can happen with abstractive and generative AI (Davis, 2025). As designed, the JUCS corpus is enriched with part-of-speech tagging and the full complement of Sketch Engine tools, for example word sketch, key word in context (KWIK), N-grams and trends. Thus, in addition to undertaking the set exercises within the course, students can independently explore discipline-specific vocabulary, fostering continuous learning. The course also includes reading, listening and speaking activities.

This innovative course design leverages corpus linguistics to provide targeted, flexible and relevant English language support for STEM students. The focus on an aspect of English that is of direct relevance to those studying Maths and Computer Science helps to maintain the students' motivation, thus promoting learner autonomy and preparing them for international academic collaboration.

Keywords

Syllabus design, English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Corpus Linguistics, distance learning

1. Introduction

English Learning Support at the FernUniversität in Hagen is housed within studyFIT, a student support division that offers dozens of bridging courses, workshops, events and other services for both current and prospective students. And whilst German is the language of instruction for all degree programmes at the university, in some disciplines there are nevertheless isolated English-language modules, opportunities for international collaboration and certainly myriad encounters with English-language texts. The unassailable position of English has been discussed in many contexts—Achebe (1965) focusing on African literature and more recently by scholars commenting on the publication language of international research journals (see Arenas-Castro et. al., 2024; McIntosh & Tancock, 2023 and Thelwell & Sud, 2022). Before devising a concept for English Learning Support for the university, it was important to ascertain the specific requirements of the faculties and to also solicit information directly from the students. Thus, in 2022 a campus-wide survey was deployed, attracting 1397 participants. Their responses informed the design of the courses, as did the findings from interviews with four professors and six lecturers. The preliminary survey and interviews showed emphatically that separate courses would need to be developed for each faculty. With three ESP courses successfully deployed for Humanities and Social Sciences, Psychology and Business and Economics by 2024, attention turned to the needs of the students of Maths and Computer Science.

International collaboration and project work are core components of contemporary education in Mathematics and Computer Science, and proficiency in academic English combined with discipline-specific lexical knowledge is essential for productive participation. Distance learning intensifies this need by bringing together students with widely varying levels of language preparedness, making targeted bridging provision a necessity. Traditional general English courses often fail to equip STEM students with the precise terminology, collocational patterns and textual conventions they encounter in research papers, technical reports and conference discourse, producing gaps that hinder comprehension, peer collaboration and academic writing (cf. Widdowson, 1983; Flowerdew, 2001; Belcher, 2006 and Hyland, 2006). Effective ESP interventions therefore foreground authentic texts, targeted lexical items and the rhetorical patterns characteristic of disciplinary discourse. Pedagogical recommendations include identifying high-priority vocabulary, creating tasks that mirror real disciplinary activities and also including tasks that facilitate transfer in a self-study format.

2. Literature Review

There are three main pedagogical strands that directly inform the design and rationale of the *English for Maths and Computer Science* source: Syllabus design for ESP, Corpus Linguistics in the age of AI and learner autonomy in distance education.

2.1 Syllabus design in English for Specific Purposes

Syllabus design for English for Specific Purposes consists of four phases: needs analysis, determining the intended learning outcomes, selecting the material and instructional methods and then evaluation (see Flowerdew, 2025 and Anthony, 2018). As asserted by Dudley-Evans and St John (1998), ESP is inherently learner-centred, with its design shaped by the linguistic, communicative and disciplinary requirements of a specific professional or academic community. The syllabus should therefore foreground authenticity, relevance and practicality, ensuring that language instruction mirrors real-world contexts. These considerations were central in developing and eventually implementing the *English for Maths and Computer Science* course. A dedicated corpus would serve as a source of the relevant vocabulary for devising learning activities, and it would also give students ready access to a powerful tool that affords independent learning.

With corpus-based vocabulary building activities at the centre of the course, other exercises were integrated into the course design, namely reading, listening and speaking activities.

2.2 Corpus Linguistics in the Age of AI

The advent of generative AI has been disruptive across all disciplines of higher education, calling into question everything from instructional design and classroom practice to approaches to assessment. It is easy to assume that the astounding capabilities of generative AI models obviate the need for traditional corpora. Recent debates in language-teaching technology contrast empirical corpora with generative large language models. Scholarship supporting corpora use stresses verifiability, traceability to original sources and immunity to the hallucination problems that can affect abstractive generative systems (cf. Davis, 2025; Schepens et. al., 2025 and Xu et. al., 2024). Desagulier (2024) argues that studying an imitation holds little value if linguists are unable to reliably link its linguistic features to authentic human experiences. Likewise, making generalisations about an artificial language created through a process of dehumanised abstraction serves no meaningful purpose. Thus, this new age of AI need not be the death knell of Corpus Linguistics.

Pedagogical accounts argue that corpora afford evidence-based examples of usage that can be interrogated and validated by learners, while also supporting reproducible analytic workflows (Desaugulier, *ibid.*). Critical perspectives on automated text generation caution against uncritical adoption for pedagogy because of potential factual errors, opaque provenance and inconsistent register control—concerns that reinforce the value of curated, discipline-specific corpora for ESP purposes.

Specific corpus tools can be co-opted for learning activities. Features such as concordance lines, word sketches, keyness measures, n-gram lists and collocation tables each support different learning aims: concordances for contextualised meaning and phraseology, word sketches for grammatical patterns, keyness for domain-specific vocabulary and n-grams for frequent technical phraseology. In setting a corpus as central to the course, it is argued that scaffolded tasks using these tools—guided discovery, gap-fill based on authentic sentences and composition informed by collocational prompts—lead to better retention and transfer. To date, positive feedback has been given by students enrolled in the *English for Maths and Computer Science* course.

2.3 Learner autonomy and distance education

Distance learning environments demand materials that support self-regulation, flexible pacing and sustained motivation. Research into autonomous learning shows that domain relevance is a major motivator: students engage more with materials when tasks map clearly onto their academic goals (Johansen et. al., 2023). In online, self-paced learning, achieving higher completion rates and satisfaction is more likely when content is modular, dynamic and includes optional formative assessment that gives learners a sense of progress (cf. Biederbeck et. al., 2024). The literature also highlights the role of optional synchronous or oral assessment to provide communicative practice and teacher feedback without undermining the scalability benefits of asynchronous design (Conrad and Openo, 2018). In light of the fact that *English for Maths and Computer Science* was designed as a bridging course, an important consideration was the students' disparate backgrounds in terms of academics and life experiences. It is for this reason that studyFIT offers a wide range of courses, workshops and other events that ease the transition into higher education. For a student to decide that this is the modus best suited to their educational pursuits is merely the first step. Time management and prioritising learning are up to the student; it behoves instructional designers and teachers to create courses that do not hinder what is already an uphill learning journey.

3. Creating the corpus-centred course

Corpus-driven, discipline-focused language support is a scalable, motivating and pedagogically robust strategy for preparing Mathematics and Computer Science students for global academic collaboration. This assertion holds true when considering the construction of the JUCS corpus, alongside its pedagogical design, assessment procedures, implementation challenges and initial outcomes. Such comprehensive corpus construction and application offer valuable insights and practical effectiveness in equipping students with the necessary academic language skills in these disciplines.

3.1 JUCS overview

Professor Jörg Keller, Chair of Parallel Computing at the FernUniversität in Hagen facilitated access to thirty years' worth of articles and editorials from the *Journal of Universal Computer Science* (1995-2024). The *Journal of Universal Computer Science* (J.UCS) is a prestigious, monthly peer-reviewed open-access scientific journal established in 1994, covering a broad spectrum of computer science research. It is published by the J.UCS Consortium, supported by nine research organisations internationally. J.UCS prides itself on a rigorous peer review process, employing a single-blind system with at least two editorial board members reviewing each submission. The journal has a notably low acceptance rate, below 16%, which underscores its selective and high-quality editorial standards, contributing to its reputation as a significant knowledge base in the field.

J.UCS maintains an open-access policy, which allows free access for both authors and readers, promoting wide dissemination and accessibility of computer science research. Its publication record includes both regular monthly issues and special issues focused on specific topics curated by guest editors, reflecting contemporary and novel developments in the discipline. The journal also boasts a substantial international editorial board and a history of documenting and connecting computer science research globally since its inception.

J.UCS is indexed in major academic databases such as the Science Citation Index Expanded and Scopus, and it holds a respectable impact factor in the range of 1.0 to 1.3 in recent years, reflecting steady influence in the field. It offers an average turnaround time for first editorial decisions of about 76 days, balancing thorough evaluation with reasonable speed (Journal of Universal Computer Science, 2025).

3.2 Creating the corpus

Under the supervision of the course creator, an undergraduate undertook the work of uploading 3095 documents—articles and editorials—on the Sketch Engine platform, and she ultimately produced a B.Sc. thesis entitled *Relevante Informatik-spezifische Begriffe im Englischen und ihre Entwicklungen im Lauf der Zeit* (“English-language Computer Science-specific terms and their evolution over time”) in partial fulfilment of her degree. Her success on both accounts is to be commended.

Sketch Engine was selected for its dynamic interface, ease of use and its being a Europe-based entity, an important consideration in our data-driven world. It is a sophisticated corpus analysis platform designed to explore authentic language usage across a wide range of languages. It caters to professionals such as linguists, lexicographers, translators and educators by offering access to extensive corpora and advanced analytical tools (Sketch Engine, n.d.). Likewise, casual users and students can readily avail themselves of its many features with minimal training.

Among its standout features are concordance searches, which allow users to examine how words appear in context; word sketches, which summarise a word's grammatical relationships and typical collocations; and term extraction, useful for identifying domain-specific vocabulary. Other tools include keyword analysis,

frequency lists, thesaurus building and parallel text alignment, all of which support detailed linguistic research and practical language applications.

The JUCS corpus contains over twenty-seven million tokens (27. 277. 885) from almost twenty million words (19. 867. 218) in 815.461 sentences. Corpus size critically shapes the reliability and comparability of frequency-based measures, since many standard metrics vary with the amount of data and may distort normalised frequencies when corpora differ in scale (Wolfer and Koplenig, 2025). Larger, well-balanced corpora improve representativeness and support robust generalisations about language use, while smaller or highly heterogeneous corpora risk producing noisy or domain-specific results that limit external validity and pedagogical application (Curry and McEnery, 2025). In terms of both its size and the period of time that its source materials span, the JUCS corpus presents a rich source of authentic language on the evolving discourse of Computer Science. In its original and definitive conceptualisation, it is to be presented on the same Sketch Engine platform on which it was created, since the wide range of search functions grant flexibility for users.

For example, the eponymous word sketch function displays collocations for any given search term, clearly identifying parts of speech such as the subjects, objects and prepositional phrases associated with the term as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A word sketch for the search term “*augment*” – Image from JUCS Corpus, via Sketch Engine

An unfortunate aspect of using Sketch Engine is that access to the JUCS corpus is dependent on an institutional licence, the fees for which, at the time of writing, are not available in light of the economic environment. Since the corpus was created in both .vert and .txt formats, hosting it independently is a viable alternative, and the essential language-learning activities can be undertaken seamlessly, albeit with some modifications. Suffice it to say, the Sketch Engine experience is superior and will be reinstated as soon as finances permit.

3.3 The intended learning outcomes

The overall intended learning outcomes of the course are that students who participate diligently in all tasks will gain the knowledge and skills to:

- Leverage language corpora for vocabulary building

- Discuss the contributions of selected Mathematicians
- Demonstrate adherence to the standards of academic integrity
- Describe the structural elements typically required of an undergraduate thesis
- Evaluate the utility of language learning in AI-driven, media-rich environments

Thus, in addition to the corpus activities that are built into the course, there are also reading, listening and speaking activities. The readings consist of peer-reviewed articles that focus on accessible narratives on outstanding and seminal achievements by Mathematicians of times gone by. The Leibniz/Newton controversy is proffered by way of introducing topics such as academic integrity, citation practice and document management in STEM fields. The other units feature Euler’s musings on the Seven Bridges of Königsberg and the enduring impact on computer science; Gauss and his polymathic proclivities; and then the life and times of Nicolas Bourbaki. The readings are accompanied by a selection of listening tasks from the BBC Radio 4 podcast series *A Brief History of Mathematics*. As an asynchronous course there are no opportunities for speaking practice, *per se*; however, the tasks are nevertheless provided, and students are invited to upload MP3 files in Moodle should they require feedback.

3.4 Optional assessment

Taking into account the importance of flexibility in the context of a bridging course, the end-of-course assessment is optional. It consists of a thirty-minute oral assessment in which students are expected to display a high register conducive to their studies and indicative of their having taken the vocabulary-building activities earnestly; astuteness in discussing highlights from the History of Maths; proficient responses in discussing the relevance of natural language processing and corpus research; and familiarity with the core elements of an undergraduate thesis in their field. As with all studyFIT self-paced bridging courses, a certificate of accomplishment is awarded for a passing grade. At present, no ECTS are awarded for these courses, though this situation is likely to change should the courses ever be offered as micro-credentials through the OpenEU, the pan-European open university that is as yet a work in progress (see OpenEU, 2024, “Joint Mission Statement”).

4. Assorted activities

Launched in April 2025, the course *English for Maths and Computer Science* is set in Moodle, the central learning platform of the FernUniversität in Hagen. The Moodle instances in use are provided and integrated into the university IT landscape by the Centre for Digitalisation and IT (ZDI) and maintained in conjunction with the Centre for Learning and Innovation (ZLI). Moodle contains a rich set of pedagogical features and customisation options for creating interactive activities, managing assessments and aligning the learning environment with a specific instructional approach. The functionality coheres well with the modular course design of *English for Maths and Computer Science*, whereby there are four instructional units in all, primarily sequenced by theme. A forum for questions, links to corpora and an overview section containing the syllabus for download and an introductory interview with Professor Keller—filmed in the university TV studio — complete the line-up. The course interface is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The Moodle interface for the course *English for Maths and Computer Science*

A wide range of vocabulary building activities were created and integrated throughout the four-units of the course. Figure 3 depicts a vocabulary activity that entails searching the corpus, recall, understanding, application and synthesis.

19	Identify five common collocates of each of these terms:
	decode
	decrypt
	encrypt
	scramble
	unscramble
20	Using your understanding of the five terms, design a simple encryption system where a message is first scrambled and then encrypted.

Figure 3: An example of a vocabulary building exercise and follow-up task

Activities centred on the JUCS corpus were foundational to the course design; however, the course also introduces students to other corpora of relevance, such as the British Academic Written Corpus (BAWE) and the MDPI Open Peer Review Corpus which are freely accessible on Sketch Engine as well as other corpora hosted elsewhere online. Whilst the wonders of generative AI are welcomed, the enduring relevance of corpus studies is emphasised in the course, and students who are so inclined may choose to tackle an aspect of natural language research in the context of a term paper or even thesis research. Some avenues of exploration are listed in Figure 4, an excerpt from the corresponding presentation given at the Innovating Higher Education conference held in October 2025.

Figure 4: With a dedicated corpus, a wide range of studies into natural language can be undertaken

5. Conclusions

The *English for Maths and Computer Science* course demonstrates that a specialised, corpus-driven approach delivers targeted lexical gains for Mathematics and Computer Science students in distance learning. The JUCS corpus provides authentic, verifiable evidence of disciplinary usage, enabling learning activities that prioritise high-frequency vocabulary, collocational patterns and genre-specific phraseology. Implementing the course in a self-paced format via Moodle with optional oral assessments balances scalability with opportunities for formative feedback. Informal student feedback thus far suggests improved learner autonomy, sustained motivation through discipline-relevant materials and clearer pathways to productive participation in international STEM collaborations. A next step would be to initiate a structured student survey and follow-up study in order to measure long-term transfer into academic tasks.

The primary remaining challenge pertains to budgetary matters should the corpus be accessed in the manner in which it was initially designed. Hosting the corpus on an alternative platform is feasible but eliminates some of the attractive features in Sketch Engine.

Overall, corpus-based English support offers a robust, evidence-driven alternative to generative systems and a pragmatic route for preparing students of Maths and Computer Science to engage confidently in global research and project work.

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